

This document features the English translation of the PhD thesis by Marta Montanini “Redenzione forzata: sviluppo, post-apartheid e pratiche di appropriazione a Red Location”. The thesis has been submitted in Italian, for the PhD in Social and Political Change, University of Turin, Italy, in 2017. The thesis supervisor is Prof. Irene Bono.

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FORCED REDEMPTION

**Development, post-apartheid and ownership practices in Red
Location**

Marta Montanini
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To Irene Bono, who supported and encouraged me even from afar, and who taught me that research must be done with passion, rigor, elegance, empathy and many de hors in the sun, go my deepest gratitude and sincerest esteem.

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Caution: Red Location people will think that the museum is theirs, as it would keep their voices alive.

(RLM, 'Toward a vision and mission for Red Location Museum', workshop report, 2005)

Siamo noi ad essere qui, ora. Vi chiederete quali siano le nostre ragioni, noi ci chiediamo quali siano le vostre. Non le ragioni per distruggere e sovvertire, ma quelle per resistere di fronte a ciò che viene distrutto e sovvertito.

*(C. Bersani, M. D'Agostin, *The Olympic Games*, 2017)*

Introduction

May 26th, 2016: the South African national television channel SABC 2 broadcasts live from the Red Location Museum (RLM) in Port Elizabeth, in the Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality of South Africa. At the beginning of the programme, the reporter remarks upon the exceptional nature of this event: it is the first time in three years that the museum has opened to the public after having been under occupation by the Red Location Steering Committee (RLSC), a group of residents of Red Location, the township in which the museum is located. The group had forced the closure of the cultural centre to demand that the Municipality uphold its promise of repairing over two hundred nearby social housing units. The reopening of the museum coincided with the handover of the keys back to the mayor – the handover, but not the return. The photograph taken at the close of the press conference speaks volumes: on the right, Executive Mayor Danny Jordaan holds in one hand the iron keyring; on the left, Khusta Mbotyi, appointed representative of the RLSC, grasps the bundle of keys. Beside them, another representative from the residents' committee points to their two hands.¹ The message is clear: the keys belong to them both. At the end of the ceremony, the mayor makes a statement that will be cited by all the journalists present, “this key that the RLSC is handing over to us does not only open the doors to the Red Location Museum, but it also unblocks the entrance and opens the path to the township’s economy and cultural economy”.² This day marks more of a ceasefire than an endpoint in a conflict that has lasted almost twenty years, since the Red Location Museum and Cultural Precinct (RLMCP) was first designed.

I went to Port Elizabeth, South Africa, in 2015 for a sixteen-month visit to the Development Department of Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU) as part of my doctoral studies in “Social and Political Change”, facilitated by a EUSA_ID Erasmus Mundus mobility grant. My research project centred on the concepts of ownership and appropriation, primarily their role in socio-economic development projects. South Africa struck me as a particularly apt site to investigate the ways in which development policies pursue the objectives of ownership and restitution in contexts that are marked by processes of dispossession and deprivation. I was also

¹ See Appendix 3.

² SABC 2, news, 26/05/2016.

interested in the relationship between development projects and the formation of the new South African nation, as the reduction of economic inequality and the abolition of past segregation seemed like immediately necessary conditions for post-apartheid transition. Additionally, I set out to closely analyse the effects of public policy on identity frameworks and everyday dynamics of recognition and ownership.

Upon arrival in Port Elizabeth, I thought it would be useful to get an idea of the city's history. All the tourist websites praised the innovative character of the Red Location Museum, a museum that was part of a cultural centre being built in the small location of Red Location,³ in the township of New Brighton. During the first week of my stay, I decided to visit the museum as part of a tourist trail called "The Real City tour" that promised to guide participants through the discovery of Port Elizabeth's townships. The tour's website read, "townships are the heart of urban African life. They're vibrant, heart-breaking, heart-warming, resilient, cohesive, and dynamic".⁴ The museum was meant to be the last stop, the culmination of the tour. To my great surprise, however, as soon as we reached the centre of the Red Location Museum and Cultural Precinct (RLMCP), the tour guide limited herself to speaking only about the architectural qualities of the buildings, adding that they and the museum were closed because of "community protests", and so that it was impossible to go inside.

The cultural centre, consisting of the museum, a library and an art gallery, was flanked by informal settlements on the one side and social housing on the other. The RLMCP and the surrounding dwellings comprised a sort of district in themselves, not far from the industrial area of Deal Party and connected to the main road and the train station. The cracks in the glass doors, the broken windows, the graffiti on the walls and a few scraps of paper on the ground testified to the abandoned state of the buildings, while the shadows of security guards inside the buildings and the groups of teenagers hanging about gave an impression of vitality, of a place that was lived in.

³ In the Eastern Cape, the word "location" refers to the *Native Reserve Location Act of 1902*, an act passed by the Cape Colony government that created residential areas designated for Black Africans (so-called "natives") in order to remove them from the city centre, ostensibly to improve health conditions following an outbreak of the bubonic plague. Subsequently, the use of the term "township" to indicate larger settlements or groups of settlements has become commonplace. Today, citizens of Port Elizabeth generally refer to the Black residential areas built in the twentieth century before and during the apartheid government either as "locations" or "townships" (or "kasie", an isiXhosa word derived from the Afrikaans for location, "lokasie"), according to their toponymy, which can often reveal much about the creation date and use of the established term, an aspect I explore further in Chapter 9.1.

⁴ Calabash tour website.

The door of the main entrance was emblazoned with two notices: the first, typed out on the computer, warned in a tone that was somewhere between formal and intimidating that permission from a member of the Red Location Steering Committee (RLSC) was necessary to enter the buildings.⁵ The second was handwritten and listed the names and phone numbers of the representatives of the RLSC, with no indication of any particular hierarchy. The buildings that made up the RLMCP were inaccessible from October 2013, when the RLSC made the decision to occupy them for as long as it took for the Municipality to start repair works on the by-then derelict social housing. The repairs, which had been promised for years, are yet to be completed.

The RLMCP was a project initiated in the mid-1990s that aimed to promote urban regeneration in the location through the creation of an anti-apartheid history museum and investment in the sectors of tourism, art, culture and entertainment. The project planned for the construction of a large cultural centre and simultaneous improvements to the surrounding area through building social housing and reorganising the main public transport infrastructures. The first phase involved preparations for a museum and the construction of an art gallery, library and restaurant, while the second anticipated the construction of several auditoriums for theatre and cinema, rehearsal rooms and spaces for creative workshops, alongside the establishment of an arts school. The project was supposed to inspire a complete transformation of the location, making it an utterly innovative district.

The RLMCP can be described as a project aimed at the “redemption” of a marginal space. The word “redemption” carries multiple meanings. On the one hand, it can imply release, liberation and emancipation, but on the other, it is associated with the religious concepts of forgiveness, absolution from original sin and reconciliation with the divine. While the first meaning foregrounds the agency of those who redeem or free themselves, the second indicates the presence of someone or something else through which the redemption occurs. The redemption of Red Location, however, struck me as “forced”: while the organisers imposed the project on the residents, in some way, the residents sabotaged it. In having imposed their own presence and occupied the spaces of the museum, they “forced” the project open to seize ownership of it. The RLMCP therefore struck me as an interesting starting point

⁵ See Appendix 3: Images, figure 14.

from which to explore and understand the relationship between ownership, appropriation and development policies.

In this thesis I examine the ownership and appropriation practices that have accompanied the history of the RLMCP – from its initial conception through to the conflicts of recent years – as diverse actions through which multiple actors participated in the governance of development. Additionally, I will demonstrate how ownership practices operate simultaneously through temporal and spatial dimensions, on symbolic and material levels, sparking conflicts and confrontations that not only shape social change but that also contribute to the redefinition of belonging and substantiate the exercise of citizenship.

Between two “post”s: post-apartheid and the Post-Washington Consensus

The twenty years that followed the initial scoping study exploring the potential for the RLMCP in 1996 were intersected by two interconnected processes. On a national level, the declaration of the Constitution in 1996 prompted the process of democratic transition and the construction of the South-African nation, through the presidencies of Nelson Mandela, Thabo Mbeki, Kgalema Motlanthe and Jacob Zuma. On an international level, increasingly heated debates over the policies of the Washington Consensus led to the passing of the Heavily Indebted Poor Country Initiative (1996) and pro-poor policies. This was part of a wider attempt to combine economic growth with the eradication of poverty and mitigate the collateral damage of the neoliberal policies previously implemented by the World Bank (WB) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Filho 1999; Fine 2010 and 2016; Freund 2012). The history of the new South Africa and debates that developed within the ANC and between social movements and political leadership should be read alongside the policies promoted by international institutions, especially the WB and the IMF, that were implemented particularly efficiently by Pretoria (Freund 2012; Fine 2016). The first post-apartheid South African government, led by Mandela, found faced with the task of manoeuvring the new South Africa into the world economy, having to redeem the country’s reputation and guarantee its stability. The new government adopted policies in line with international finance organisations and designed a national development

strategy to correspond with this aim. In 1996, the adoption of the Growth, Employment and Redistribution programme (GEAR), which prioritised macroeconomic reforms over policies aimed at reducing poverty, signalled the South African government's change of direction towards markedly capitalistic and neoliberal policies (Hart 2002; Adelzadeh 1996).

Analysing the twenty years that followed the end of apartheid means understanding the intersections and imbrications between promises of equality, restitution and redistribution, and the objectives of economic growth, investment attractiveness and the dynamization and diversification of the national economy. In the wake of the dissolution of the Soviet Union and the crisis in socialist rhetoric that had inspired the more radical fringes of the anti-apartheid movement, the language of libertarian freedom and struggle against oppression merged with the language of development, to the extent that economic development came to be upheld as the primary goal of national policies (South Africa was and is defined by its leadership as a “developmental” state), with all other functions carried out by the state being essentially reduced to dependent variables of economic growth.

In this sense, we can conceive of the “service delivery protests” calling for free access to public services in the townships from the early 2000s as the sign of a short circuit at the intersection of two *posts* – post-apartheid and the Post-Washington Consensus – and subsequent policies (Stokke and Oldfield, in Harris *et al.* 2004). Promises of equality, redistribution and protection of socio-economic rights collided with a public administration that, in their provision of basic services, frequently resorted to privatisation, referring to cost-benefit relationships and economic sustainability. In the twenty years of the RLMCP's lifetime, therefore, two distinct attitudes towards and two different conceptualisations of ownership coexisted in South African political discourse.

Ownership and (re)appropriation

Two different modes of defining ownership are interwoven throughout the RLMCP project. The first is linked to the policies of the Post-Washington Consensus and their integration into the South African political system, while the second is linked to the period of post-apartheid and nation-building in South Africa. The RLMCP was a

decidedly neoliberal project that handed the development of the township over to economic growth, innovation and investment attractiveness, prioritising entrepreneurship over redressing inequality. At the same time, the project was deeply rooted in post-apartheid politics and so was grounded in social cohesion, reparation for past injustices and acknowledgement of individuals' suffering as a form of symbolic restitution.

The first mode of conceiving ownership is related to the discourse and policies of the Post-Washington Consensus and can be understood in terms of "project ownership", as in of development projects. This conceptualisation of ownership resulted from renewed concern for the economic inclusion of lower socio-economic classes and "good governance", two of the central policies promoted by Joseph E. Stiglitz, ex-Chief Economist of the WB, from the latter years of the 1990s. The policies of the Post-Washington Consensus also reflected increasingly advanced processes of neoliberal bureaucratisation (Hibou 2012; Darbon 2014; Bierschenk and Olivier de Sardan 2014), that transplanted techniques from the management sector into the field of development in order to standardise interventions and be able to quantify their efficiency and effectiveness.

The word "ownership" is specified in the Paris Declaration (2005) and the Accra Agenda for Action (2008), the final documents from the second and third High Level Forums for Aid Effectiveness that brought together multiple countries (including South Africa), organisations and bilateral and multilateral development agencies with the aim of enhancing the impact of development aid. In both documents, the central notion of "ownership" refers to a country's ability to establish their own strategies for poverty reduction and utilise national systems for aid delivery.⁶ In line with these two statements, the World Bank refers to "country ownership" or "national ownership" as the ability of national governments to assimilate the policies proposed by the WB and the IMF into their own systems through reforms and strategic

⁶ The Paris Declaration notes, "Ownership: Developing countries set their own strategies for poverty reduction, improve their institutions and tackle corruption"; the *Accra Agenda for Action* reads, "Ownership: Countries have more say over their development processes through wider participation in development policy formulation, stronger leadership on aid co-ordination and more use of country systems for aid delivery". These forums led to the signing of the Busan Partnership for Effective Development Co-operation in 2011, which established a framework for development cooperation that combined traditional funders, BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, South Africa), civil society organisations and private funders. The process was led by the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and development (OECD).

development plans.⁷ The expression “national ownership” (or its variant, “local ownership”) is also used in the United Nation’s (UN) peacebuilding interventions, here referring to the ability of national governments to take responsibility for political change. In both senses, the definition of “ownership” is rather ambiguous, if not outright misleading, containing contradictions that range from the sovereignty of the nation-state, adherence to the principles promoted by financial institutions, to the mere implementation of the expected policies (Reich 2006; Wilén 2012).

The use of the term “ownership” in the context of development is rooted in European development agencies and EuropeAid, the European Union’s development agency. The increased use of project cycle management (PCM) and the logical framework approach (LFA)⁸ dates back to the early 1990s.⁹ PCM and the LFA were increasingly considered essential tools for designing, formulating and above all, presenting a project to funders; they became, in other words, a way of articulating both national and local development initiatives on a transnational scale, following in the footsteps of the analysis frameworks of policy cycles developed in the second half of the 1950s.¹⁰ To find the word “ownership”, we have to turn to project cycle management, which is generally conceived of in five stages: programming, identification, formulation, implementation, evaluation and audit. “Ownership” is implied to be one of the indicators to be inserted in the “logical framework”, and at the same time is highlighted as one of the key criteria for a project’s success. EuropeAid’s project guidance, for instance, reads: “participation and ownership are

⁷ For the WB, “country ownership” is an essential condition that countries requesting loans must fulfil. Despite this, the organisation itself admits that establishing the criteria through which the degree of national ownership can be evaluated and measured is somewhat difficult. See, for example, *Conditionality in Development Policy Lending*, 2007.

⁸ The Logical Framework is a project management tool for both publicly and privately funded development projects. It consists of a table detailing information about the project goals, activities, the verifiable indicators and means of verification, the risk factors and external factors that could influence the project’s success.

⁹ The European Union produced the first handbook on Project Cycle Management (PCM) in 1993, but the Logical Framework Approach (LFA) dates back much further. It was developed by two American consulting firms commissioned by USAID, the United States Agency for International Development, in 1971. In the 1980s, several European development agencies, such as DFID in Britain and GTZ in Germany, adopted the LFA, and in the 1990s the LFA became the model for all European agencies and later, for EuropeAid, JICA, the Japanese International Cooperation Agency, and for several international agencies, such as the United Nations Industrial Development Organisation (UNIDO) and the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO). See Nakabayashi (2000).

¹⁰ For definition and description of the policy cycle, see: Lasswell (1956), Jones and Anderson (1970), Howlett and Ramesh (1995); for a critical analysis, Neveu (2015).

fundamental to ensure relevance, effectiveness and sustainability” (EuropeAid Cooperation Office 2004: 118).

In development project documentation, the term “ownership” is usually preceded by the adjective “local”, in reference to the individuals and institutions who reside or belong to the area in which the project will be carried out. Even if all project stakeholders, including institutional representatives or non-governmental organisations, can theoretically be considered equally plausible “owners”, the term is most often applied to a project’s direct and final beneficiaries.¹¹

The term “appropriation”, the taking of ownership, however, is not defined by any development agency or international organisation, though there is mention of the possibility of measuring appropriation or ownership gained through the potential transfer of skills or increase of knowledge in a certain area. Ownership is thus understood to be an indirect outcome of a project’s activities. In fact, “taking ownership”, appropriating, is an expression borrowed from management literature to refer to taking responsibility for managing a business project. It therefore has nothing to do with the actual possession of goods produced by a project nor with project design, but rather indicates an understanding of the project’s aims and adherence to the principles or values advanced by the project organisers.

The use of the word is accompanied by a series of assumptions: the idea that participation in a project automatically implies acceptance of its foundational principles and aims; the idea that the act of taking ownership or appropriation is a process that operates simultaneously and consistently across multiple levels; the belief that knowledge of certain practices or codes or a certain use of space also implies endorsement of a precise set of values; and the idea that taking ownership, appropriation, consists of irreversible actions and commitments that occur under constant conditions – in other words, that once participants have appreciated the importance of and learnt how to use a certain code or procedure it is unlikely they will turn back to their previous approach. Ownership, then, in a similar way to funding, has contractual connotations: taking ownership or appropriation is expressed through the acceptance of an objective, regulation or procedure, and at the

¹¹ Le Meur, on the subject of participation, which is another term predominantly used in reference to the beneficiaries or recipients of development aid, discusses the reproduction of the distinction between *développeur/développé* (Le Meur 2008).

same time, constitutes a sort of commitment. Appropriation is therefore conceived of as a linear and non-selective learning process.

Le Meur has written about the “common world” of development, in which standardised procedures can produce long-distance relationships (Le Meur 2008). This “common world” extends beyond the field of international development and is relevant also on national and local scales. The “development community” ends up sharing the same vocabulary, whether the project is nationally or internationally funded. The term “ownership”, therefore, can be seen to ricochet between international and local contexts, while remaining just as ambiguous.

The second mode of conceptualising ownership brings together multiple terms that have aligned with questions of extreme political importance in South Africa, from the context of post-apartheid to the present day. The term “ownership” to indicate a state of (legal) possession is usually associated with land, and repeatedly resurfaces in contemporary political debate about the need for agrarian reform and the dispossession, reappropriation and redistribution of land stolen during apartheid (see, for example, the Abahlali movement’s statements on the right to housing and land). Alongside this is the phrase “state ownership”, such as the nationalisation of resources and land demanded by the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF). In this case, the term “ownership” is connected to that of “entitlement”, to rights, privilege or legitimate possession.

The other phrase that frequently arises in contemporary debates is “cultural appropriation”. The topic of cultural appropriation speaks to broader criticisms of the persistence of segregation, that today finds expression in unequal access to rights and services but most of all in perceived societal divisions between the classes of oppressors and oppressed. “Appropriation” is used with negative connotations, referring to the seizure of something for private use usually without permission, and in the case of culture refers to the use of another (usually subaltern) culture’s symbols or objects without acknowledgement or respect.¹² The inverse of cultural appropriation is “heritage reappropriation”, the desires of previously oppressed individuals and groups to reclaim and value their own culture. Essentially,

¹² For example, see: Haupt, ‘Die Antwoord’s revival of blackface does South Africa no favors’, *The Guardian*, 22/10/2012; S. Jason, ‘Blackface, white guilt, grey area’, *Mail and Guardian*, 23/01/2015; M. Bongela, ‘Whites seek that ol’ black magic’, *news24*, 30/11/2015.

appropriation is understood as an act of systemic theft, taking ownership of something that is not legitimately yours, while reappropriation is seen as a form of liberation and redress of inequality.

The construction of the cultural centre was presented as restitution to the inhabitants of the location in economic terms, as the inhabitants would benefit from the financial returns of the project; in symbolic terms, since the project celebrated the efforts of the inhabitants who participated in anti-apartheid struggle; and in artistic and cultural terms, as the RLMCP aimed to recognise the cultural heritage and artistic creativity of the location. The RLMCP therefore amounted to a sort of reappropriation occurring through institutional mediation.

Being or having?

The two modes of conceptualising ownership and appropriation intertwined in the RLMCP project therefore refer both to a set of values and behaviours and to the restitution and possession of material goods. The first conceptualisation is more prevalent in the definition of ownership inherent in the policies of the Post-Washington Consensus and development literature, while the second is shaped by the prevailing discourse of the post-apartheid years.

In technical development literature, ownership is primarily understood as a state of “being”. It is in the project organisers’ interests that stakeholders get to know the project, that they take part in it and recognise it as their own. In other words, this way of conceptualising ownership focuses primarily on regulating participation through a series of activities (awareness raising, lectures, meetings, public assemblies) that seem more geared towards persuasion than consultation. Understood in this way, taking ownership, appropriation, implies the unfurling of an array of self-disciplinary mechanisms – an action that, although presented as a gain for the beneficiaries, exposes an asymmetrical relationship between the organisers and the beneficiaries of development. Participating in development means performing exactly the sort of ownership prescribed by the project organisers in the name of the project’s supposed neutrality and a separation between development and politics (Ferguson 1990). In this way, ownership in the context of development policies participates in the adoption of that tangle of biopolitical technologies,

including surveillance and the individualisation of responsibility, that constitutes the production of subjectivity in the neoliberal era (Foucault 1975; Butler 1997; Benasayag and Schmit 2007; Boltanski and Chiapello 2011). In other words, it reflects the “engagement” demanded by capitalism (Boltanski and Chiapello 2011), whose power ebbs without open, unconditional and dedicated participation. In the context of the RLMCP, this conceptualisation of ownership was manifested through the requirement that all participants adhere to a certain set of behaviours and conducts, lest they be excluded from the benefits of the project.

During post-apartheid, however, taking ownership, appropriation – or rather, reappropriation and taking *back* ownership – was principally conceived of as the restitution of something that had been illegitimately stolen. Ownership in this context therefore pertains to “having” and “having for oneself by the authority of something”; the term is thus largely to do with socio-economic rights and is understood in terms of identification with or belonging to an oppressed class or group. The term is therefore used more in reference to groups than to individuals and is related to pre-established and simplistic identity categorisations. In post-apartheid, citizenship is intrinsically connected to property, in contrast to the years of racial segregation when property rights were severely limited (especially by the Group Areas Act and the Native Land Act).¹³ A citizen is someone who can purchase and possess. Property rights, restitution and compensation are governed by Art. 25 of the Constitution of 1996 but this article, being the result of a compromise between the African National Congress (ANC) and the National Party (NP), is extremely exacting both in terms of the protection of property and dispossession, making the process of returning land or property seized during apartheid extremely complicated. In the RLMCP, this ambiguity between restitution and redistribution was manifested by efforts to capitalise on and valorise the location’s history, as a form of symbolic compensation and reparation.

In general, the term “ownership” can be deployed both to designate the act of having or possessing – owning an object or a resource – and to denote actions that pertain to the realm of being and representation, implying reflexive processes such as the appropriation or ownership of a certain representation of identity, culture or

¹³ Act 41 from 1950, 77 from 1957, 36 from 1966 and Act 27 from 1913. For an analysis of property legislation in South Africa, see Chaskalson and Lewis (1998).

knowledge. The RLMCP project involved acts that can be attributed to both meanings: the appropriation of the area of Red Location for building the cultural centre, the museum's appropriation of artefacts from the location's history, the residents' taking ownership of how they were represented by the project and the museum, etc. Yet, in the context of Red Location, there were also practices of ownership and appropriation that cannot be completely encapsulated by these meanings. Further, practices of ownership and appropriation are not isolated actions, but rather are interlocking and entwined.

An analytical proposal: appropriation as “making appropriate”

The meanings of ownership and appropriation that I have analysed pertain to the fields of having and being, but neither encapsulates both dimensions simultaneously. However, having and being are deeply intertwined, and appropriation – whether material or symbolic – implies an interaction between these two dimensions. Furthermore, neither of these interpretations can account for the central fact that ownership and appropriation, whether of an object, space, person or group, always unfolds relationally. For a definition that can bring together these multiple senses of appropriation, taking ownership, I return to the Italian etymology of this ambiguous term.

Literally, “to appropriate” designates the act of taking ownership or making one's own, but it also indicates an adaption or making appropriate, since “proprio” derives from the Latin *pròpius*, or “proximate”, and by extension, “that which belongs, is appropriate for someone, specifically, uniquely and especially” (this is also the derivation of the adjective “appropriate” and the adverb “properly”). The etymology of “*appropriazione*”, the act of taking ownership, spans a complex, multifaceted semantic field, with meanings ranging from taking possession of something or possessing something exclusively, transforming something (“adapting, making appropriate”), to bringing something closer to the speaker, to modifying something that does not completely belong to the one modifying.¹⁴

This interpretation satisfactorily encompasses simultaneously the senses of “being” and “having” and at the same time also introduces a relational dimension:

¹⁴ See Etimo, the Italian etymology dictionary, and the dictionary Treccani.

“making appropriate” is an action that is carried out on something or someone, with someone, often to the detriment of someone or something else, and through someone or something. Considering appropriation or taking ownership in this way avoids reducing it to an action that is unique to a particular social group (as is often the case in technical development literature or in the demands of post-apartheid) and, further, does not rely on a dichotomising view of society. For example, in the case of the RLMCP, all groups partook in acts of ownership and appropriation, and each time this was the expression of an unfurling power relation.

Since to appropriate or take ownership of something is originally to “make it appropriate”, ownership practices depart from Gramscian “conceptions of the world”¹⁵ and develop according to a certain idea of the future (one appropriates or takes ownership of something because it is considered useful for the present or for a close or distant future).

Acts of ownership and appropriation are also extremely generative, unsettling prior equilibriums and giving rise to redefinitions of an individual or group. At the same time, ownership practices do not exist in isolation but are responses to previous demands that will in turn enable successive appropriations, thus constituting recursive configurations.

Ownership and appropriation operate on multiple levels simultaneously, both because their object can be time, material or symbolic space, ideas, etc., and because appropriation in one domain can trigger change in another (for example, something that someone comes to own can change their self-perception, in the same way that appropriating a space can involve repositioning oneself, physically and symbolically, in relation to the city). Ownership relates to the present and the space of the present alongside the imagined future but must also be analysed in relation to the past. You appropriate or take ownership of something following an acquired set of codes and based on your self-perception or on the representation and narration of belonging

¹⁵ Liguori explains: “The expression, therefore, has a wide range of uses. It indicates everyday reason and common sense, as much as elaborate conceptualisations, hegemonies or potential hegemonies; broad collective ideas as much as the individual theorisations of great thinkers who, while departing from a pre-existing conception of the world in which they live and have been shaped by, contribute to the creation of new and original worlds”. He continues, “the conception of the world is decisive for the delineation of collective and individual identities”. G. Liguori, *Gramsci project, Dizionario Gramsciano*, entry: “Concezione del mondo”.

that you have come to claim or assume. In turn, the appropriated object says something about its owner, coming to constitute a part of their identity. Analysing ownership therefore means simultaneously observing multiple relationships: that of the individual to self, time and space; between subject and object; between individuals and groups; between institutions and citizens; but also between multiple institutions, or local, regional and national levels of government.

The field of the RLMCP allowed me to observe the interactions between multiple actors and contexts as a dynamic, interconnected whole in which ownership practices and appropriations contributed to the transformation of structures and hierarchies. Le Meur notes that “the reproduction of the context of development is not simply the reproduction of hegemonic discourse, but a process of controversies, translations and complex mediations that sometimes allow actors to question broad, common knowledge and shift certain boundaries” (Le Meur 2008: 33). Although implicated in asymmetrical power relations, development actors, whether institutions or ordinary citizens, do not take part in development projects naively or submissively but rather they learn, subvert and transform the vocabulary and intentions of other parties. Elements of development projects are appropriated in the same way as other common objects: selectively, voluntarily, irregularly and with varying levels of intentionality.

Understanding appropriation as “making appropriate” also means moving beyond the idea of taking ownership as a linear, incremental and irreversible process: observing ownership and appropriation over the course of twenty years in the context of the RLMCP allows us to appreciate how ownership and appropriation are not self-evident, linear or constant, but are instead the result of actions that are intermittent, not always coherent and sometimes improvised. Ownership and appropriation, therefore, participate in the everyday trajectories of invention and reinvention identified by De Certeau (1984).

Necessarily, speaking about ownership means touching, at least obliquely, on the concept of property. Xifaras stresses the inadequacy and vagueness of the legal definition of property, limited as it is to designating the act of possessing something and using it in accordance with your own wishes. He prefers instead to distinguish between “primary” property of a psychological and philosophical nature, constituted by the owner themselves (exemplified in the expression of “my freedom” or “my

rights”) and “other property”, designating legal property and material things such as objects (Xifaras 2004).

In this analysis, I explore not only the legal and exclusive ownership of a particular object, but also the “feeling of being an owner” or “considering oneself the owner”, regardless of the legitimacy, formal accuracy or relation to reality of this perception. In other words, in addition to legal property rights I consider property through the lens of belonging to a place (the township) or group (the residents), as well as property “as use”. I also consider discourse about ownership to be more relevant than actual ownership itself, and indeed in some cases I note how the borders of belonging can symbolically expand the concept of property even beyond a subject’s intentions and horizons (for example, the feeling of belonging to the entire continent of Africa allows one to perceive extremely geographically dispersed material objects and cultural phenomena as one’s own, at least symbolically).

This thesis, therefore, does not aspire to an exhaustive definition of ownership. Instead, through analysing diverse ownership practices, it indirectly addresses multiple forms of ownership in a context in which considering only legal or formal ownership cannot account for the everyday realities of conviviality and blurred boundaries between formal and informal, licit and illicit, legal and illegal activities, and where fluid networks of multiple relations guarantee the perpetuity of the city (Robinson 2002; Simone 2012; Judin 2008; Mbembe 2004; Weisenthal 2010). This ambiguity also allows me to concentrate on analysing practices without necessarily having to draw a “poverty line” between the haves and the have-nots. Poverty is not absent but is re-interpreted through the categories provided by the field: it is understood, for example, in terms of theft, lack of redistribution, violation of rights (in the view of several residents), or in terms of inherited oppression or even dependence on aid, according to some politicians and local officials.

Analysing conflict through the everyday

In his 1997 essay, “Museums as Contact Zones”, James Clifford analyses the ways in which museums become spaces where a series of exchanges occur through which the relationships between power, history, politics and morality are negotiated and made explicit (Clifford 1997). This was certainly the case for the RLMCP. The cultural centre

struck me as the product of at least two distinct workings of ownership: on the one hand, the new buildings constituted a particular apparatus for governing the location in the name of a salvific effect for the whole city. On the other hand, the residents' occupation of the cultural centre was a declaration of the right to the ownership of those buildings, a right based on belonging, reparations for past injustices and the proximity of housing. This reappropriation of the museum sparked a further series of questions: who did the history narrated inside the museum belong to? And similarly, who had the right to decide on the future of the cultural centre? How much of the present was interwoven with the past? And which of the acts of ownership colluding in Red Location were rooted in or explained by other places and sites elsewhere? Ownership practices carried out by multiple actors, by the same token, can only be understood through considering the other phenomena that influenced and shaped them: the political history of the location and the city, the multiple representations of the township produced in the years of apartheid and post-apartheid, the coexistence of various forms of conduct to which behaviours could be ascribed, the geography of the location, etc.

Throughout the entire course of the project, contact in the space of the cultural centre took the form of open conflict, or rather, a series of conflicts of varying forms and intensities. The field constituted by the RLMCP therefore offers an opportunity to think through the "persistence of conflict" (Benasayag 2007) – the substance and the main actors of the conflict were present in the field on a daily basis; they were in constant opposition and constant communication, even though there were not always sky-high levels of tension, nor a constant sense of danger, exacerbation, or immanent crisis. Rather, the conflict was woven into the ordinary fabric of everyday life.

Smith (2016) has written that the Red Location Museum can be understood today as a place that commemorates death on the inside, that represents a real and symbolic interment, and therefore that the residents' appropriation of the museum can be read as resistance to a "house of the dead" (173). Paradoxically, however, despite their closure, the buildings around the RLMCP were a lively space. The vitality of this space and the debates that animated it are evidenced precisely by the persistence of conflict, by differentiation, confrontation, exchange and relation between the actors involved. Benasayag and del Rey assert that a society that purges itself of conflict is a society that condemns itself to a binary logic of confrontation,

whose members converge into reductive, compliant and dichotomising positions, making it impossible for dialogue to progress (2007). What restores society's dynamism are the moments of conflict and the resulting spaces of cooperation. In a similar vein, McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly stress how social interaction, communication and dialogue are not merely expressions of structure, rationality, consciousness or culture, but are active sites of creation and change (2007: 22). In this research, therefore, I consider conflict as but one possible dimension of relationality, and as a constitutive and intrinsic component of the formation of society.

Analysing ownership practices from the perspective of conflict was not a decision that stemmed from the uniqueness and extraordinariness of the situation, but rather from the desire to observe participants when they were most unmasked, that is, as they asserted, reformulated and carried out their ambitions and motivations. Conflict is a time and place of relentless and repeated communication, when dialogue and interaction can also take the form of hostility and silence. The use of violence during protests in the townships in South Africa was often attributed to the residents' attempts to open dialogue with local government, so much so that the protests were nicknamed "the public phone".

In observing and analysing the conflict, I made use of theoretical tools from literature on European and African social movements: the constitution of the residents' committee and the protests were enabled by specific political opportunities that recall the rhythms of the "protest cycle" (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly 2007); it is possible to identify repertoires of political practice (Bayart 1985; Tilly 1986); it is possible to trace an articulation between neoliberal policies (and neoliberal cities) and protest (Della Porta 2015). At the same time, this conflict stuck me as "irreducible to a schema of separate and clashing identities, [it was] a complex fabric, a tangle of elements articulated in a labyrinth of tensions that do not necessarily correspond with the identities at play in the situation" (Benasayag and del Rey 2007: 94). I do not, therefore, treat conflict as a moment of polarisation that bolsters rigid and oppositional identities and clearly outlines the figure of the enemy, but rather I consider conflict as a site of the "multiplication of identity" (Benasayag and del Rey 2007) of individuals that prompts a complex web of connections, relations and exchanges. I additionally strive to analyse the conflictual relations that I identified in the field of the RLMCP from a historical perspective, in an attempt to understand their

trajectories and transformations (conflict, as a site of transformation, is itself subject to many reformulations). A diachronic view of the everydayness of conflict also allowed me to draw connections – for example, between practices and lexical choices – that breach the symbolic border dividing South African history into periods of apartheid and post-apartheid. In this way, I was able to identify continuity and rupture, the reclamation of certain terms and the persistence of others, with regards to both political leadership and members of the residents’ committee or officials.

Studying the intersections

Analysing the RLMCP project meant studying several intersections simultaneously, observing phenomena generated by interactions between multiple processes and discourses. The RLMCP was almost entirely state-funded, with funding from municipal and national governments, but in its early stages it also benefited from international funding. The project’s ambitions, in terms of culture, tourism and internationalisation, gave rise to the permeation and fusion of national and international discourses and *savoir faire*. The project was part of a series of infrastructural interventions that characterised the transition in South Africa and was simultaneously presented as a form of restitution and development. In this way, it drew on both the vocabularies of post-apartheid and the Post-Washington Consensus. The internal grammar of the RLMCP evolved with the passing of time, revealing itself as sensitive to both fluctuating approaches in local, national and international development, and to the nuances of national debates on racial segregation and its consequences. The project represented the attempts of local government to draw attention to the foundational principles of anti-apartheid struggle, such as equality and social justice, while simultaneously embracing neoliberal policies aspiring to efficiency, economic diversification and investment attractiveness. As a development project, the RLMCP constituted part of an attempt to advance a narrative of South Africa as a country that was resource-rich and full of opportunities. Development policies worked to neutralise the symbolic and material legacy of apartheid, with a view to normalising the present and presenting South Africa as being as ordinary as possible, allowing it to enter the global economy as an important international player.

The RLMCP, furthermore, as a state intervention, was presented as a single solution to a multiplicity of problems: its aims touched on a wide range of issues, from social inclusion to technological innovation, from urban regeneration to the creation of community and social cohesion. The project, therefore, is a highly appropriate site for understanding how multiple features of the township were constructed as public problems, as a “panopticon of social fears, emergent beliefs and the reorganisation of frameworks for perceiving the social world” (Neveu 2015: 10).

A varied cast of actors orbited the RLMCP: officials, citizens, residents, local managers, experts and consultants on urban regeneration and national and international development, local and national politicians, students, artists, curators, etc. It is therefore also a highly relevant site of interaction and dialogue between diverse components of society with regards to nation building, civil society, memory and citizenship.

A field so complex allows us to consider several configurations and move through multiple dimensions. It is possible, for example, to explore the intersections between post-apartheid, neoliberal policies and urban planning; to observe interactions between multiple visions of the future and multiple senses of belonging; to explore the relationship between memory and political practice; to understand the structures of security, development and the construction of a non-racial community. The possibility of considering these multiple aspects makes the analysis of ownership practices richer and more compelling and calls for a highly multidisciplinary approach.

Accessing the inaccessible. Origins of a centrifugal study.

While the RLMCP project struck me as an extremely interesting and fruitful research site from my very first visit, in addition to a truly unique observation point for the study of ownership and appropriation as relational and transformational, accessing the site was not straightforward. As I expected, when I arrived the buildings were resolutely closed and under occupation by (or in the custody of, depending on the perspective) the RLSC, a committee whose power lay precisely in the steadfastness, consistency and daily commitment of their actions. The effectiveness of the occupation stemmed from the committee members’ determination to prevent anyone

from crossing the threshold of the museum (and in theory also from staying in the area, though this was rarely enforced), and above all to force construction workers to negotiate entrance – for example for urgent checks or maintenance problems – that they would in fact sometimes be refused.

I asked myself, then, if it would even be possible to conduct research within these parameters, and to do so in a way that respected the wishes of the protesting residents' committee by relinquishing any hope of going inside the museum, art gallery or library. Almost immediately, however, I realised that discovering information about the internal structure of the buildings would not be an impossible task; rather, as it was an important and one-of-a-kind project in the Eastern Cape several theses and works had already been dedicated both to the architecture and the internal outfitting of the museum and art gallery.¹⁶ The RLMCP and the Red Location Museum in particular have been analysed as a project of state architecture and collective memory construction, and, in one case, as a potential lever of tourism in Port Elizabeth. However, there had been no works in which the RLMCP is analysed as a development project. Thanks to the various awards it has won, multiple articles have been published on the Red Location Museum in specialist journals, some of which have chosen the museum as the cover image.¹⁷ The photographer Iwan Baan, whose work explores the life of architectural works after their formal opening, carried out a photoshoot at the RLMCP in 2009. There therefore existed a wide array of secondary sources from which I could draw. Furthermore, since its earliest stages, lively local debate about the RLMCP has flared up at salient moments in the project's trajectory (at every new funding allocation, political visit, protest, etc...).

During the course of my research, I realised how fruitful the question “can you tell me what this museum (or this building) contains?” could be for understanding what type of interpretation of the RLMCP and each of its constituent parts prevailed among my interlocutors, and also for realising that many residents had crystal clear ideas about the project without ever having set foot inside any of the buildings.

Although my inability to visit inside the museum undoubtedly imposed a restriction on my project, it also forced me to visit and experience other sites. For

¹⁶ See Findley (2004 and 2005); Deckler, Graupner and Rassmuss (2006); Murray, Shepard and Hall (2007); Lepik (2010); Baines (2011); Roux (2015); Smith (2016); Noero (1999, 2006, 2012); Eicker (2012); Botha (2013).

¹⁷ See Appendix 3: Images, figure 7.

example, the courtyard in front of the museum with its vibrant coming and going (it is on the way from the station to the social houses, but also provides a social space for young people and, when the need arises, a football or cricket pitch) became a meeting place between me and representatives of the RLSC. It was also at the tiny office at the New Brighton entrance that I met the museum staff who were waiting for the museum to reopen. In short, the closure of the museum paradoxically made this research richer as I immediately found myself obliged to look elsewhere, prompting a process that in fact became a methodological approach.

The field as encounter: the choice of interlocuters and the interview structure

At first, even identifying the most appropriate interlocuters for my research meant overcoming several difficulties. Firstly, the RLMCP was a highly complex project, involving a large number of officials and municipal departments. Secondly, some interlocuters seemed decidedly less accessible than others (for example, the members of the residents' committee who were initially rather reluctant to meet me). To navigate these problems, I proceeded by degrees of proximity, adopting the concept of "exposure" (Shwartz-Sea and Yanow 2012). Shwartz-Sea and Yanow note how the selection of participants for qualitative or "interpretative research" initially depends on the proximity of the researcher to people or organisations who are more accessible or part of their day-to-day life. These initial contacts constitute the beginnings of a web that grows progressively wider. Olivier de Sardan, similarly, attests, "the choice of interviewees functions for the most part through arborescence: each interview triggers new orientations and new potential interviewees through direct or indirect suggestions arising from the interview" (Olivier de Sardan 1995: 14).

The people who were most accessible to me and who could help me penetrate the logics of the RLMCP were academics who had in various ways collaborated with the project. Several of my first exploratory interviews with these academics helped to guide my understanding of the organisational structure of the project and to intercept project organisers and staff members of the museum, art gallery and library. In turn, these interlocuters provided me with contacts for officials at the Municipality and members of the institutions involved in the RLMCP. In parallel, I also pursued other

channels that put me in contact with several inhabitants of Red Location and with some people engaged in arts and recreation, sports and local clubs. This second type of contact enabled me both to piece together various interpretations and opinions of the project and its potential beneficiaries, and to investigate further dimensions of everyday ownership.

Having spent a significant amount of time in Port Elizabeth, I made some acquaintances at the University and elsewhere in New Brighton, Red Location and the neighbouring areas who transpired to be people with a wide and varied knowledge of the themes that I was researching. This allowed me to make use of a sort of “testing ground” where I could explore doubts and ideas about my research. I therefore proceeded in a recursive manner, alternating between conducting interviews and various sorts of observation and then returning to my “testing ground” to present my primary analyses and test their coherence and significance. This process allowed me to bridle interpretations that were unconsciously exoticizing and restore normality to behaviours that at first glance could have struck me as extraordinary or peculiar. These interlocutors also often functioned as “semiologic translators” (Olivier de Sardan 1995), facilitating a transfer between the sense system of the local milieu and my own. Further, these testing grounds, made up of people with a reasonably detailed knowledge of my research but also of my background and moods, encouraged me to embark on a doubly reflexive journey, analysing not only my own actions but also the evaluations and considerations of people whose judgement I trusted. In short, it was a way of enacting what Fine describes as “working the hyphens” (Fine 1994), a continual interrogation of the boundaries between the researcher and the Other, of mutual permeability, affinity and distance. Finally, these testing grounds allowed me to contextualise my reflections, lift my eyes from the field and widen my exploration beyond the symbolic borders of my research.

The interviews I conducted were framed as dialogue and exchange. In this sense, I adopted an approach of “discussing uncertainties”, that is, “the possibility of letting the interlocuter express their doubts, reflect on a situation in a situation, show changes in attitude, gestures, behaviours, ways of speaking and enunciation” (Bono, Hibou, Meddeb and Tozy 2015: 21). With some interlocutors I carried out a single interview; with those that I judged more meaningful and collaborative, the dialogue was protracted across multiple sessions, sometimes over the course of months. I had

more meetings particularly with the residents' committee, museum staff members, several officials who were central to the implementation of the project, several local politicians and the project organiser.

Portelli stresses how “the interview is important because it has a tendency to always broaden the terms of the debate. It always starts beforehand and finishes afterwards” (Portelli 2005: 16). Returning to the same interlocuter at different points in time, or phoning them for a comment or quick clarification, allowed me not only to return to several points which required elaboration, but also to establish a relationship of mutual respect and, in the best of cases, trust. Being a recurring presence in the corridors of the same offices and developing ever closer relationships with my interlocuters allowed me to get a sense of their “beforehand” and “afterwards”, to be guided in ways that I had not previously anticipated. Olivier De Sardan highlights how “rather than being perceived simply as a way of obtaining ‘good answers’, the interview should generate new questions” (Olivier De Sardan 1994). I hoped that repeating interviews once or twice would broaden the terms of the debate and establish relationships and connections that would have been conceivable only through continual access to the field. In these exchanges, I was not searching so much for the truth about the project or the history of the township – although I tried to verify information through triangulating my sources – but rather I prioritised the meaning that my interlocuters conferred to decisive events and actions.

I carried out forty-five formal interviews, but this thesis is also nourished by many reflections that derived from everyday socialising and informal conversations.

Investigating the dimension of everydayness (the project's everyday practices of ownership and appropriation, but also the daily practices through which citizens made the place they live “appropriate”) also meant giving adequate space to participant observation and immersion or “impregnation” (Olivier de Sardan 1994) in the everyday lives of multiple individuals in Red Location. On the one hand, investigating ownership practices meant stepping back from the physical space of the project, tending towards “intertextuality” (Shwartz-Sea and Yanow 2012), an analysis intersected by interviews and various other types of documents. On the other hand, however, the research demanded getting progressively closer to the field and the lives of my interlocuters. Many of the conversations that I discuss in this thesis are the

result of prolonged contact, shared spaces, comments made at plays, political meetings, conferences, speeches triggered by reflections on a passer-by.

In general, during interviews I privileged “consultation” and “narration” (Olivier de Sardan 1994). The formal meetings had three stages. Firstly, if my interviewee was directly involved in the project, I would ask them about it and their role in relation to it, or I would ask more evasive questions about their knowledge of the project (what are they building in Red Location? What is the project like? Have you seen inside the museum? Etc.). Secondly, I would try to direct the conversation towards daily practices: I would ask for a more detailed description of the activities carried out (both by those responsible for implementing the project and the protesting residents), of the difficulties faced, of the relationships between various actors. I also tried to encourage my interviewees to talk about events that they had previously been involved in, eliciting comparisons with the present, and to react to reflections from other interlocutors or comments in newspaper articles. It was possible to proceed rather naturally from this stage to the third: exchanging opinions on such a complex and contentious project and its difficulties and contradictions directly steered the conversation towards more general reflections on the links between post-apartheid and development, inequality and citizenship, participation, the relationship between voters and politicians, and the relationship between past and present. Many of this research’s themes are those that my interlocutors themselves had gradually come to associate with the project.

As for the investigation into ownership practices “beyond” the RLMCP, my interviews took on a semi-structured, unstructured and prolonged nature. After having introduced myself, I would explain that part of my research focused on the relationship between the RLMCP and the local residents. I would explain how one of the RLMCP’s stated aims was to develop and improve the township’s environment, and how I was interested in what other methods the residents could employ to promote wellbeing where they lived and make the township more appropriate for their needs. After an initial meeting along these lines, I would tackle different topics according to the interlocutor and the direction in which they preferred to channel the discussion. The most frequent themes were differences between everyday life in the township’s present and past, the identification and description of public or private social spaces, the importance of education, security and emancipatory recreational activities, and

the relationship between citizens and local institutions in terms of the townships, the environment, housing and psychophysical wellbeing.

During the interviews, I deliberately avoided using the words “ownership” and “appropriation”, paying attention instead to when the word spontaneously came up in my interviewees’ responses. I tried to direct the conversation towards power relations and social-political dynamics, noting the use of terms that are adjacent to the concept of “ownership” and the understanding of appropriation as “making appropriate”: possessive adjectives, terms relating to the proximity, familiarity or distance of an object or group, terms indicating symbolic or material borders, terms relating to the possibility of action, management or expert use of knowledge and skills (“to master”).

Identifying a dispersed field

This research was conducted in a wide range of sites. Exploring ownership and appropriation in the specific context of the RLMCP development project meant going beyond the timeframe of the present and the space of the cultural centre. The interpretive research methodology that Shwartz-Sea and Yanow describe as “abductive” consists of “following the object”,¹⁸ trying to trace backwards the elements that contribute to constructing and formulating phenomena and processes, starting from an object or event around which the research questions are built. My research, therefore, consisted in explorations across dispersed sites. It did not investigate only the physical space in which the cultural centre was built and the area of the township called Red Location, but it also involved interviews with the local ward councillor and several councillors at the municipal level; specific departments of the Municipality (the Directorate of Human Settlements, the Directorate of Sport, Recreation, Arts and Culture); research centres at Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (in particular the Centre for Advancement of Non-Racialism and Democracy and the Centre for Integration of Post-School Education and Training, but

¹⁸ In the words of Shwartz-Sea and Yanow: “abductive reasoning begins with a puzzle, a surprise or a tension, and then seeks to explicate it by identifying the condition that would make that puzzle less perplexing and more of a ‘normal’, ‘natural’ event” [...] in this puzzling-out process the researcher tacks continually, constantly back and forth in an iterative-recursive fashion between what is puzzling and possible explanations for it, whether in other field situations or in research-relevant literature” (2012: 801).

also several members of the Department of Development Studies and the Faculty of Art); local branches of the ANC; and technical architectural and urban planning studios.¹⁹

In spatial terms, as Makhulu has observed, research in a segregated city means above all carrying out an “ethnography of dislocation”²⁰ consisting of continual movement from the centre to the peripheries, a chain in which the researcher also forms a link. In my case, coming to understand disparate ownership and appropriation practices meant continually oscillating between public spaces (offices, conference rooms, the area in front of the museum) and homes and gathering spaces (backyards and private courtyards converted into artists’ studios and collective spaces, multipurpose rooms, gyms, churches, pubs, sports fields), between institutional meetings and informal gatherings (public meetings, jam sessions, open-air meetings, meetings on the side of the road, spontaneous and organised meetings). Furthermore, in the location of Port Elizabeth, there are outdoor spaces that can be qualified as semi-domestic: above all, as noted above, the courtyard in front of the museum, whose use varied according to the groups there at various times throughout the day, constituted one of my principal sites for carrying out interviews with residents of the location. Valuable, informal conversations were conducted in *tchisanyama*²¹ or in front of roadside restaurants. Ironically, studying a circumscribed and immobile place necessitated a high degree of readiness for mobility and the capacity, at least temporarily, to inhabit the street. In an attempt to better understand the ownership practices that the residents enacted on a day-to-day basis, I also decided to participate as an observer in the Mdali workshop – a free, extracurricular, afternoon workshop ran by Xolisa Ngubelanga, a theatre director, at Cowen High School in New Brighton. The workshop focused on creative writing in English, based on themes of current affairs or the students’ lives (school, sport, the township). My interest in participating in this workshop was twofold: for one part, it was a way to understand how adolescents lived in the township and situated themselves in New Brighton and the city. I elaborate on this in the second and third parts of this thesis.

¹⁹ For a map of research sites, see Appendix 4: quoted interviews and research sites.

²⁰ Makhulu speaks of a “patchwork of sites”, accounting for the sense that many inhabitants of South African cities have of a disjointed space (Makhulu 2015).

²¹ Exclusively used in reference to the townships, this word indicates a sort of pub where it is possible to buy hung meat and grill it on the spot.

For another, I was interested to understand the values and principles that Ngubelanga felt an urgent need to impart to the teenagers. This second aspect allowed me to reflect on the concept of moral regeneration and moral spaces within the township.

As I was in contact with a small collective called Art Studio in New Brighton and Red Location, I was able to ask some young artists to visually represent the RLMCP, as a way of providing another perspective of the site to enrich and complement my own (in this case I was simply a customer). I also wanted to understand what their familiarity and affinity with this space was. Some of the photographs at the end of this thesis arose from this encounter.²²

In my attempts to reconstruct diverse representations of Red Location and trace the history of the RLMCP project from its conception through to its execution, the archives of *The Herald* newspaper, in addition to documents in private archives (especially those of Rory Riordan and various active members of the RLSC) were indispensable sources. Similarly, consulting the business plans and master plans for the cultural centre, alongside documents produced by the Department of Human Settlement (city planning, guidelines for the creation of Sustainable Development Units, etc.), allowed me to envisage Red Location's imagined future. The sites of this research are therefore many: interviews with local councillors took place in their offices in Red Location, New Brighton and, with municipal councillors, the city centre. Interviews with officials engaged in the implementation of the RLMCP and the housing projects were held in the offices of various departments, situated primarily in the city centre and municipal districts. Several interviews were conducted in bars, by request of the interlocuters themselves. The interviews with museum staff members were carried out in the provisional headquarters of the Red Location Museum's management in New Brighton, but also in bars, libraries, or other museums. Interviews with academics and museum organisers were carried out in their respective offices. Interviews with the Red City footballers and the kung fu group were carried out in sports facilities, but also in the courtyard in front of the museum. The interviews with the residents of the RLSC were mostly carried out in the courtyard in front of the museum and sometimes in private homes. Interviews with other residents of the location and several artists (in particular, writers, theatre directors and

²² See Appendix 3: Images.

musicians) took place in private homes, headquarters of clubs and libraries. Interviews with other residents were carried out in bars and *tchisanyama*, private homes and on the street. Participating in conferences on various topics²³ at the Nangoza Jebe Hall in New Brighton, at political meetings in New Brighton and nearby townships (for example at the youth division of the United Front and at the local ANC branch), at plays, performances and concerts, activity days organised by the Methodist churches in Red Location (for example the Women's Day or the Youth Event), and in schools (especially Jarvis Gqamalana Primary School in Red Location and Coven High School in New Brighton) also helped me to understand the discursive dimensions, range and form of public debate. In this sense, I engaged flexibility as a "conscious and intentional choice" (Shwartz-Sea and Yanow 2012), also seeing as one of this thesis's aims was precisely to investigate the multidimensionality of ownership practices, especially where they are not normally accounted for.

Understanding a fragmented city: the appropriation of the researcher

Port Elizabeth can be described as a city formed of multiple, overlapping historical layers (Mbembe 2008). Reading between the dissolving lines of the racial city, the colonial city is still legible. Structural traces of social engineering from the early twentieth century and the 1950s and 1960s live on in the townships. The partially disused industrial plants and the great viaducts across the city centre recall periods of strong industrialisation and economic growth, while the design and architecture studios in converted, refurbished Victorian-style buildings or unused warehouses, prefigure the city yet to come. Researching in and navigating Port Elizabeth above all else means understanding how a city made up of extremely diverse parts constitutes normality, grasping what it is that makes Port Elizabeth an "ordinary city".²⁴ Rather than asking whether the city is more or less workable or more or less liveable, we need to ask instead *how* it works and *how* it is appropriated on a daily basis by its inhabitants. The answers to these questions are far from obvious and tracing the

²³ Such as what to do with the symbols of colonialism still present in Port Elizabeth and the relationship between community art and identity, diversity and social transformation.

²⁴ With this term, authors such as Robinson (2006) and before her Amin and Graham (1977) refer to the daily practices and social construction of the city and relationships within it. In this sense, every city is ordinary and therefore comparable to other cities, regardless of their supposed level of development or position in international economic systems.

movements of individuals can be much more conducive than letting oneself be guided by the borders erected by geography, history or architecture. While, at first glance, the city might seem like an archipelago of separate islands, two conceptual endeavours are necessary: “engag[ing] the island as a world as well as the worldliness of islands” and thinking of a “mobile, flexible, and voyaging subject who is not physically or culturally circumscribed by the terrestrial boundaries of island space” (DeLoughry 2007: 3).

Understanding the meeting places and reference points of multiple subjects in various parts of the city demanded constant efforts to listen and observe. The choice of sites for interviews and meetings, for example, was informed by the fragmented nature of the city: spaces that were reassuring for some interlocutors were alienating if not outright hostile for others, according to a cartography that was far from self-evident. A bar in the racially-mixed Old Town (a neighbourhood that has been entirely razed to the ground and whose few remnants are now amassed in a community museum) on the border between the suburbs and the business district was an important space where activists from across the city would meet to discuss and deliberate, and although it was almost twenty kilometres away from Red Location, several interlocutors preferred to meet there. The same thing happened with one of the two NMMU campuses: the Missionvale Campus, previously a campus for non-white students and now surrounded by shacks, despite being a seat of knowledge and power was perceived as a more neutral and welcoming space than the South Campus, which was located in one of the richest areas of the city. Some of these sites were perceived as an extension to peripheral neighbourhoods, spaces that were distant to the townships but still customarily frequented by young artists, middling officials, trade unionists and activists. These spaces were sites that reflected the township from a more detached perspective and were chosen particularly by those who wanted to reconstruct events not from a position of neutrality but of greater rationality and reflexivity, or by those who wanted to shed themselves of institutional trappings. Where I lived – on campus in the suburbs, next to the accommodation for South African scholarship students and international students – was perceived by some people as a sort of no-man’s land, where the restricted access (to enter you had to pass through two security checks) was balanced out by its legibility and familiarity.

The limitations and challenges of an ethnography of a contested space

When I set out on my research project the tensions between local authorities and residents were at their peak; it was a moment of stasis when there were concerted efforts, particularly on the part of public officials, to evade responsibility and avoid further compromising themselves. There was a certain caution around expressing personal opinions in public, especially if they ran the risk of being deemed politically incorrect (racist, or excessively critical of the ANC, etc.). In this context, it was essential to establish relationships of trust that were based not only on standards of professional and ethical research (I often found myself having to explain the difference between a researcher and a journalist), but that were also strengthened by the demonstration of my desire to understand and listen to the motivations of all participants.

The RLMCP was undoubtedly a space in which elements of “contentious politics”²⁵ interacted with “uncontentious” political processes, such as various forms of public administration. Confrontations between different participants never turned violent, and at the same time the practices of these participants, including institutions, underwent constant change. Participants’ own identities changed throughout the course of the conflict: “participants in contentious politics constantly manipulate, strategize, modify, and reinterpret the identities of parties to their contention, including themselves” (McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly 2004: 56). Interactions that develop through confrontation and conflict prompt trajectories of growth and innovation. And yet, these processes occur within asymmetrical power relations, constantly crossing from the institutional to the unofficial, from the formal to the informal, from public office to private life.

Recording varying formations and opinions, practices and repertoires, slippery meanings, uncertainties and frustrations, is an extremely significant, necessary but also delicate task, as it is often perceived as risky (and here I do not refer only to an individual’s safety, but more broadly to the political or reputational

²⁵ McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly define the expression “contentious politics” as the “public, collective making of consequential claims by connected clusters of persons on other clusters of persons or on major political actors when at least one government is a claimant, an object of claims, or a third party to the claims”. (2007: 261).

risk) by the person who consents to discuss their confusions, doubts, explicit accusations, and divisions.

For these reasons, I preferred to not record interviews, relying instead on a pen and notebook. An additional feature that made me veer away from using a voice recorder were the strong winds that blow through the bay of Port Elizabeth almost all year-round, combined with the fact that I held almost half of my interviews outside, on the threshold of houses or in backyards. The interviews were mostly conducted in English, sometimes in the presence of participants – in particular Xolisa Ngubelanga, Nkosinathi Jikeka and Yolisa Mazonda – who would transform into translators or facilitators on special occasions. The few isiXhosa words that I knew were not enough to allow for satisfactory interactions in the majority language of Red Location, but when I demonstrated my desire to learn (I often found myself having to explain that I knew a few words because I was attending a language course), it often contributed to forming a connection between my interlocuters and myself.

The possibility to autonomously move between the various areas of the city by car – and to use this means of transport as a place for conversation on the many occasions in which owning a car gave me the honour and the onus of serving as a taxi-service – was one of the principal entry points to my relationships both in the township and in the city centre. Moving about by car allowed me to mitigate (though not completely overcome) the difficulties of poor transport connections between different areas of the city and to satisfactorily confront the omnipresent issue of security. To this day, most of the townships are considered dangerous areas not only by the suburban middle classes but also by the townships' residents themselves (during meetings and interviews I was repeatedly urged to make sure that my car was parked somewhere visible or advised to switch streets frequently so as not to draw too much attention). At the same time, my access to the field, much like the relationships of trust, mutual respect and friendship that were established between myself and the many people who participated in this research, depended on my having demonstrated a mix of awareness, caution and acceptance of risk. Knowing how to linger alone on the street for a long time, having strong references both on a topographical level and in terms of a network of relationships, knowing the streets

and how to navigate them, and learning to negotiate “load shedding”²⁶ are factors that contributed to making me less of a foreign presence in the daily life of the township and to creating an image of me as more complicated than my appearance (female, white, student, foreign) might suggest. At the same time, my choice to acknowledge and discuss the differences in status and the limitations linked to my position as an outsider in at least two senses (being foreign and white), and my decision to opt out of participating in certain activities for reasons of the safety of myself or others, for many people represented an act of due diligence that was sometimes rewarded with a tacit respect.

This grey area between paranoia and risk management, between claims that an ethnography of normality was possible even in places that were considered difficult and acknowledgement of my inescapable foreignness, gave rise to an experience of constant yet intermittent access to the township, characterised by immersion in spaces and relationships that were concentrated and dispersed throughout the city, along the lines of the movements of various inhabitants of Red Location and its surroundings. My intention to put spaces and social groups into relation with each other rather than considering them separately corresponds with my firm conviction that representations of the townships as isolated and homogenous ghettos is counterproductive and misleading.

During both the fieldwork and writing stages of my research, I tried to respect the privacy and availability of my interlocutors as much as possible, avoiding forcing anything on them. I tried to engage in a “radical reciprocity” through “not asking participants for more than they are willing to give” (Shwartz-Sea and Yanow 2012). I consider myself to have acted with what Tillmann-Healy describes as an “ethics of friendship” (Tillmann-Healy 2001), which does not necessarily mean forging binds of unconditional friendship with every participant, but taking constant care, both in the field and when writing, to treat each interlocuter as if they were more than an acquaintance, interrogating the consequences of actions that might affect them, and writing with the expectation of being read by the participants themselves.²⁷

²⁶ “Load shedding” is a series of controlled blackouts, rotating round various districts of the city, to compensate for a lack of electrical power. In the townships, where the roads are poorly maintained, narrower and more irregular, load shedding can make driving more difficult.

²⁷ Tillmann-Healy summarises relationships interwoven in this manner as characterized by a desire for “mutual respect, understanding, self-analysis and [personal] growth” (Tillmann-Healy 2003: 746).

At the same time, observations of ownership practices also arose from nonverbal communication, silences, self-representations, exaggerations and multiple versions of the same story. Reconstructing events related to the conception and execution of the RLMCP, considering both the facts and various interpretations of them, turned out to be a complex exercise and definitely not one free from inaccuracies and shortcomings. This research spans a temporal arc of almost twenty years. In that period, there were many changes in the representatives of clubs, organisations and local leaders. Of course, “groups do not store traces of the past in the same ways that individual brains do and different individuals in a group call up distinct and even conflicting memories of past contention” (McAdams, Tarrow and Tilly 2007: 262). While there are written accounts of a few salient events, for others it was necessary to turn to witness’ memories or oral histories. In a context of a high degree of mobility between districts, it was sometimes difficult to track down people who might have been able to provide more detailed information, especially with regards to past events.

Other inaccuracies and omissions undoubtedly arose from restricted movement and the awareness of being unable, in the space of a few months, to overcome the race and class barriers of apartheid that still condition political, social, public and private life in South Africa. My choice to concentrate on Red Location and New Brighton, majority Xhosa townships,²⁸ meant dedicating less attention to the other cultures, histories and relationships with local government and the state that were possibly present elsewhere in the city.

Without a doubt, being a foreigner and so somewhat removed from prevailing social norms allowed me to sidestep, at least in part, forms of social control that more than any physical division continue to mark the border between places that are deemed appropriate or inappropriate for the white middle-class. Being European, white, and associated with the University was an unquestionable advantage when it came to crossing between various places and accessing the top floors of several departments and offices. At the same time, the colour of my skin certainly influenced and made some of my interlocuters in Red Location more cautious. Certainly, my

²⁸ The amaXhosa people, along with the amaZulu, Ndebele and Swazi peoples, are a Nguni group with Bantu origins whose members mostly reside in modern-day Eastern Cape. They are the second largest ethnic group in South Africa, after the amaZulu. Their language, isiXhosa, is one of the officially recognized languages of South Africa.

imperfect English, perceived youth, and constant need for information about places and behaviours were factors that often tempered my “whiteness” and the power that comes from this, generating solidarity and partnership with respect to my condition of being a “foreigner” in town. Portelli states that “it is common ground enables communication, but it is difference that makes it meaningful” (Portelli 2010: 3). In Red Location and Port Elizabeth, relationships of trust and the presence of difference allowed me to instigate meaningful communication, that was, in the best of cases, relatively free from the conventions, reserve and cautious formality that bridle relationships between people identified as belonging to different racial groups in contemporary South Africa.

The Score

This thesis proposes three different ways of “scoring” the ownership practices observable in the area of the RLMCP – three trajectories in which different characteristics, purposes and forms of ownership and appropriation emerge. The word “score” refers to the musical notation of a complex arrangement of vocal and instrumental parts that make up a piece of music. The trajectories that I examine are similarly formed of multiple, overlapping, simultaneous parts, and it is possible to read the various actions of different actors at the same time. These trajectories, however, do not form a coherent whole, even if it is possible to make out melodic lines among them.

This thesis, therefore, focuses on (1) the relationship between ownership and change; (2) the relationship between ownership and belonging; and (3) the relationship between ownership and citizenship.

The first section of the thesis, *Projects and Proposals: Ownership and Change*, analyses the RLMCP as a development project shaped by neoliberal politics and discourses on post-apartheid reparations. This section focuses on the forms of appropriation and theft that the project generated in the name of transforming the township, and on how residents gave new meaning to these processes. The first chapter, *Red Location: A place worth giving new life to*, discusses the ideation and planning phases of the project, from the construction of the RLMCP as a state intervention to its position in Port Elizabeth’s development agenda, starting from the

construction of the narrative of Red Location as an exception historical site. The second chapter, *Local Sheet Metal and International Tourism: from capitalisation to development*, considers the project's delivery phase, concentrating on how the meaning of the project was constructed and reformulated by the organisers and on the relations between the RLMCP and neoliberal development policies. The third chapter, *Experiments for a Future City*, explores the RLMCP project in relation to previous attempts to build experimental, densely populated urban areas and subsequently produce of virtuous communities.

Analysing the RLMCP as an attempt to govern the social relations that encapsulated the foundational values of national belonging led to the exploration of the relationship between ownership and belonging, to which I devote the second part of this thesis: *Preparing and Prescribing: Ownership and Belonging*. In the fourth chapter, *The RLMCP: a sanctuary of social harmony*, I analyse the RLMCP as a site for disciplining behaviour in the name of social cohesion and individual responsibility. The fifth chapter, *Stratified Identities and Moral Orders*, revisits the residents' criticisms and protests against the disciplining of behaviour and unequal constructions of citizenship embedded in the township, and explores how other identities came to be associated with national belonging in the township. The sixth chapter, *Beyond prescription: deliberate desertion*, instead concentrates on the ways in which the identities of actors orbiting the project were reformulated through conflict and confrontation.

Analysing the forms of occupation and defence that developed around the RLMCP meant exploring the intertwining of ownership and citizenship. This perspective led me to analyse various ownership practices as the substance of citizenship, the everyday bustle of citizenship, from demands for access to services to the reformulation of subjectivity. The final part of the thesis, *Inhabitation and Defence: Ownership and Citizenship*, is dedicated to this topic. The seventh chapter, *Bread, butter... and roses*, examines the relationship between inhabitation and ownership by retracing the multiple waves of protests over housing issues that residents of Red Location were engaged in from the 1990s to the present day, reaching a peak with the occupation of the structures of the RLMCP. I turn my attention to emphasising the close link between demands for the right to dignified housing and increasing calls for recognition and the legitimacy to direct the township's development agenda. The

eighth chapter, *Preserving Memory, Rebuilding Roots*, focuses on how the township's past was variously appropriated in the context of the project both by the organisers and the residents, and on the relationship between memory, experience and citizenship. The ninth chapter, *Defending Physical and Symbolic Spaces*, dwells on practices observed in Red Location that can be attributed to defence and guardianship as forms of ownership and appropriation. Such practices entail being and staying present, but also gaining ground and seizing upon the land of others, in addition to the creation of symbolic and material spaces where human healing became possible through the promotion of value systems that contrasted with or provided an alternative to those taken as common sense.

The first two "scores" (*Ownership and Change* and *Ownership and Belonging*) are characterised by a primary melodic theme shaped by the project documentation and statements from the project organisers. Within these chapters, it is also possible to discern a countermelody overlaying or underlaying the first in the reactions of residents living near the project, public officials, academics and local politicians. A third melody (everyday practices as ownership), on the other hand, forms a counterpoint, a collection of independent melodies (the trajectories of the different participants) that give rise to a harmonic, polyphonic sequence (inhabiting the city), in which conflict is considered and reconceptualised as but one possible form of citizenship.

A note on anonymisation and use of terms

I did not adopt a uniform process of anonymisation when writing this thesis. Guaranteeing the anonymity of every person I interviewed would have been impossible unless I did not specify the name or geographical location of the project. Had I decided to omit details of the geographic, social and historical contexts in which this specific development project took place it would have been extremely difficult to describe the steps of the research and justify my conclusions. Further, many of the individuals I cite have been repeatedly interviewed in the media and have written articles for daily newspapers or academic journals, participated in conferences and conventions, and have been identified in videos and photographs. Several of these people are very well-known or have repeatedly made their involvement in the project

explicit. For this reason, and also so as not to appear duplicitous, I chose to not anonymise those people who have willingly associated their names with the project (for example Noero, the architect behind the entire cultural centre, or Riordan, the primary project organiser). I used people's names if they referenced articles that they had written or previous interviews they had given to the press or that were available online. I anonymised, however, all interviews that I carried out to make it more difficult to uncover the source of potentially sensitive comments. I anonymised to the greatest extent possible public officials, museum staff members, politicians and residents, especially when their comments took on a confidential tone.

Through reflecting on identity representations and forms of belonging, appropriations and reappropriations, part of this thesis engages with the difficulty of finding new terms to describe the changed society of post-apartheid South Africa, or, at least, a society that wants itself to have progressed away from the segregation of apartheid. Contemporary everyday life in South Africa is still steeped in racialised terms from the segregationist regime and, even where there now exist terms that are considered more appropriate and politically correct, these have not always been integrated into everyday use. In Port Elizabeth, the linguistic sediments of place names and common expressions from the apartheid years, alongside new terms and distinctions on top of colonial toponymies, evoke the image of a city in which the scars of segregation run deep, while at the same time borders are redefined by different social configurations.

In this thesis, I have reproduced terms referring to racial categories (Black, Coloured, Indian, White, etc.) when relevant, for example when discussing my interlocuters' identification with or alienation from a certain group or individual.

As for place names, I more often use the name Port Elizabeth, which is undoubtedly more frequently used in current parlance than Nelson Mandela Bay (the name of the metropolitan city established in 2001 that encompasses Port Elizabeth, Uitenhage and Despatch). Similarly, I alternate between the terms "location" and "township" in reference to Red Location, while I always use "township" in reference to New Brighton, the area that also encompasses Red Location, again, following common custom. The term "township", a word with connotations of the Black residential areas of the apartheid years, today does not correspond to any administrative unit, but it is still commonly used by everyone living in the city,

whether or not they live in those areas themselves. Red Location is a part of New Brighton, which is in turn part of the area of Ibhayi.²⁹ I also use the word “township” to refer to Ibhayi.

Despite making plain the persistent legacy of apartheid on spatial, economic, social and relational levels, in public policy and everyday practices, the aim of this research project is not to represent South Africa as a static and rigid society completely at the mercy of its ghosts. On the contrary, the reflections of this research, the doors opened, the dialogues and conversations generated, were made possible thanks to various people who out of self-interest, good-nature, political choice or protest have forged alternative paths and underground connections that bring together the fragments of the city.

²⁹ See Appendix 1: Maps, figure 2.

Part One. Projects and Proposals. Ownership and change

In 1996 during a discussion at an open meeting in Port Elizabeth about the intended use of the old postal building in the city centre, councillor Rory Riordan proposed the idea of creating a museum of anti-apartheid struggle in Red Location, an area of only 1.45km² and inhabited by 15,286 people,³⁰ located in the township of New Brighton. This was the first official reference to what would in years to come become the Red Location Museum and Cultural Precinct (RLMCP). The RLMCP, whose master plan would be altered many times over the years, was presented as a multisectoral state intervention consisting of the construction of a museum and other buildings, such as a library and an art gallery, on the vacant land next to the train station.

From its conception, the RLMCP was presented as an initiative that could achieve two distinct and intertwined objectives: firstly, the project proposed to trigger a dynamic of socio-economic development in the location through substantial investments in the sectors of art, culture and the preservation of artistic heritage – in short, through transforming several homes in the location into a museum. Secondly, the project was seen as an initiative aimed at urban regeneration. This regeneration in turn was portrayed in terms of reparations to the inhabitants of the location, or as compensation for their active participation in anti-apartheid struggles and the enormous suffering that they had endured.

The RLMCP was conceived as the first, crucial step towards the development of the location and as a driving force of social change. This change was generated through the unfurling of multiple forms of ownership and appropriation: on a spatial level, the organisers of the RLMCP identified the site, beneficiaries and headquarters of the project, separating them from possible alternatives. On a discursive and symbolic level, the singularity of the chosen site and its inhabitants, and the urgency of the need for external development, were used to justify these choices. On a material level, appropriating or taking ownership of the project entailed valorising what was deemed functional, and devaluing or dismissing elements judged superfluous. The project organisers viewed change as a linear path towards liberation and development, involving construction and therefore a selection. Contrary to what the project designers had envisaged, and as had been the case with similar projects that

³⁰ NMBM (2013), A Demographic profile of Ward 15 in Nelson Mandela Bay, Port Elizabeth.

had previously been developed in the location, change was not a coherent process. Rather, it resulted from further reappropriations and retranslations of the project by the other participants, and also from continual negotiation and trial and error. While development projects sometimes tend to confuse discourse on change (projections of potential changes onto the present) and change itself (what does actually change), the RLMCP brought to light the contradictions between discourse that presents change as unstoppable and transformations that occurred on the site of the project that were instead ambiguous, incomplete, notably slower and not always similar to those that the organisers had hoped for.

The RLMCP envisioned and constructed change through projecting and proposing. The acts of projecting and proposing are inextricably intertwined, as indicated by both words having etymological roots in the act of “throwing forwards”.³¹ Projecting and proposing are actions that are carried out in the present with a view to building an imagined future. Projecting, further, has a secondary meaning of “forcefully pushing out or forward”, linking this action to the “transfer outwards of impulses, feelings, interior states that the subject refuses or does not recognise, locating them in other persons or things”. In medicine, a “projected pain” is a pain that is “felt in a different area of the body to the part that is injured”.³² A projection, then, evokes the subject or conditions of its generation, but only if it is possible to read its less visible part or reconstruct the process of transfer and distance between source and creation. It is therefore essential to analyse the RLMCP’s processes of projection to understand what type of change the project organisers envisioned for Red Location.

In order for the project to garner support, the RLMCP had to be presented as the best possible solution to a significant and inescapable public problem. It required, therefore, the problem it proposed to resolve to be prioritised on Port Elizabeth’s development agenda (Kingdon 1984). The project aimed to accomplish the regeneration of Red Location and it was essential that the urgency and importance of such an intervention was publicly recognised and prioritised by the Municipality.

Riordan’s speech prompted what Dvora Yanow has described as the “struggle for the determination of meanings” (Yanow 1996: 19), the process of “framing” a problem. Riordan strove to ensure that the representation of Red Location that

³¹ See Italian etymology dictionary, Etimo.

³² See the entry for “proiettare” in the Treccani dictionary.

prevailed was of a place that was both extremely impoverished and that had a great historical and cultural heritage to draw upon. The project organisers steered the township towards modernity via “enrichment capitalism” (Boltanski and Esquerre 2017), based on the generation of profit through the interactions between art, culture, tourism and capitalisation. Regeneration in the township was presented as a way to manage poverty and social marginalisation – the process would lead to the formation of cohesive and safe communities, alongside the inclusion of inhabitants of disadvantaged areas in the project of the new city. In this regard, geographer Loretta Lees writes of the “emancipatory city”, referring to the paradoxes and possibilities inherent to the modern city’s promises of liberation (2004). The project was represented as crucial for the entire city, but above all for the inhabitants of Red Location, the primary beneficiaries of opportunities to be created by the project in terms of employment, business creation and urban regeneration in the location. Enrichment capitalism and urban regeneration were seen as the driving forces behind socio-economic development: the proliferation of individual opportunities to enter the workforce and the integration of the location into the knowledge economy, creative economy and innovation were put forward as the panacea to Red Location’s problems and a form of restitution to the inhabitants, as opposed to redistributive policies or the advancement of social justice. Similar processes have been identified in Cape Town by Booyens (2012) and in the United States by Zukin (1995) and Neumann (2016), particularly with reference to post-industrial transition.

The project organisers utilised a projected, imagined future as a persuasive strategy and performative action: as soon as they painted a picture of the future that the project would bring about, it started to exist as a real possibility and materialise into precise objectives. The process of “framing” and communicating meaning, the interpretative framework of the problem and its solutions, made space for dynamics of inclusion-exclusion (Snow and Benford 1992; Rein and Schön 1996) that occurred through multiple appropriations. In this way, the image of the township and its inhabitants was “made appropriate” for the trajectory towards liberation. The production of hierarchies and dynamics of exclusion-inclusion which shaped the representations of space, time and the inhabitants generated forms of dispossession, deprivation and expropriation, not only in terms of potential ownership of goods or property (such as the relocation of “shacks” built on the land chosen for the project),

but also in terms of the denial of social and political recognition and the restricted freedom to decide whether to confer value to an object, space, etc. (Elyachar 2005; Harvey 2004; Buthler and Athanasiou 2013).

On a spatial level, the project organisers projected a cartography of becoming onto everyday places. In this sense, the location was perceived to be a patchwork of “empty space” and “sacred places”. While the sacred places – to be rediscovered, valued and preserved – were crucial to imagining the future and future coexistence (they included, for example, sites that had been the stages of anti-apartheid struggle), areas that were deemed unnecessary or controversial were construed as empty space. The shacks, smaller shops and shebeens (informal taverns) were dismissed as useless and so were at risk of being dismissed and forgotten. On a temporal level, the past and objects from the past acquired great value, while the present was reduced to a stepping-stone on the journey towards a radiant future. As for the inhabitants, they were predominantly represented as a disadvantaged and disintegrated community that was nonetheless brimming with potential that the project could bring to fruition, as it would constitute a socially diversified and attractive space for the middle-class.

These representations were in turn liable to further interpretations and appropriations. Considering representations as the attribution of meaning and attributions of meaning as acts of subjection, Judith Butler maintains that “any mobilization against subjection will take subjection as its resource” (1997: 104). Subjects can appropriate the meaning that is ascribed to them through translation or semantic shift, in other words, through reattributing meaning, redefining identities and neutralising the top-down impact of normative or classificatory power (Butler 2004; Spivak 1999). Resignification, then, is in effect a form of appropriation, and in the context of the RLMCP it took various forms – from the rediscovery of pride about living in Red Location and so the feeling of justification in claiming the protection of socio-economic rights, to the inhabitants’ incorporation of the image of a cultural community.

1. Red Location: a place worth giving new life to

The first proposals for the regeneration of Red Location, a small township in the Municipality of Nelson Mandela Bay,³³ date back to 1996. In that year, the architect John Rushmere set out on a series of surveys commissioned by Rory Riordan, an African National Congress (ANC) councillor in the Transitional Local Council, the first mixed administration of the city of Port Elizabeth. Riordan was the mastermind of the One City Budget, the first document to amalgamate the previously separately governed districts into a single financial plan. Rushmere was asked to conduct a feasibility study for the construction of a museum of the struggle³⁴ and other public buildings in Red Location, an area that was notorious for conditions of extreme poverty and disadvantage, but also for the residents' commitment to anti-apartheid struggles. The area was overpopulated and lacking paved roads, drinkable water and sewerage systems. The houses, made out of wood and sheet metal, periodically had their roofs blown off by storms and the strong winds that blast through the bay incessantly year-round, and frequently suffered fires that left residents homeless and killed multiple victims.³⁵

Rushmere introduced his proposed master plan with two sentences that in addition to providing a succinct description of the site read like a declaration of intent. The first read: "a special place with a community assembled over many generations and with a history rich in unpublished anecdote worth conserving. A place worth giving new life to" (Rushmere and Thompson 1996). The second, immediately beneath it: "a poor barren place with the potential to become much, much more, for itself and for the others" (*ibid*). This two-sided representation of an unwieldy, simultaneously glorious and painful past and of a potentially prosperous future about to bloom has accompanied the entire recent history of Red Location.

The 1990s, even before the formal end of apartheid and the democratic elections of 1994, were characterised by the desire to rework South Africa's

³³ In the 1990s, Port Elizabeth was still its own administrative area. In 2001, the city was merged with Despatch and Uitenhage, giving rise to a metropolis of 1,500,000 inhabitants – Nelson Mandela Bay. See Appendix 3.

³⁴ In common parlance, the term "struggle" refers to anti-apartheid resistance.

³⁵ In the local paper *The Herald*, in the period 1993–1996, Red Location made headlines very rarely and, when it was mentioned in the news, it was usually describing yet another fire: '100 are homeless after fire', 31/03/1993; 'Three burnt to death in shacks fire', 05/11/1993; 'Fire destroys Red Location homes', 19/01/1995; 'Families destitute, homeless after fire', 05/04/1995.

tumultuous history and memory and the urgent need to shape a new national project, founded on unity in diversity. These years gave rise to both the institution of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), that concluded its operations in 1998, and the drawing up of the new South African Constitution (1996), whose preamble reads:

“We, the people of South Africa, recognize the injustices of our past; Honour those who suffered for justice and freedom in our land; Respect those who have worked to build and develop our country; and Believe that South Africa belongs to all who live in it, united in our diversity” (Opening to the preamble of the South African Constitution, 1996).

For the local government of Port Elizabeth, the reconciliation between past and future manifested itself in a series of hybrid policies aimed at amending the geography of a deeply divided and fragmented city, granting full citizenship rights to subjects who had previously been discriminated against and bridging the distance between the suburbs and the townships, including through improving services and infrastructure. Poverty reduction policies, extensions to social security, and the creation of libraries, community centres and hospitals, went hand in hand with the valorisation of and capitalisation on the memory of apartheid. To illustrate the efforts undertaken by local government at that time, during an interview councillor Riordan showed me a table compiled in the 1990s that listed all the townships in Port Elizabeth, what infrastructures each was already equipped with and which were missing. The councillor explained, “we would try to fill the gaps” (Rory Riordan, interview 13/03/2015). Riordan’s statement provides a striking example of early post-apartheid policies that delegated economic redistribution to public investment in infrastructural improvements and understood service provision as one of its primary functions. The establishment of the RLMCP fits perfectly within this way of conceiving urban development.

Before 1992, the city of Port Elizabeth was governed by a series of different councils that were characterised by the intense racialisation of apartheid: the Port Elizabeth City Council (PECC) governed the white majority city centre; the North Areas Management Committee (NAMC) overlooked a Coloured and white area; several Black Local Authorities (BLA) formed local government in the Black townships, in particular the areas of Ibhayi, Motherwell, KwaMagxaki-KwaDesi. Between 1992 and 1994,

members of the Transnational Local Council of Port Elizabeth came together for the first time in a united town council to commit to getting to know each other, acknowledging each other and charting a way of working together and reaching a shared understanding of development in the city, on the basis of shared objectives across multiple areas. When Riordan was the leader of the Human Rights Trust before becoming the city government's finance manager, he raised funds from several European embassies to embark on a sort of tour with other future councillors to discover various possible forms of city government that countries employed.

Some twenty delegates, including representatives from the ANC and the Democratic Alliance (DA), long-standing officials, finance managers, engineers, etc., visited New York, Washington, Moscow, Berlin and Bern. The delegation was led by Nceba Faku, a New Brighton local who would later become the city's first mayor, after having served thirteen years in detention on Robben Island for his affiliation with the ANC. Ernest Malgas, an activist who grew up in Red Location, member of the ANC following the uprisings of 1952³⁶ and member of Umkhonto weSizwe since its inception,³⁷ also participated in the tour. Malgas, who was subjected to fourteen years in detention on Robben Island and who was brutally tortured in a second period of detention during the state of emergency, was already ill during this journey and died several years later in 1998. Remembering these years, Riordan connected the idea for the RLMCP project to a phrase that Malgas had uttered one day during the international tour: "Malgas called us and asked us for two things: make sure that the fight against apartheid would be memorialized and improve terrible conditions in Red Location" (Rory Riordan, interview 17/11/2015).

As the 1990s came to a close, the valorisation of memory progressed hand in hand with infrastructural improvements and urban regeneration, as if they were two sides of the same coin. In 1998, for example, the Emlotheni Memorial Park was created in memory of six ANC/Mk³⁸ activists, including Vuysile Mini, who was among

³⁶ For further discussion see the following chapter, 1.1.

³⁷ Umkhonto weSizwe, Mk. was the armed wing of the African National Congress (ANC).

³⁸ Daniel Ndongeni, Nolali Mpentse, Wilson Kayingo, Samuel Jonas, Zinakile Mkaba and Vuysile Mini. The memorial stone of the monument reads: "This monument is a fitting tribute to the heroism, selflessness, courage and patriotism displayed by the gallant fighters who are buried here as the first detachment of the glorious people's army [Umkhonto weSizwe] to be butchered by the apartheid forces. As a present generation and for those to come we will forever remain indebted to their supreme sacrifice for freedom, justice and democracy in our country".

the first to be condemned to death by the apartheid regime in 1964. The memorial was located at the intersection of Limba Street and Nqadini Road, on the western borders of Red Location. Emlotheni in isiXhosa means “the place of the earth/the sand”: the memorial hosting the tombs of the six activists stands in a space that was previously a patch of earth on the corner of a street, previously used for clandestine meetings and gatherings. The memorial was also conceived of as a way to regenerate a semi-abandoned area: the monumental tombs stand in front of a cobbled square, furnished with concrete benches and a few palm trees.³⁹

1. The construction of historical singularity

Councillor Riordan, following the advice of the activist Malgas, chose Red Location as a potential site for the RLMCP because of the pre-existing representation of Red Location as a space of fervent political activity and of New Brighton as a space of artistic creativity. Riordan’s task (and that of the project organisers and later, the museum staff) was to select and combine various elements of these interpretations in such a way as to give rise to a narrative of singularity. There were many sites of anti-apartheid struggle in Port Elizabeth and across South Africa, and so it was necessary to justify the choice of Red Location as the site for the museum and the regeneration project, rather than other townships that could have boasted equally impressive records of resistance and were just as in need of urban regeneration projects. Boltanski and Esquerre underline how the creation of difference, identity and exception, and the promotion of certain places as “destinations” are typical characteristics of a new form of capitalism – the “collection form” – and relate this to the “induced creation of cultural heritage” (2014). Noting the arbitrary nature of the distinction between Red Location and other townships and retracing the processes that produced this singularity does not mean belittling the events that took place there, nor doubting the validity of the symbolic events of anti-apartheid struggle that occurred in the township. Rather, my aim is to analyse how the project planning phase triggered a gradual mechanism in which the identification of Red Location as the most

³⁹ *Emlotheni*, conceived in the same years as the RLMCP, presents similar ambiguities, although on a reduced scale: a “one-way” rereading of history and a complete detachment from the lives of the inhabitants of the neighbourhood. The monument was vandalised, had electrical and building material stolen, and was subsequently fenced off. It remains closed most of the time.

appropriate site for a museum of the struggle required the project organisers to encourage and steer academics, residents and museum staff towards a certain representation of the location's history. In turn, research projects pursuing this line of enquiry (concentrating on the events and protagonists of anti-apartheid struggle in the location) produced knowledge that ended up consolidating and confirming this original interpretation.

In this way, Red Location came to be considered as exceptional because it was a relatively confined space that had staged a series of key events in anti-apartheid resistance, the relevance of which reverberated beyond the confines of the city. Because of their past suffering, the residents of Red Location were also considered integral to the history of anti-apartheid struggle. The residents' extraordinary resistance was interpreted from wide political mobilisation and very high rates of ANC membership even during the party's underground period, and from the artistic, cultural and sports vitality of the location. Art, culture and sport were used to evidence the extraordinary sense of community, solidarity and resilience of Red Location and New Brighton inhabitants. In making the case for the project, Red Location was presented as a space teeming with history, where history had left more traces than in any other part of the city. Many other places with powerful legacies of anti-apartheid struggle are only a few minutes away from the border of the RLMCP. In Red Location, history is not only multi-layered, in the sense that it is possible to trace the entire history of the struggle in a single township, but these layers are visible and legible in the location's architecture. Tony Lancaster, director of the National Arts Festival of Grahamstown, one of the biggest national arts festivals, described Red Location as a "historical landscape", as if the location's history could be grasped through the landscape alone. In Red Location, one of the earliest locations to be established in South Africa, it is also possible to trace the stages of colonial oppression.

Red Location was therefore seen as a stratified zone in which the ex-hostel for migrant workers, the bottle stores, various churches, the last old houses still standing, the train station and the main community halls constituted parts of a broader whole. A simple wander through the location's streets could retrace the city's political history. The area has always been inhabited by an amaXhosa majority and the stories handed down mostly pertain to these groups. However, there are also Jewish businesses, as well as Afrikaners and English-speaking residents. The organisers of

the project, however, presented the location as if it were a textbook example of the history of oppression and resistance of Black Africans.

New Brighton and Red Location were represented as a series of sites, each constituting a symbolic place that evoked the various stages of anti-apartheid struggle. Ibhayi's Local Spatial Development Framework, the document which formed the basis for urban planning in the Ibhayi area, even devotes a specific section to memory sites⁴⁰ that were seen as unique to the area.⁴¹

The singularity of the area was also expressed through the singularity attributed to those who inhabited it. The memories of eminent protagonists of the struggle recorded in contemporary histories paint an ambiguous picture of the everyday life of Red Location inhabitants: the proximity in which the residents were forced to live is evoked as much as to attest to the extreme poverty and tough living conditions that people endured as to explain the development of a particularly strong collective political consciousness. Countless accounts of clandestine meetings taking place in the more hidden parts of residential areas attest to this ambiguity. The historian Pat Gibbs writes:

When Mkhonto we Sizwe began underground, Red Location provided a convenient hiding place for political fugitives (and criminals) as there were 'cells' between the shack floors and the ground on which shacks had been erected. Residents of the location were happy to give political fugitives a place to hide. In such a small area, people knew their community members well.⁴²

One of the most cited statements on the history of Red Location is from Govan Mbeki, in an interview with the historians Janet Cherry and Pat Gibbs. The activist explains the location's almost "morphological" tendency towards clandestinity:

They said an armed struggle couldn't succeed in South Africa. There are no mountains, no big forests like in Algeria and other places. My view was – which was the view we adopted – that places like Red Location were the forests for underground work. If you influence and persuade

⁴⁰ NMBM (2015), *Ibhayi Local Spatial Development Framework, 2014-2020*, p. 40.

⁴¹ For further discussion on sites of the struggle in Red Location, see Appendix 2: Map of the Struggle.

⁴² Unpublished text written by Pat Gibbs (2013) for an exhibition on the history of Red Location that was supposed to be set up in the Red Location Museum, but that never took place because of the RLSC's occupation.

people over time to support the organisation, they would not give it away. So in that respect, the townships, especially areas like Red Location, became a virtual forest for the African National Congress (Cherry and Gibbs 2007: 116).

Historians have described how rising numbers of migrant workers, combined with the number of irregular inhabitants (including many women without residence permits who would settle in male hostels) led to the proliferation of informal settlements and families gradually moving into spaces that had previously accommodated single people (Baines 2002). Additionally, many immigrants came from Transkei, where they had suffered a sort of double oppression – from the apartheid government and from independent Bantustan.⁴³ Once these immigrants arrived in Port Elizabeth, they came into contact with trade union organisations (in the 1950s, particularly the South Africa Congress of Trade Unions, SACTU). Red Location was therefore also portrayed as an exemplary case of collaboration and coordination between intellectual elites, the urban proletariat and migrant workers.⁴⁴ In the ANC's darkest hour, when the movement was outlawed and went underground, the New Brighton branch counted 60,000 members, registered according to a complex system of codes in order to protect their identity (Cherry and Gibbs 2007: 119). Such wide support for the ANC, however, makes it rather difficult to trace the histories of those people who participated in other forms of politics or who were not part of movements and trade unions.

In all the descriptions of Red Location that accompanied the RLMCP, the history of the location is narrated as a sequence of historic events and heroic acts. Lists of the primary champions of the struggle always include a series of activists originally from the township. This is the case for Raymond Mhlaba, member of the South Africa Communist Party (SACP) and then the ANC, commander of Umkhonto WeSizwe until 1963 when he was condemned to a life sentence in prison during the Rivonia Trial,⁴⁵

⁴³ The Bantustans were established as formally self-governed regions in 1959, with the aim of incorporating the largest number of native Africans into their territories, following the logic of separated, coexisting ethnicities making up the country. Transkei, the Bantustan designated for the AmaXhosa – many people were forcefully deported there – declared itself independent in 1976, but its independence was only recognised by South Africa as another form of separation and population control.

⁴⁴ In reality, the city was not exclusively a site of resistance. See Cherry and Gibbs (2007).

⁴⁵ The Rivonia Trial lasted from 1963 to 1964 and led to the arrest of ten ANC leaders, convicted of having committed more than 221 acts of sabotage. Rivonia was the name of the suburb of Johannesburg where Liliesleaf Farm was located, which was used as an ANC refuge. The Trial had the

and who in 1994 became the Premier of the Eastern Cape. Equally consistently present in the lists of heroes is Govan Mbeki, member of the SACP and founder of the Umkhonto weSizwe, who was convicted in the Rivonia Trial and released in 1987. Mbeki, the father of the ex-president Thabo Mbeki, was one of the greatest Marxist intellectuals of apartheid South Africa. Ever present is also Lilian Diedricks, trade unionist and founder (in 1954) of the Federation of South African Women (FEDSAW), one of the four women at the front of the Women's March against legislation concerning the "pass" in 1956.⁴⁶ There is also Francis Baard, member of the ANC Women's League, and Florence Matomela, representative of the executive of the ANC, President of the Provincial Section of the ANCWL and Vice-President of FEDSAW, who was incarcerated for involvement with clandestine groups. The activists cited are above all those whose importance and fame extended beyond the location or the city of Port Elizabeth. It is also possible to discern a correlation between heroes and pioneers, with those who were the first to participate in a movement or to usher in new strategies of resistance being celebrated as heroes.

2. Genealogy of the extraordinary: the historiography of Red Location

The RLMCP's reconstruction of the location's history, oscillating between narratives of anti-apartheid heroism and details of everyday struggles, is a condensed version of the various ways in which different currents of South African historiography have chosen to narrate and interpret the history of the township during the years of the segregationist regime. The narrative of the location's singularity in fact results from the convergence of two different historiographic frameworks: one concentrating on the feats of anti-apartheid, the other on the township's social history.

precise aim of neutralising the movement. During this process, Nelson Mandela gave a long speech that expressed the reasons for the ANC's decision to move towards the use of violence and the creation of the armed wing of the Congress, the MK. Having been a "Rivonia trialist" is still today considered hugely impressive.

⁴⁶ In 1956, in Pretoria, 10,000–20,000 women marched on the Union Buildings, the seat of the South African government, to present a petition to Prime Minister J. G. Strijdom against the extension of permit regulations. The "passes" were perceived as a way of controlling Black African labour-power and restricted access to urban space only to individuals in possession of these permits, failing to recognise the rights of a large proportion of the population. With increasing numbers of women employed mostly as domestic workers between 1910 and the 1950s, the apartheid government tried to apply these regulations also to female workers. The Women's March did not only represent women's resolute refusal of the pass laws, but it was also the first, crucial feminist demonstration in the context of anti-apartheid struggle.

The apartheid regime lasted forty-four years from 1948 to 1992. Several of its underlying principles, however, were already present in embryonic form in the years preceding the rise of the nationalist party. Similarly, what is called “anti-apartheid struggle”, the multiple ways of resisting and defying the regime of racial segregation, spans an extremely wide temporal arc. To this day, divisions of the apartheid regime and anti-apartheid struggle into distinct historical chapters are highly contested. For example, some scholars date the origins of the anti-apartheid movement to the birth of the ANC in 1912, while others argue that the beginnings of a form of government founded on racial separation must have its roots in British colonialism and domination.⁴⁷

For simplification, historians, but also school textbooks, tend to divide the history of anti-apartheid struggle into decades: the first waves of protests and the consolidation of the ANC in the 1950s; the Rivonia Trial, the arrest of ANC leaders and the Congress being forced underground in the 1960s; students and trade union movements coming centre stage in the 1970s; the conflict intensifying and the declaration of a state of emergency in many cities in the 1980s; and the release of Nelson Mandela and the beginning of the transition the 1990s. From this perspective, Red Location is represented as an exemplary historical site: places and buildings recalling events that occurred in the location throughout the entire period are still standing, and so it is possible to identify elements to represent each decade and period of the struggle.⁴⁸ In the eyes of the organisers, Red Location therefore offered a material expression of this way of structuring the history of anti-apartheid struggle.

Given the length of the period under consideration, the history of apartheid was not written only after the end of the regime in 1994, but also during the years of segregation. To this day, the historiography written during the apartheid years provides an indispensable basis for historians trying to understand the complexity of

⁴⁷ Criticism of liberal historians who have identified the origins of apartheid in the border wars and conflicts between Boer and Bantu populations are attributed to Martin Legassick and other so-called “revisionist” South African historians working in the 1960s. According to this view, apartheid is instead considered to be consequence of political dynamics, cultural encounters and conflict. The revisionists presented a Marxist materialist interpretation, considering racial segregation to be the result of conflict and pre-colonial border relationships, the introduction of British capital, development of the mining sector and consolidation of an economic system founded on migrant labour. See Legassick (2010). Essentially, the revisionists analysed the concepts of class and race as interconnected. Disagreements over the relationship between apartheid and capitalism, class and race, persist to this day.

⁴⁸ See Appendix 2: Map of the Struggle.

almost half a century of events, protests and socio-political struggles. Alongside providing an unavoidable legacy, however, historical works and studies from these years present several peculiarities that complicate the historical tasks of selection and reconstruction. The history written during the apartheid years was an emergent history, a “history in a hurry”, to use the eloquent expression of Albert Grudlingh:⁴⁹ a type of historical reconstruction that is almost immediate and immediately put to use, produced through consulting multiple sources (local newspapers, popular works, leaflets, public statements, etc.). It was a history that made use of activist testimonies and was determined to narrate the movement from the inside-out. This type of history was by its very nature admittedly partisan, to the point of intentionally producing a militant history. From the 1960s onwards, writing history in South Africa or writing the history of South Africa was for many historians a sort of civic duty, aiming to narrate and expose forms of oppression and record social and political struggles. The issue of the availability of sources overlapped with that of the uniqueness of testimonies: in prolonged years of repression, censorship and forced clandestine activities, it was difficult to salvage first-hand testimonies and often oral accounts were the only source available for writing history, with all the limitations and problematics that they entail.⁵⁰

The narrative of Red Location inhabitants’ activism undoubtedly reflects this first stage of South African historiography, giving the impression of a fortified, compact and cohesive district, in which every action had a strategic end and a political connotation.

The end of the 1970s and the 1980s represent a turning point in the historiography of the struggle. In 1977, a group of historians from Wits University in Johannesburg launched the History Workshop (HW). These scholars, following in the footsteps of the British HW,⁵¹ wanted to express a Marxist humanism and chose to write social history by concentrating on the local, considering the formation of social

⁴⁹ Cited in Sapire 2002: 15.

⁵⁰ See Portelli (1998) on oral history. Portelli identifies oral history as a narrative resource, with all the characteristics of tales and folklore.

⁵¹ The British HW was born in 1967 at Ruskin College, Oxford and was inaugurated by Raphael Samuel. The HW was also influenced by the Communist Party Historian Group, in which E.P. Thompson participated. Many South African historians were inspired by the methodology and principles of this social historian. While the British HW drew to a close at the beginning of the 1990s, the South African version still exists today and continues to provide a reference point in the study of contemporary South African history.

classes in the light of capital and economic dynamics. The historians of the Hw proposed a view of the townships as spaces that fostered social and cultural alternatives of resistance, and contact and relation between urban elites and migrant workers. Urban material culture and artistic outputs were analysed as testimonies of the “agency” of the “Black working class” (Bonner 1994; Posel 2010).

While the birth of the Hw produced research into the differences and specificities of South African townships, the protest movements of the 1980s transformed the representation of these spaces. The townships became “collective heroes” and narratives of their political mobilisation and role in the journey to liberation were prioritised over all other aspects (Sapire 2012). From the 1980s, the Hw’s methodology was criticised for the fact that its representation of the townships as “incubators of resistance” (Sapire 2012) created a strongly negative portrayal of those places (the accounts of resistance are in fact proportionate to those of domination and oppression). There were also criticisms that excessive localism obscured the relationships and interactions between local and national levels and precluded any generalisation. Finally, the overwhelming reliance on oral history was considered to be indicative of scarce historical veracity and reliability (Sapire 2012). In the 1980s, therefore, two almost opposing historiographical currents established themselves: the by-then consolidated tradition of social history which drew on anthropological research carried out in the 1960s⁵² and focused on the everyday life in the township was matched by a type of history that was more inclined towards what the historian Noor Nieftagodien has defined as “struggle heroization” (2010: 169), the representation of the history of anti-apartheid struggle as a succession of heroic figures and extraordinary events, usually in connection with the ANC. In the 1990s, several works – for example, the encyclopaedic collection “The Road to Democracy in South Africa” – tried to bring these two trends together through considering a larger number of movements and trying to find points of similarity between the different regions of South Africa.

In general, two types of narrative and formalisation of the location’s history have endured and informed the approaches that shaped the design of the RLMCP: the first participates in the social history tradition and dwells on cultural production and

⁵² For example, the research of Philip Mayer and his team. For more information see Bank (2002).

everyday practices, which in any case are often interpreted as practices of resistance or subversion. The second, on the other hand, belongs to the register of anti-apartheid history that is characterized by decisive moments and characters in the struggle on a local level but that resonate on the national level.

The RLMCP organisers' suggestion of arranging Red Location's anti-apartheid history within a museum was an attempt to homogenise an extremely polyphonic and fragmented narrative into a coherent line. Apart from Cherry's and Gibbs's dense chapters on the Eastern Cape in the volumes of "The Road to Democracy in South Africa" and a handful of other monographs,⁵³ the history of Red Location still essentially sits in the memories of the protagonists, inherited folklore, and archival documents held by local government and the security police.

3. Red Location's borders. Variations on a theme

The construction of the RLMCP made the perception of the borders around Red Location and the project highly variable. I use the word "borders" mostly in reference to symbolic separations since, as mentioned above, Red Location does not correspond to any administrative unit. The representation of the space changed in two ways. Firstly, Red Location had previously always been described as a small district of New Brighton, but with the construction of the RLMCP became a reference point that other places were situated in relation to ("X is close to Red Location"), thus extending its symbolic borders. At the same time, the site of the project was pinpointed as the centre of the location. Before the project, the stand-out feature of the location had been the train station. Even today, people coming and going from the station or crossing the pedestrian bridge to the factories of Deal Party pass alongside the RLMCP.

The creation of Red Location dates back to 1902. For all intents and purposes, Red Location can be described as the oldest part of New Brighton, seeing as the other locations that make up the township developed only from the 1920s (initially White Location, then McNamee Village in 1948 and then Kwaford, Boastville and Elundini between 1948 and 1951). When it was first established Red Location was a very small

⁵³ Including: Cherry (2011); Baines (2002), whose narrative stops at 1954; Matyu (1996), in which fact and fiction merge into each other; Robinson (1996), who focuses on the apparatuses of the apartheid government using PE as a case site; and the autobiography of Raymond Mhlaba (Mhlaba and Mufamadi 2001), which provides a sort of annual report.

area of only 0.22km² that would later come to be bordered to the west by a block of houses covering an area of similar dimensions called White Location. From the end of the 1950s onwards, Red Location was incorporated into New Brighton, while still maintaining its own distinctive characteristics. The contemporary area of New Brighton is about 4.2km², so around twenty times bigger than the original area. Today, New Brighton is divided for administrative purposes into New Brighton 1 and 2, though people living in Port Elizabeth generally speak of New Brighton without differentiating between these two zones. The name Red Location also continues to be used by the inhabitants of the township. Specifically, it is the symbolic border of Avenue A, to the west of the township, that separates White Location and Red Location from McNamee.⁵⁴

After the announcement of the RLMCP project, however, the area of Red Location started to gradually become more important, and so the toponym “Red Location” came to indicate a wider area than it had done originally. Today, for example, the name “White Location” is rarely used, the entire area is instead referred to as “Red Location”. The symbolic borders of Red Location have expanded to such an extent that today people say they are from Red Location even if they live nearer to Elundini or Boastville. This is because Red Location has become a popular place that it is ever easier to identify with even for those who do not live nearby.

From an administrative point of view, Red Location is located in ward fifteen. The ward is increasingly described as the “Red Location” ward, even though in reality it encompasses a much wider area. In this way, Red Location has developed porous and variable borders that fluctuate according to whether someone is referring to the specific site of the project, the original area of Red Location, or the immediate surroundings of the location. Additionally, people from Red Location occasionally say that a building or house is in Red Location when it would be more accurate to say, “in New Brighton”. Other times, conversely, when asked to list the schools or churches in the location, people also include those that are situated in nearby areas. The project therefore contributed to a vision of Red Location and New Brighton as being on a continuum, or even as interchangeable, with the only separation still being represented by Avenue A. In addition to Ferguson Road to the south, Avenue A. can

⁵⁴ See Appendix 1: Maps, figure 3.

be defined as what Lynch would describe as an “edge”, a border or penetrable barrier that mark discontinuity (Lynch 1960). At the same time, the project master plan mapped out new features that would contribute to the reestablishment of a sort of “spatial specificity” in the location. Singaphi Road and the train station became “nodes” (Lynch 1960), points of intersection, confluence or convergence. In other words, in creating or improving roads leading to Red Location, the project contributed to the establishment of a “district” (Lynch 1960): a section of the city with a recognisable and identifiable character, that you have the impression of entering. Still to use Lynch’s terms, the buildings of the RLMCP constituted a “landmark” or a “node”, a characterising symbol that could be seen from afar and from multiple perspectives. In the logics of the project, the RLMCP was the centre, the heart of Red Location, and thus encapsulated its identity. It was, for all effects and purposes, a spatial-temporal reference point.

4. The suppression of the ordinary

Placing the project on the city’s development agenda required first and foremost a separation: the declaration of Red Location’s singularity and the rewriting of its borders separated and distinguished it from the other townships. This spatial separation also impacted the inhabitants, prompting dynamics of inclusion-exclusion and drawing divisions between insiders and outsiders, beneficiaries and non-beneficiaries, populated and empty spaces. Within the area selected for the project, the ordinariness of everyday life came to be suppressed.

The RLMCP contributed to the creation of an official mythology that celebrated the political history of Red Location as something exceptional. In his analysis of Alexandra, a township in Johannesburg where a project akin to the RLMCP with similar aims of valorising memory and promoting local development was launched in the 2000s, Nieftagodien notes how Alexandra was also put forward as a “special” place with regard to its political history, but that had the adverse effect of marginalising “ordinary people” and their everyday experiences. A similar dynamic also occurred in Red Location. Baines observes, “in the case of the (hi)story of the townships, the triumphalist narrative of the liberation struggle tends to overshadow the memories of the marginalised people who inhabit them” (Baines 2005: 244).

The representation of the township as a series of historic sites consolidated over time gives rise to an extremely partial interpretation of the location's complexity, even on an architectural level. At first glance, it is actually extremely difficult to pinpoint sites of historical significance in Red Location, just as it is difficult to understand the unique qualities or importance of completely ordinary buildings. In the township, furthermore, there are other historically significant sites that are not recognised as such because they do not relate directly to anti-apartheid struggles. This is the case, for example, for places of worship like the Ethiopian Church, the Bantu Church of Christ or the Edward Cook Methodist Church, which were founded in the early years of the twentieth century. Even memories associated not with specific places but rather with paths or routes that were significant in the years of the struggles – such as escape routes, open doors, courtyards, crossings – were not included the version of history that the project commemorated.

Discussing informal settlements, Anne-Maria B. Makhulu notes how “the shantytown demanded a very particular on-the-ground spatial knowledge” (Makhulu 2015: 55). In Red Location, though not a slum, this spatial knowledge was essential: the topographical layout of the location has become gradually more complicated, despite the clarity and simplicity of its initial designs with long rows of houses arranged in straight lines on perpendicular streets. Additionally, although some brick-and-mortar houses continue to represent an exception in terms of longevity, many of the wooden houses have disappeared and been replaced by houses built as part of the Reconstruction and Development Programme. At the same time, far from being crystallised in the remains of these houses, Red Location in the 1990s was a dynamic township undergoing constant change. Some residents left their homes in pursuit of more modern neighbourhoods, others were forced to abandon them when their houses collapsed, others built new shacks. Over the years, many activists changed address, some died or remained in exile. Red Location, in short, became a diversified place, connected to the rest of the city and, as with everywhere else, subject to socioeconomic dynamics that characterised and still characterise the rest of South Africa.

Lists of historical sites and heroes did not only gradually come to consolidate into a reductive narrative, but they were also the first sign of processes of dispossession not dissimilar to those identified by Julia Elyachar in her analysis of

how NGOs in Cairo “incorporated the social practices of the poor into the free market”. This process, with the purported aim of emancipation, gives rise to dispossession.⁵⁵ Elychar states, “part of what is being dispossessed, in my view, is the power to decide what matters or, in other terms, what is value” (Elyachar 2005: 8). In the context of the RLMCP, it is possible to see that from the project’s very beginnings, it was the organisers who decided where the township’s value lay, triggering processes of dispossession and suppressing ordinariness from potential future projects in the location. Referring to Johannesburg and projects aiming to create and preserve cultural heritage, Mbembe notes, “specific historical objects are ripped out of their contexts even as the state busily tries to memorialize and museumize, to build new monuments and historic landscapes that are supposed to bring together the different fragments of the nation” (Mbembe 2008: 63), perfectly encapsulating the paradox at the heart of the construction of the RLMCP. In Red Location, the practices of ownership and appropriation evident in the planning and proposal phases had two sides. On one side was the appropriation of the township’s history and of some of its spaces in the name of improving the location, for example through creating new opportunities for employment, clubs, socialising, etc. On the other side, advancing a specific representation of the location in order to change it involved removing and excluding certain features of the place that continued to exist in parallel to the project but were not taken into consideration. Identifying shortcomings and highlighting potential therefore aspire to the same goal – they both involved reducing meaning so as to justify the project’s relevance. With this reduction of meaning, development can be represented as a linear, logical process; it can be expressed in terms of objectives, positioned on a timeline and mapped out in terms of outcomes. It becomes, in short, a process which is straightforward and reproducible.

⁵⁵ Elyachar refers to Harvey’s expression “accumulation by dispossession” to indicate the persistence of the exploitative practices of primitive or original accumulation in contemporary capitalism, from the privatization of land and the eviction of land workers to the conversion of collective property rights into private rights. Harvey further notes how capitalism has given rise to new forms of oppression, such as the marketisation of culture, history and intellectual creativity (Harvey 2004).

2. Local sheet metal and international tourism: from capitalisation to development

The narrative of Red Location as exceptional and unique does not completely explain the choice to invest public funds in this area rather than elsewhere. From the first proposals for the project, Councillor Riordan closely connected the themes of singularity and necessity: Red Location was presented as a disadvantaged area where development could be achieved through capitalising on history and expanding the tourism sector. Urban regeneration would have followed, both to modernise the location's infrastructure and to encourage tourism. The idea was that the more appropriately Red Location could represent and elucidate its history, the greater chance there would be for economic returns from the tourism sector to spread to the benefit of the residents. The project organisers connected the residents' poverty with the legacy of the apartheid regime, and investment in the township was therefore presented as a form of reparation. Material reparation would then be accompanied and strengthened by symbolic recognition, that is, by the possibility of retrospectively assuaging the suffering of those who had struggled against oppression.

In the guidelines for the nation-wide call for architectural tenders announced for the construction of a museum and cultural centre in Red Location, there was a clear intention to combine the valorisation of memory, economic development, material and symbolic restitution and the creation of an innovative public building embodying the ideal characteristics of contemporary South Africa. The construction of the museum and later the other buildings making up the cultural centre, involved a specific representation of the township's present. The RLMCP organisers gradually created an image of Red Location as a tourist destination and a site to host South Africa's greatest cultural centre. Reconciling the aims of capitalisation and development proved to be, however, a complex and far from certain operation.

1. The RLMCP as an economic development project

The RLMCP project was first announced in September 1996. During an open meeting about the fate of the old post office on Bakeens Street, the then City Councillor and Finance and Administration Committee Chairman Riordan announced to attendees that the Council was ready to seek funding to create an apartheid museum in Red

Location. During the meeting, which was attended by many journalists, Riordan stated that the project would be backed by an investment of 10–20 million rand and aired the possibility that it would be twinned with the Holocaust Memorial Museum in Washington, a partnership that never came about. At that time, another anti-apartheid museum was about to be built in South Africa. What in 2001 would become the Apartheid Museum in Johannesburg, however, was part of a project to build a casino: the consortium who won the contract, Akani Egoli (Gold Reef City), had included the construction of a museum in the proposed master plan because the call for tenders required applicants to indicate how proposed projects would develop the tourism sector and contribute to the creation of jobs.⁵⁶

Riordan, however, placed the RLMCP project on the local public policy agenda from its earliest stages, distinguishing it as an economic development project aimed at desegregating the township:

“[He said] the council had inherited a city in which about 17,000 families were still forced to endure the indignity of the bucket system and more than 15,000 had to walk distances to obtain water. The council was committed to bringing development to areas where there was at present no viable commercial life. It was hoped the Red Location Museum was an initiative to encourage this. Without these kinds of initiatives in the townships, they would simply become ghettos”. (‘R100m apartheid museum planned’, *The Herald*, 23/09/1996).

During our first interview, Riordan justified the RLMCP project with an analogous argument: “I quote Keynes: the state must deliver economic efficiency, social justice, individual freedom. We have achieved the last two and we need to concentrate on the first one. Now we have schools and clinics everywhere: access is universalized, but economic efficiency is not in place” (Rory Riordan, interview 17/03/2015.)

Riordan’s statement, as well as painting a slightly too rosy picture of access to services and social justice in post-apartheid South Africa, implies a precise understanding of the development problem as an eminently economic issue, to be resolved through integration into the market economy, the creation of business and improvements in investment attractiveness. Riordan, in short, advanced an extremely

⁵⁶ The museum was inserted in the project as a Section 21 company, a non-profit organization. For further comparisons between Red Location Museum and the Apartheid Museum see Findley (2011).

neoliberal vision, corroborated by the fact that, in another interview, he underlined how the township's residents had become overly dependent on a development logic in which the state bestows welfare payments and infrastructure: "Township community has changed. From being helpful and willing development, to what government can do for me" (Rory Riordan, interview 13/03/2015).

In the various briefs and business plans that accompanied the project, the word "inequality" is never mentioned, even though in the years immediately following the end of apartheid the topic of social justice was omnipresent. Red Location's poverty was emphasised as an obstacle to integration and to the residents' progress towards modernity. The competition brief, the document that presented the nationwide architectural competition for the contract for the project and museum, was illustrated by a very suggestive photograph of a woman standing on the doorstep of one of the location's original houses; the caption, a quote from the theatre critic Atkinson, reads, "say 'yes' to the seedlings and a giant forest cleaves the sky. Say 'yes' to the universe and the planets become your neighbours. Say 'yes' to dreams of love and freedom. It is the password to utopia" (Albrecht Heroldts Architects, 1998). The adjective "poor" is usually replaced by "disadvantaged". Similarly, the notions of "restitution" and "symbolic restitution" are favoured over the term "redistribution". The tourism economy and the opportunity of access to international tourism gradually became interpreted as a form of visibility and recognition for the location's residents.⁵⁷

Economic and social development were viewed primarily as a form of inclusion, in contrast to apartheid exclusion. Secondly, development was presented as a sort of payment of an outstanding debt, the material translation of symbolic restitution: through development policies, the local administration would recognise the contribution of the township's people to the constitution of the democratic state. Further, it can be stated that this recognition was proportional to the role attributed to the residents: a more significant role in the struggle for liberation would be met with a higher level of public investment. Thirdly, development corresponded to poverty deconcentration, that is, the transformation of the townships to make them more like residential areas, more attractive to newcomers with a higher average

⁵⁷ Further analysis in chapter 2.2.

income and so diversified in terms of the social background of their inhabitants. Justifications of emancipation were, in short, a smoke screen for processes of gentrification and the further marginalisation of urban poverty.⁵⁸

The RLMCP is an extremely relevant example of a state intervention that views economic development as a prerequisite for social development. The cultural centre was understood primarily as a tourist attraction and was charged with the task of improving Red Location citizens' quality of life. This process, as argued by Hibou and Bono (2016), has a dual value of presence and absence: the municipal government was present, but at the same time avoided direct responsibility for inequality, unemployment and lack of services, intervening instead in the sectors of culture and cultural heritage.

In the broader context of South Africa, the RLMCP was a truly pioneering project with regards to the dual function that it was assigned: on the one hand, it was and still is tangible evidence for how the state, on all levels, continues to be "developmental". On the other hand, it represented and represents an opening up to global economic models, favouring projections onto the international scene.

The proposal for the RLMCP was followed a few years later in 1994 by the launch of the Reconstruction and Development Plan (RDP), a set of measures to promote economic growth and reduce poverty. In the years immediately following the formal end of apartheid, the transformative component of socio-economic development, understood as the restoration or declaration of rights and the implementation of measures encouraging economic growth, was considered a principal instrument for building a democratic nation. Development was seen as the natural culmination of anti-apartheid struggle and was therefore identified as a panacea to the various ills that citizens had endured during the period of racial segregation. The answers to demands for freedom, struggles against oppression, extended rights and recognition, resolutions to socio-economic inequality and democracy were condensed into a single strategy: prompting development through state intervention. The remedy represented by development was also applied to calls for redistribution and restitution: economic development was presented as a sort of reparation whose positive effects were bound to multiply over time.

⁵⁸ Further analysis in chapter 3.6.

Bill Freund interprets the RDP as more of an “election manifesto” than an actual plan for economic recovery and social development (Freund 2012). The plan was abandoned in 1996, when the ANC was established in government, and was replaced by the adoption of GEAR (Growth, Employment and Redistribution), a collection of decidedly neoliberal macroeconomic policies. GEAR was the most significant manifestation of one of the ANC’s most unresolved issues. In the early 1990s, the Mandela government found itself having to represent a coalition between “pragmatists” and “socialists”, between proponents of integration with neoliberalism and those who favoured the institution of a socialist republic, first and foremost among them members of the South African Communist Party (SACP). Freund highlights how ANC leaders – from Tambo and Mandela to Mbeki – never actually favoured a socialist solution or the socialist undertones to the Freedom Charter (Freund 2012).⁵⁹

From the earliest days of its government, the ANC set out to integrate South Africa into capitalist economics while remaining the party for the emancipation of the “previously disadvantaged”, all those people whose opportunities were curtailed by racial segregation. The new South African government and those that followed it, in short, needed to demonstrate “South Africa as a well-run, efficient participant in the global economy that play[ed] by the rules but [was] governed by the ‘previously disadvantaged’” (Freund 2012: 194). In the 1990s and for many years later projects like the RLMCP were tasked with translating this vision into highly impactful material projects: they were seen as demonstrating the potential of combining social development and economic growth, prototypical examples that would speak to both national and international contexts.

The South African government, from 1994 to today, has always defined itself as “developmental”. Ben Fine, however, notes that this word has “become a sort of buzzword” (Fine 2016), evoked whenever a state intervention happens to have good results, or generally referring to a state that favours government intervention in a

⁵⁹ The Freedom Charter was a policy document adopted by the Congress of the People in 1955. The document was produced by the Congress Alliance, made up of the ANC, the South African Indian Congress (SAIC), the South African Coloured People’s Congress (SACPC), the South African Congress of Democrats (SACD) and the South African Congress of Trade Unions (SACTU). It was the expression of a multi-racial anti-apartheid front. The Freedom Charter articulated the shared objectives and common principles of the alliance. Some of these objectives, such as the redistribution of wealth, the emphasis on workers’ rights and land ownership for land workers, had a clearly socialist character.

much broader set of sectors than industry alone. In the National Development Plan 2030, passed by the South African government in 2012, economic growth and investment are charged with triggering virtuous cycles whose benefits range from more jobs to greater psychophysical wellbeing. The underlying assumption is that if on the one hand “government begins in the home, grows into the community, expands towards the city, flares toward the province, and engulfs the entire land” (NDP 2013: 11), on the other, politics should leave the economy room to prosper.⁶⁰ In any case a combination of participation, gradual decentralisation and most of all social development generated by economic growth continues to be, at least on a rhetorical level, the formula invoked by post-apartheid governments. Economic growth is set as the foundation which underlays the proliferation of opportunities and the revitalisation of social capital. Entering the formal economy and entrepreneurship are prized as exemplary actions, while excessive dependence on welfare support or state interventions are severely frowned upon.

When considered in the context of South African institutions’ interpretation of development the RLMCP starts to look a lot less exceptional. It represents to this day an attempt to demonstrate that a combination of state intervention and the free-market would benefit everyone – in Pretoria, Johannesburg, or even a little location in the Eastern Cape.

2. The construction of Red Location as a tourist attraction

In 1998, after Rushmere, the project architect, had designed the initial master plan, the Municipality of Port Elizabeth announced a national open architectural design competition for the design and construction of a museum of the struggle and a cultural centre in Red Location. The buildings would be constructed on what Riordan still to this day describes as an “empty piece of land” (Rory Riordan, interview 17/03/2015). On closer inspection, however, the space where the museum and the project’s other buildings now stand was by no means empty: the area was and is still home to multiple informal settlements. Homeowners who agreed to leave the area were

⁶⁰ Fine shows how the vision according to which everyone can prosper, starting with the most disadvantaged, presumes a unity of purpose and identity that does not account for the minority that exercise economic power, internationalized and financialised capital, and do not have any necessary commitment to the country (Fine 2016).

persuaded to move house in exchange for measly compensation.⁶¹ In this sense, too, the RLMCP was born as a mark of dispossession.

In announcing the competition, the local newspaper wrote about “a 44-million-rand metamorphosis”,⁶² describing it as a “competition to design Red Location transformation”.⁶³ The project, in short, was about transforming the whole location. The tourism element became gradually more pronounced: “Part of Red Location is to be rezoned and transformed into a ‘tourism village’ in the terms of a decision announced by the Town Planning and Land Use Committee this week”.⁶⁴ The project was also justified through reference to the historical importance of the location. An article by journalist Thando Dlula made the headlines of the *Algoa Sun*, “Memories were made of the material of Red Location”,⁶⁵ “Port Elizabeth first official ‘Black township’ seems to set to close the millennium by turning into a modern urban village”⁶⁶ and the *Herald* followed suit: “Tourism plan for city ‘struggle’ hotbed”.⁶⁷ Albrecht Heroldt, the architect leading the judging panel, confirmed, “Red Location was chosen because the site has major political significance and it has an interesting architectural legacy of corrugated iron houses dating from the turn of the century”.⁶⁸ A phrase with similar connotations was then included in the museum’s business plan, signed by Dojon Financial Services, Riordan’s consulting firm that was responsible for the project’s financial aspects: “No city in South Africa can match this New Brighton mix: history, great buildings and the space to build more, and an historic Township situation with a profound struggle history”.⁶⁹

In the preface to the Competition Brief, Nceba Faku, then Mayor of Port Elizabeth, declared that the aim of the project was to “transform Red Location, a sad and neglected place of great political significance in the history of the anti-apartheid struggle in the Eastern Cape indeed, the whole country, into a major tourist attraction”.⁷⁰ Mayor Faky’s statement continued, promising that “[the project will

61 Interview 20/08/2015.

62 ‘Competition to design Red Location transformation’, *Algoa Sun*, 03/09/1998.

63 Ibid.

64 M. Matavire, ‘Tourism plan for city’s ‘struggle’ hotbed’, *Algoa Sun*, 27/11/1998.

65 T. Dlula, *Algoa Sun*, 27/11/99.

66 Ibid.

67 M. Matavire, *op. cit.*

68 “Competition to design Red Location transformation” (1998).

69 Dojon Financial Services (2011a: 2)

70 “Competition to design Red Location Transformation” (1998).

offer] the tourist a multi-faceted cultural experience, a taste of vibrant Africa, a celebration of the talents of local artists and craftsmen. [...] In Port Elizabeth, Red Location, New Brighton, is hallowed ground.”⁷¹ The members of the Selection Panel, charged with judging the project proposals, also functioned as a bridge between present and future, between the memory of exploitation and development, between catharsis and international tourism.⁷²

The coordinator of the competition, Herholdt, was a university professor and architect with a specialisation in cultural heritage preservation. In 2001, he created The Matrix studio that to this day enjoys a sort of semi-monopoly on urban design in Port Elizabeth – almost all of the most important public works in the last ten years have requested consultancy or designs from this studio.⁷³ Herholdt’s office has a highly suggestive location: the ex-Masonic Temple of Port Elizabeth, with all its emblems intact. After evaluating the proposals, The Matrix carried out various consultations for the RLMCP project. Gawie Fagan, one half of a duo of famous architects originally from Cape Town, was chosen as the President of the Selection Panel. The panel was then composed of Anya Van der Merwe Miszewski, a Cape Town architect; Gus Gerneke, then Professor of Architecture at Pretoria; Govan Mbeki, one of the defendants at the Rivonia Trial and a preeminent activist from Red Location; and Jeff Peires, historian and author of the famous “The Dead will Arise”, one of the most comprehensive works on the history of the amaXhosa people. Sharon Zukin underlines how:

Cultural strategies of redevelopment are complicated representations of change and desire. Their common element is to create a “cultural” space connecting tourism, consumption, and style of life. They appreciate archaic living and working sites, but push them deeper into the past. They incorporate these sites into an image of local identity by defusing their contentiousness (Zukin 1995: 83).

⁷¹ Faku, introduction to Albrecht Heroldt Architects, *Competition for the Transformation of Red Location* (1998).

⁷² The RLMCP is certainly not a unique example of the desire to connect tourism and memorialization in South Africa. See, for example, Murray and Witz, who analyse the relationship between heritage and tourism (2014), and Witz, Minckley and Rassool (2005) who address the relationship between cultural tourism, heritage and the creation of *ad hoc* products and buildings (2017).

⁷³ Witness several of the most recent urban regeneration projects carried out by *The Matrix*: the Urban Design Masterplan for Motherwell, Parliament Street, pedestrian zones in Govan Mbeki Avenue, the Helenvale precinct upgrade, and the master plan for Coega Industrial Development Zone.

According to the Competition Brief, the intention was to create a space and project that was as uncontroversial as possible and that could represent a new post-apartheid South Africa – portraying memories but not accusations, representing diversity as an asset and presenting shared history in the name of a common future. Several of the contradictions that emerged during the project’s delivery phase were evident from its conception.

The competition brief envisaged the construction of a museum, library, art gallery, an area to use as a market, a centre for performative arts, a conference centre, and a centre for welcoming and accommodating visitors. The construction should have been completed within a period of five years and taken place in three phases: the first phase should have entailed the construction of the apartheid museum and the restoration of an unspecified number of houses dating back to the early years of the twentieth century. The organisers insisted heavily on the fact that the architecture must restore or reinforce “a sense of place”, though in no part of the brief was it explained exactly what this meant. The brief suggested that several houses should be chosen to be included in an open-air exhibition or even integrated into the museum itself (Albrecht Heroldt Architects 1998: 11). In any case, the exact way in which the architecture should have been preserved seems to have been unclear to the project organisers themselves.

The beginning of the brief reads, “The corrugated iron houses, originally placed on a regular grid plan, cover the greatest part of the site. Competitors may however move some of these structures to make place for other buildings, courtyards, axis and open spaces. It is intended that all the inhabitants be moved into new houses in Masangwanaville, which is located next to Red Location” (Albrecht Heroldt Architects 1998: 10). The next page of the brief, however, asks that proposals explore ways of renovating or expanding the buildings to encourage a more varied environment and, implicitly, occupation by a different class of inhabitants (Albrecht Heroldt Architects 1998: 11). It is also stated that this renovation would not be a funded part of the project and that it would be the inhabitants themselves who would have to carry out these works, according to a self-build scheme that at the time was frequently used to build social housing.

The project aspired to preserve memory and evoke an atmosphere frozen in time, though it was difficult to say whether the aim was to reconstruct Red Location as it was in the 1950s, 1960s, 1970s or 1930s. In fact, however, the project alterned the last few remnants of this past through its attempts to reinvent them. Zukin underlines how “painful memories of place must be buried deep in the past – or presented as an aesthetic sight” (Zukin 1995: 81) for culture to successfully contribute to urban regeneration. The fact that the sheet metal houses were exploited as the archetypal symbol of Red Location, almost fetishized for their connection with apartheid, also demonstrates the difficulty of considering the possibility of evolution or development, of a process of becoming that diverged from the project of post-apartheid emancipation. There was no room to recognise that although the inhabitants had long been living in those houses dating back to the early twentieth century, over the course of a century the ways in which they were used had inevitably changed, as had the social configuration of public and private spaces.

In any case, delivering the conservation strategy outlined by the Competition Brief was impossible: between the end of the 1990s and the early 2000s, winds, floods and several terrible fires with fatal consequences because of the unsafe and poorly built buildings destroyed many of the historical sites. The winning proposal ended up incorporating one of the houses on the border with the Art Gallery building. As we will see later, even the conservation of this single house entailed many problems.

3. Industrial aesthetics, memory and modernisation

Following the Competition Brief guidelines, architects competing for the RLMCP contract were faced with the task of designing a museum and cultural centre that could also be expressions and vectors of economic development alongside bringing about social improvement. The architect would be charged with assuaging the wounds of the past, transforming pain and coaxing a complex past to blossom into a prosperous future, or, more simply, with combining the valorisation of memory, tourism and job creation. The project detailed in the guidelines developed in two directions – on the one hand, it insisted on conservation and reconciliation with the past as a symbolic leap towards progress and the future; on the other, it emphasised the benefits the museum would bring in terms of employment and investment.

The Panel selected the project submitted by Jo Noero, from the Noero and Wolff Architects studio.⁷⁴ Noero's proposal emphasised two elements: (1) the use of local materials and buildings that recalled the township's industrial past; and (2) integrating the buildings into the landscape of the township while simultaneously producing a sense of dissonance:

The first proposition is to locate the museum and the new building in neighbours close to where the people who were once victims of apartheid live, The buildings are integrated into the neighbourhood so that they become part of the daily life of people. In this way the horrors of apartheid becomes more apparent simply by the presence of, for example, the Apartheid Museum within a functioning community (Noero 1999: 19).

The project was awarded a budget of 44 million rand, and the finalist architecture studios were awarded a prize of 400,000 rands, 100,000 rands of which went to the winner.

The museum's external appearance recalls an industrial factory, following Noero's proposal. Even though many factories still stand only a few hundred metres away from Red Location in Deal Party, because there are no similar buildings in the immediate vicinity of the museum the building stands out against the surrounding houses. For Noero, the architect, the township's industrial past was key to understanding the site, especially since the township's liberation had been achieved largely through the mobilisation of trade unions. During a conference at the Architectural League of New York, Noero explained how trying to emulate an industrial style was an attempt to make the building more legible to the township's inhabitants and simultaneously fit the building into the surrounding landscape, built from rough, low-cost material. "The language of the new buildings is utilitarian and industrial, and it is hoped that this will act as a connection to a proud union past and

⁷⁴ In 1997, the City Administration and Finance Committee allocated 13 million rand for building the RLMCP, in the context of an urban regeneration programme across several townships (the programme, worth 52 million rand, involved the construction of green spaces and community social spaces in the Northern Areas, and in Motherwell, Kwazakhele and Bethelsdorp). Some funds were also recovered from the City Reserve through rechanneling several grants from the Swedish International Development Agency (SIDA). The creation of the Museum and the regeneration of the surrounding area was also enabled in part by a partnership between the cities of Port Elizabeth and Gothenburg. The presence of Swedish aid occasionally gave rise to the perception that the RLMCP was an international project, implemented with foreign funds. In reality, these funds represented only a small portion of the project's financing; for all intents and purposes it was a national project.

seek to remember the labour of those people who gave up their lives for the struggle”.⁷⁵

According to Noero, a building in the style of a factory would have been better received by the residents and would have been able to act as a sort of catalyst for community. His idea was that the “factory as a place of struggle [...], of civic virtue”⁷⁶ would essentially be met with uncontroversial approval. During the conference in which he expressed himself in these terms, Noero clarified his thinking on the functionalism of an architecture that privileged a utilitarian aesthetic, claiming, “in Southern African Black languages for example, there’s no word to describe beautiful, something that is autonomous [...] the idea of beauty as being a property without purpose... everything that is beautiful is functional”.⁷⁷ Paradoxically, statements such as these, instead of bringing Noero closer to those of his compatriots whose rights he claimed to defend, distanced him from them, recalling Bourdieu’s bourgeois distinction between “pure taste” and “barbaric taste”.⁷⁸

An article written by the museum curator Christopher du Preez several years after the RLMCP had opened judged that the claim that the residents identified with the museum’s industrial structure was very weak. The grandeur of the building compared to the surrounding houses recalled inequality, of an elite opposed to normal people, and more rarely the presence of untapped potential (Du Preez 2014).

Inside the museum, there was an arrangement of twelve “memory boxes” – cubic exhibition spaces made from corrugated sheet metal, evoking the cases that migrant workers would use to carry their most precious memories from countryside to city. The exhibition space, cold and predominantly cement, without a specific guided route to follow, was supposed to inspire an emotional reaction of simultaneous thoughtfulness and unease. Inspired by Andreas Huyssen’s expression “twilight memory” to refer to the gap between past and present, between the experience and the memory of an event, Noero used natural light to beam two rays of sunlight to illuminate the space between the memory boxes. There were no plans for a mapped-out route through the exhibition; instead, conditions were created to allow

⁷⁵ Noero, cited in Lepik (2010: 53).

⁷⁶ Noero (2010), Conference of the Architectural League of New York, minute 04:40.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ Noero’s words seem to recall “aesthetic distance”, “the detachment and disinterestedness which aesthetic theory regards as the only way of recognizing the work of art for what it is, i.e., autonomous, [...]” Bourdieu (1983: 32).

visitors to move freely from one room to another. This double confusion – the struggle to remember and spatial disorientation – was proposed as a strategy to emotionally engage the visitor, who would find themselves imprisoned in the same feeling of disorientation that had characterised apartheid:

In this way one seeks to recreate a sense of slow erosion of moral and ethical framework that was created by apartheid. There was a sense of normalcy. But there was at the same time a sense of horror and impending terror that was undeniable. The space that was created by these contradictory and confusing sensibilities created a void which was a space of disquiet in which the complexities of the apartheid world were simultaneously hidden and revealed at every turn. Visitors will be challenged to make their own decisions about how to make their way around and into the boxes (Noero 1999: 20).

The architect Murray has expressed doubts about the way in which South African architects construct public buildings in an aesthetic that reduces culture and identity to preestablished “values”, reifying them and translating them into spatial forms (2006). This is exactly what happened with the Red Location Museum, a place that tried to create as much of a sense of a shared past as possible, alongside evoking a deep feeling of emotional participation through liberal use of symbols, references and suggestions. The museum’s spatial layout sublimated anti-apartheid struggle into a series of feelings, such as suffering, memory or loss, and then translated these into value categories, such as courage or justice. Once again, the idea was to advance a narrative that was as inclusive as possible and in which no one was made to feel uncomfortable.

The assumption underlying Noero’s proposal for a public cultural building seems in many ways akin to a certain school of European architecture that understands buildings as capable of transforming the space and citizens around them. In an interview, the architect Renzo Piano described public cultural buildings in such a manner: “it’s important that these public spaces are places where people can get together and share values – for example, the values of justice, beauty, scientific research – these are the places that make cities civilised places”.⁷⁹ Analogously, it can be argued that the act of incarnating and representing the foundational values of the

⁷⁹ Piano (2015) “Making civility”, interview with Francesco Merlo.

new South African nation and transforming the township into a “civilised place” was part of the function of the RLMCP.⁸⁰ The building, furthermore, elucidated and consolidated a certain type of narrative about the township’s residents: the factory, migration and poverty were rearticulated as simplicity and sobriety. Mbembe, describing Johannesburg, notes how “the unconscious of a city is made up of different layers of historical time superimposed on one another, different architectural strata or residues from earlier times. In times of transition, these layers and strata become elusive and precarious. Architecture and urban design then tend to become acts of repression, separation, and fantasy” (2008: 64). The RLMCP was surely a work that evoked the unconscious of the city of Port Elizabeth, advancing a specific narrative about the location’s inhabitants and their history.

Due to internal tensions, it took a long time for the councillors of the ANC majority to agree on the appointment of a museum curator. A few months after opening, Christopher du Preez was hastily appointed in February 2005 with the task of drawing up the organisational chart of the museum, compiling the job descriptions and overseeing the appointment of all other staff members in time for the museum’s opening date, fixed for June of that same year. Du Preez, a visual artist, had behind him the experience of creating the South End Museum, a museum commemorating different communities in the central district of South End, a district that had been destroyed by the application of the Group Areas Act,⁸¹ and the subsequent forced relocation of its inhabitants to other areas of Port Elizabeth. This museum, inaugurated in 2001, in some ways provides a point of comparison for Red Location: conceived of in the same period by a group of people whose families had been forcibly evicted from the neighbourhood, it was privately funded and followed a logic of gradual expansion.

Du Preez found himself faced with multiple problems, the most urgent of which surely being that of defining the museum’s objectives. A few months before the opening, in fact, it was still not clear if the museum should be about the history of the struggle at a local or a national level, nor if it should only perform the function of an

⁸⁰ Further discussion in Chapter 4.

⁸¹ The Group Areas Act, a series of three acts that came into effect in 1950 and underwent many amendments, established areas across the entire national territory dedicated to different racial groups, both in terms of land occupation and property rights. These acts were the origin of several forced evictions of non-white groups and their transferal to areas that were far from the centre, less developed or subject to environmental risks.

exhibition space or also that of a social space. Not even the target audience seemed to have been established: schools, local tourists or international tourists? There was no pre-existing collection; the museum had to build one from scratch. These problems remained essentially unresolved: in 2010, five years later, du Preez wrote a report for the Municipal Oversight Committee, in which he noted the persistence of these challenges:

The questions that remain unsettled are: is Red Location part of a special section of cultural heritage linked to spaces of “awareness”? Whose past is it, whose memories are we archiving in the RLM and what is explicitly excluded from the curational narrative? Is the RLM a community museum, and how are we defining community? What type of expertise do we need, and how can we build sustainability? How can the museum strike a balance between its “professionalism” and the needs of the nearby community, and what does it mean to “remember the past in many ways”? These are only some of the complexities that the museum must face as a post-1994 development institution. (Du Preez 2010a: 4).

4. The museum and job creation

Reconstructing how the museum was presented to the community at a distance of almost fifteen years and following multiple changeovers of ward councillors⁸² was a rather difficult task. Riordan, du Preez, and a museum employee all claimed to have accompanied Noero in presenting the project to the community.⁸³ However, not one of my interlocuters – whether they were project organisers, politicians, municipal officials, inhabitants of the Location – was able to adequately describe exactly how the project was presented to the residents. In his lectures, Noero himself mentions a public consultation process, but gives no further details of this. According to the recollections of a member of the project staff, the project was presented to the Ernest Malgas chapter of the ANC in New Brighton. Du Preez and Riordan maintain that the project was mostly well received by the inhabitants, albeit with some hesitations. My interviewees repeated that one of the most difficult issues to resolve was explaining what a museum was and what purpose it served, because during apartheid access to

⁸² A ward councillor is a directly elected councillor who represents their ward on the Municipal Council.

⁸³ Interviews carried out 12/03/2015, 16/03/2015 and 17/11/2015.

museums had been restricted to white people. Museums were mostly associated with a middle-class, suburban lifestyle: du Preez recalls that one woman asked where the swimming pool would go, and another when the animals would arrive (for the zoo).⁸⁴

The lack of sufficient evidence about the public consultation process is probably due to the fact that the residents' participation was conceived of in terms of awareness of and adherence to the aims of the project, and was forcefully related to the job opportunities that the project would create.⁸⁵ The residents, with the exception of some more illustrious individuals such as renowned local artists, were generally viewed as a pool of unskilled labour. The community's increasingly insistent doubts about what benefits the project would bring them were met with a growing emphasis on the jobs that the RLMCP would create. One inhabitant, now a ward councillor, recalls:

At that time, I was a young activist so I would go to public meetings about the museum. Before you own a house you need to own the information; we would ask: what are you coming here with for us? Which one will be your input? And what do you answer if we say that our priority is housing? But people would be easily convinced that the tourists would bring money to be reinvested there. The truth is that a museum is not something that creates revenue! (Interview 24/11/2015).

In several interviews with the local newspaper, councillor Riordan presented job creation as one of the cornerstones of development in the township: "the project will create hundreds of jobs for the unemployed people of Red Location. It will start small, but it will grow into something really big".⁸⁶ Riordan's insistence on job creation recalls Zukin's analysis that moments of crisis in particular lend themselves to hope in and wagers on culture as a vector of economic growth.⁸⁷ Proposing development as a coefficient of employment is certainly an effective and frequently used method to

⁸⁴ Interview carried out 12/03/2015. Further discussion in Chapter 8.

⁸⁵ Marschall stresses further how in memorialisation projects in South Africa public consultation processes are often nonexistent, reflecting the top-down way that monuments and memorials were constructed and imposed during apartheid (Marschall 2012).

⁸⁶ Rory Riordan interviewed by N. Kota in 'Vision of township apartheid museum becoming a reality', *The Herald*, 24/06/2000.

⁸⁷ "It is quite a wager this museum will create a tourist industry and that tourism will save the town from economic decline. But when the last factories have closed their gates and neither business nor government offers a different scenario, ordinary men and women can be persuaded that their city is ready to enter the symbolic economy" (Zukin 1995:79).

gather immediate consensus. It proved, however, to be a double-edged sword for the project organisers: after the first few months of construction, during which some residents had been offered a fixed-term job, the project failed to keep its grand promises.

Construction works on the museum started in 1999 under the management of SBT Building from Nelson Mandela Bay. The construction company, together with a project committee formed by a delegation of residents, established that a third of the “unskilled” labourers would be chosen from inhabitants of areas in the immediate vicinity of the museum. These workers would be trained and employed for a period of three months, at the end of which a new group would be selected. This decision was a generous interpretation of the Construction Procurement regulations in South Africa, that oblige the judging panels of public and private calls for tender to consider the employment of members of previously disadvantaged communities.⁸⁸ To facilitate the construction works the Red Location Cultural Centre Working Group (RLCCWG) was established, an entity that reported to the Administration and Finance Committee, presided over by Riordan. This group included public officials, councillors, the residents committee and architects.

The construction process experienced several deadlocks: in 2001, the New Brighton Concern Residents’ Group (NBCRG) formed with the aim of giving voice to people living around the museum and who had to move to make space for the construction works. In 2003, twenty-six people were arrested for protesting in front of the museum, charged with violation of property. In 2012, during the National Book Week organised within the museum, residents protested over job opportunities, in particular challenging the arbitrary selection of forty waged volunteers. According to the group leading the protests, the selected individuals were not from the location and had the selection processes had been non-transparent. Protests over the museum and cultural centre’s hiring processes have been a constant throughout the history of the RLMCP. The residents have always demanded that the project organisers and staff keep true to their original promise of reducing unemployment in the location. The organisers have always maintained that not all the professionals required by the

⁸⁸ When the SBT started the construction work, however, the Broad-Based Black Economic Empowerment (BBBEE) act was not yet in force. The act involved the implementation of positive discrimination regulations to encourage groups who had been disadvantaged by the apartheid era to access work and create and manage businesses and was approved in 2003.

cultural centre had to be sourced from the location, while also repeatedly underlining how 95 per cent of the museum's staff, when it was working at full capacity, was composed of residents from New Brighton.⁸⁹

Fraught communication between organisers, museum staff and residents also resulted from the different ways that these parties defined the inhabitants and Red Location. For the organisers and staff of the cultural centre, Red Location was equivalent to New Brighton and people who were originally from Red Location but who had moved away for reasons of family, study or work were still considered part of the location. For the residents, Red Location had a much tighter border and priority for jobs in the museum should have gone to unemployed people who actually lived in Red Location, rather than across all of New Brighton. Still to this day, the question of job creation is highly controversial: the business plan projected the creation of 1567 jobs by the end of the project and 2230 by its fifteenth year of operations (Dojon Financial Services 2011b: 105), but the residents' frustration and dissatisfaction at not seeing concrete opportunities remained high.

5. The expansion of the cultural complex and its limits

While the project organisers' triumphant tones were accompanied by more doubtful notes in Port Elizabeth (the museum had started to be described as a "white elephant" within the township), on an international level the museum was celebrated as an innovative building, a successful example of futuristic architecture. Even though the residents' protests intensified when the museum opened in 2005, the building was awarded several international prizes. In 2005, the Municipality of Port Elizabeth received the World Leadership Award for Architecture and Civil Engineering (a prize awarded by the World Leadership Forum of England and dedicated to the city's leaders who distinguish themselves for imagination, inspiration and resilience); in 2006, the Municipality won the Dedalo Minosse International Prize, an award conferred by the Italian organisation ALA-Assoarchitetti, for having commissioned the building; in 2006, the building was honoured with the Lubetkin Prize of the Royal Institute of British Architects, as the best architectural project outside of Europe and

⁸⁹ This statement was frequently brought up in conversations with the museum staff. For example, in interviews on 16/03/2015 and 20/03/2015.

Britain. Noero was then invited to the MoMa in New York (2010) and the Venice Biennale (2012), among other prestigious venues, riding the wave of the project's success. In one of his presentations, Noero claimed:

You build a museum where people live and the people live in shacks and the shacks sit comfortably in front of the museum and it changes entirely the reading of the city and it changes the reading of the city for people outside of South Africa.⁹⁰

His speech, in which architecture assumed a central role, echoed the museum's business plan, which reads:

It is impossible to put a value on good architecture, but it raises property values; creates public spaces of value; preserves historic sites; lifts the human spirit and puts weight behind the causes it enshrines in building. All of this is inestimably valuable. (Dojon Financial Services 2011c: 29).

These awards encouraged the project organisers to extend the scope of the project and seek support and funding for the expansion. At the same time, the results of two studies commissioned by the organisers – one evaluating the museum's contents and activities and the other considering the RLMCP's potential returns in terms of development – assuaged significant doubts about the relationship between the museum and the inhabitants. In 2009, thanks to a Neighbourhood Development Partnership Grant (NDPG) of 25 million rand, a grant from the national government that at the time privileged strategic projects addressing the township's economic development (or, as more aptly described by Strategic Projects Manager at the Municipality, that worked "to attract the private sector to invest in the township"),⁹¹ the RLMCP moved into a new phase, with the construction of an art gallery and a digital library next to the museum. The construction of these two buildings entailed the relocation of 44 families who were living in shacks built on the land that had been designated for the cultural centre. The construction works were met by renewed protests from the residents, whose relocation was chaotic and whose compensation

⁹⁰ Noero (2010), Conference of the Architectural League of New York, minute 51:39.

⁹¹ Interview 21/03/2015.

had been symbolic, and the completion of the two buildings, planned to coincide with the world cup in 2010, fell back by a year.

In the meantime, however, the project's master plan was embellished with new features and the cultural centre seemed to expand ever further from the base of Red Location. The organisers suggested creating a car park, erecting a statue commemorating the Rivonia Trial, assigning one of the areas of the cultural centre as a television studio and even relocating some municipal offices to the cultural centre. At the same time, regenerating the area around the cultural centre meant the Municipality had to deal with other nearby buildings. In 2008, a women's cooperative was established and from 2012 managed the Red Location Lodge, a facility for welcoming tourists and guests. The Lodge was built in the converted beer hall on Singaphi Road, the road leading to the museum, and funded by Municipality. In the same period, reconstruction works started on the Mendi bottle store, a shop on the borders of Red Location that had sold alcohol during apartheid, to convert it into a cultural centre and theatre. Carrying out the Mendi bottle store project, however, proved more difficult than expected: the call for tenders for the reconstruction was put to one side almost ten years after its announcement, and in 2014, the selected construction firm suffered an armed robbery on the construction site and was then replaced because of non-fulfilment. The works only recommenced in 2015.

In 2011, five years after its initial opening, the museum totalled 117,155 visitors a year, a number that almost equalled the Apartheid Museum in Johannesburg, even though the RLM was in a township and had been operational for a much shorter period of time. In the annual report for 2011–2012, the museum staff requested more employees, fearing being unable to manage such a high number of visitors (Du Preez 2012: 8).

From 2011, the RLMCP was included in the city's Integrated Development Plan (IDP), the South African Municipalities' primary policy document that had been partially participatorily composed and outlined the priorities for each ward and the Municipality as a whole. In the IDP, the project is described as "Red Location Tourism village" (NNBM 2015b: 28) and as one of the contributing factors to "Positioning Nelson Mandela bay as a destination of choice to both investors and tourists through the development of a prosperous and diverse economy" (NNBM 2015b: 368).

Since the centre opened, the art gallery had only hosted a single exhibition (and it was heavily criticised because rain penetrated the building and ruined the photographs on display). The library, on the other hand, was neither opened nor ever provided with the materials and equipment necessary for it to function, a task that should have been the responsibility of the Municipality but that was allocated insufficient funding. The perennially closed library, together with the absence of concrete responses from the Municipality with regards to the housing issue, exponentially heightened the residents' pressure on the museum and cultural centre.

6. Deadlocks and utopia

In an attempt to respond to criticisms about the gap between the museum and the inhabitants, and in order to fulfil the monitoring and evaluation requirements entailed by the use of public funds, between 2012 and 2013 two important documents were drawn up. The first resulted from the constitution of an expert review panel tasked with evaluating the workings of the already completed structures and advising project organisers. The second was entitled "Red Location Cultural Precinct: A developmental study to maximise the social and economic impact of the Red Location Cultural Precinct" and was edited by the architectural studio The Matrix with guidance from several consultants. From different perspectives and with different objectives, these two documents described the relationships between the RLMCP, the residents and the city. Alongside the Development Study, two workshops were conducted with local artists and civil society representatives with the aim of eliciting the opinions of citizens and local arts and culture experts about potential uses and developments of the RLMCP.

The review panel was composed of Albie Sachs, originally from Cape Town, Constitutional Court Judge, exiled ANC activist who was considered one of the heroes of the struggle – in Mozambique he suffered an attack perpetrated by the apartheid Intelligence Service that cost him his arm – and one of the fathers of the contemporary South African Republic's judiciary system; Tony Lankester, director of Grahamstown National Art Festival, the most important arts festival in the Eastern Cape and one of the largest on a national level; Dorelle Sapere, project manager of the Nelson Mandela Development Agency (NMBDA) of the Municipality of Port Elizabeth; and Michael

Berry, artist, co-founder of the South-End Museum and director of the Arts and Culture Department at Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU). The panel was also supported by Janet Cherry, a Professor of Political Economy at NMMU with an activist past in the Congress of South African Students, the United Front and the End Conscription Campaign in Port Elizabeth. Zwai Mgijima, a young film director originally from New Brighton, was also present on the panel as an expert witness to life in the township.

As had happened with the selection panel, the choice of people to sit on the review panel also suggested the desire for a sort of double legitimacy provided by the authority of the past (for the most part they were ex-anti-apartheid activists) and strengthened by technical knowledge or professional role. These experts focused on the necessity of revitalising the aesthetic spaces of the cultural centre; Sachs described “no sense of radioactivity”,⁹² despite noting that the museum was well-known as a meeting place for the city’s Black intellectuals: “it’s a space that Black people feel at home in”.⁹³ A strong emphasis was placed on the need to involve residents as much as possible in the museum’s activities and to resolve the housing problems as soon as possible. Lankester, in a letter to Riordan in which he summarised his main observations, wrote:

I am deeply and utterly outraged at the fact that a facility as magnificent as the Library (and, soon no doubt, the Gallery) is standing empty, waiting to become derelict. With equipment standing packed in cardboard boxes waiting to be used. It is a crime and a travesty and if I lived next door I would be forcing the doors open and squatting in there out of anger and frustration. For me this is the tragedy of the project as it exists today: the resources are there; the political will was (is?) there...but there is zero momentum behind making it happen [...]” (Lankaster in Dojon Financial Services 2012).

In the same letter, Lankester expressed doubts about how cultural buildings of such great dimensions could function in that context: “The 1000-seater issue: I still maintain that it is something that should be approached with caution and thought

⁹² Sachs in Dojon Financial Services (2012).

⁹³ Ibid.

needs to be given to the economy viability of having a 1000-seater venue in the precinct” (Dojon Financial Services 2012).

The Developmental Study described the relationship between the RLMCP and the residents as “A strained relationship. It’s not mutually-complementary (reciprocal) relationship” (Development Partners and The Matrix 2013: 7) and at the same time tended towards a compromise in which the residents and their desires were considered as but one of many equally important stakeholders, not to be given the last word about the direction the cultural centre should take. The document further warned against falling into what it described as a logic of “redistribution” that would prioritise the redistribution of resources over development policies and so economic growth. Finally, it warned how the RLMCP should not become a run of the mill multi-purpose centre lest it fall short of its cultural objectives. It was therefore suggested that the project progress gradually in step with the “social development of the community”. The studio also recommended constituting a RLCP (Red Location Cultural Precinct) Community Forum to concentrate on community education and participation.

A few months after these two studies were conducted, in October 2013 a group of residents formed the Red Location Steering Committee (RLSC) and decided to force the closure of the museum and occupy the space of the cultural centre, preventing staff from coming to work and making it so that any visitor or authority figure could only approach the RLMCP with prior permission from the committee leaders. The occupation only came to an end in June 2016.

Even though the museum and the other buildings remained closed for almost three years, Riordan kept fundraising for the project, making several presentations to the management of the Minister of Art and Culture and applying for national lottery funding to finance parts of the project. They still needed to find funding for and deliver the third phase of the project, that planned for the construction of a theatre with a thousand seats, a theatre with 400 seats, a theatre with 150 seats, a cinema with 250 seats and a stage, a cinema with 150 seats and a smaller stage, and two rehearsal rooms – one the same size as the stage in the 1000-seat theatre and the other the same size as the stage in the 400-seat theatre. There were also longer-term plans to build an arts school with rooms for facilitating creative workshops. There was also still the

need to build 210 two-floor houses.⁹⁴ The social housing units were also designed by Noero and should have been completed by 2014, but building works had not yet even started because of bureaucratic delays, in addition to the Department of Human Settlements being placed under external management after several corruption cases, and because of the difficulty of drawing up a satisfactory list of beneficiaries.

In 2014, in the midst of the closures, the curator and staff of the art gallery and the director and staff of the library were finally appointed, despite being unable to work on site. The project moved from being defined as a “tourism village” to a “cultural precinct”, then becoming a “cultural hub” and, finally, the largest South African cultural centre. Noero claimed, “when we’ve finished with this project, we will have created an entirely new kind of South African city centre, which will be culturally based, where people live twenty-four hours a day, and it will have been built probably the poorest part of the city – very brave!”⁹⁵

7. Valorisation, between revaluation and exploitation

The RLMCP was a state intervention that wholly participated in neoliberal politics. It was a project that aimed to generate profit through increasing the economic value of the location: urban regeneration and the construction of the cultural centre were interventions designed to prompt a gradual process of wealth generation through making the location more attractive to multiple and varied investments. To use Riordan’s words, the RLMCP was a development project that aspired to economic efficiency.

Valorising the location operated through the commodification of its past, history, culture, objects and artefacts. Here we encounter what Boltanski and Esquerre have defined as an “enrichment economy”, a new form of capitalism understood through two simultaneous processes: de-industrialisation and heritagisation, an exploitation of heritage by museums or organised cultural events such as festivals in set places (2017). Artefacts are commodified through difference and association with an identity: “things that come from the past and may be undergoing a process of degradation are selected [...], then rehabilitated and

⁹⁴ See Appendix 3: Images, figures 3 and 5.

⁹⁵ Noero (2010), Conference of the Architectural League of New York, minute 54:00.

associated with [...] a historical narrative intended to orientate their interpretation and to augment their value” (Boltanski and Esquerre 2014: 38). From this point of view, the tourism industry plays a critical role. In Red Location, even emotions and feelings of suffering, anger or shame were commodified.

Valorisation was justified in terms of revaluation and redemption. Attributing value to the location and its history was seen as a way of repaying a debt after years of the location’s potential, exemplary inhabitants and precious memories being unjustly undervalued and shamefully dismissed. At the same time, to fully benefit from the economic returns that would result from the township’s augmented market value, artefacts needed to be rehabilitated, buildings restructured, history and culture assigned a role in the project of working towards creative economies. Innovation became a central concern: Red Location could move towards development only if modernised, or even better, if it excelled past the present state of design and became a pioneering space of experimental urban architecture.

Being the result of an experimental pilot or pioneering project is what allowed the project to surpass national borders and be internationally competitive. Indeed, one of the adjectives that was used from the outset to describe the RLMCP was “world-class”, and the project organisers continually compared it to other projects in Europe or the United States (the project organisers looked to Europe much more than they tried to make comparisons with other African organisations, apart from those in South Africa).

Valorisation also translated to exploitation: despite promises of job creation, the residents were mostly offered temporary and precarious contracts (as with the construction work) that were often semi-voluntary, especially when it came to providing fixtures and fittings. The residents’ labour was viewed as a form of social inclusion or training opportunity, even as a vocation or passion project rather than the source of a worker’s livelihood. The type of employment offered by the cultural centre seemed more geared towards governing the residents’ growing resentment than at creating real employment opportunities.

A further form of exploitation relates to the township’s history, and demands that the residents share stories, anecdotes and objects relating to anti-apartheid struggle – knowledge and objects that, once placed in a museum, would assume significant economic value.

The paradoxes that were gradually brought to light by the staff charged with directing the museum's activities – and then later also by academics and the residents themselves – are paradoxes that accompany many neoliberal policies that are part and parcel of enrichment capitalism. The state was both minimally involved in the project and yet also extremely bureaucratic (Hibou 2013). The division of tasks between different Municipal departments and the museum staff was unclear and confusing, and institutions swung between being absent and interfering. At the same time, the staff and officials complained of the extreme slowness of any procedure, from acquisitions to the employment of new staff, caused by excessive bureaucracy, whether transparency regulations or evaluation reports. Finally, the Municipality ended up with an overspend for the construction and maintenance of the RLMCP; the library in fact remained unequipped due to the lack of council funding.

Change always entails some sort of valorisation. Stakes are placed on an object whose value has increased to generate economic returns. Valorisation is a form of appropriation in as much as it involves the material or symbolic ownership of an object and its transformation into a commodity (Harvey 2004). The project chose to capitalise on history rather than on the social capital of the residents, and so had to resort to other strategies in order to keep its promise of growth and development. Job creation was almost presented as a taster of much larger profits to come when the project reached its full potential. The residents' protests and demands to immediately access the project's economic returns upturned the logic underlying the RLMCP. Capitalising on the location's history and current use had a price beyond the cost of urban regeneration or the building works: the project would survive only if it contributed to increased employment, that is, if it paid the price of the social costs (inequality, marginalisation, exploitation) that the location had been subjected to by third parties (neoliberal political leadership, the privileges the economic elite had inherited from post-apartheid, corruption).

3. Experiments for a future city

The RLMCP was not only a project aimed at preserving memory and fostering cultural creativity, but it also constituted an attempt to develop a new form of city and to

utterly transform the face of the township. Adjacent to the main buildings, in fact, took place a part of the project that was dedicated to experimental housing.

The creation of an innovative district was underway in Red Location – a district that could embody what South Africa might become in the future, where people of different cultures, origins and social backgrounds lived together in harmony; a district that was respectful of the environment, healthy and safe, “smart” and “low-cost”, an incubator for business and artistic creativity where economic activities improved local employment rates and made public spaces appropriate. Architecture and urban design were charged with triggering a much broader process – creating virtuous communities and establishing public spaces that were appropriate for a democratic, peaceful, neutral, safe and inclusive South Africa.

The RLMCP was not the first project to propose turning Red Location into a prototypical, experimental pilot project. It followed, in fact, in a long line of measures and state interventions that have shaped the history and geography of the township since the beginning of the twentieth century. Different processes and procedures were employed in pursuit of the same goal: the governance and normalisation of marginalisation. The inhabitants of the township have variably been represented as morally corrupt and lacking in social harmony, or else as victimised, oppressed and deserving of reparations. Over time, the residents took ownership of or reappropriated the representations proposed by the project organisers and policy makers, reusing them for other means or retranslating them into more functional language or terms.

1. Housing and virtuous communities

In November 1999, a delegation from the Swedish government visited Red Location. The delegation was led by the prime minister Göran Persson, who was accompanied for the occasion by Lisbet Palme, widow of prime minister Olof Palme, who was assassinated in 1986 and had been famous for his commitment to anti-apartheid struggle and for having supported ANC from Sweden. The delegation travelled to the township by train, even though rail was an unusual method of transport, used predominantly by labourers and considered to be more dangerous than communal taxis. The delegation visited for the occasion of the naming ceremony of one of the

township's streets, 14th street, after the Swedish prime minister. From the outset, the desire to create a new image for the township was evident.

The Swedish delegation's visit providing an opportunity to flaunt the township's hospitality. The local papers staged what the location might become as a result of the new regeneration projects: tourists enjoying themselves tasting traditional beer (*umqombothi*) and savouring a meal of meat and *samp* (a maize-based dish), local historians telling stories of anti-apartheid struggle and Swedish and South African musicians coming together for a jazz concert. One of the sheet metal and wood shacks was turned into the headquarters for the Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency (SIDA) during the days devoted to celebrating the partnership.⁹⁶

The delegation also officially launched a project called PELIP (Port Elizabeth Low Income Housing Programme). This was a pilot project, a cooperation between SIDA and the Municipality of Port Elizabeth, for the construction of fourteen to eighteen low-cost houses to be built with a government grant (15,000 rand for each house) supplemented by a micro-loan (5000 rand for each nuclear family unit). The housing complex, worth 700,000 rand, was part of the Red Location Cultural Development Node. Two apartments would be rented to the Port Elizabeth Self-help and Rehabilitation for Disabled People organisation. The project was described in the local newspaper as "revolutionary" and "an attempt to shift the values and expectations of both institutions and ordinary citizens".⁹⁷

The project was unique in its use of easily available and low-cost materials and also in its creation of "high-density housing", multi-storey buildings that could accommodate more families than the typical layout of South African RDP houses, which up until that point had generally been a series of small buildings (at the time around 48m²), with a space in front and a space behind to allow for a yard or future extensions. During his presentation, Thomas Melin, a Swedish urban planning consultant, claimed, "the 'one house, one family, one plot approach is unsustainable, and experimental initiatives to explore new ways of address South Africa's housing problems are needed".⁹⁸ The local paper, quoting local authorities, commented that the building project has allowed ordinary citizens a better understanding of housing

⁹⁶ I. Randall, 'Shack becomes head office', *Algoa Sun*, 21/10/1999.

⁹⁷ "This project will test new accommodation solutions", *Algoa Sun* 11/11/1999. The same idea is present in L. Mosia, 'Revolutionary housing development launched', *Algoa Sun*, 20/11/1999.

⁹⁸ Melin cited in "This project will test new accommodation solutions", *Algoa Sun* 11/11/1999.

possibilities and how housing can contribute to improving their quality of life”.⁹⁹ The project served to demonstrate to citizens who were reluctant to live in apartments or in houses that were difficult to renovate or that had shared spaces that it was possible to conceive of another way of living.¹⁰⁰ The PELIP houses were presented as an opportunity for modernity and a South African response to international standards, that in the 1990s were aspiring to the creation of liveable and sustainable cities. The assumption underlying the PELIP project was that building better houses would make for a better life and prompt a virtuous cycle encompassing health and wellbeing, economic growth and increased investments.¹⁰¹

Jo Noero also designed these houses and imagined them as a prototypical community space: on the ground floor the houses would be structured to hold small commercial activities. They would also be allocated to different types of family: young and old, and families with disabled members. The construction of these houses was completed in 1999, and still to this day they mark the eastern border of the museum and echo its architectural style: clean lines and coarse concrete. The PELIP experiment, however, did not achieve its desired result: the residents, after ten years of renting, were supposed to own the houses, but PELIP, the agency who managed the project, went bankrupt and was incorporated into the Municipality and the Swedish partnership came to an end. The inhabitants found themselves therefore without anyone to present their case to, and without a proprietor to make the transfer of ownership.¹⁰²

The examples of the PELIP houses and the Red Location Museum were referred to in the “Sustainable Communities Planning Guide” by the Nelson Mandela Bay Municipality in 2007. Images of the PELIP houses are even featured on the front cover. The guide, aimed at council officials and city planners, outlines a plan for sustainable

⁹⁹ “This project will test new accommodation solutions’, *Algoa Sun*, 11/11/1999.

¹⁰⁰ During interviews, some council officials ascribed the hostility of amaXhosa people to living in apartment buildings to the fact that many traditional ceremonies required an outdoor space in which to invoke ancestors. While an explanation of this sort does not seem impossible, there were undoubtedly also more practical reasons (for example, a single house can be more easily extended), and the fact that it was difficult to forgo even a scant degree of privacy.

¹⁰¹ “[...] Good, thoughtful design could make in achieving a better life for all. This is not to suggest that a well-designed house will solve the problems of equity in a highly unequal society. However, to us architects involved in the field of housing, it’s clear that a well-designed home can make all the difference to a family in as much as it can become a vehicle for better health, capital growth and investment and can also become the social and cultural centre of a vital family life” (Noero 1999: 28).

¹⁰² Interview 02/11/2015.

communities achieved through the subdivision of zones of the metropolis into Sustainable Community Units (SCU). The SCU is the smallest unit of urban planning that then feeds into different Local Area Spatial Development Frameworks (LASDF) – that take into account multiple SCUs. These in turn contribute to the Spatial Development Framework (SDF), the city’s Local Development Framework.

The SCU structured urban planning areas around notions of “reasonable distance”, meaning that services such as clinics, libraries, schools, community centres, recreation spaces and even workplaces should be within walking distance of home and a maximum of two kilometres or thirty minutes’ walk from the city centre. The design of the SCU brings together different principles, including poverty reduction, attention to special needs (children, disabled people, people with HIV, etc.), gender equality, respect for the environment, participation, local development, accessibility, containment of urban expansion, development of alleyways and multipurpose areas.

The PELIP houses were seen as exemplary because they constituted a housing cluster, a group of thirty to fifty housing units which shared a location on the same street or in the same open space, arranged so as to be able to watch over areas traversed by pedestrians or bicycles. According to the project guidance, the high-density housing project would also encourage mutual aid, neighbours looking out for one another and street committees. A sort of virtuous circle came to be identified between the environment’s aesthetic qualities, safety, the inhabitants’ culture and lifestyle, sustainability, tolerance and the protection of diversity.¹⁰³

The PELIP houses were not the only project in the vicinity of the RLMCP. The architect Noero was also tasked with designing houses for the 150 families who had been displaced from the area they had lived in to make space for the cultural centre. This project, whose details were yet to be confirmed, foresaw the construction of semi-detached houses that would open up onto communal courtyards, forming a sort of small public square. The plans for these houses depicted leafy neighbourhoods with room for cars and pedestrians alike, with children playing on the street and various commercial activities animating a bustling neighbourhood. Even more telling,

¹⁰³ “The character and identity of a community area depends on the culture and lifestyle of inhabitants, and the quality of the built and natural environment, which is important to most people, and contributes to social identity and sustainability. Positive and responsible attitudes are fostered by a functional and well-designed townscape and pleasant surroundings. Tolerance and valuing diversity are important for social and economic integration” (NMBM 2007).

however, is the work that Noero presented at the Architectural Biennale in Venice in 2012 for the exhibition “Common ground/different world”, exhibited next to a huge tapestry produced by the Keiskamma Trust Hamburg Women’s Cooperative for the Red Location library (‘Keiskamma after Guernica’, a work about the tragic effects of HIV on the community). It consisted of a massive blueprint, 9.4 by 3.5m, entirely hand-drawn and intitled “The transformation of Red Location”.¹⁰⁴ The blueprint depicted plans for the completed cultural centre, crisscrossed by people’s journeys between its various spaces. The Red Location imagined by Noero is a busy and interconnected district, with green spaces and sports facilities, urban allotments and car parks. It is accessible, with buses dropping off visitors and people gathering in the newly built square. In an interview explaining the work, Noero claims: “The drawing I made of the plan of Red Location is ready to show you how we are trying to establish a new common ground in our city in Port Elizabeth [...] being able to share with people of Europe the idea of how we are making a set of public places in South Africa [...]”.¹⁰⁵

2. Public space and “the racial city”

The RLMCP project aimed to create a public space that was appropriate for the new South African nation. The creation and reinvention of public spaces that could be accessed and visited by anyone was one of South African municipalities’ biggest concerns, in part because the geography of apartheid did not provide for such shared spaces, especially not spaces where the townships could have easily come together. Mbembe writes about the “racial city” as a type of city in which “racism became a constitutive dimension of the city’s modernity” (Mbembe 2008: 44), referring to the relationship between racism and the transition to capitalism through the construction of an urban proletariat. Replacing the racial city is a difficult task: “The unconscious can easily accommodate the survival of archaic formations beside others that have supplanted them, even on the same site. It bears witness to an irretrievable loss—the loss of the racial city. This is a case of traumatic amnesia and not of forgetting, of the disavowal of time as opposed to memorialization” (Mbembe quoting Damish 2008: 64). The creation of a post-apartheid public space at the site where segregation had

¹⁰⁴ See Appendix 3: Images, figure 4.

¹⁰⁵ Noero (2012), interviewed by the Venice Biennale channel, minute 01:15.

been at its strongest and most overt collided with the lingering traces of that segregation, whose persistence had become a sort of lack. In other words, the space of neutrality that the project organisers aspired to was in fact a space in which racial categories emerged not as weaker but as sublimated and retranslated through other terms (such as security or diversity).

Many people – architects, urban planners, local politicians – shared the idea that the township needed healthy public spaces in which edifying alternatives to the consumption of alcohol or drugs could take place and that could prompt new community configurations. This view, however, relied on the assumption that there were no such beneficial spaces in the townships, that these could only be found only in the suburbs. It also assumed that the location's sports team membership and cultural vibrancy belonged to the past, suppressing the places and practices that actually existed and flourished in the township, albeit underground or in a not always formal guise.

At the same time, the definition of public space varied according to which group of people was being considered. An academic, commenting on the project, explained:

There are different ideas on public spaces: for the middle class or the Municipality, public spaces are spaces for everyone in the metro, whereas for the community, public space is before their space and after the one of everybody. That's because they have been excluded or removed from other spaces.¹⁰⁶

Essentially, in the eyes of the project organisers the RLMCP was a contemporary South African public space, safe and accessible for everyone to mingle. The project business plan reads, "In a racially polarized Metropole, the Red Location stands out as a bastion of non racialism" (Dojon Financial Services 2011b: 137). There were concerted efforts to represent the project as belonging to everyone, not as the privilege of a single community at the expense of others. This was not a secondary concern: in a still highly segregated city like Port Elizabeth it is not unusual for the Municipality to be accused of privileging areas inhabited by an amaXhosa majority over those inhabited by a Coloured majority. The organisers' struggle to find new and neutral terminology to

¹⁰⁶ Interview 17/02/2015.

describe the different groups composing the South African state and citizens is evident in all discourse about the RLMCP. Complex circumlocutions straining to be “politically correct” clearly demonstrate the discomfort around descriptions of diversity and undeniable socio-economic difference. A profoundly unequal society struggled for as neutral a vocabulary as possible in the hope that if the word “race” disappeared, all forms of structural privilege and supremacy would be dismantled along with it and a transformed society would ensue.

The idealised image of Red Location as a futuristic, inclusive and accessible space collided with a much less ideal reality in which Red Location and New Brighton had a reputation as being particularly dangerous townships. For many of the suburban middle-classes (but also those from more residential areas of the townships) they were almost no-go areas, or at least unwelcoming. The most frequent comments on the RLMCP from people from the suburbs included, “the museum is a good idea, but I wouldn’t run the risk of going there” or, more simply, “I’ve never been to Red Location”. Some of the people I met in the suburbs struggled to locate Red Location and would also occasionally represent the township as somewhere very far from the city centre. A woman from Summerstrand, the suburb where the university campus is located, claimed “it’s at least an hour’s drive to get to New Brighton”, when in actual fact the location is around twenty-five minutes from the suburb.

The project master plan includes phrases such as “Like the Young Vic and the Shakespeare’s Globe theatre, the RLCC (Red Location Cultural Complex) must determinately attract a younger and more adventurous audience, and one that celebrates South Africa’s diversity. The architecture of the Performing Art Complex will be a vital player in creating this youthful, dynamic following” (Dojon Financial Services 2011a: 5). Comparisons were and still are made between the RLMCP and other projects abroad to make it seem innovative, justified and frequented at least by a “young and adventurous” audience (though it is unclear if the adjective “adventurous” refers to a certain type of artistic creativity or a propensity for risk-taking).

There are also more explicit phrases such as “Functions here (at Red Location Museum) are genuinely non-racial. Probably because of the quality of the architecture and the excellent cleanliness and security in the area, this is a preferred township venue for non-racial events” (Dojon Financial Services 2011b: 17), where the adjective “non-racial” clearly implies “safe for everyone who does not live in the

township". In a similar manner, the business plan proposed building a secure car park, since obviously the cultural centre could not have relied on on-street parking.

In an interview, an academic noted how there are contrasting views about the creation of cultural infrastructure in the townships, especially where there are still traces of a certain kind of segregation:

The authorities want to bring those kinds of resources to the townships but the people from the townships want to be included in city spaces, they don't want white facilities in Black communities, they want to profit from those same facilities. Especially middle-class people: they claim these spaces.¹⁰⁷

The Sustainable Communities Planning Guide defines social integration as the presence of different social and cultural groups (NNMB 2007). According to its authors, social integration can have various beneficial effects: "social interaction, co-operation, understanding and tolerance, people from different backgrounds enriching one another, cross-cutting interest groups, overcoming differences and enhanced human resources and capacities available in communities". The guide also identifies a sort of virtuous circle between sustainability, participation and democracy: sustainability is defined in terms of "ensuring diversity in communities as well as democracy and participation in planning processes" (NNMB 2007). In turn, participation is described as promoting "a sense of togetherness, identity, common vision and goals and sharing of responsibilities" (NNMB 2007). Great emphasis was placed on security, or rather the creation of an environment in which "the inhabitants can move freely without fear of crime and where pedestrians are given priority" (NNBM 2007).

The bicycle came to symbolise modernity and progress, to be the symbol of a "smart city" especially when reference was made to European urban planning. The guidance for sustainable municipalities is full of photographs of bicycles and cycling; one of the most used photographs of Red Location Museum foregrounds a child riding a blue mountain bike in front of the museum. Cycling was promoted as the transport of the future: cheap, non-polluting and evocative of a peaceful society where you can move about without fear of theft. In reality, at least in Port Elizabeth, cycling is still an elite method of transport and is almost never used in the city. It is sometimes used on

¹⁰⁷ Interview 17/02/2015.

the seafront and on safe suburban streets, but even here it is usually associated with sport, and so leisure, and therefore expense.

3. For the common good. The creation and recreation of a model township

The RLMCP represented a new way of making cities, intent on correcting the injustices of apartheid segregation and creating peaceful, healthy and innovative places. Yet, at the same time, the project's goals and methods did not seem that far removed from those pursued by the colonial government a century beforehand when they first established township of Red Location.

The RLMCP was not the only experimental project to have been piloted in Red Location. In fact, since its creation in 1902 Red Location had been renowned as a testing ground for local government practices. Tracing the township's history back to its establishment, it is possible to discern various parallels between the motivations and justifications for constructing the township at the beginning of the twentieth century and the motivations for the foundation of the RLMCP project at the end of the 1990s.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, solutions were sought for the perceived public problem of the degradation of areas inhabited by Black African workers who had come to the city from the countryside in search of work. According to the Union government, this had led to epidemics of the bubonic plague.¹⁰⁸ Degradation was also considered a problem in need of state response in the 1990s, though at this time it was understood to have been produced by past discrimination and the township's underdevelopment, manifesting in poor job opportunities, high levels of social disparity and widespread criminality. Finding a solution to these problems, both at the beginning of the twentieth century and ninety years later, was judged as in the public interest and for the common good. Inversely, it was thought

¹⁰⁸ The nexus of health-environment-urban degradation and policies to displace poorer swathes of the population to other areas of the city is obviously not unique to early 20th century South African politics. Today, various authors have reflected on "bourgeois environmentalism", especially in relation to the city of Delhi: attention to the environment, health and decorum are on the flipside of ambiguous policies dealing with social exclusion and spatial justice for less wealthy citizens: see Baviskar (2003); Baviskar and Ray (2011); Follman (2014); Bhan (2009). In relation to the United States and for a comparative perspective, see Nightingale (2012).

that if the problem persisted, it was liable to culminate in the dramatic deterioration of living conditions across the entire city.

In the second half of the nineteenth century, the administration of Port Elizabeth had a highly progressive reputation: in contrast to other South African cities in Port Elizabeth there was no form of registration required for Black Africans arriving in the city. Up until the 1930s, there was some uncertainty as to whether to define Black African labourers as “temporary workers” who would stay in the city for a limited period of time and then return to their home villages, or whether to treat them as fully-fledged resident workers. While more conservative groups were suspicious of the influence of ever larger numbers of Black Africans in the white city, industrialists keenly watched the growing opportunities to take advantage of cheap labour (Baines 2002). Ever-tighter living quarters with Black Africans, however, prompted collective hysteria. Mbembe writes: “the racial city was always a psychotic city or space of delirium. This delirium was of both a political and a psychic nature. And in both cases, it had a paranoid and schizophrenic dimension. Because of this dual structure, delirium at times manifested itself through the production and overcoding of fears and fantasies, faked objects and images” (Mbembe 2008: 45). Baines, for example, reports various cases of white women pressing charges of assault against Black men without sufficient evidence or proof (Baines 2002).

The concerns of the affluent gave rise to tighter curfew rules. From 1885 to 1930, Black Africans were forbidden from circulating in the city centre between nine o’ clock in the evening and four o’ clock in the morning, at least not without a “pass”, available to property owners or upon the request of an employer. This regulation was later revoked, again when industrialists wanted to attract a higher number of labourers to the city (Baines 2002).

In 1901, when the first epidemic of the bubonic plague was recorded in Port Elizabeth with a death toll of at least 136,¹⁰⁹ the precarious hygiene conditions that Black Africans lived in in the city centre was given as the cause of the disease. The colonial authorities suggested establishing a designated district out of the city centre in which to transfer non-white people. The constitution of a Plague Board accelerated

¹⁰⁹ Unless otherwise indicated, the data referenced in this chapter come from Baines (2002), who remains the most accurate source regarding the various phases of Red Location’s history up until the 1950s.

the demolition of houses that were considered a public health risk – Baines reports the demolition of 350 houses in the city centre and at least three times that number in the peripheries (2002). The passing of the Native Reserve Location Act of 1902 turned the emergency legislation on public health into ordinary law, constituting a judicial framework for the establishment of the locations and laying the foundations for racial separation. This connection between health and the poverty governance was further strengthened in 1919 when, through the Public Health Act, the central government obliged local authorities to provide adequate housing, essential services and to fiscally manage the locations with municipal budgets.

The creation of Red Location and later New Brighton was enabled by the Cape Town authorities' acquisition of two factories known as Cradock Place and Deal Party, situated eight kilometres to the north of the city. The people who would be displaced requested the guarantee of being able to purchase the title deeds for the new houses, but this request was not well received. The houses were assigned in order of arrival of those who were willing to move. Initially, the expectation was to house 1500 people in three types of accommodation: class A (two-room flats for families of so-called "civilised natives"), class B (studio flats for regular workers), and class C (dormitories for "single men", migrants who had moved to the city from the countryside without their families). The original plan also established a separation within the location, since churches and shops would be arranged to divide "civilised natives" from "uncivilised natives", those who had not lived in the city for long. The Public Works Department planned to reuse the wood and sheet metal houses from the Uitenhage concentrate camp of the Anglo-Boer war in order to reduce costs and house a larger number of people. These houses were in fact converted into dormitories to house 2800 migrant workers. These lines of houses were painted red, hence the name Red Location. Even though the settlement had been designed by the central government, Red Location was supplied with neither electricity nor adequate sewerage; it had communal latrines and the wastewater was channelled into the river running alongside the location. Formally established to address public hygiene problems, the location suffered the same problems it was supposed to provide the solution to.

Since many Black Africans would have preferred to move to another location, Korsten, that guaranteed title deeds and had less strict regulations, the authorities decided to instigate a system of compulsory change of residency through intimidation

and demolition. In 1905, the location grew from 1197 to 4516 inhabitants (Baines 2002: 71). Co-optation was another way in which Black Africans were pushed into other locations: the government approached families who could independently afford to build their own houses in an attempt to diversify the social composition of the location. Baines discusses a Reverend of the Order of Ethiopia Church who convinced his congregation to move en masse (Baines 2002: 73). Gradually, even the houses allocated to “single men” were converted into houses for families, while the township was equipped with a police station, an administration block, canteens and shops. Other districts were also built – firstly, Newtown-White location and then, in 1941, McNamee village, the place that would later be identified as the jewel in the crown of the city administration.

McNamee, to the east of Red Location, was built with two objectives: eliminating the shantytowns in Korsten and designing an ideal settlement that would not experience the same problems as Red Location, including overpopulation, the difficulty of confirming which people and families were actually residents, and growing criminality. McNamee, effectively designed as an improved Red Location, was composed of 784 two-roomed flats for two families; 2698 three-room flats for two families; and 24 single units. Many services were included later, including shelters, community rooms, old people’s homes, a swimming pool, refuse collection and tarmacked roads. Residents also received free medical care. A central square was created and an annual prize was awarded to the best garden; the houses were whitewashed once a year, paid for by the Municipality. A McNamee resident recollected, “they [the officials] would come and check how you would keep your house and your garden and if you weren’t clean, you would be sent to Red Location”.¹¹⁰ The Municipality hailed the district as an example of how the eradication of informal settlements would beget improvements on physical, moral and psychological levels and reduce criminality (Baines 2002: 91).

It was also emphasised how living in a clean and aesthetically appropriate environment would generate virtuous behaviour from citizens who were encouraged to take better care of their homes. Indeed, Matyu, a historic resident of Javabu Road, journalist and novelist, recalls:

¹¹⁰ An informal conversation in New Brighton, March 2015.

Our fathers and mothers who moved into McNamee were bamboozled by the white man's magic world of transformation from the smelly night soil bucket system to flush toilets, neatly built brick-and-mortar two-or three-roomed electrified houses each with a Dover stove using coal or wood. They were a far cry from the dilapidated wood-and-iron houses in a slum (Matyu 1997)

In 1947, McNamee was included as one of the destinations on the British royal tour to the Union. During a ceremony celebrating the construction of the 300th house, the Minister of the Interior and Public Health claimed that Port Elizabeth provided an example for the entire nation. Beyond the insistence on the district's virtues and the role performed by the colonial government (and from 1923, by local governments), living conditions in New Brighton were far from ideal: refuse collection and imposed hygiene standards did not stem the spreading of epidemics of typhus and tuberculosis; the handful of schools did not solve the problems of precarious and insufficient levels of education.

Matyu lists several criminals from the district who have gone down in history (Matyu 1997). Baines discusses one measure in particular that was proposed to tackle crime between the 1930s and 1940s: the superintendent suggested that adult children of residents should be obliged to pay a fixed sum of money to obtain a "lodger permit". Young people would be forced to find a job to pay for the permit. In New Brighton, the formation of neighbourhood guards and vigilante groups dates back to the 1920s – tired of the dangerous conditions they were forced to live in, the township's inhabitants decided to create teams of volunteers to police the surrounding area (Buur 2006), even calling for harsher penalties for those who committed more serious offences like murder or armed robbery.

Robinson underlines how there was a gradual change in the governance of the location, from a liberal administration to a bureaucratic, distant and seemingly repressive regime (Robinson 1996). While there is no doubt that apartheid and the increasing number of social confrontations that ensued from it led to growing coercion and the establishment of an increasingly violent regime, it is also true that successive South African governments during and immediately following apartheid stayed relatively close to a paternalistic attitude to government. This can be seen in

the modernist conceptualisation of architecture and urban planning in which functionality, control and social order were combined to produce a city that would guarantee living and working conditions that would be most appropriate for citizens' social classes and racial classifications. Those with formal work and so who could pay rent were entitled to some form of recognition and visibility. On the contrary, unemployment, casual work and unlawful or informal residence in the township led to exclusion and invisibility. However, this did not mean freedom from other forms of power or oppression. Housing, then as now, was established as a form of social control. A prime example in this regard is the Municipality's decision after the Paint Riot¹¹¹ to transfer funds that had originally been allocated for a housing project for white people to the township of New Brighton, with the caveat that as soon as there were further protests, this decision would be revoked (Baines 2002: 294).

Even during moments of greatest conflict and the worst violence, the apartheid government declared itself to be democratic and relied on democratic processes, albeit in a rather distorting manner. The South African government even justified racial separation and the ban on interracial marriages by arguing that it was prioritising the common good over individual desires and lives. Racial separation was forcefully established, but it was sustained mostly through behavioural governance. While it is true that the history of Port Elizabeth is tragically marked by the demolition of entire districts and the forced removal of groups of individuals, it is also true that, for example as in the case of McNamee, middle-class Black Africans (teachers, nurses, freelance professionals) chose to relocate elsewhere and tried to keep the new areas clean and safe to distinguish them from poorer, rougher areas. New Brighton was fenced off and to enter and leave it was necessary to present a "pass", and yet at the same time, once within the location it was possible to enjoy free medical treatment.

The ambiguity of the colonial and apartheid governments' operations is exemplified by controls on beer production. New Brighton was designed as an exemplary space that would produce exemplary residents, and yet, despite pervasive controls, the residents did not behave as expected. Baines describes the legislation on beer production as a "beer brewing dualism" (Baines 2002): section 14 of the Native

¹¹¹ The Paint Riot took place in 1952 in New Brighton. Two police officers fatally shot a man suspected of having stolen a pot of paint. As many of the onlookers present protested, the police opened fire on the crowd. For further discussion, see Appendix 2.

Reserve Location Act ruled that no type of brewing or distillery licence could be granted to the residents. However, article 16 simultaneously prohibited bringing “intoxicating liquor” or traditional beer into the township and authorised the domestic production of a limited quantity of the beverage, with the dual aim of preventing liquor being brought into the township and controlling the production of a substance that the residents would not have given up.¹¹² Areas in Red Location were subdivided into “wet” and “dry”, that is, places where alcohol production was authorised or prohibited, and a sort of production shift was organised in the “wet areas”. This legislation, however, prompted the creation of makeshift speakeasies in private homes where migrant workers would gather. Beer brewing became one of the main means of subsistence for women in the location, but it was also considered unorthodox and promiscuous. Payment of the production permit and respect for shift patterns were closely monitored by the local authorities, who carried out frequent checks and would destroy illegally produced beer and punish those who broke the rules. In 1962, with the coming into effect of the Liquor Act, municipal beer halls were established to generate profits from beer sales and to increase controls on production.

Baines insists on the fact that rather than speaking about a model township, we should talk about “the narrative of a model township” (Baines 2011). If this is true for the first half of the twentieth century, it continued to be the case with the RLMCP. Indeed, the project and the way in which the organisers justified it generated new representations of the residents of Red Location and New Brighton.

4. The reinvention of community: oppressed, subversive, or long-term residents?

Depending on the goals being pursued or the claims being made, New Brighton has been variously represented as a rough, destitute, hard-working, progressive, disorderly or dangerous district. Analysis of these various representations – two of which were promoted by Riordan, the creator, organiser and custodian of the project at different points in the 1980s and 1990s – reveals how the township went from being represented as a disorderly and deprived community and started instead to be

¹¹² On “beer brewing dualism”, see Nieftagodien interviewed by C. Blignaut and S. Sithole, ‘A twisted tale of alcohol and apartheid’, *news24*, 27/01/2014; Mager (1999); Roth (2016).

represented as a cultural community held together by a varied heritage and structured by the framework of emancipation. It started to be portrayed as a community that shared political convictions, sports teams, creative trends and charities. This process of reinvention inevitably reduced and homogenised the citizens and essentially excluded those who did not fit into this standard representation. Tellingly, the etymology of “reputation” reveals connections to the acts of pruning, trimming, tidying up through cutting off useless or unsightly branches.

In 1986, Riordan, acting as president of Operation Real South Africa, was involved in tense negotiations about a municipal project to demolish the illegal shacks in Red Location and relocate the families living there to Motherwell, a township around twenty kilometres away. During these negotiations, three key representations of the inhabitants of Red Location emerged. The first came from the Municipality, whose attempt to restructure the township was really motivated by a desire to deconstruct what they considered to be a nest of subversions. The second came from Riordan, his colleague Sawage and partner organisations, who presented the location’s inhabitants as oppressed and forced to live in degradation. The third was advanced by a group of inhabitants who were at risk of being evicted from the location and relocated elsewhere, many of whom presented themselves as elderly residents and families.

According to Pullen, Town Clerk of Ibhayi Town Council, Red Location’s shacks were in a state of such advanced decline that the residents had to move to other houses in Motherwell. Pullen linked safety to hygiene: “The Red Location is a dangerous, unhygienic place. The Security Forces are spearheading, with Council, the upgrading” (Riordan 1986). These were the official justifications for the Town Clerk’s decision to move residents from Red Location to Motherwell. During a private interview with Riordan and Sawage, however, Pullen expressed his motivations for the evictions in terms of maintaining the public order. Riordan and Sawage write:

He then asked us (something he later repeated twice) if we had ever seen a necklace victimas he had – and it isn’t very pretty. He noted that he had problems with comrades and other extremists who necklace innocent people [...] the intention of the security forces in the black townships was to adopt an ‘Oliekol approach’. You drop a drop of oil here, and

spread it out. Firstly they would do New Brighton, by applying the security fence and roadblocks. They would then ‘stabilise and neutralise’ New Brighton, until it became a ‘sterilized area’. [...] He confirmed that the Red Location was difficult to control and that was why it was being done first (Riordan 1986).

Riordan and Sawage also recorded a comment from Le Roux, Senior Township Manager of the township of Zwide, who claimed: “lodgers and unregistered tenants, described by Mr Pullen as being ‘in the path of progress’, would be moved from the Red Location. The area cannot be re-developed because of them” (Riordan 1986). The inhabitants of Red Location, in short, were deemed dangerous in at least two senses of the word: as unruly subjects, prepared to commit heinous crimes even against their own, and as illegal and/or disadvantaged occupants who obstructed the path towards development. The approach adopted by Riordan and Sawage was also twofold. In the South Africa of the 1980s, years characterised by intense repression, their role was not exactly to overtly oppose institutions so much as to ensure respect for human rights in a nation that had always considered itself to be democratic. The letters that they wrote to institutions therefore employed the same language as state officials; they translated the residents’ demands in a language that was more acceptable to institutions. As a result, they ended up sharing the Municipality’s objectives (easing tensions, improving living conditions, all with a view to development and maintaining the established order), albeit via alternative methods (in an interview, Riordan clarified “I’m a liberal” to distinguish himself from the more left-wing factions of the ANC).¹¹³ For this reason, their representation of the location’s residents simultaneously emphasised their oppression and insisted on the urgency of developing the township. Riordan described the enormous problems arising from the institutions’ negligence towards the area, and referenced the needs for water supply, electricity and hygiene services. At the same time, he highlighted families’ reluctance and inability to leave the township (Riordan 1986).

Riordan described the first and only demolition of a shack – the campaign against evictions in Red Location was successful in preventing further houses being knocked down – as a brutal act of senseless violence against the residents.¹¹⁴ The

¹¹³ Rory Riordan, interview 13/03/15.

¹¹⁴ “Everywhere there is the din of hammers at work, the wailing of women, the throb of truck motors, the shouts of policemen. It is a thoroughly rotten scene, of bullying, of threatening, of

journalist Jimmy Matyu witnessed the scene and in his description of the residents emphasised their vulnerability: “the residents, some of them infirm, disabled and blind, sang hymns”.¹¹⁵

While Riordan spoke out publicly against evictions in of Red Location, he did support regeneration in the township, and maintained that this could have been achieved through restructuring urban planning and housing and maintaining a cohesive community:

It appears to be quite beyond controversy to any observer, including all of the residents to whom I have spoken, that the area needs to be totally re-developed with an entirely new services and housing network. There can be no case for the retention of any of the existing housing stock as I have seen them. Only shops, schools, churches and a few other public buildings merit retention. Given the validity of the above two points, our position would be that the Red Location should be redeveloped to maximum density housing with as little disruption to the existing community as possible, and with every possible energy being expended to retain the entire community in the re-developed area as that is the wish of the community (Riordan 1986).

Residents countered threats of eviction by emphasising how long they had lived there, evoking visceral relationships to the location as their home. Their references to the notions of community and family were not coincidental. In organising meetings against the evictions, they claimed, “they say they are going to take the shacks, but the shacks are our children”; “The Red Location is like the mother of all the townships. It was the first here. It has grandchildren now”; “There is a saying in the Bible; ‘I begot children, made them to grow up, fed them, then they turned against me’. It is the same in the Red Location. We have stood with Mr. Mundel until the place became old – now he turns his back on us, and sends the SADF [the South African Defence Force, the army, charged with executing the demolition]”.¹¹⁶

In the 1980s, despite support for the anti-eviction committee from various civil society organisations, the residents involved represented themselves primarily as

insensitive, crude thoughtless bureaucrats smashing up people’s lives for no reason, and to nobody’s gain” (Riordan 1986).

¹¹⁵ J. Matyu, ‘Call for Red Location Residents to Unite’, *Evening Post*, 24/11/1986.

¹¹⁶ Interview with the residents of Red Location, reported by Riordan (1986).

long-standing residents, the lifeblood of the location, rather than drawing attention to their reputation as resisting militants.

5. Rebuilding and reputation: Red Location as a cultural community

Establishing the RLMCP in the 1990s entailed advancing an alternative representation of the residents and the township. In many ways, this process, as a prelude to the transformation of the township, employed the same methods that were used to create and transform Red Location at the beginning of the twentieth century. Both were interventions that institutions justified by stressing the need to improve living conditions and promote development. Further, the direction of these representations was decided by the organisers in order to facilitate transformation and complement urban regeneration. In the 1990s, the transformation of Red Location into a “model township” came about through it being represented as a cultural community. In a similar manner to “New Brighton, the model township”, the image of Red Location as a cultural community was a form of progressive social engineering focused on the values of post-apartheid.

In both cases, the primary aim seemed to be to improve the township’s reputation rather than to accurately represent its real circumstances. Advancing the image of a cultural community served as a sort of endorsement for the residents’ worthiness and so corroborated the need for the project to take place in precisely that location. It was also used to demonstrate how the project would fit perfectly into the history and context of the location. Moreover, focusing on artistic creativity meant emphasising on one of the most multi-racial elements of the city’s history.

The RLMCP was conceived at the beginning of the transition to democracy, a period marked by refusal of the racial categories of apartheid and the desire to rewrite relationships that had previously been imagined exclusively as a binary opposition between oppressed and oppressors. There was a desire to forefront the silenced, overshadowed history of the townships, alongside the cultures and traditions of other people who had not been recognised as full citizens during the segregationist regime. The organisers claimed and the local politicians repeated that there was more to the township than met the eye. At the time, New Brighton was one of the areas most

affected by criminality, unemployment, inadequate services and daily violence,¹¹⁷ but the project relied on the idea that the location could not be reduced to first appearances: the idea was that obvious poverty and disadvantage hid great richness, important cultural heritage and a strong, cohesive community of freedom-fighters.

In reality, these two aspects do not always coincide: a culturally vibrant community might not be particularly politically militant and vice versa. However, as the project progressed and the museum was established, the organisers understood that emphasising New Brighton's artistic and cultural heritage would allow it to attract more support and mitigate risks that the exhibition inside the museum would simply tell the local history of the ANC. Among the concerns that the curator Du Preez found himself faced with following his appointment were the issues of generalising Red Location's history to all of New Brighton, and about the type of history that the museum should narrate. Should a museum of anti-apartheid struggle detail a precise timeline of events or try to evoke more of a general atmosphere? Should it cover the entire period? Should it limit itself to political activism or include any move for freedom?

Art and culture helped to widen the site under consideration. The curators repeatedly wondered, doesn't New Brighton's heritage basically belong to the entire city?, and evoked the image of a smouldering creative potential ready to erupt again. This choice was reinforced by the conviction that allowing "potential to flourish" and "making the most of the specificities of certain areas" was one the main objectives and maieutic tasks of development agencies. In the view of the project organisers, popular forms of art that were deemed worthy of being dignified and integrated into the pantheon of national culture – New Brighton jazz being a prime example – would appeal to certain swathes of the middle-class who considered themselves to be open-minded, progressive and having been on the frontlines in the march to freedom. This, they believed, would made the RLMCP an attraction across the entire city for diverse types of audiences.

With these considerations in mind, the history and contemporary reputation of New Brighton was reinterpreted and rewritten. The growing interest in the social

¹¹⁷ This accolade has now passed to Bethelsdorp, where the rates of armed murder have grown exponentially (from 89 to 137, as opposed to 69 cases in New Brighton in 2016) as result of gang rivalry. See the website Crimestatasa.

and material history of the townships that emerged in the 1990s also affected New Brighton and Red Location. The representation of New Brighton as a key site in the development of theatre and jazz from the 1950s onwards produced a depiction of the location as a peaceful place where social cohesion and solidarity had enabled resistance to the violence of apartheid and created a concordant everyday normality. Of course, elements such as the political violence of the 1980s,¹¹⁸ criminality and inequality are excluded from this representation.

Every document published by RLMCP organisers, even the introduction to the business plan, included references to the location's cultural life and lists of the artists who had contributed to the township's fame. For example, the Motivated Architect Brief included in the business plan for the first part of the project has a section on the context of the location which is divided into the following chapters: "New Brighton and theatre, New Brighton and music, New Brighton and art, New Brighton as a site of struggle". With regards to the RLMCP, Baines writes: "irrespective of the motives of its initiators and planners, the project represents a real danger that outsiders might impose their vision of what New Brighton's past should mean for those who have lived there " (Baines 2005: 257). Indeed, the organisers' vision started to impact the way in which the residents themselves represented the township. For example, through their discovery of the township's past cultural life, young local artists strengthened their connection to previous generations and formed new relationships that could somewhat occlude the sufferings of apartheid, concentrating instead on domestic space and the freedom of underground art.

In 2014, the singer Azanda Mqiki filmed the video "Phakama" in New Brighton with the local jazz band *Take Notes*. The video jubilantly celebrates a 1950s–1960s version of the township that is purged of segregation and daily violence and reconstructs a certain mode of self-expression and creativity in public spaces. The characters are dressed in period fashion and move between historical buildings that are now topped by solar panels, with pastel colours, colonnades and vintage shop signs. The video is steeped in an atmosphere of romantic decadence, and closes in a collective dance to jazz music in an improvised town square. This single song

¹¹⁸ In 1985-86 in New Brighton, there were various clashes between partisans of the United Democratic Front (UDF) and the Azanian People's Organisation (ASAPO), involving the destruction of several houses and multiple injuries. The clashes were likely manipulated by the security forces, as argued in the final report of the TRC (TRC 1998, volume 3).

encapsulates a whole gamut of recovered images: social cohesion and a shared musical style that would become the township's brand, community mingling, the depiction of the township's creative energy, nostalgia and attachment to a time when New Brighton set trends. In 2013, *The Herald* published an insert to mark 110 years from the creation of the township. The insert consisted of four parts intitled, "A hub of art and culture", "At the political forefront", "Driven by small business", "Birth place of sport stars". Taken as a whole, the insert reconstructed New Brighton from the four components that had become its fundamental cornerstones: art, political activism, buzzing social life and sport. An article on the eminent opening of the art gallery explained, "New Brighton is the most culturally alive area in the whole of Nelson Mandela Bay, it is the home of music, art and theatre".¹¹⁹

While this representation was welcomed by the inhabitants, who watched their reputation transform from ghetto-dwellers to bearers of the city's history (having lived in New Brighton or being from New Brighton has today become something to be proud of), an alternative New Brighton continued to exist. In 2014, the township was identified as one of the least safe areas of the city and the museum itself, when it was operational, suffered thefts and more serious crimes: in 2014 a security guard employed by Metro Security Services (MSS) was mugged and killed while on shift at the museum. In a lengthy interview, two teachers from the Jarvis Gqamalana state primary school, located a few hundred metres from the RLMCP, painted a particularly alarming picture of the location:

[Red Location] it's a poor community, underprivileged, with a high unemployment rate. Children are raised by their grandparents, the community is dependent on social grants, there's a high crime-rate, there's a high rate of substance abuse, teenage pregnancy, HIV and unhygienic living conditions. It's an illiterate community and education is not at the top of the values, it's not seen as a key to improve life. We are not safe and we don't feel safe. [Last year] gangsters have been shooting just outside the school and one of them run inside the courtyard. A professional psychologist had to come and to perform emergency therapy after the shooting.¹²⁰

¹¹⁹ N. Joordan, 'New art gallery for Red Location centre', *The Herald*, 11/11/2010.

¹²⁰ Interview 06/08/2015.

It is not my aim to establish which one of these extreme depictions (a cohesive or fragmented community; the importance placed on culture or the absence of shared values) most accurately represents the township. Rather, I aspire to shed light on the coexistence of multiple different nuances that were mobilised according to different purposes. The excessively schematic nature of the project organisers' portrayal of the location, while tempting, would come to be appropriated by the majority of people involved; it was denied and deconstructed through the various phases of the RLMCP. Indeed, during the project's delivery phase, various other representations of the township emerged.

6. Arranging the public city

The elements of the RLMCP that relate to housing projects and urban regeneration recall the governance of the "public city" (Di Biagi 2006; Bressan 2012). Bressan writes that the expression "public city" refers to a city's overall legacy of social housing and public space. In South Africa, as in Europe, governance of the public city is increasingly delegated to urban planning and architecture, and so it is architects and urban planners, rather than social workers, who are more often asked to meet social needs and to make the outskirts more appropriate and liveable.

Certainly, the RLMCP organisers acted so that urban regeneration and improvements to social housing would increase the real estate value of the township and open the road to further projects and profit-generating opportunities. However, the housing projects that accompanied the RLMCP, much like the RLMCP itself, can be analysed as more complex interventions. The RLMCP was an initiative that aspired to govern poverty through a spatial transformation of the township.

The idea that architecture can trigger social change and that urban planning and architecture are effectively instruments of governance was not a new concept in South Africa. Murray argues that apartheid architecture was heavily influenced by European modernist architecture, widespread in Europe in the period between the two world wars (the architects of Italian Rationalism were also part of the modernist movement, the movement that informed the architecture of the Italian fascist regime). He further stresses how South African architects never abandoned the foundational principles of modernism and that still today these shape many public building

projects carried out in South Africa (Murray 2010). South African architects and urban planners embraced the lessons of Le Corbusier, who argued that architecture had the responsibility of revising values and manifesting them in buildings and material objects through analysis and experimentation (Le Corbusier 2008, first edition 1923). Le Corbusier saw the house as a “machine for living in” and designed Unités d’Habitation and prefabricated housing, inaugurating a form of social housing in which functionalism and standardisation were seen as synonymous with beauty. Le Corbusier additionally saw a continuity between architecture and urban planning, or in other words between the design of homes and the design of cities.

The segregated city of apartheid was shaped following the principles of modernist architecture and with the conviction that spatial design was equivalent to the organisation of society. Smit *et al.* remark that in South Africa the adage that “good houses make good people” is still very current (Smit *et al.* 2014). There is a sort of spatial determinism inherent in this relationship between decent housing and civilised living, the idea that the shape of space can determine social processes (Balestrieri 2011) and that individuals reflect the places they live in. Red Location demonstrates a clear continuity between apartheid and post-apartheid urban planning. The peripheries, still to this day, are seen as an “unfinished city”, and for this reason are perceived as excellent testing grounds.

In Red Location, the prospect of intervening on the imperfections of unfinished, empty space has been a constant throughout the entire history of the township. The unfinishedness of the architecture ended up being associated with the residents themselves, who were seen as “unfulfilled” citizens who if left to their own devices, just like the buildings, risked becoming a danger unto themselves and others.

This modernist interpretation of spatial construction was accompanied by neoliberal policies and the governance of diversity. The housing experiments that were conducted around Red Location had two explicit goals: poverty deconcentration and the foundation of close-knit community spaces. The ways in which these objectives were pursued, however, revealed other implicit assumptions. Deconcentrating poverty was a way of creating a space that was considered welcoming and liveable for the middle-classes, that is, a place in which the housing was diversified and services were varied, accessible, safe and respectable. The vision of the RLMCP as a public space responded to this aim – it was perceived as a tool to

allow the Municipality to access the township and create a sort of enclave where an institution (the project) would guarantee security and the possibility of relationships across difference. The township was seen as a sort of proto-city in the making, in need of external intervention if it were to become fully fledged.

On the other hand, the creation of a place of neighbourliness was seen as a way to improve safety through prompting the residents to participate in mutual aid and mutual control. Even the arrangement of the houses was designed to ensure a greater degree of protection. Again, this both demonstrates how the state tried to reduce its presence and attests to the idea that a community space would be more attractive for the middle-class – living near an experimental district certainly sounds better than living near a “no-go area”. The creation of neighbourly communities entailed the further marginalisation of those who were not considered to be project beneficiaries, and so deepened divisions along poverty lines. While, on the one hand, the housing projects around the RLMCP, once completed, would satisfy the needs of a considerable number of families, on the other hand, they would contribute to the removal and eviction of shack-dwellers and others who were not considered beneficiaries.

Wacquant notes how relegation – a term whose etymology refers to the distancing of an individual or group without the removal of their political and civic rights¹²¹ – is a collective activity. It does not only result from government action, but also from the behaviour of media, educational institutions, etc. (Wacquant 2016). From this point of view, urban regeneration alone is not sufficient to reduce marginalisation. The RLMCP rather than reducing urban poverty, displaced and stratified it.

Urban regeneration entails the unfurling of an array ownership and appropriation practices that can lead to others being dispossessed (as happened with the owners of the shacks who were forced to move elsewhere to make room for the project). The change that results from this is ambivalent. The RLMCP was an attempt to transform the township through the exorcism of its most frightening features, namely security concerns. It was a way of domesticating the township, building a bridge between the positive, productive and emancipatory version of the city and its

¹²¹ There is an etymological difference between *relegare* (distancing while formally maintaining civil and political rights) and *banire* or “banishing” (an act that requires civil rights to be removed). See Etimo, etymological dictionary.

inverse. Ruddick (2009) and Heap (2009) underline how cities are places of proximity with alterity, where that which is perceived to be hostile and different is met with a mixture of curiosity and repulsion. Urban regeneration promised an opportunity to reconceptualise this proximity and neutralise its more unsettling aspects. When the museum was open, the cultural centre was not unlike a suburb, alienating some Red Location residents so much that they asked whether they were allowed to enter the buildings.¹²² In case of the RLMCP's attempts at transforming the location, attraction to diversity (i.e., the inhabitants' poverty) and its displacement proceeded hand in hand; the socialisation of diversity was only possible through controlling it (Tissot 2014).

¹²² This anecdote was shared with me by various members of the Museum's staff, and also by several members of the RLSC. An official also recollected how during the months in which the restaurant was operational, a rather embarrassing situation arose because the restaurant had transparent glass walls and children would clamber on the outside to see what the tourists were eating. Informal conversation, December 2015.

Part Two. Preparing and Prescribing: Ownership and Belonging

The RLMCP project was conceived by its organisers as a journey towards emancipation, reflecting and concluding the path to national liberation and contributing to the construction of a new South Africa. On the one hand, encapsulating the memory of anti-apartheid struggle in the museum was seen as the crowning achievement of the struggle itself, the crystallisation of its values as the foundations of the state and a legacy to be bequeathed to future generations. On the other hand, the RLMCP called upon all members of society, a multitude of individuals, groups and institutions, to rally behind development just as they had for the cause of anti-apartheid struggle. Development was neither an end-goal nor a prerequisite for the new South Africa to gain and keep a place in the global economy, but predominantly the method through which citizens were urgently called upon to contribute to nation-building. From this perspective, the project wholly subscribed to the neoliberal rhetoric of “there is no alternative” (TINA)¹²³ – South Africa’s only option was to integrate itself into the global economy, and South African cities had no alternative but to become international, in terms of technology, sustainability and competitiveness. This required committed engagement from every member of society. Failure to integrate or “keep up with the times” would inevitably lead to stagnation and ruin. For Red Location inhabitants, this ultimatum was expressed in terms of a choice between taking advantage of the development opportunities on offer, or remaining residents of a poor, marginalised and marginalising area.

Despite these premises and justifications, that remained more or less consistent throughout the project’s lifetime, Red Location residents organised into committees and frequently protested over issues related to the cultural centre and the housing policies that accompanied the urban regeneration of the location bordering the RLMCP. In addition to housing disputes, the residents protested against the content of the museum’s collections, the cultural centre’s broken promises of job

¹²³ “There is no alternative” was an expression used by Margaret Thatcher to introduce neoliberal reforms and create the impression of constant teetering on a knife-edge between victory and defeat, between economic growth or national paralysis and isolation. Hart uses this expression to describe the ANC’s justification for their introduction of GEAR (2002).

creation, and disregard of alternative uses of the RLMCP that would better respond to local need. The RLMCP was a battleground from the construction works up until the occupation by the Red Location Steering Committee (RLSC) in 2013.

RLSC members were accused by project organisers and local politicians of misunderstanding the project's aims, or of sabotaging the township's only hope of socio-economic improvement. The occupation was dismissed as a show of antagonism, as harmful but essentially insignificant. However, as we turn our gaze away from the neoliberal rhetoric enveloping the project and focus instead on the everyday lives of Red Location inhabitants, it becomes possible to assign new meaning to the occupation. As the residents' most forceful and obvious act of appropriation and claiming ownership, the occupation is closely linked to the way in which Red Location inhabitants constructed and experienced belonging and identity.

Two forms of ownership and belonging collided in the context of the RLMCP. The project organisers construed ownership as adherence to the project's fundamental values, expressed through everyone fulfilling the roles that the project had assigned them. The residents' committee, on the other hand, understood ownership as the power to direct the project's fate. From the perspective of the organisers, those who endorsed the project's aims could be included in the project, participate in development and thus confirm their place in the new South African nation. The residents refused this conflation between ownership and endorsement, between participation in the project and strengthened national identity. The residents maintained that the cultural centre belonged to the township's inhabitants – it was built on the township's land and out of the township's history – and that the residents were therefore entitled to a say in the project. The demands of the RLSC and other residents reveal the stratified nature of belonging and complex relationships with the state that cannot be reduced to national identity.

The RLMCP regulated ownership and belonging by “preparing” and “prescribing” the behaviour of various groups. Fassin, discussing the language of humanitarianism, highlights how development projects inextricably link values and affects, serving both to define and justify practices of the government of human beings (Fassin 2010). To prepare is to get something ready, to put it in its proper place, in order, according to an established plan and for a desired end. It is therefore an action pertaining to an arrangement in space and time, the establishment of hierarchy and

the distribution of tasks and roles, ranging from the creation of a project organisational chart, to decisions about the responsibility for and legitimacy of project interventions, to making assumptions about what standards of behaviour residents or citizens should conform to. Prescribing, on the other hand, refers to “ordaining in writing” and normalising behaviours, whether that be through regulations, bureaucracy and administration, or processes of homogenisation. Prescribing pertains to stipulating agreements between various stakeholders, writing up contracts and guidelines, but it also involves categorising individuals according to their roles, backgrounds, and crystallisations of their identities.

Prescribing and preparing imply a “correct” form of behaviour and to varying degrees stigmatise any behaviour that deviates from these established norms. The project prescribed modes of ownership in a way that compartmentalised participants into discrete roles: the project organisers were the brains behind development; politicians were tasked with publicly supporting the project and convincing the local community of its importance; ground-level officials and project workers were responsible for the practical nuts and bolts of project delivery and putting a face to the absent state; academics were called upon to sanction the project’s aims, to ratify its quality and importance, pre-empt any criticisms and ensure the project’s international competitiveness; artists were seen as important representatives, mediators and educators of the community, vehicles of the values to be promoted by the project; the residents were mostly considered as bearers of or witnesses to the past, but also as a pool of unskilled labour for the precarious work required by the project.

The project, however, could not set about prescribing and preparing on a blank canvas, but rather in a township where the social fabric was woven with the complex imbrications of different moral orders. The use of the word “community” to group the township’s inhabitants into a uniform mass serves to simplify a space in which social relations were structured by the tessellation of various moral dichotomies – some inhabitants were condemned as dangerous while others were labelled vulnerable; places associated with emancipation alternated with places of ill-repute. Further symbols and value systems derive from Red Location’s status as a majority Xhosa township. Complex forms of belonging and identity in the township must further be understood from a historical perspective, taking into account the way in which

asymmetrical models of citizenship have consolidated within the location. The residents' occupation of the museum, like their previous protests, can therefore be interpreted as the demand for readmittance into the political sphere, not as an amorphous "community" but as citizens with various identities and forms of social belonging. Protests around the RLMCP, however, were not a simple two-sided conflict between distinct parties – the project organisers versus the residents, or the state versus the citizens. They were instead the result of constant exchanges and interactions in which the motives and rationales of different groups ended up bleeding into each other. In Hibou and Bono's analysis, societies are composed of interactions between people who come together, consciously or unconsciously, wilfully or involuntarily, to organise and discipline ways of living together (2016). From this perspective, conflict can offer particular insight into "tensions between multiple worldviews and attempts to find middle ground between them" (2016: 31).

In the context of the RLMCP there were several discrepancies between prescribed and practised behaviours. In some instances, it was exception to the rule rather than strict compliance that allowed the project to progress. As in all conflicts, opposing factions encountered each other on a daily basis in the space of the cultural centre, got to know each other well, spoke to each other casual terms and sometimes even silently shared the views of their counterparts. The RLMCP, then, was more of a forum than a battlefield, a space for public discussion and negotiation. In occupying the cultural centre, the location's residents expressed multiple identities and allegiances, but the same can be said for other actors in the conflict including officials and politicians. Interactions through the project can also be characterized by a sort of aphasia in the absence of new terms to replace the categories of apartheid. The residents' actions can be read as an attempt to fill the void of identity constituted by this aphasia: the occupation did not invent new terms, but it did give voice to forms of national and local belonging that had been overlooked by policy makers.

4. The RLMCP: a sanctuary of social harmony

In *Building Change*, a book analysing the relationship between power, space and architecture through four architectural case studies, including the Red Location Museum, architect Lisa Findley writes, "the monumentality of the Museum has had a

curious effect on the people of New Brighton. Suddenly, their neglected and marginalized town is the location of a large, serious public institution. They are now part of the metropolitan area in a way they have never been. The civic urban sensibility this brings has inestimable value” (Findley 2005: 158). In this view, the presence of the museum (when Findley wrote the book the other components of the centre were yet to be built) increased the residents’ sense of belonging to the city and encouraged them to become more aware of the rules of social harmony. Findley’s assessments are often reproduced in public discourse about the RLMCP, even though they are easily disproved by the fact that the townships have always been a natural outcome of state apparatuses, closely connected with the governance of the city and even characterised as forms of oppressive, pervasive institutional surveillance. Many people maintain that the project’s presence prompted the transformation of the residents into more mindful citizens.

In the section of the project’s master plan outlining the creation of new infrastructure and the completion of the cultural centre, the project organisers noted: “the museum is solemn and has a sense of shrine and pilgrimage” (Dojon Financial Services 2011c: 2). In short, the buildings were attributed a sense of the sacred, even the miraculous (as the Competition Brief had already detailed, the project aimed to heal the wounds of the past). A sanctuary is a particular sort of holy space, a specific spatialisation of the expression and use of the sacred.¹²⁴ Findley’s observations and the RLMCP organisers’ description of the museum converged in effectively considering the RLMCP as the architectural and artistic translation of the foundational values of post-apartheid¹²⁵ (reconciliation, cohesion, development and inclusion), but also as a place capable of promulgating and disseminating those values (of triggering Findley’s “civic sensibility”).

The organisers intended the project to connect the township to the rest of the city, and then ultimately to the whole of South Africa and the wider world, not only through tourism, but also through the RLMCP’s educational aspirations and potential. The project aimed to reintegrate the residents of Red Location into both the city and

¹²⁴ Before it officially opened, the RLM almost became a mausoleum for the remains of Govan Mbeki and Raymond Mhlaba, see Chapter 5.

¹²⁵ Discussing post-apartheid South African architecture, Findley highlights how architects had to be extremely careful about the values their buildings implied, pointing to the power and importance of architects’ role in post-apartheid and conferring an enormous performative and transformative capacity to architecture (2005: 159).

the nation. Maintaining and strengthening social cohesion were the cornerstones of the project's educational ambitions.

Social cohesion was institutionally viewed as way of binding people together, or rather, of oiling the wheels of the new South Africa. Not coincidentally, social cohesion was inflected with a sort of inclusive nationalism that aimed to overcome the fractures of the past. In the case of the RLMCP, the dissemination of these values was connected to the issuing of roles and duties that needed to be fulfilled in order for the project to function smoothly; established through agreements between Municipal departments and intended to consolidate into habitual practice. Adhering to these values and performing the roles that the project prescribed was to do your part for the (continued) existence of the South African nation.

1. Social cohesion and individual responsibility: greasing democracy

While the RLMCP was primarily conceived with the aim of material and symbolic restitution in contrast to the deprivation of apartheid, the project in fact functioned as simultaneously the product of and the antidote to social unrest. While opposing an unjust regime had been acceptable during the years of oppression, in the post-apartheid period protests were criticised as detrimental to the cause of development. Red Location inhabitants are still repeatedly told that although the subversions of the past helped to build the new South Africa, times have moved on and liberation must now be pursued by other means. In 2011, before the closure of the museum, RLM Communications and Marketing Manager Annette du Plessis published a letter in the local newspaper, *The Herald*, criticising a caption which read "RLM visitors can throw stones at this old Casspir on display".¹²⁶ She corrected that the museum denounced such acts and that the Casspir was a generous loan from the police force, in an example of obvious and outright refusal to bring back a conflict from the past. Indeed, reference to frays in the social fabric are still taboo in the new South Africa, not only when it comes to racial segregation but also in terms of distinctions between social classes, growing tribalism, sexism, criticisms of the values underpinning democracy, etc. Vigilantly avoiding conflict is seen as necessary to the survival of the nation.

¹²⁶ *The Herald*, "Museum doesn't allow stone throwing", 20/12/2006. The Casspir was the most commonly used armored vehicle by the South African army and still today remains a symbol of apartheid military force and oppression.

Over the course of twenty years, the RLMCP followed a political path from reconciliation to social cohesion. As previously noted, in the early 1990s justifications for the RLMCP project focused on the urgency of restitution to previously oppressed groups, poverty reduction and economic development. With the dissolution of the Soviet Union at the end of the nineties, however, South Africa's socialist dreams dramatically faded (Pithouse 2016) and South African economic policies took a decisively neoliberal turn. New justifications for the project were added to those cited above, as was the case in many other states across the African continent and beyond. The view of "development as delivery", as service provision and state intervention, was gradually replaced by a logic in which the individual is held up as free to make their own choices, and therefore chiefly responsible – and chiefly culpable – for the consequences of their actions on the lives of themselves and others. The RLMCP project was a precursor to the intertwining of the objective of social cohesion, as portrayed in the 2006 documentary "A nation in the making",¹²⁷ and the emphasis on individual responsibility that was establishing itself as a critical nation-building tool. In 2012, the Department of Art and Culture (DAC) published "A National Strategy for Developing an Inclusive and Cohesive South African Society", a strategy document for social cohesion and nation-building which listed many of the approaches already trialled by the RLMCP. The document's policy intentions are clear from its introduction, which includes the coat of arms of the South African army and on it, a military motto written in IXam, a Khoisan language that is today considered extinct.¹²⁸ The motto reads "!ke e: Ixarra Iixe", which translates to "diverse people unite". The document then stresses the need to create a society that was not only "caring" but also "proud", in contrast to apartheid's "denationalisation" (sic) of a large part of the population. A conflation between national community and society reappears throughout the text. Nation-building and social cohesion are also used interchangeably throughout the document, resulting in rather curious policy recommendations. For example, alleviating social injustice is suggested in the same breath as disseminating national symbols, as if these measures shared the same goal (Palmary 2015).

¹²⁷ The Presidency (2006), *A nation in the making: A discussion document on macro-social trends in South Africa*, Pretoria.

¹²⁸ The generic term "Khoisan languages" refers to languages spoken by the Khoikhoi and San populations.

The document defined social cohesion as “the degree of social integration and inclusion in communities and society at large, and the extent to which mutual solidarity finds expression itself among individuals and communities” (DAC 2012: 30). Social cohesion is thus presented as something that was both quantifiable and expressed through good-natured and inclusive relationships between citizens. Social cohesion is also described as resulting from active citizenship: there are frequent references to citizens’ awareness of their rights and responsibilities, alongside their capacity to exercise their right to political participation and aspirations to unity rather than discordant interests and worldviews. The document presented citizens as “active participants working together for the attainment of shared goals designed and agreed upon to improve the living conditions for all” (DAC 2012: 30).

“Nation-building”, on the other hand, was defined as “process whereby a society of people with diverse origins, histories, languages, cultures and religions come together within the boundaries of a sovereign state with a unified constitutional and legal dispensation, a national public education system, an integrated national economy, shared symbols and values, as equals, to work towards eradicating the divisions and injustices of the past; to foster unity; and promote a countrywide conscious sense of being proudly South African, committed to the country and open to the continent and the world” (DAC 2012: 30). National reconciliation was related to national pride, which in the context of South Africa can be understood as a “banal nationalism” (Billig 1995) that, unable to employ a rhetoric of shared roots, draws its force from an imagined, shared future and hazily defined “commitments to the country”.

Institutions were charged with two main tasks: education and the creation of material conditions that would enable social cohesion. Firstly, institutions had to educate South Africans as to their responsibilities as well-behaved, law-abiding citizens in “vertical relationships with public bodies” (DAC 2012: 20). Secondly, institutions were called upon to undertake development projects that would complement nation-building policies. Many years before this strategy document was produced, the RLMCP falls squarely into this category of development project. Like the strategy document, however, the RLMCP project was unclear with regard to how exactly institutions should contribute to social harmony. The document limits itself to listing the essential characteristics of social harmony and describes citizens’

behaviour as the predominant deciding factor.¹²⁹ In other words, institutions and public bodies gradually moved away from governing inequality, protecting minorities, raising awareness on non-discrimination, etc., and simultaneously increased attempts to moralise private life. Federico Zappino notes how “depoliticising and reducing a social problem such as poverty (though many others could be listed) to a question of failed personal choices goes hand in hand with a paternalistic sort of state benevolence that can be characterised by the tendency to maintain a status quo founded on inequality without resorting to coercive force” (Zappino 2005: 163).

The benevolent paternalism and neoliberalism of the ANC government was reflected by its advancement of the logic of personal success and its many measures and provisions that intended to aid the most disadvantaged members of society but that actually penetrated so far into the private sphere as to infringe on personal freedoms, sometimes even pushing against the limits of the law. In 2016, for example, there was public outcry over the Municipality of Uthukela (KwaZulu-Natal)’s introduction of a university scholarship for virgin girls, that was later declared unconstitutional but that would have obliged recipients to undergo compulsory virginity tests in order to reduce the number of young mothers.¹³⁰ The depiction of urban poverty as naturally corrupt or the result of adverse circumstances seemed almost unchanged from the moralising of the early apartheid years. Still today, the descendants of families who migrated from rural areas to the city almost a century ago appear not to be fully integrated in South African society. The disciplinary intent of state welfare projects is evident in continual references to “worthy” behaviours, the equivalence made between good behaviour and being worthy of receiving aid from the state. Citizens who misused public services were seen as not fully aware of their duties and responsibilities towards the state, as individuals who slowed or obstructed

¹²⁹ The cornerstones of social harmony indicated in the document are: (1) belonging, defined as a sense of affiliation, identification with and acceptance of a community or wider society; (2) inclusion in social activities and equal access to opportunities; (3) recognition, understood as knowledge of and respect of difference, without discrimination; (4) legitimacy, or the integrity of public bodies and political leaders; (5) shared values: democracy, liberty, equality, justice and mutual respect; (6) cooperation; (7) belief in the community and citizens (DAC 2012: 20). Besides the point on institutional integrity, something the document frequently calls attention to, all the other characteristics primarily fall on the shoulders of citizens, or else remain ambiguous as whose responsibility they are.

¹³⁰ *Jeune Afrique*, ‘Afrique du Sud : la « bourse de vierges » jugée illégale’, 19/06/2016.

the gears of democracy. Soss Fording and Schram have described a similar pattern in the USA, with the addition of extremely coercive disciplinary procedures (2011).

The rhetoric of personal success was used with a view to overcome inequality and economic disparity. High school end-of-year speeches and the various outputs of Toastmasters workshops,¹³¹ which are very popular in Port Elizabeth, are telling in this regard: they mostly focused on the education a sure way to achieve success. In an article entitled “New frank look at racism”, the Port Elizabeth local newspaper described an initiative at the South End Museum, led by the pastor Afrika Mhlophe, to hold monthly discussions on contemporary racism. To demonstrate the need to talk about racism in a segregated city, the pastor drew on an example: “some time ago I was speaking with some students during a break, and I encouraged them to walk around Summerstrand¹³² and look around. After several days they were still speaking about this episode. I want to encourage them to dream of these double-storey houses and one day to live there. I tell them that it’s good to dream and that there are Black people who live there”.¹³³ For the pastor, the eradication of racism meant social mobility and above all personal journeys to the prize of accessing middle-class spaces and conventions.

2. Archiving the past and the victim–oppressor dialectic

To understand the symbolic impact of locating the RLMCP in Red Location it is necessary to consider the central issues of reconciliation and reparation in the process of constructing the nation of South Africa. South Africa’s post-apartheid reconciliation process is to this day considered a benchmark. It is not my aim to diminish either the difficulties of achieving transitional justice in South Africa nor the enormity and complexity of this operation and its multiple effects. Rather, I intend to reconstruct and analyse how this process, or rather, this set of processes, led to the emergence of a series of social behaviours and conventions that impacted the context of the RLMCP. Indeed, widespread communications from the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC), the possibility of following live updates from the trials and the international interest in the process – essentially whole event of the TRC – resulted in

¹³¹ Toastmasters International is an organization working to develop public speaking and leadership skills. It is very active in South African high schools.

¹³² An upper-middle class suburb in the south of the city.

¹³³ Mhlophe interviewed in E. Ellis “New frank look at racism”, *The Herald*, 20/08/2016.

the widespread dissemination of the TRC's foundational values, including in local contexts.

Plans for the institution of the TRC predated the declaration of the Constitution of the Republic in 1996 and were included in the Promotion of National Unity and Reconciliation Act in 1995. According to this document, the TRC would be assigned three fundamental functions: recording crimes committed from 1960 up until the date of the Constitution; establishing the truth by offering amnesty to perpetrators of crimes in exchange for their testimony; and making recommendations for compensating the victims of apartheid. Bevernage underlines how the Commission, whose organisers initially advocated for amnesia and amnesty, were asked to hold the past at arm's length, guarantee a fresh start and differentiate the present from all prior regimes (Bevernage 2012). Portinaro, however, stresses how such commissions often end up acquiring an almost constitutional power (Portinaro 2011). The South African nation presented itself as a symbol of change, in contrast to its dark and illiberal past. Murray and Witz similarly discuss a "narrative of becoming", in which the new South Africa is presented as the culmination of emancipation (Murray and Witz 2014).

In the foreword to the final report on the TRC's work, President of the Commission Archbishop Desmond Tutu wrote, "the past, it has been said, is another country. The way its stories are told and the way they are heard change as the years go by. The spotlight gyrates, exposing old lies and illuminating new truth. As a fuller picture emerges, a new piece of the puzzle of our past settles into place" (TRC 1998: 7). The reconstruction of historical truth was considered a sufficient condition for archiving the past, but the act of archiving can refer to both recording something and setting it aside (Bevernage analyses this ambivalence through referencing Derrida).¹³⁴ The report's foreword urged all South African citizens to close this chapter of their past for the good of the whole nation. It was a plea for change in both the public and private spheres, and implicitly prescribed certain behaviours: "My appeal is ultimately directed to us all, black and white together, to close the chapter on our past and to strive together for this beautiful and blessed land as the rainbow

¹³⁴ For Derrida, who saw in the word "archive" both commencement and the commandment, where order is given (from the Greek root *arkhé*), "La pulsion d'archive, c'est une pulsion irrésistible pour interpréter les traces, pour leur donner du sens et pour préférer telle trace à telle autre. Donc préférer oublier, ce n'est pas seulement préférer garder. L'archive [...] ce n'est pas une question de passé, c'est une question d'avenir" (Derrida 2014 : 129).

people of God. The Commission has done its share to promote national unity and reconciliation. Their achievement is up to each one of us” (TRC 1998: 23). The present was seen as the inverse, not the continuation, of the past.

Bevernage makes another observation about the TRC: in order to map out the crimes of apartheid, the Commission carved out a new national timeline in which events such as the Sharpeville Massacre¹³⁵ and the Soweto Uprising became for the first time precise points around which history was reconstructed. In Tutu’s words, “the report that follows tries to provide a window on this incredible resource, offering a road map to those who wish to travel into our past” (TRC 1998: 2). It was a historical reconstruction that primarily addressed victims or “survivors”, despite the Commission’s efforts to identify the motivations and chains of command behind the crimes of apartheid. The introduction to the Commission’s report also clearly sets out how, since there were no clear victors and defeated in South Africa but instead a negotiated transition, reconciliation was the only way forward, lest the country find itself in the grips of civil war (TRC 1998: 21).

The RLMCP project adopted the principal precepts of the TRC: on the one hand, archiving the past in the museum would lead to a future to contrast with the dark period that had come before, and the library and art gallery would open the door to emancipation and education, and so to liberty and equality. On the other hand, while the project was conceived of as a form of reparation for the victims of apartheid, thus maintaining the victim-oppressor dialectic, it also aimed to involve the entire population of South Africa in the collective catharsis of signing a new social contract that prescribed a commitment to development.

3. Hierarchies and multifaceted roles: the organisers

The RLMCP was a multisector project involving diverse stakeholders. The project’s master plan and early documents do not list all the groups and individuals who over the years would collaborate in the construction and operations of the RLMCP: some were added at a later stage, others became more prominent over time, and others still acted as protagonists and co-protagonists only in specific phases of the project. Through analysing the master plan alongside interviews with the project organisers,

¹³⁵ In 1960, the Sharpeville police force opened fire on Pan African Congress (PAC) demonstrators, killing 69 people.

it is possible to map out a hierarchy and division of roles within the RLMCP's operations. This structure, which only partially corresponded to the project's organisational chart, clearly transpired as an instrument of governance when negligence was exposed, when protests broke out or when it was difficult to identify who was responsible for things going wrong (such as, for example, when the staff was criticised for the content of exhibitions, or when there were attempts to reconstruct events that had led to the closure of the museum in 2013). The RLMCP was steered by an extremely small group of individuals who acted as a sort of control room throughout the course of the project. Everyone in Port Elizabeth could easily identify these figures, though they were not frequently talked about as attributing such a large-scale project to such a small organising group would be incompatible with the widely shared idea that decisions about important projects should not be made by a privileged few. The initial idea for the project did not even come from its official organisers, but from Malgas, a national hero who had sacrificed himself for the country and whose résumé is almost unanimously considered proof of his utter dedication to the public good.

The chief organiser of the RLMCP was without a doubt Rory Riordan, spearhead of transition, human rights activist and Municipal director of finance. Through his many roles with the Municipality, he made a significant contribution to bringing the situation in Red Location into public debate, presenting it as greatly problematic and in urgent need of attention. In short, Riordan can be described as a "policy entrepreneur" (Neveu 2015). His consulting firm was officially charged with managing the project's finances and he is today in fact predominantly responsible for keeping the project running. Backed by a wide network of ex-activists, businesspeople, architects, politicians, academics and artists, Riordan can be considered the primary representative of the project. His diary contains the contact details for all the project stakeholders, even though his interventions on the ground were moderate and usually limited to accompanying politicians on visits. His ability to switch between different roles with successive Municipal administrations – under ex-Mayor Danny Jordaan, for example, Riordan resumed the post he had held during transition as Municipal director of finances, after a ten-year hiatus from politics – made him a reliable, omnipresent even if sometimes backstage, point of reference. His

prestige derives from having been present through all key moments of the city's political transition.

Jo Noero, the architect who designed the entire cultural centre, also figures prominently among the organisers. It is to him that the project owes its international fame and emphasis on innovation and experimentation. Noero made no attempt to disguise his ANC sympathies, yet was able to draw upon a wide network of South African contacts and cosmopolitan admirers, which often brought him to work in the United States.

The project's "control room" occasionally admitted new and influential participants. Successive mayors of Nelson Mandela Bay supported the project, allowing it to be carried out and making official visits to the site. The project has always needed the support of public bodies in order to advance. The project master plan saw almost no changes because of external pressures. Paradoxically, the most significant changes – for instance to the project's timeline – were provoked by the actions of the residents.

4. Institutional roles and political positions: the supporters

The project's most recent business plan was published in 2011 and included a recommendation for the successful implementation of the RLMCP that reads:

Working in Red Location, New Brighton, is working in history – you are working where there are many stories to tell that will captivate a visitor and thus provide wonderful opportunities to enrich buildings and programme, but at the same time there is a history to commemorate in an appropriate way. Politicians have to be involved – community commiserated with – and the right decisions finally made (Dojon Financial Services 2011a: 2).

The general recommendations seemed to be that the project could not overlook the involvement of local politicians, should commemorate history "appropriately" and establish good relations with local residents.

Given that the RLMCP was conceived as a project to be organised by public bodies and designed by city councillors, Riordan initially rallied his colleagues, from City Council to local councillors. On the Municipal level, the project was discussed and recognised by the City Council as a priority. On the local level, however, the project

was presented through the channels of local ANC offices. In several townships in Port Elizabeth, including New Brighton and across the broader Ibhayi area, ANC candidates continued to win between 56% and 80% of the vote,¹³⁶ even though the party experienced a sharp fall in votes more broadly between 2011 and 2016, leading to the election of a mayor from the Democratic Alliance (DA) in the Municipal elections of 2016. As the ANC was still extremely present in local government, it is unsurprising that the local ANC office was established as the place for debating a state-sponsored project.

Over the years, the roles set out by the project organisers have increasingly mirrored the roles that the ANC assigned various social groups, especially during post-apartheid. Fluid relationships between different groups were also encouraged by the fact that the aims of the RLMCP project have never been precisely defined; it has always been a multidimensional project, intervening simultaneously in the sectors of culture, tourism, education, housing, politics, etc. Consequently, depending on how it was interpreted, different groups have been or have felt involved and have tried to influence decisions about the project.

For many of my interviewees, the museum was the most significant and central feature of the RLMCP, the heart of the project. In his explanation of the museum's decision-making processes (which had to go through both the Assembly of Councillors and the Mayoral Committee), a member of staff within the Directorate for Sport, Recreation, Arts and Culture, pointed out, "for special projects, politically inclined projects, you have to go through that way" (interview 20/11/2015). Another staff member explained, "it's the politicians that thought about it [the museum], they didn't want history to disappear, they wanted a place to keep our history, they thought that history must be recorded and known" (interview 21/04/2015). When I asked the councillor representing a ward neighbouring the RLMCP to describe what was happening in Red Location, the councillor started by saying "the museum is a political structure with the history of the struggle" (interview 24/11/2015). A member of the museum's staff stated: "the Municipality sees us like a department; the Executive Director is a politician. There's a top-down approach and we report to the Council

¹³⁶ In Ward 15, the ward of the RLMCP, the ANC candidate won with 56% of votes, while in 2011 the previous candidate had won 88% of votes. The situation in Ward 15, however, is unique, as in 2016 part of the ward was merged with Ward 16, and there were therefore some shifts in voting patterns. Data: IEC (2016) *Municipal Election Results*.

instead of a board of directors” (interview 12/03/2015). The museum was effectively the area of the project on which local politics had the greatest influence. Political representatives for the wards of and surrounding the museum, alongside several Municipal councillors, thus became acquired a great degree of influence on the project. Successive Port Elizabeth mayors, several national politicians and external consultants for different Municipal agencies were also variously consulted or actively participated in the project. Several staff members discussed moments when ANC politicians directly and explicitly intervened in the museum, most obviously when a mausoleum for the remains of Mbeki and Mhlaba was built within the museum. The opening of the cultural centre was delayed and ANC factional battles behind the building of the mausoleum made headlines, discrediting the institution before it even opened. In other cases, prominent figures demanded that an exhibition on the Langa massacre¹³⁷ be renamed from “You are my witness” to “Langa Massacre”, a title that was decidedly more dramatic but that made fewer demands of the present for reconciliation.

Because of its symbolic legacy, New Brighton, Port Elizabeth, is often chosen as a destination on tours of provincial and national politicians, as well as being a reference point for local offices. For example, in 2015, mayoral candidate Danny Jordaan received his investiture in the Nangoza Jebe Hall, in New Brighton, and in 2014, President Zuma himself chose to communicate the results of his Siyahloa Presidential Monitoring Visit to Port Elizabeth to the community of New Brighton. Lindiwe Sisulu, Minister of Human Settlements and Deputy Minister of Defence and Military Veterans, also visited New Brighton and Red Location on multiple occasions, promising to take measures to resolve the problem of the decrepit social housing units. During his visit in July 2016, Sisulu discussed these issues with New Brighton veterans. Local politicians and national deputies or members of government therefore often encounter each other in New Brighton, and rank-and-file party members are able to confront political leaders. The role that the RLMCP entrusted to politicians, however, varied depending on whether they were representing constituents on a ward, municipal, provincial or national level.

¹³⁷ In 1985, in Langa, Uitenhage, police killed 20 people on the twenty-fifth anniversary of the Sharpeville massacre.

National and provincial politicians were encouraged to support the museum's activities by making funds available in the relevant budgets. The museum organisers continued to arrange meetings with ministers, in which they would emphasise the history of the location, its centrality in anti-apartheid struggle, and its contribution to the cultural and artistic life of the nation in order to highlight the many opportunities it offered for tourism and economic development. The uniqueness of this sort of museum was emphasised to draw special attention on a national level; several ministers were invited to visit the cultural centre.

The Executive Mayor and municipal councillors had different responsibilities: their task was not so much to direct the project, but to ensure its sustainability through approving funding allocations and fostering unanimous agreement as to the urgency of building the cultural centre, and therefore of prioritising the RLMCP over other comparable projects. Councillors had to successfully explain to communities that the project would not benefit only a few groups of inhabitants but would encourage development across the entire city. On a local level, the Councillor of Ward 15 (in which the RLMCP was located) had the task of conveying this message in such a way that it would be understood by local residents.

As the project entered its delivery phase, the then ward councillor was fully committed to the idea of the RLMCP as the driving force of development in the location. He appeared in videos presenting the museum and was often recorded alongside the figures of Riordan and Noero.¹³⁸ His job as a Black councillor who was originally from the area was to confirm previous statements about the location's singularity and to insist on the concept of "transformation", a word that in contemporary South Africa carries the precise socio-political connotation of sort of development informed by constitutional values and capable of triggering socioeconomic change. The ex-councillor concluded an interview with me saying, "in ten years, New Brighton will be completely changed: X. wants to build a mall in Red Location, there is an old building which will be converted in youth developmental centre, the roads will be upgraded and there will be a pool for swimming" (interview 21/04/2015). Because of his central role in promoting the RLMCP, this councillor came to be strongly associated with the project organisers and so was targeted by the protests of successive housing

¹³⁸ See for example the documentary, "Red Location: repairing an urban fabric" (2010), produced by The Architectural Review.

committees in Red Location. In 2009, for example, protest leaders applied the so-called “bucket system” and emptied buckets of human faeces in front of his office.

The councillor who succeeded him, a year after the closing of the museum, found himself operating in a climate of great tension. He adopted a different position, formally presenting himself as a facilitator who would make the construction works run smoothly (the first time that I interviewed him, he declared, “the community [of Red Location] is arrogant” (interview 21/04/2015), firmly placing himself on the side of the Municipality). Informally, however, he maintained an attitude of dialogue and openness towards the members of the RLSC, who he would meet every Wednesday for several months. One of the leaders of the residents’ committee declared in no uncertain terms: “the councillor feels much more secure when he works with us” (interview 3/11/2015). The new councillor’s lack of resolution during the project’s delivery and up until the closure of the museum was certainly seen as a risk by the project organisers, who were more deferential to national and municipal policies and whose judgement of local councillors was much more explicit: “Nowadays councillors spend their life protecting their back!” (interview 17/11/2015). Local councillors were essentially understood as holding a more precarious position: they were seen as susceptible to political blackmail, as the position is often the first step in a political career and ward councillors often go from being unwaged to receiving a very high salary, and their proximity to the community is also thought to make them extremely vulnerable (in South Africa there are frequent episodes of violence against ward councillors, even including murder, property damage, blackmail and threats against family members). It was also this proximity, however, that enabled them to communicate the museum’s benefits in a language that the local community would understand.

5. The minimal state and project coordinators

The museum and other buildings of the cultural centre employed both specialists and general cleaning, maintenance and security staff.¹³⁹ The library and art gallery, which

¹³⁹ In 2009, the staff counted 21 employees: a curator, a secretary, an exhibition curator and curatorial assistant, a receptionist, four exhibition assistants, a marketing manager, a researcher, a logistics driver, three security staff and five cleaning staff.

never formally opened, hired chief curators but very few other employees. Several public officials from the Directorate for Sport, Recreation, Arts and culture, the department overseeing the museum, were also tasked by the project organisers with practically delivering the project on the ground. During interviews, several of these officials implied that there was a pre-established hierarchy that they had to comply with and refer to when defining their roles and responsibilities. For example, one of the officials I interviewed explained the difficulty of putting into effect adequate measures to resolve contentions with the residents as resulting from bureaucracy, stressing how any decision about the museum had to go through the Mayoral Committee. He also noted that meetings and coordination between Municipal departments was a decision that fell to his superiors (interview 04/11/2015). Similarly, when I asked another official if the museum staff had any authority to intervene in the conflict with the residents, he commented, “the safety of the museum staff is under my responsibility: they can filter but they have to inform us. They can advise us but not act on our behalf” (interview 20/11/2015). A third official responded along similar lines: “we are officials, so we are just managers, we haven’t got the political authority to intervene” (interview 04/11/2015). One of the urban planners from the Department of Human Settlement commented on public interventions in the city, saying, “it’s always a combination between pressure and politics” (interview 12/05/2015).

Public officials faced the challenge of negotiating hierarchies, bureaucracy, political priorities and their professional duties. In short, they had to navigate the complexities of the neoliberal minimal state which withdraws, makes itself minimal, delegates social security to a range of organisations (non-governmental organisations, security forces, etc.) while never completely abdicating from governance and control. In this context, public officials became the most visible aspect of the state while paradoxically evidencing its absence since they came to perform coordination roles and were forced to make decisions about complex issues that politicians and institutional representatives chose not to worry about.

The project coordinators on the ground found themselves in a position of liaising between the project organisers, local politicians and residents. Whether acting as directors and deputies of the art gallery and museum, or providing support to departmental executive directors, public officials had a dual role. Officially, they

were asked to strictly abide by their mandate and, to varying degrees, report to the Municipality. Each of them was a project manager of one strand of the project, but their capacity to intervene was radically restricted by irregular funding and staff shortages. Indeed, when the RLMCP closed in 2013 many job vacancies remained unfilled. The managers of the library and the art gallery were only appointed once the buildings had closed. Public officials were often the only ones communicating the Municipality's strategy to local communities.¹⁴⁰ Precisely because of the role they played on the ground, they became negotiators who could set, reset and postpone deadlines. Their weekly visits were expected as fixed appointments, and they differed in the eyes of the residents from those who simply "showed up", those who would boldly cross the museum courtyard even once it had been occupied by the RLSC (obviously with permission), and directors from the city centre who had lost all credibility. One official told me:

The community raises legitimate concerns using municipal assets like leverages. We have the responsibility to protect those municipal assets [...] I try to engage with the community: we negotiated to put the lighting outside [...]. The building has also to comply with health and safety regulations" (interview 08/10/2015).

This official's attempt to restore the lighting outside the art gallery (the lights had all been unscrewed and stolen) involved a long negotiation with committee members, which actually strengthened his relationship with the leaders of the dispute. The residents' awareness of the public officials' extremely restricted ability to influence policy was demonstrated by the fact that they distinguished between the activities of the officials as specialists or experts and the political strategy of local government. Even when tensions were at their peak, public officials were never targeted by physical or verbal attacks. For their part, the officials could openly admit that the residents' demands were legitimate without contravening their official duties.

The fragmentation of the various Municipal departments involved in the project alongside the fact that museum staff worked on the ground in the township gave them a particular autonomy. A museum employee claimed to have organised

¹⁴⁰ They were not exactly development 'brokers', to use de Sardan's (1995) phrase, since they were often far from 'local' and did not always have the power to control the redistribution of resources. Yet they shared with de Sardan's development brokers a certain capacity for appropriating the project's terms and translating them into a language that was more appropriate for the residents.

debates as a form of “resistance” to political pressure,¹⁴¹ and when doubts were expressed about the museum’s purpose, it was primarily its employees who tried to find a response to satisfy the residents, even though there were disagreements about the outcomes of this process. One employee, Ralo, wrote an article for the local newspaper, *The Herald*, intitled “Museum unsure of function”,¹⁴² in which he warned local policymakers and the wider public that the museum should maintain neutrality in order to serve the higher purpose of preserving history and memory, rather than making compromises to satisfy local needs, lest it transform from a cultural institution into an instrument of political propaganda.

Several employees of the cultural centre made public statements about their role and responsibilities: they participated in debates, wrote articles and gave interviews. In this way, they brought their own role into question, criticised the hierarchy they were a part of and exhorted local politicians and the mayor to take responsibility. The closure of the museum further deepened the divide between those who managed the project and those who delivered it on the ground. Above all, the museum staff resented being left in the dark when it came to decisions about housing policies. A building manager for the cultural centre, however, offered an interesting perspective: “Who can exercise the power? Until now, we decided not to exercise it, not to use our power! The opening will coincide with the power shifting: we will be the ones signing for the money!” (interview 08/10/2015). The manager was referring to the fact that, if and when activities in the cultural centre recommenced, it would be the curators who would have the authority to decide how to use the allocated funds. Their ability to direct the strategy of the RLMCP would therefore be significantly enhanced.

6. Academics: the endorsers

Several academics, artists and professionals from Red Location, the surrounding area, and also across the city played an important role in promoting the project. Academics were asked to participate in judging panels for the award of contracts, to provide various forms of consulting (such as on the histories that the museum would represent), to speak at conferences, and, as previously outlined, to conduct

¹⁴¹ Interview 12/03/2015.

¹⁴² M. Ralo, ‘Museums unsure of functions’, *The Herald*, 17/03/2012.

evaluations of the museum and impact assessments for the project. In each case, their involvement was implicitly aimed at endorsing the project in terms of quality (of architecture, design, proposed itineraries through the museum, etc.), importance in the world of culture and research, and also in terms of ethics and moral integrity. Often, in fact, the academics chosen for these roles had an activist past in the anti-apartheid movement which was meant to stand in for moral integrity, knowledge of the township and its inhabitants, and an ability to recognise justice. These individuals' agreement to participate in, evaluate and more generally to associate their names with the project was used by the organisers to proclaim its significance, urgency and the contribution that it would make to the city's development. Often, the names of academics would be cited even if their overall judgement of the project was not actually all that glowing. One of the most renowned individuals called upon to endorse and support the project was the judge Albie Sachs, who, as previously mentioned, was also asked to draft a mid-term report on the project.

The beginning of the business plan for the third phase of the project quotes an email from Sachs to Riordan, an email that was then frequently referenced during fundraising presentations to ministers. In the email, Sachs congratulates the project's originality and concludes by stating "Red Location is emerging as one of the greatest feathers in South African's cap!" (Sachs in Dojon Financial Services 2011b, foreword). In reality, Sachs had not always had such a positive opinion of the cultural centre: in his report on the museum, for example, he had urged the Municipality to resolve the social housing problem and exhorted local government to find the funds to operationally equip the library. It is his general encouragement of the project, however, that is often cited in documents about the museum.

Other activists and academics in the city were involved in the project, both through evaluating initiatives and collaborating in the creation of exhibitions. While the names of academics who approved of or looked favourably on the project were used to advance its reputation, any criticisms were dismissed as idealistic and removed from the everyday reality of life in New Brighton. When, for example, a prominent academic expressed doubts about the content of the museum, she was immediately accused of being a white intellectual who was hypocritically criticising a key aspect of her own profession. Intellectuals approached by the project organisers were mostly specialists in governance, or political commentators with an activist past

who had become academics during post-apartheid. They typically moved in the same social circles as Riordan: middle-class, white, and boasting an international profile. Political thinkers and writers associated with the ANC were also solicited to promote the museum's activities.

In 2008, the museum staff decided to host a series of debates. The proposed topics included several key anti-apartheid themes that were still considered to be relevant, such as the concept of identity in contemporary South Africa, the challenges posed by the consolidation of democracy and the history of Marxism in South Africa. The speakers came from the world of academia: lectures organised in honour of Govan Mbeki were given by the historian Colin Bundy, the ex-vice-chancellor of the University of Witwatersrand, and the writer and academic Mbulelo Mzamane. The historians Andrew Nash, Kwandiwe Kondlo and the political commentator Steven Friedman were invited to speak. The museum also hosted several political figures, such as Trevor Manuel, finance minister from 2006 to 2009 and "Minister in the Presidency" until 2014, and Kader Asmal, ex-minister for education. CANRAD, the Centre for the Advancement of Non-Racialism and Democracy at the NMMU, and *The Herald* newspaper collaborated with the museum to organise the lectures and debates. There were also book launches, such as for Alan Wieder's book on Ruth First and Joe Slovo. The museum's openness to sensitive topics and genuinely critical discussions within the ANC, however, provoked very strong reactions from local politicians who, being unable to prevent the lectures, tried to control them through sending representatives into the audience to intimidate the organisers. A museum employee recalled that several events in particular were targeted, including the book launch for James Ngculu, a figure who was considered divisive for having been part of the faction of the ANC that was opposed to President Mbeki. The decision to invite historian Martin Legassick was also widely criticised as he had been dismissed from the ANC in the 1980s for theoretical differences. The book launch for "The Things that Could Not be Said" by Frank Chikane, a volume about South African social problems that President Mbeki had failed to resolve, was perceived as too biased in favour of the faction opposing the President's. Pallo Jordan's lecture on the importance of the

tripartite alliance¹⁴³ met a similar judgement.¹⁴⁴ But since the museum had to constitute a liberal and democratic space, none of these events were cancelled.

Given its nature as a cultural space, the RLMCP was characterised as a welcoming space for intellectuals, academics and researchers, but it hosted events more than it fostered ideas. As the residents' protests and demonstrations intensified, many people questioned whether the precinct itself had come to reflect inequality, segregation and housing issues, as if the museum truly was a community museum, then it should have been able to accommodate discussions about its own history and legitimacy. In the same period, there were even proposals for an exhibition on the residents' protests. None of these proposals were well-received: the museum employees were committed to completing the activities that were already underway, and Municipal departmental directors involved in the project insisted that the residents protesting against the Museum were only a small minority of the Location's residents, and so that it was counterproductive to pay too much heed to their discontent.

It was also hoped that the involvement of academics and intellectuals would provide grounds for future projections. For example, the part of the business plan about building theatres cited the results from Riordan's and Noero's explorative study of projects comparable to the RLMCP in London and Cape Town. As previously noted, the only study into the project's development potential was completed in 2012 when tensions with the residents were almost at their peak, and in fact served to justify the direction the project had already taken.

7. Key partners, educators and mediators

Local artists were rallied to serve as key partners, educators and mediators. Two groups were in particular were targeted: artists whose work had made the township famous in the sixties and seventies, and those that an appendix of the business plan described as "young artists" or "township artists" (Dojon Financial Services 2012). Artists whose career had peaked in New Brighton in the sixties and seventies were

¹⁴³ The term "Tripartite Alliance" refers to the alliance between the ANC, the Congress of African Trade Unions (COSATU) and the South African Communist Party (SACP). The alliance was forged in 1990 but is today very fragile.

¹⁴⁴ Interview with a member of museum staff, 19/02/2015.

called upon to support the culture centre, even though many of them no longer lived nearby. Support from these artists was thought to imply that the cultural centre could represent the first step to reproducing the artistic atmosphere of the township's creative past.

In 2013, for example, a jazz concert was organised outside the museum and attended by veterans of the location, such as the musician Dudley Tito. The purpose of the concert was to promote one of the museum's most successful exhibitions, "Generations of Jazz", which told the history of jazz musicians who had made New Brighton famous. In 2009 to 2010, the museum also launched a project teaching jazz music to young musicians. Mahola, a poet who grew up in New Brighton and still lives in Zwide, in the Ibhayi area, was asked to hold poetry workshops in local schools. He was an up-and-coming young poet in the 1970s and is considered one of the major representatives of a certain stark realism that was popular at the time.

For many of these artists, the museum was first and foremost a job opportunity. Although this older generation of artists approved of the idea of establishing a cultural centre in the location, few of them truly believed that the project could actually transform Port Elizabeth's cultural sector, given the scarcity of funding, meagre political will and inadequate venues. During the live coverage of the museum's reopening, an enthusiastic presenter interviewed Nkonyeni, a semi-famous actress who had cut her teeth in New Brighton. The presenter's questions touched on the contrast between the challenges of being an artist during apartheid and the opportunities offered by the democratic government. Nkonyeni's responses were extremely cynical:

“Presenter: Let's just talk about the area we are broadcasting from and Port Elizabeth...have you seen major changes within the area and the surrounding areas?

N.: I wouldn't say much changes, no, no I wouldn't say much changes, there are no changes as such in terms of my work, in terms of the industry I'm in, I'm still struggling to survive, as an actress here and now [...].

Presenter: [...] What do you think is standing in the way?

N.: There are no work opportunities, no funding, nobody cares about the art per se, I don't think our province cares much about us, the only thing they care about is for us to come and entertaining them, that's all it is to them”.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴⁵ Nkonyeni (2016), interviewed by SABC News.

Those defined as “young artists” or “township artists”, on the other hand, were seen as the cultural centre’s main beneficiaries. The art gallery would have held temporary exhibitions of “local” works and multiple planned rehearsal rooms and workshop spaces would have hosted various types of artistic performance from across the area. The organisers believed that the RLMCP would offer the artists of Port Elizabeth a unique opportunity for jobs in the culture sector. Local artists were expected to perform two functions: to promote through their art the values of social cohesion, unity and the richness of diversity, and to set an example of the sort of young person that the township should produce – integrated in the city, self-starting, but also embedded in the local community and ready to offer personal support to educational and “empowerment” projects. The handing over of the museum keys to the mayor was arranged to coincide with the establishment of an Art Council, an advisory board within the Department of Sport, Recreation, Arts and Culture, formed from community representatives from various artistic disciplines. The Art Council never passed comment on the controversies surrounding the RLMCP, but upon the news of a possible reopening started to build connections within the township and played an intermediary role between the RLMCP and artists living nearby. The news that the occupation had come to an end was also accompanied by the announcement of some twenty jobs to be created in the culture sector. Specifically, these positions would be in theatres and workshops, but at time of writing they have yet to be filled.

While the project organisers did not seem to see the definition of a “local artist” as particularly problematic, the majority of artists I interviewed or was in contact with, aged between twenty-five and forty, viewed it as a convenient institutional label, made for presenting public projects as inclusive and pleasing funders. Describing a piece of work commissioned by a Municipal project, an artist in their thirties told me, “they use my name twice, written in a different way, to justify their contribution to local art development” (interview 19/11/2015). This same artist also complained of differences in pay: a “township artist” was simply an artist who was paid less with the excuse that they lived in an impoverished district and so would welcome any amount of money.

Refusal of the “township artist” label (a definition that is more often applied to Black South Africans than Coloured artists) was unanimous: it was considered

degrading, segregating and above all unrepresentative of a reality made up of mobility and connections. The response to the RLMCP was a mixture of curiosity and scepticism. One artist observed: “we fail to develop the love for art, we never did audience development. They keep building but they don’t know what to do with what they have built [...] They should, at least, try to build up the audience: they should show two plays per month and see who makes money and who brings money and how. They should give local talents a chance and see how many people they can bring” (interview 24/06/2015). This artist was sceptical about the idea of building a cultural centre that could accommodate thousands of spectators, when one of Port Elizabeth’s primary problems was a lack of audiences – “have they seen people flocking in from Grahamstown?” (*ibid.*), he wondered. Discussing the politics of the project, he added, “the Department of Arts and culture is just very political, in meetings people struggle to define concepts, they don’t know what we are talking about [...] They are just officials that embrace their job, how can they make the city more vibrant?” (*ibid.*).

Relationships between artists and the Municipality were consistently ambivalent throughout the various phases of the project. Public art – such as the commemorative monument for the Rivonia Trial defendants or the assortment of benches furnishing Singaphi Road on the approach to the cultural centre – was included in the project both as a form of aesthetic improvement serving to mark a distinction between townships inside and outside the city centre, and as a sign of a sort of obviously material achievement, being installations that were both free and in public space. The independent projects of individual artists living in the city were another matter: in a democratic South Africa, freedom of expression was protected and encouraged, but there were disagreements about if and how dissenting artistic expression should be supported. An employee of the RLMCP claimed, “the building should be for artists that can educate the community” (08/10/2015), but then specified that art should be disruptive: “the state looks for ‘oneness’ but art must question and make uncomfortable’ (*ibid.*). On the 21st June, three artists (Banele Njadayi, Bamanye Lethu Ngxale and Zinziswa Mavuso) launched an exhibition entitled “Let the truth be told: a visual story of why the Red Location Museum was closed down by the Red Location Community”. The exhibition was funded by the Municipal development agency (NBDA) and held in the Opera House, a Municipal venue in the city centre, far away from the RLMCP. On the Red Location Precinct’s

Facebook page, the museum staff shared a post about the exhibition, and lamented the fact that they had not been invited.

8. Mediums and witness, or manual labourers...

In the Competition Brief for the design and construction of the RLMCP, Faku described the project as “a catharsis for many with pent-up anger and frustration birthed by the past. Simultaneously the new complex could create a window of insight into the plight of the inhabitants of these areas for those who did not join in the struggle.” (Faku in Albrecht Heroldt Architects 1998, 10). The word catharsis refers to both purification and release from a state of conflict or anxiety through the evocation of the causes of a subject’s pain. In psychoanalysis, it involves such events being consciously relived on a rational and emotional level.

Catharsis implies evoking the past in the present; it was a central process in post-apartheid reconciliation. It is often associated with the work of the TRC and was seen as a necessary step towards the possibility of a shared future. Evocation and catharsis were also two central elements of the RLMCP. As already noted, the idea for the RLM was attributed to Singqokwana Ernest Malgas, an activist with a complex past who had been imprisoned for fourteen years on Robben Island, tortured on multiple occasions and submitted to various kinds of police violence – his house had been burnt down and one of his children killed. Malgas, a wheelchair user since a heart attack that was probably caused by years of torture and detention, appeared to give testimony before the TRC on the third day of the trials. His speech was introduced by Boraine, a member of the commission, who concluded saying, “your situation is quite different from a whole lot of other people. You are a victim of torture, of harassment, of imprisonment, and we want you to tell us your story, but in order to assist you”.¹⁴⁶ When Malgas gave evidence of the torture he had been suffered, Archbishop Desmond Tutu, President of the Commission, lowered his head and started to weep. This has remained one of the strongest images of the TRC – even the President of the Commission was, under the eyes of South African citizens and national television, personally involved in the process of catharsis. Malgas was simultaneously both a

¹⁴⁶ TRC, *Human Rights Violations, Submissions – questions and answers*, 17/04/1996. Accessible at: www.justice.gov.za.

witness and a victim. His physical suffering was an indisputable sign of the evil of the apartheid regime. He was, in other words, an archetypal *porteur de memoire*.

The TRC was part of a trend that developed in second half of the 20th century to centre victims in the reconstruction of history, to ensure that the “witness [is] increasingly identified as a victim” (Traverso 2006: 14). This assumption of equivalence between witnesses and victims has several important consequences. Prizing witnesses’ testimonies as the pinnacle of historical truth or sending into oblivion things that would sooner be forgotten not only obviously shapes the way history is narrated, but in the case of Red Location it also produced the idea of a sort of idealised, exemplary resident. Red Location residents were seen as victims and therefore as witnesses whose testimonies were crucial for all of South Africa to progress; the act of remembering and re-evoking the past was thus considered a civic duty. The project also viewed the residents as mediums, capable of acting as conduits between the township and the wider world and mediating between the suffering of the past and hopes for the future. The residents who were most involved with the RLMCP reappropriated this representation through prompting or alluding to catharsis each time they found themselves having to describe the location or their place in it to outsiders.

After several weeks of fieldwork, I met with several representatives from the women’s cooperative that runs the Red Location Lodge, a hostel that is part of the culture centre and hosts visitors staying overnight in New Brighton. I was mostly interested in understanding how the idea for the hostel had come about, how the cooperative was formed and most of all who had occupied the old beer hall before it was converted into the hostel. I was also looking for responses to the RLSC’s criticisms of the cooperative for continuing to offer accommodation while the protests were underway and all other services had been suspended. Although I had clearly introduced myself as a researcher, when I arrived I was greeted in much the same way as were groups of students or international tourists. Answers to my questions about the present made constant reference to the women’s activist past in in the ANC Women League or Amabutho.¹⁴⁷ The fact that my visit coincided with the anniversary of the Soweto Uprising made this type of retrospective narrative especially powerful.

¹⁴⁷ Amabutho was formed mostly of young UDF supporters in the cities in the Eastern Cape, who devoted themselves to the paramilitary organization. In the 1980s, they undertook true urban guerilla

During our meeting one of the representatives of the cooperative started to recall the moment when she had been imprisoned and tortured for burning down the beer hall with the Amabutho I knew that tourist and school visits typically ended with Mama A.'s tragic testimony, but I did not expect to hear it during the interview. As I was neither recording nor transcribing the truly horrific, harrowing account, one of the other women interrupted Mama A.'s tearful narration to demand why I was not documenting such an important testimony.

Their proximity to the cultural centre and the fact that their activities were a product of the RLMCP project¹⁴⁸ meant that these women reproduced the same types of narratives of emancipation that the project relied on. Living in Red Location is strongly associated with past and present membership of the ANC Women's League, and the status of these women as activists and eyewitnesses meant that they had been able to gain employment through activities connected to the cultural centre. Through narrating themselves as witnesses – and as the narrator's role comes to constitute identity and citizenship – the women managing the hostel acted as mediums, emotionally re-evoking the suffering and gains of anti-apartheid struggle for their audiences.

Residents who were not included in this sort of narrative (and who were neither local artists, students or art enthusiasts), such as younger residents who had been children during the last years of apartheid or were born after it formally ended, were put in a broader category. They were seen as the inheritors of oppression and segregation – or more simply, the urban poor and unemployed. People in this category were considered to be the local beneficiaries of the RLMCP's vaguely defined economic returns. The residents' repeated demands that the RLMCP provide job opportunities for local people meant that the inhabitants of Red Location were treated as a pool of labour power. Their role in development was essentially limited to providing manual labour: officials insisted that the residents' low levels of education posed an insurmountable barrier to employing them within the project as anything except

warfare, in addition to maintaining discipline in the townships during the state of emergency and boycotts of white businesses.

¹⁴⁸ The president of the cooperative recounted: "We happened to be the people that were involved in the struggle and we were unemployed, we would go to councillor office and we would ask about strategies on how to survive after freedom. We were all women and the councillor asked us what we wanted to do. He advised us that if we made a group we could find a job easily as we could present ourselves as an organization" (interview 16/06/2015).

cleaners or unspecialised construction workers. The officials argued that the residents could not even be employed as museum attendants because public sector projects had to abide by strict procurement policies, using only a restricted list of approved suppliers.¹⁴⁹ The project, in short, could help to balance the job market but not address the inhabitants' lack of training.

9. The dissidents

In the early phases of the RLMCP, Red Location residents were represented as the legitimate beneficiaries of the development project. As the protests escalated and intensified, however, they were portrayed in an increasingly negative light. According to those who did not agree with the protests, the residents were being selfish, acting in their own interests rather than in the interests of the city, and presumptuous for expecting development from above. They were judged short-sighted and incapable of moving past skin-colour, vilified for renouncing their children's futures, being stuck in a divided and segregated world and being ignorant of their own good fortune, as other townships had not received the same level of investment.¹⁵⁰

This change of attitude can be attributed to the ultimatum imposed by neoliberalism: if you did not support the museum you were against it, and if you were against it you were against development and thus jeopardising everyone's wellbeing. Massimo Cuono and Raffaella Sau have argued that "state benevolence is a pretext for the legitimisation of power that is far from being overcome by the politics of liberal democracy" (2014: 31). The confidence with which the organisers of the RLMCP conflated the project with the common good aligns them with a sort of neoliberal paternalism that justifies itself through "a very accentuated version of 'economic naturalism' and [...] strong 'moral polarisation'" (Cuono and Sau 2014: 40). In condemning the residents' actions, the organisers aimed to depoliticise the project through "distancing decisions made in the name of economic necessity or moral imperative from the sphere of politics and debate" (Cuono and Sau 2014: 40). Through practices and discourse referring to anti-apartheid struggles, through

¹⁴⁹ Interview 21/03/2015.

¹⁵⁰ These judgements were expressed during several interviews with politicians, particularly on 18/05/2015, 13/03/2015 and 21/04/2015. They were also echoed in informal contexts, for example during dinners in other parts of the city, especially the suburbs, when the conversation turned to the RLMCP.

rejecting the oppressed-oppressor dynamic, and through refusing to accept responsibility for the project's hiatus, the residents' actions shook the project's legitimacy to the core.

The residents' protests made comparisons between their struggle and the struggles of anti-apartheid. As was happening with service delivery protests across the whole country, the residents condemned the endurance of apartheid governance practices and still segregated cities. In other words, they condemned the continuation of the past in the present, the presence of a "past-not-passed". Protests over housing had remained unresolved for over twenty years, since before the formal end of apartheid, and the lack of jobs and limited social mobility were clearly related to forms of oppression that were reproduced through the mechanisms of segregation.

The protests were a way of declaring that the inequality and exclusion of apartheid and colonialism did not belong to the past. Enzo Traverso has written that "memory is always assembled in the present" (2006: 15), in the sense that it is heavily dependent on context and the needs of those remembering. Bevernage argues, similarly, that "memory of offense ignores the 'hierarchies of time,' refuses to let the atrocious past go, and keeps the irrevocable irrevocable in all its frightening closeness" (Bevernage 2011: 20). Bergson maintains that "in a word, our present falls into the past when it no longer has current relevance. This holds true for individuals and nations alike: an event belongs to the past and enters history when it no longer has any direct relevance to our current politics and can be forgotten without great impact to the concerns of the present. As long as its effects are felt, it forms part of national life and remains present" (Bergson 2011: 30). The protests did not only condemn the endurance of the past in the present, but they also questioned the uniformity with which time – or more precisely, historical change and becoming – was being represented. They brought to light multiple different temporal frameworks that cannot be reduced to a single interpretation.

In opposing the ANC government – the government of the party that had declared itself the primary champion of their demands – the residents proposed a dialectic of oppressed–oppressor that moved away from the clear-cut binaries of post-apartheid. Manifesting their discontent exposed the contradictions of a nation built on pacification and simplification. The desires to keep past, present and future apart and to reduce the past to a unilateral mythology of the ANC influenced the public

representation of history through nullifying and erasing hundreds of personal histories and trajectories. In accordance with retributive justice, a model in which the punishment imposed is supposed to correspond to the harm provoked (Portinaro 2011), the equivalence made between victim and witness encouraged narratives which prioritised violation of rights and episodes of violence. On the one hand, such accounts are imbued with a cathartic value and can perform a judicial purpose in distributing responsibility across multiple levels of the chain of command. On the other hand, however, the historical narrative of apartheid as a period characterised by perpetual horror legitimises the imposition of censorship and taboos.

Muxel maintains that memory plays a crucial role in identity construction, as every subject must reappropriate and come to terms with their own past in order to construct their identity (2000). In denying the multiplicity of the past and its possible afterlives, the official history advanced during the democratic transition constructed and commemorated certain histories while making it extremely difficult for some people to make peace with their past and so understand their place in the present.¹⁵¹ A separate discourse applies to those who were not labelled victims but placed in the racial category of “oppressors”. Fairly standard upper-middle class lives became almost “unspeakable” in public discourse, as the mere allusion to past comfort would immediately evoke inequality and social injustice: their comfort had only been possible at the expense of other citizens. Similarly, narratives about the psychological discomfort of being white in South Africa or about ignorance of the level of exploitation that parts of the population endured and the intrinsic injustice of apartheid, are considered neither welcome nor interesting. Ian Ewok Robinson, a rapper from Durban, in his performances “Yobo” and “I and I” reflects on the condition of being white in contemporary South Africa, describing himself as “an angry man who has been told that he has no reason to be angry” (Robinson 2015), with no public outlet for expressing his anger or frustration given his privileged position. He asks himself, “why do I have to stay on this side of history? Why can I not move to the right side of history?” (Robinson 2016). His performances have been heavily criticised

¹⁵¹ For example, while MK militants are commemorated and awarded special rights as veterans, the Amabutho faced many more difficulties in being recognized as a group who had served the cause of anti-apartheid struggle and suffered the various consequences of this. In the same way, it is only in the last ten years that gender historians have uncovered women’s histories in apartheid, and not only the stories of anti-apartheid heroines, but also more domestic and everyday histories.

almost exclusively by white journalists and critics, as if the discourse on whiteness exclusively concerns the white minority.

Thirdly, the residents insisted that it was the institutional representatives who were responsible for the suspension of the project, and that the duration of the occupation depended on how long the Municipality would take to meet their demands. In this way, they deconstructed both the project's values and the politicians' and organisers' attempts at depoliticisation. In halting the project the residents declared that their acquiescence was neither unconditional nor to be taken for granted, just as it should not have been taken for granted that the project represented the common good. In this way, the protestors brought the project back into the realm of politics: they insisted that it was the project managers who should have guaranteed social cohesion and found a resolution, as they had been publicly elected to make decisions about wealth distribution and welfare. Discussing the Municipality and politicians, committee members often repeated, "they have to listen to us, 'cause we voted for them" (interviews 02/11/2015 and 03/11/2015).

Any sanctuary relies on a group of individuals who understand it as such. In the case of the RLMCP, there was something of a short circuit between the organisers and the residents: a specific type of architecture and declarations of good intentions were not in and of themselves enough to inspire admiration and a sense of "civic duty" in the local community. Various waves of protesters in Red Location had made multiple suggestions: improving and implementing housing policies, creating jobs, opening the cultural centre up to local associations, establishing support and training schemes for young people... When their requests were not taken seriously, the residents lost all faith in the rhetoric of national unity and social cohesion and jumped at the chance to bring the project aims back into question.

The residents' actions were simultaneously an act of appropriation (reclaiming ownership of the project), and of rejecting the reduction of belonging as merely consenting to be involved in the project. In the same way, the occupation of the museum and everything that ensued made the residents' existence and belonging in the nation more visible. The occupation could therefore be described as an alternative strategy for inclusion.

5. Stratified identities and moral orders

In institutional documents, newspaper articles and public discourse, the inhabitants of Red Location are described as a “community”. “The community” was understood to be the subject of the residents’ protests and demands, the victims of disadvantage and poverty, and the beneficiaries of development projects. In common parlance the word “community” is generally used exclusively to refer to inhabitants of the townships; upper-middle inhabitants of the suburbs, for instance, do not tend to be described as a “community. When used by public bodies, the term seems to indicate a particular characteristic or insufficiency of those who live in the locations, something which means they cannot be described as “citizens”. The word “community” is used to refer to a homogenous group of people, bound together by virtue of living in the same marginal space and who are thought to identify with the same set of interests, values or lifestyles. When it comes to the definition of community, Wacquant invites us to “remain agnostic as to the particular social and spatial configuration assumed by the resulting district of dispossession. In particular, we cannot presume that the emerging social entity is a ‘community’ (implying at minimum a shared surround and identity, horizontal social bonds and common interests), even a community of fate, given the diversity of social trajectories that lead into and out of such areas” (Wacquant 2016: 1078).

While the project organisers represented the inhabitants of Red Location as individuals who could be grouped together by their shared basic survival needs, interviews I conducted with residents returned the image of an extremely complex form of citizenship characterised by stratified identities, shifting affinities and multiple moral orders. A cross-section of interviews and conversations with Red Location residents reveals three frequent articulations of identity: narrating oneself as a township resident, as amaXhosa, and more ambiguously as a citizen in relation with public bodies and institutions. These three different narratives correspond to three different articulations of belonging and behavioural codes.

Red Location was the site not only of a sort of “cognitive polyphasia” – the coexistence of multiple knowledge systems and social representations of the self and

world¹⁵² – but also of the coexistence of multiple modes of citizenship, arising from colonial segregation and further complicated by a range of social formulations that have developed throughout South African history.

1. Township Life: moral dichotomies and dangerous reputations

Although the residents sometimes disagreed about how the cultural centre could be used, there was general agreement that the RLMCP should create steady employment for the township's young people. Many people believed that unemployed youth were at risk of being forced out of the location, or of falling into a vicious circle of poverty, truancy, substance abuse and street gangs, becoming a danger to themselves and others.¹⁵³ This concern contributed to pressure on the Municipality to get the library up and running.¹⁵⁴ The cultural centre was not only seen as a hopeful source of employment, but residents also suggested that the RLMCP could offer training courses for employment skills that would empower people to integrate into the workforce.¹⁵⁵ Young people needed jobs, but they also needed to be kept busy and out of harm's way.

Young people were the first to pay the price for the township's reputation as a dangerous, sordid place. The insistence that the project would offer deliverance from the dangers that the township posed reflects a moral dichotomy between good and evil, criminality and virtue. This dichotomy developed as a form of protection against the perceived danger posed by the environment of the township. My interviewees widely believed that young people suffered the consequences of the township's negative influence, expressing fears that young people were both in danger and dangerous.¹⁵⁶ This was also expressed during a workshop organised in 2012 by

¹⁵² On the concept of cognitive polyphasia, see Moscovici (1961), also Swartz's discussion of Langa (Swartz 2009).

¹⁵³ This concern, expressed here in my own words, was frequently repeated by a wide range of individuals, both teenagers and adults.

¹⁵⁴ This was expressed by various individuals in informal conversations and was also one of the RLSC's demands. Interviews 03/11/2015 and 02/11/2015.

¹⁵⁵ This was expressed in interviews both with residents and museum employees. Interviews 11/05/2015, 12/03/2015 and 19/02/2015.

¹⁵⁶ This fear of the unpredictability of youth has a long history in New Brighton. Authors such as Nieftagodien (2011) and Bank (2011) have described ambivalent attitudes towards younger generations, highlighting simultaneous concerns for their safety and futures and fears about what could happen if they got angry. In the 1970s-80s, student movements allied with the Amabutho, and activists groups, but also with tsosi ("criminals"), giving rise to some of the most intense moments of the anti-apartheid struggle, rioting in the township in defiance of the guidance of older generations.

project organisers to understand the community's perceptions of the RLMCP, in which several "local artists", social workers and also regular citizens were invited to express their views on the project. Alongside opinions more explicitly about how the buildings were operating, the workshop report includes statements such as "the problem is the youth, they take drug too much and do robbery kill the people when they do drugs [...], if we can get jobs I think this thing will stop" (Brennan and Riordan, 2012).

According to Buur, in New Brighton "in many and sometimes surprising ways, crime and/or the criminal has come to stand in not only for increases in violent deaths, rapes and robberies, but also for teenage pregnancies, unemployment, the breakdown of social cohesion [...], the lack of development funds and investments, and so forth. The concept is therefore profoundly polyvalent – able to give a name to local grievances and problems of order and disorder [...]" (Buur 2008). The township was perceived as a violent, dangerous and hostile environment in which "life must be lived in terms of a presumption of malice" (Ashforth 2005: 313), under the assumption that anyone with any reason to do harm, will do harm. Proximity and distance, empathy and disinterest, intimacy and otherness are all part of everyday life in the location. A regular at the kung fu gym confided in me, "it's about connecting and it becomes like a daily task: wherever you go you are like an active computer that processes information. You become a shield to your brothers who are fighting to build a better community" (interview 11/06/2015). Constant vigilance became a genuine *habitus*, a repetitive, collective behaviour shared by multiple social groups (doublechecking for pickpockets when you get out the keys for your house or car, parking in well-lit or visible areas, not walking alone in dark or remote places, etc.). Although the rhetoric of ubuntu¹⁵⁷ was often referenced by the inhabitants of the township to speak about solidarity or mutual aid within communities, a cautious reserve marked relations between neighbours, who would, for example, try to hide their possessions inside their houses and stay alert to what was happening on the street.

When the struggles of the anti-apartheid movement are spoken about in Port Elizabeth's townships, there is often reference to how strictly the "comrades" enforced month-long boycotts, inflicting severe punishments on those found to have purchased products from white shopkeepers.

¹⁵⁷ For a definition of ubuntu see chapter 6.2.

Red Location residents carefully watched the youth unemployment rate (48% for men and 57% for women between 15 and 24 years old).¹⁵⁸ There was a pervasive fear that young people would turn into dangerous criminals. Despite the fact that over a third of New Brighton inhabitants were unemployed and that the townships suffered the consequences of precarity particularly acutely, in New Brighton work continued to be synonymous with moral integrity. Swartz describes how also in Langa employment was connected with good behaviour, dignity, setting an example for others and not needing to resort to illegal activities to support oneself (Swartz 2009). Urban identity in South Africa is constructed on a correlation between being a legal worker and a legal inhabitant – for many years, having a job (or being the dependent of someone with a job) was a necessary condition for residing in the city. Gainful employment is still today considered necessary to move away from reprobation; while a job does not guarantee social mobility in and of itself, employed people are considered differently within the community.

The residents' accounts reveal a difference between the nature of intergenerational relations before and after the 1980s, generating further divisions between the morality of past and present. Older people recall negative changes in behaviour, while younger people focus on the revolutionary impact of youth clubs. An elderly poet living in Zwide recounted, "things have changed during the unrest. People wanted to be recognized as been activists. In those days, there has been a breaking of the moral: youngsters were beating elders" (interview 13/05/2015). Describing the same events, an activist narrated, "the activists were the big bosses of the township, they were respected by the gangsters. During the Consumer boycott gangsters were still allowed to operate in town. The elders were more afraid, they didn't want to fight as the youth" (interview 28/05/2015). A woman from Red Location described her concerns for the youth of today: "it's just that we are a forgiving nation, otherwise...some of the youth is very angry about what happened to their parents. I forgave, but I'm not right. I'm worried for what is happening now" (interview 16/06/2015). The spectre of violent youth uprisings haunts South African politics.

¹⁵⁸ World Bank data, 2014.

Recent student protests against rising university fees¹⁵⁹ and for free universal education have been quickly quashed lest they become anti-establishment revolts.

At the same time, demonstrations of discontented youth were also understood as demands for radical change and as symptoms of much graver social problems. Young people were seen as both a hotbed of revolt as the primary victims of social inequality, as “at-risk”. A New Brighton councillor described the poverty and poor living conditions of young people living in houses that they could not afford to maintain or setting up home in “backyards” rented from parents or other family members. This also makes it difficult to calculate how many families actually live in New Brighton.¹⁶⁰ A resident told me:

The majority of unemployed people are young, and the youth is the health and the strength of any nation. Education helped me to break the circle of poverty: it took me a very long time before I could think about buying a house [...]. In the sixties we were staying in somebody house and in the nineties, we were still staying there. Then I bought a piece of land for my parents [...]. There is a mushrooming of backyards dwellers [in New Brighton], the population has increased even if you don't see any new informal settlement. The parity in terms of wages-gap came very late: parents bought houses very late and they couldn't accumulate. They must use their pension to pay off and the kids are sometimes left with debts or with houses they cannot maintain (interview 24/11/2015).

Oldfield describes the perennial precarity that many families find themselves living in while awaiting the allocation of social housing as a “politics of waiting”. This can be a sustained period characterised by either the immobility of being stuck in families' backyards, or by the hypermobility of searching for temporary housing that keeps younger families without medium- to long-term plans stuck in a cycle of apathy and violent protest (Oldfield 2015).

Like its inhabitants, the township's imagined geography is subdivided into emancipating, respectable places and corrupting, devious places. In other words, particular places in the township are imbued with an intrinsic sense of morality. The moral connotations of certain places also fluctuate throughout the day: in general,

¹⁵⁹ The 2015 #FeesMustFall national campaign against increases in university fees included demonstrations, pickets in major university campuses and police violence.

¹⁶⁰ Morange (2002) has analysed the particular use of backyard shacks as a form of housing in Port Elizabeth.

dusk (which in New Brighton can start as early as seven in the evening, when shops close, people come home from work and taverns light up) is perceived as the temporal boundary between licit and illicit activities, an attitude to nightfall that is possibly shaped by the apartheid government's mobility controls and by the curfews imposed by emergency legislation in the 1980s.

The residents' words and behaviours suggest that the space of the RLMCP itself was also subject to these categorisations. During a conversation in front of the museum, for example, a member of the residents' committee told his son, a boy of around ten-years-old, to go home, and then explained to me that he didn't consider the museum to be an appropriate space for a child. After hours, the outdoor area of the RLMCP merged with the street, and was therefore perceived as unpredictable and uncontrollable. Even when the museum was open, residents preferred their children not to linger about the RLM for too long, as several groups of children had embarked upon the much frowned upon practice of asking tourists for spare change.¹⁶¹ To fulfil its emancipatory ambitions and be a space for more than tourists, the RLMCP had to merge with other edifying spaces in the township such as schools and churches and provide a space for intergenerational contact to proceed in a mediated and supervised manner.

Swartz (2009) observed a similar perception in Langa, Cape Town – while in the daytime the street was a space of lively socialising, friendliness and exchanging pleasantries, as soon as the sun goes down it became extremely dangerous. People on the streets at night could not, therefore, be morally trustworthy:

Good people and right behavior are associated with being 'at home' rather than to aimlessly *khangela* (wander around and look for a good time) the township, especially at night. Sleeping away from home is behavior reserved for *skollies*, gangsters, and those who are corrupt. In fact, as young people tell me, you can easily see who is a *skollie* because they are unkempt, unwashed, and dirty in appearance" (Swartz 2009: 62).

When I asked a participant in the Mdali workshop whether she would prefer to watch a play in the township or the city centre, she deliberated that she would bump into people she knew while walking to see a play in the township, but if it finished late she

¹⁶¹ This was told to me on various occasions and confirmed by the museum staff.

would run the risk of getting robbed on the walk home.¹⁶² While walking along the street, say to catch a bus, is an everyday occurrence, lingering on the street for extended periods of time, especially in less visible or populated areas, is seen as very risky. Another girl participating in the workshop, for example, worried about a ruined house on the side of the road that she passed everyday: “that house puts people’s life in danger. There are hooligans and groups of people that stand in front of that house and they are smoking dagga [cannabis] and other drugs. They could take someone and put her inside and rape that person” (from a Mdali workshop session, August 2015).

Alcohol consumption, and so bars and taverns, were regarded with a similar degree of wariness. Taverns had been totally illegal during apartheid, but become tolerated and legal or semi-legal in post-apartheid. Whereas during apartheid it had been a privilege, a status symbol of the Black middle-class, to possess or consume industrially bottled alcohol (rather than the traditional homemade beer drunk by the working-classes), but in post-apartheid, alcohol and the tavern became synonymous with vice and loose morals. Taverns are frequented exclusively for consuming alcohol and so are not neutral meeting places but are considered dens of immorality. Several musicians told me that it was frustrating to perform in the taverns because people were overwhelmingly more interested in alcohol than music: “creative spaces are being taken over by popular culture mostly that of drunkenness. It is for drunk people that musicians find themselves performing for more and more, and one needs to be careful when dealing with a drunk crowd”.¹⁶³ The taverns’ reputation as dangerous is related to perceptions that they were out of control: frequenting a tavern meant having to be constantly vigilant for the mood turning sour and conversations degenerating into brawls. There was also a moral separation between those who would leave the tavern before losing lucidity or getting embroiled in a sticky situation, and those who on the other hand would skulk inside in a state of inebriation.

Educational institutions, libraries, workplaces and places of worship, on the other hand, were seen as emancipatory spaces, despite guaranteeing neither the morality nor the safety of those who frequented them. When asked about the purpose of education, the students at Cowen High School, a secondary school a stone’s throw from Red Location, repeat the mantra that attending school means above all learning

¹⁶² My fieldnotes from observing a Mdali workshop.

¹⁶³ Email correspondence, 12/02/2016.

to steer clear of drugs, alcohol and, the girls added, teenage pregnancy.¹⁶⁴ School was considered the best safeguard against deviant behaviour.

The various forms this stark morality took during Sunday sermons¹⁶⁵ and other group events such as lectures, school assemblies and funerals, offers a framework through which to understand and analyse changes in the township, including the establishment and development of the RLMCP.

2. Evoking Xhosa Identities

Although I did not explicitly ask my interviewees about their ethnicity, many of those from the township spoke about “being umXhosa”, in the sense of sharing traditions, values and familial and intergenerational practices. This was mostly expressed in terms of a vague desire for returning to authenticity and rediscovering “traditional” values; through reference to alternative temporalities and spatialities; and through descriptions of values, norms and modes of relating that were considered beyond state regulations. Ultimately, Xhosa identities opened up the possibility of an alternative moral order to contrast with the neoliberal social norms regulating contemporary South African cities.

Xhosa identity was often invoked to describe dense, supportive social relationships that contrasted with feelings of suspicion and insecurity in South African society. But being Xhosa also indicated a certain closeness to rurality, a spatial-temporal positioning that exceeded the urban and the immediate and expressed itself through strong links to the past, origins and traditions. Rurality was reappropriated in particular by younger amaXhosa people as a fundamental element of their identity. In his analysis of townships in East London, Bank writes:

The presence of the ‘rural in the urban’ is never simply a matter of the transposition of rural cultural materials into the city, but involves reworking, reconstituting and renegotiating ideas about the rural in the urban in what might be defined as a ‘third space’ (2011: 12).

¹⁶⁴ This was reformulated many times during Mdali workshop sessions at Cowen High School.

¹⁶⁵ I attended, for example, a day for young women in a Methodist church where various speakers warned the girls of the perils of going to taverns or being on the street at unsavoury hours.

In post-industrial townships, rekindling connections to nature and the distant rural is related to the renegotiation and reproduction of “traditional knowledge”. Relationships with elders and, where possible, family members living in rural areas are therefore greatly valued. Growing vegetables, knowing how to slaughter a goat or chicken and identifying edible plants are skills through which one’s Xhosa identity can be expressed and reappropriated.¹⁶⁶ Tracing one’s rural roots means being able to rely on an identity that exceeds formal citizenship. As Portelli has noted, it is meanings, rather than facts, that make traditions (Portelli 2010). A young man from New Brighton, describing the district’s nightlife, advised me, “you should stay until four in the morning, when everything is silent and there are only the cows feeding out there” (informal conversation, November 2015). A distinctive characteristic of the locations, and not only the peri-urban ones, is the free circulation of goats and cows, a rural way of accumulating and exchanging wealth that is closely connected to the performance of traditional Xhosa rituals. Discussions of traditional values also often allude to male initiation rites (*ulwaluko*), though details are usually held back as the initiations are shrouded in secrecy. This “secrecy principle” is often invoked to suggest the existence of another world that eschews the classifications and codes of everyday life.¹⁶⁷

Respect for elders (*ukuhlonipha*) was one of the most frequently invoked values: “we Xhosa respect our elders”, I was told many times, as if this was a mark of distinction from non-Xhosa people. Respect is expressed through everyday care and

¹⁶⁶ This was a frequent topic of conversation during social events in Red Location and New Brighton.

¹⁶⁷ Initiation, the process by which amaXhosa youths are admitted into the adult world, is a resilient and reinvented practice that constitutes one of the foundational rituals of Xhosa society. Over time there have been attempts to adapt the ritual to changes in urban life. The period that initiates must spend in semi-isolation in the ‘bush’, for example, has undergone various adaptations according to the presence or absence of a suitable patch of land near the township (Kepe, McGregor and Irvine 2015). The huts that initiates in villages still build out of natural materials for temporary shelter are in the townships increasingly replaced by brick and mortar buildings that are not burnt down at the end of the period in the bush. Safety or logistical necessities have led families to avoid areas that are too dark or unpopulated. The ritual drum that announces the initiates’ rite of passage has been replaced in some areas by a slab of clay or a pistol shot (Dold and Cocks 2012). Several scandals, such as the case of rape committed by two initiates in Zwelitsha in 2006, have prompted a lengthy and pronounced reflection on initiates who take advantage of being away from their families to take drugs or drink alcohol (Vincent 2008; Ntombana 2011). The circumcision ceremony itself has been the target of many doubts and controversies due to the high number of infections and deaths caused by conducting this operation with non-sterile instruments or in unhygienic environments. The governance of initiations and efforts to make them safe, for example through medicalization, provides an interesting arena for tensions between different identities and forms of belonging.

attention – for example, older men strictly must be served food first; one must not speak before being invited to do so by someone within the group; one must introduce oneself properly. I was repeatedly instructed to respect these codes during my research, even in contexts that seemed far from “traditional” (for example, during my interview with the kung fu team or while observing of a meeting of an anti-pollution group in the township that was comprised mostly of young volunteers).

Relationships founded on clan identity exceed the geographical borders of the location, tracing trajectories across the whole city. It is a fairly common occurrence for a family to make a journey to participate in rituals, not only from the city to an ancestral village but also from newer residential areas to their original township. There is, for example, a high degree of mobility between New Brighton and Motherwell, a township very far from the city centre that was built in the 1970s, as many people gradually moved from New Brighton to Motherwell in search of work or a larger home.

As being Xhosa means evoking an identity that exceeds national belonging the RLMCP’s silence about cultural belonging and ethnic identity is extremely significant. The RLMCP was orchestrated by a political system that purported to “honour”¹⁶⁸ cultural diversity – through various initiatives ranging from formally recognising traditional chiefs to organising national heritage festivals to fictional television series – yet simultaneously rejected and relegated it to the private sphere.¹⁶⁹

The RLM sought to pay tribute to anti-apartheid struggles. Because of the colour of their skin, Red Location residents were identified as those who had suffered the greatest injustices under apartheid; the museum considered them as representative of the “Black working class”. The RLMCP, however, strove for relevance across the whole city, to be a point of reference for such a wide range of individuals that alternative expressions of identity and belonging – especially those that were deemed divisive – were suppressed. There was no explicit reference to anything relating to Xhosa culture within the museum. Port Elizabeth remains an extremely segregated city and Red Location is almost exclusively inhabited by people who define as amaXhosa. 99.34% of Red Location inhabitants are listed in the census as Black African, 0.2% as Coloured, 0.16% as Indian or Asian, 0.12% as White, 0.27% as Other.

¹⁶⁸ The verb “to honour” is frequently used in public discourse on diversity.

¹⁶⁹ Further discussion in chapter 6.2.

91.8% of residents also indicate isiXhosa as their first language. There are similar statistics in neighbouring wards (wards 16 and 17). While the cultural centre represented South Africa as an infinitely multiracial country, this was an abstraction and an allusion. The cultural centre wanted to be a space for everyone and so presented itself as neutrally as possible, the implicit assumption being that greater neutrality would put visitors at ease (in reality, the museum received criticisms that their excessive efforts to create a neutral space actually came off as impersonal, cold and unwelcoming).¹⁷⁰ At the same time, the organisers were wary of producing a folkloristic imaginary that was blatantly reminiscent of segregation and colonial representations.¹⁷¹ The result was a total absence of any reference to what many residents perceived as a fundamental dimension of their identity.

3. Expressions of citizenship: asymmetries and contaminations from colonialism to democracy

Multiple and intersecting ways of exercising, defining and shaping citizenship coexisted and overlapped in Red Location. Some residents identified first and foremost as working class, some felt a particularly strong sense of belonging to amaXhosa or other clans' cultures, while others put greater emphasis on their religious identity. Others still, especially younger people, identified much more broadly with the wider continent of Africa. Descriptions of Red Location as a site of working-class identity, a nexus of post-industrial heritage and as a cradle of activism relate not only to present-day stratified identities but also to expressions of citizenship that have intersected and intertwined throughout the course of South African history.

Citizenship throughout South African history can be analysed through various lenses, not only through race but also, for example, through the dichotomies of rural-urban, integrated-excluded, migrant worker-resident worker, stable-precarious employment and township- suburbs. Not all of these dichotomising expressions of

¹⁷⁰ These criticisms are reported in Cherry's review of Red Location Museum (2012), and were repeated by several residents during focus groups between 16–18 April 2012 (Brennan and Riordan 2012).

¹⁷¹ Rassool has dedicated several articles to the relationship between folklorification and the reinvention of identity and indigeneity during post-apartheid, especially with reference to the creation of museums. See Rassool (2009) on District Six Museum in Cape Town and Rassool (2000) on the relationship between heritage and the reification of cultures.

citizenship are formally institutionalised, but they are nevertheless evident in everyday inequality, prejudice and discrimination, and even modes of self-representation. This fragmented citizenship predates colonialism and can be traced to the encounters between pre-colonial and colonial power systems. It has also been heavily influenced by the anti-apartheid movement's reconfiguration of the individual in the 1980s.

In "Citizen and Subject", Mamdani describes the colonial state as a legal and institutional nexus that reproduced certain identities (Mamdani 1996). He reads the colonial state as a "bifurcated state" in which power was expressed in urban spaces through civil society and civil rights, but in the rural spaces through the concepts of community and culture. The colonial government's greatest contradiction was the legal distinction between race and ethnicity, with ethnicity being associated with "natives" while race was used as a category to govern and order "non-natives". People who were seen as having or being a race, as opposed to an ethnicity, were governed by civil law as members or potential members of civil society. Ethnicities, on the other hand, were linked to tradition and authenticity and subject to common law. Mamdani (1996) was one of the first authors to argue that apartheid should not be seen not as a form of government that was unique South Africa, but as a part of broader processes of colonialism across Africa. As in other states in sub-Saharan Africa, a truncated and multifaced form of South African citizenship began to form in which civil rights depended on racial hierarchies. Migration from rural areas to urban spaces entailed being subject to multiple forms of power ("traditional" rural power structures and a government elected by the part of the population with full civil rights) that produced a further stratification, dividing subjects into migrant workers without the right to family reunification and resident workers and families (Banks 2011).

The amaXhosa people were further divided by steady urbanisation and the Nongqawuse incident, which split families into categories of "Red and School" or "believers and unbelievers". Nongqawuse was a young prophet in the mid-1850s who maintained that spirits he had met on the banks of the Gxarha river had told him that if the amaXhosa sacrificed all their livestock and harvests then their ancestors would return from the sea and the amaXhosa would have had an army capable of vanquishing the British colonisers. Clans split into those who believed the prophet and sacrificed their livestock ("Red" clans) and those who did not believe ("School"

clans). Attempts to fulfil the prophecy, together with the spreading of an epidemic of likely European origin, led to the slaughter of around 400,000 head of cattle and a widespread famine that decimated the amaXhosa population and accelerated the urbanisation of surviving families (Peires in “The House of Palo: A History of the Xhosa People in the Day of Their Independence”, 1989, suggests there were 40,000 deaths). While historians have various interpretations of this incident (was Nongqawuse manipulated by the colonial government? Did the colonial government use the prophet to urbanise the amaXhosa? Did the amaXhosa really kill such a great number of cattle or did the legend come about as an explanation for the colossal famine that devastated the amaXhosa?), still to this day the story of Nongqawuse is used by the amaXhosa to explain rural-urban migration and to distinguish between a period of freedom and autonomy and a period of subjugation to a foreign, colonising regime. Nongqawuse is used to explain the loss of a golden age of plenty (and so to argue that such a golden age did actually exist) and provide reasons for the amaXhosa’s alienation from their cultural roots. This recalls the colonial distinction made between *évolués* and *indigènes* to refer to varying degrees of integration, civilisation and relinquishing of traditional clothing, languages and religions.

The schism between Red and School people was marked and obvious even to outsiders in the first half of the 20th century and then underwent various reconfigurations. Initially, it marked a division between people who maintained their rural customs and those who instead chose the path of assimilation, especially in terms of education. Today, this division is understood as separating those who endeavour to keep traditional rituals pure, resilient and resistant, and those who are thought to have lost all contact with their ancestral world and its cosmogony; between middle-class people who speak good English and aspire to social mobility and people who, for reasons of education or economic power, have been excluded, or have excluded themselves, from an ever more globalised and cosmopolitan society. A good example of the current relevance of the Red-School divide is provided by Zakes Mda’s book “The Heart of Redness” (2000), which narrates the effects of the schism across and within various families grappling with the difficult choice between preserving tradition or economic development and assimilation.

Barchiesi analyses other types of division and categorisation that should be considered alongside those discussed above, including differences that stem from

unequal access to salaried work and shared experiences of compulsory “socialisation” that produced the Black working-class. Factory work created a new hierarchical division between salaried and precariously employed Black workers that fell into the background during the most intense years of the anti-apartheid movement but remerged in all its complexity during post-apartheid. Barchiesi writes, “the centrality of wage labour in post-apartheid social policy discourse is also expressed through a moral vocabulary that pits itself against welfare dependency and obscures the deteriorating material conditions of waged labour in a context of growing unemployment and precarity” (2006: 1).

In the 1980s movements like the ANC and the Port Elizabeth Black Civic Organisation (PEBCO) strove to recreate and reunify different understandings of South African citizenship, believing that the tactics of movements against racism, patriarchy and oppression could form the basis of a society of equals.

The society envisaged by the popular movements of the 1980s was explicitly stated as being “non-racial, non-sexist and democratic”, situated within a unitary state. [...] The way in which organisations functioned and the culture of organisations were ‘prefigurative’ in anticipating the new South Africa that was being struggled for. This building of new cultures ran counter to the dominant racist, patriarchal, hierarchical and authoritarian cultures. It went beyond an oppositional culture, and explored the possibility of egalitarian relationships which fundamentally challenged the existing power relations embedded in race, class and gender’ (Cherry 2015).

These political formations analysed society through its many fragmentations, in which they saw an opportunity for a more precise form of government. They anticipated a social critique rooted in intersectionality; they recognised the complexity of interactions between multiple axes of oppression and called for diversified and targeted social interventions. The partial citizenship afforded to women, for example, required different tactics depending on race: Black women were subjected to a double or triple oppression, and white women, despite their racial privilege, were still imprisoned in an extremely patriarchal legislative framework and social structure (Cherry 2015).

In contrast to the hopes of activists in the 1980s, the democratic transition and a constitution committed to safeguarding and widening civil rights did not

automatically abolish these hierarchical divisions and partial forms of citizenship. Inequalities in citizenship are one of the most critical and criticised features of the post-apartheid years. Mamdani's view that post-independence African states deracialised without becoming democracies and replaced previous hierarchies with a division between natives and non-natives absolutely applies to South Africa. In South Africa, political parties and movements like the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF) called for a recognition of rights based on nativism and their narrative of oppression relied on a conflation between skin colour and economic power. On the other hand, Panafricanist or Afropolitanist trends among South African youth constitute alternative expressions of identity, belonging and citizenship. The spoken language of so-called "youth multilingualism"¹⁷² mixes American English with Nigerian pidgins and nonverbal communication borrowed from Black ghettos. Connections and borrowings between South African townships and Afro-American cultures are not a recent phenomenon, as demonstrated by *tsotsi* fashion or the influence of jazz on the *marabi* bands of the 1920s.¹⁷³ Fouquet describes this as the "transnational aesthetic of the subaltern" (Fouquet 2014), while Hurnst highlights how an international dialogue between *tsotsi* and the wider world can be traced back to the 1940s (Hurnst 2009). *Tsotsi* gangs took inspiration from 1950s gangster movies, in the same way that the incorporation of hip-hop and rap in the 1990–2000s did not simply reproduce but reinterpreted and reiterated these styles. Backer and Dastile, for example, describe the emergence of new, fluid, urban African identities resulting from the co-mingling of Afro-American hip-hop and its Xhosa reiterations (Backer and Dastile 2008).

This multiplicity of expressions of citizenship and identity cannot be easily reduced into a simple definition. Red Location inhabitants stressed how social hierarchies and relationships vary widely depending on who you're talking to – other township inhabitants, Xhosa people or Afrikaner officials. While the township was a site of multiplicity that enabled the free expression of multifaceted identities, the city centre and places like the RLMCP were seen as places which neutralised and flattened diversity, forcing tactical and strategic identity expressions. The exercise of

¹⁷² See Mesthrie (2008); Williams (2016); Backer and Dastile (2008).

¹⁷³ *Marabi*, a genre popular among Black South Africans in the 1920s and 1930s, drew from North American jazz, ragtime and the blues. Its development in South Africa was also partially due to bands performing on ships undertaking intercontinental voyages. See Ballantine (2012).

citizenship, then, emerged as geographically stratified, dependent on whether you found yourself near public bodies and the city centre, or within the space of the township.

4. Red Location as a tangle of identities

In Red Location, the tangle of the behaviours inherited from apartheid, working-class values and Xhosa cultural practices is difficult to unravel. A banal but significant example of this is provided by the media treatment of Bathabile Dlamini, Minister for Social Development and the President of the ANC Women's League (ANCWL).

In 2015, Dlamini visited New Brighton for the opening of a drug addiction rehabilitation clinic. During the launch, a resident criticised her for having got drunk on expensive whiskey. Dlamini later retorted that she would have hit the residents who had insulted her if the ANC had have allowed it, adding that they were proof that parents should discipline their children.¹⁷⁴

This short incident exposes various behavioural codes and prohibitions, including strong disapproval of drinking and drinking problems, a general acceptance that community leaders should act with propriety and lead by example but also that superiors in age or status were nevertheless owed respect, and a paternalistic discourse which reproduced the image of Dlamini as a mother to the community and charged the family with teaching the rules of collective life.

Behavioural codes in the township have undergone a series of reiterations and realignments. The formal end of apartheid and the decline of the working-class prompted by economic crisis did not result in the disappearance of segregation and identities based on shared socio-economic status. Everyday behaviours do not exactly die out, but rather they cross-pollinate and become hybrid. Being an inhabitant of the township meant knowing how to masterfully make use of this hybridity. Analogously, integration implied compliance with multiple behavioural codes at the same time, without any one identity becoming overshadowed by the others. For example, upwardly socially mobile people who tried to hide their township origins or stopped speaking isiXhosa were met with strong disapproval. Similarly, individuals who expressed "partial" identities, such as the children of parents with mixed origins and

¹⁷⁴ R. de Kock, *PE residents insult ANCWL president, she starts crying*, 'The Herald', 15/04/2016.

who could not speak isiXhosa despite being from the township, were suspected of trying to conceal their roots.

The multiple expressions of citizenship and overlapping moral orders in the township strongly demonstrate that it is necessary to move beyond a conception of citizenship and belonging that relies on a hierarchical structure of individuals within communities within the nation. Contemporary South Africa is often represented as being constructed on three levels: one identifies first as an individual, then as a member of a community, and finally as a citizen of the nation. There is a tendency to see these three levels as separated and shaped by separate structures: the family is thought to prompt the individual to identify with a community, and in turn the community is understood to direct the individual towards national belonging. These levels are furthermore articulated in spatial terms: community identity is perceived as more natural and closer to the individual, while national identity becomes increasingly important the further you get from the city and seats of power. The nation is further conceived as the sum of differences between communities and as a way of achieving equality between citizens (Rassool 2000). In reality, the concept of “community identity” is no less vague “national community”. Moreover, far from achieving equality, the nation is more often a cause of inequality and unfairness. It can also be noted that history has made South African citizens particularly suspicious of the artificiality of national identity and dubious as to whether it grants legal recognition and safeguards civil rights. In any case, various identities and affiliations merge and intersect, producing complex representations of belonging.

Individuals in Red Location simultaneously identify with the nation and the community, while maintaining a degree of separation between the two. National identity is understood as citizenship: a juridical relationship between the individual and the state, a status that confers rights and responsibilities to the individual as a citizen of a given territory. Community identity, on the other hand, refers more to shared practices and shared perspectives. Community identity can be constructed, strengthened or refused, while national identity (that is different from nationalism), simply *is*, once and for all.

Red Location residents and public bodies, however, referred to different things through the concept of community. Legislators and policymakers were envisioning an ethnolinguistic and cultural community that could ultimately be traced back to the

categorisations of apartheid. For the inhabitants of the township, however, the meaning of community varied from person to person. People could identify very strongly with an ethnicity, but also with the geographical area of the township, or with communities based on shared interests, age, gender, class, etc. 'Ordinary' (Carrel and Neveu 2014), performative, everyday citizenship is formed from the totality of an individual's communities, through identification with multiple different communities simultaneously. From this perspective, the township's 'ordinariness' is extremely complicated.

Red Location citizens' demands reflect this ambiguous understanding of citizenship: some demands pertained to rights, particularly socio-economic rights, while others were part of a framework in which citizenship was understood as a collection of social practices. Demands for decent housing and employment were made as South African citizens. Criticisms and protests over history and memory, and demands for local associations to be able to use the museum, training schemes and youth employment were made as mothers and fathers, elders, activists and inhabitants who wanted to create emancipatory spaces within the township.

The occupation of the cultural centre brought together both modes of expressing identity, belonging and citizenship. Through demonstrating their "ability to reflect upon the world they inhabit" (Carrel and Neveu 2014), Red Location residents insisted that they could make more informed and long-term decisions than the Municipal representatives, precisely because of their multiple, fluid identities.

6. Beyond prescription: deliberate desertion

Just as Noero had envisioned, on some afternoons the area in front of the museum came alive with the bustling activities of various different groups. When the museum was closed the residents would gather outside it, small huddles of people suggesting multiple meetings happening at the same time. Sometimes groups with almost antagonistic interests would meet just a few metres apart. Occasionally, while residents deliberated strategies and tactics, curators of the art gallery, museum or library would arrive and phone the RLMCP managers to arrange a meeting or to ask permission to enter the buildings. The following morning the courtyard would be populated by various public officials passing by to check in on the progress of the works, teams of voluntary litter pickers maintaining the public green spaces, or

members of the committee coming and going between the museum and the ward councillor's office. When the museum was closed, the ward councillor's office was used for photocopying.

Apart from the security guards who loitered in or around the entrances to the buildings, there were no uniforms visible. Excluding the arrests of several members of a neighbourhood committee in 2009 and the occasional patrol, there was effectively no police presence in the space of the RLMCP. From this perspective, the precinct seems anything but a site of confrontation. A sense of unease derives more from the abandoned nature of the buildings than from perceptions of tension. The main groups involved in the conflict – the residents, the museum and the Municipality – interacted with each other on an almost daily basis in the space of the project in a way that was far from aggressive.

What was it that enabled these peaceful and rather workmanlike interactions, the gradual negotiations and eventual decisions? The guidelines prescribed by the RLMCP certainly could not have been a sufficient condition, especially since project delivery had been sporadic since 2013. Paradoxically, these interactions were enabled by project workers in the field “deserting” the project – sympathising with would-be adversaries, turning a blind eye to illegal activities, using discretion to resist certain rules or processes and bending unwritten rules, especially those considered as the cornerstones of civil society. Desertions do not necessarily always cause revolutions, but they can open up spaces for dialogue through challenging societal assumptions. In the context of Red Location at least three social rules were contravened: (1) rather than being erased, the classifications of apartheid were reactivated in order to create new alliances and reconciliations; (2) ubuntu, the principle undergirding social harmony, was challenged by the declaration of diversity and material equality; and (3) rather than claiming to act as but “cogs in the wheel” of the structures they officially represented, officials and politicians engaged with the various complexities of their identities and sometimes contradictory principles to collaborate with the residents.

1. The reactivation of apartheid categories

Racial classifications and related stereotypes re-emerged in various ways, corroborating oppositional statements and constructing contradictory discourses,

aiming for either solidarity, empathy and cooperation, or else distance, superiority and detachment. By noting that some categories from the time of apartheid and colonialism have endured, I do not mean to suggest that their significance, value and meaning are unchanged. Rather, their persistence evidences the existence of a sort of “aphasia”, a lack of new terminology and adequate categories for interpreting the present and prefiguring the future. This is not unique to South Africa – Oushakine, for example, has described young Russians’ difficulties in understanding their own identity in contemporary Russia as a “post-Soviet aphasia” (Oushakine 2000). Aphasia occurs when social change has not been accompanied by discursive change. Oushakine described the silence of a generation that cannot not or will not discuss social issues as a “social silence” or “solipsism”, but the situation in South Africa is somewhat different. In South Africa, the lack of appropriate terminology has led people to remix and recycle the terms and categories that are available to them. By way of example, we can consider the expression “coconut” to indicate someone who is “Black” on the outside but “white” on the inside, that is to say, culturally or behaviourally. In the townships, the adjective is used pejoratively to refer to young university students who use English rather than African languages, or who have distanced themselves from their own background in other ways. In most cases, such people belong to the Black middle-class individuals – being middle-class or wielding greater economic power is still strongly associated with whiteness.

Post-apartheid history is permeated with symbolic borders and moral dichotomies. Apartheid spatially segregated “different races”, and fear of these boundaries being transgressed still finds spatial expression in post-apartheid. For example, poverty continues to be displaced from middle or upper-middle class spaces in the name of security, and very expensive private schools that present themselves as protective paradises still separate children of different socioeconomic backgrounds from the earliest age possible. This fear is also evidenced by difficulty of even conceiving of grey areas that might be beyond categorisation.

In *Native Nostalgia* (2008), a book written with the aim of complicating binary oppositions between anti-apartheid activists and apartheid collaborators, oppressed and oppressors, Dlamini wonders why it is generally considered impossible in South Africa that township inhabitants can “remember their lives under apartheid with fondness”. Dlamini considers not only the complicated dynamics between resistance

and collaboration or nostalgia about the past (it is not uncommon to hear elderly location inhabitants claim that there used to be greater control and security), but also argues that everyone born under apartheid, whether they like it or not, shares common practices and memories that depend on having lived through that particular regime. One of his most significant examples is ambivalent relationships with Afrikaans, a language that was imposed by the apartheid regime with lasting impacts on Zulu and Xhosa languages. Dlamini further explains:

There are many South Africans for whom the past, the present and the future are not discrete wholes, with clear splits between them. These are people for whom the present is not the land of milk and honey, the past not one vast desert of doom, and the ancient past not one happy-go-lucky area. For many, the past is a bit of this, the present a bit of that, and the future hopefully a mix of this, that and more (2009: 12).

The tangle of relationships and dynamics intersecting at the RLMCP clearly constitute this sort of grey area where the past is reactivated and reintegrated into the present in various different ways.

One of the most significant ways in which this happened was through reference to individual biographies. Any history of contribution to anti-apartheid resistance was taken as a guarantee of present-tense moral integrity and selflessness. During interviews, Noero referenced his work with the ANC, Riordan referenced the creation of the Human Rights Trust, Du Plessis, the museum's Marketing Manager, referenced his activism as a white artist in New Brighton, etc. At the same time, such credentials were often used to hold those flaunting them to account and demand ongoing commitment to anti-hierarchical solidarity. To justify their opinion of someone, interviewees would often claim to have known them during apartheid, to have organised alongside them, or even to have simply been neighbours with them before they made a career in politics or business.

However, anti-apartheid prestige was a double-edged sword. For example, during an interview one of the older members of the RLMCP explained, "I fought with [the name of an official] in one meeting inside the museum. I told him I knew who he was but I didn't understand who he has become. I told him: I'm surprised how you operate 'cause you were protecting the right of the people before!" (interview 02/11/2015). The official's reputation had been damaged because he was understood

to have betrayed his past ideological principles, and his critic evoked apartheid segregation and knowledge of the official's politics to strengthen his own argument. Similarly, when the housing protests reached their peak in 2013, the residents went to the then-city mayor, Fihla, for the reason that he had been imprisoned for fourteen years on Robben Island as an ANC activist, had previously lived in the location and had been neighbours with Malgas. And indeed, Fihla promised to accelerate the repair works on the houses of Red Location residents.¹⁷⁵

In addition to individuals' biographies being explicitly referenced to solicit their intervention or solidarity, apartheid categorisations resurfaced in the everyday life of post-apartheid in a way that was far from straightforward. Stereotypes and divisions that had no place in a democratic South Africa were often reproduced. For instance, a member of the RLSC, the group that was insistently demanding that jobs generated by the project should be reserved for workers living in Red Location, exclaimed heatedly during one of our meetings that he thought the museum and the other cultural centre structures should be managed by a white director as he deemed white South Africans to be more efficient.¹⁷⁶ Similarly, the curator of the South End Museum, an institution that is mandated to encourage integration and equality among all citizens of South Africa, complained on multiple occasions that the flood of funding into majority Black townships disadvantaged majority Coloured townships, which had played just as important a role in anti-apartheid struggle.¹⁷⁷

Reading society through the lens of race can prove useful in some cases, but in others, neither skin colour nor shared origins were sufficient to form connections. A RLMCP employee, for example, told me, "my staff is from the area, my mother's family is from Red Location, but it's difficult as an outsider to work in Red Location" (interview 08/10/2015). Despite being umXhosa and originally from the location, his clothes, hairstyle and use of English placed him closer to the city centre than the outskirts. Characteristics that could have been advantageous for him were overshadowed by the otherness of his education and his upwards social mobility. On the other hand, one of the managers kept a very low profile, spoke in a very informal manner, did not drive an expensive car and dressed like a "comrade" in a tracksuit

¹⁷⁵ Interview 11/05/2011.

¹⁷⁶ Interview 02/11/2015.

¹⁷⁷ Interview 23/03/2015. The curator later reiterated this belief during a seminar presenting the preliminary results of this thesis at the NMMU, 24/07/2015.

and trainers. This made him more relatable in the eyes of the residents and few doubted that he should be a manager of the RLMCP.

Racial categories were reappropriated at all levels of power, from managers to employees. They could be instrumentalised by anyone – descendants of oppressed or oppressors, inhabitants of the suburbs or the townships. Reference to apartheid segregation was at times a deliberate tactic, and at other times incidental, almost like an accidental slip of the tongue. When this was the case, it was also deployed as proof that South African society was pathologically unable to heal itself from the disease of segregation. While it is beyond doubt that South African society is still in many ways profoundly segregated, it is important to note that racial categories were not merely reproduced only to refer to very real material inequalities in almost all aspects of daily life (including access to education, public services and employment) but they were also powerfully rearticulated, reconfigured and repurposed for better and for worse – they enabled both racist stereotypes and self-affirmation; fuelled exclusive communitarianism and social fragmentation but also created connections that cut across the categories of “good” and “bad” people.

2. Ubuntu and the declaration of difference

The RLSC’s protests can be read as the forceful declaration of a difference separating Red Location inhabitants from other citizens. The residents believed that by virtue of living near the project, being the custodians of anti-apartheid values and suffering the hardships of life in the location they were entitled to make decisions about project’s future and the jobs and services it should provide. It was this very difference that enabled them to appropriate force the suspension of the project.

The fight against discrimination in South Africa (in schools, workplaces, etc.) has often centred around the recognition of diversity. Examples of this are provided by the campaign for women to be allowed to wear traditional headscarves on national television and at work, and the campaign to make school uniform rules more appropriate for the hairstyles of Black and Coloured women. The regularity of such campaigns points to a flaw in the logic of ubuntu, the philosophy that is used more than any other to characterise the construction of the new South Africa.

The word ubuntu comes from a proverb that exists in several South African languages. In isiXhosa it reads “Ubuntu ungamntu ngabanye abantu”, which can be

literally translated as “a person is a person through other persons”. Stuit (2016) notes how there is no original notion of ubuntu, but how the concept of ubuntu articulates a social humanism of interrelational care, sharing and commitment to the greater good. She also notes that in post-apartheid, the concept of ubuntu has retained only its positive connotations.

The political reuse and repurposing of “ubuntu” can be ascribed to Desmond Tutu “Ubuntu means ‘I need you in order for me to be me as you need me in order for you to be you’. It is saying really, we are bounded up together because, you see, I wouldn’t know how you speak like a human being, how to walk like a human being, how to think like a human being; all of these things I learnt from other human beings so I actually need other human beings in order for me to be human [...] we say ‘a person is a person through other persons’”.¹⁷⁸ This definition can be interpreted in various ways: with explicit roots in African Bantu tradition (ubuntu is often described as African philosophy or African ethics), ubuntu offers a view of nation-building that is founded on the inclusion of diversity. Just as a person is a person only through other people, the nation could only come to be through recognising the multiplicity of ethnicities that reside on South African territory. The foundations of equality, social justice and peaceful conflict resolution derive from reciprocity and mutual respect (“All of us are members of one family [...] we are all members of the human family and you wouldn’t want to hurt your sister...it doesn’t usually happen in a family that brothers and sisters kill each other or are violent to each other”).¹⁷⁹

The concept of ubuntu is mostly deployed by the political classes. Zuma used it to urge traditional leaders to behave in a such way that would consolidate the construction of the nation: “Traditional chiefs need to help us look back at our values and try to interrogate how to restore our dignity. 'Ubuntu' we must bring it back”.¹⁸⁰ Bam, Chancellor of Walter Sisulu University and ex-President of the Independent Electoral Commission of South Africa (IEC) called for a return to ubuntu values to propel South Africa towards development: “we can instil the African philosophy of ubuntu to mobilise [the nation] and once again be autonomous, working for ourselves

¹⁷⁸ Interview with Desmond Tutu, 2010.

¹⁷⁹ *Idem.*

¹⁸⁰ Zuma cited in T. Mohlaoli, ‘Zuma urges traditional leaders to be champions of nation building’, *SABC news*, 07/04/2016.

towards development”.¹⁸¹ Ex-vice-President Motlanthe urged citizens to repair the nation’s moral fibre and nurture the spirit of ubuntu in their communities. The Inkhata Freedom Party evoked ubuntu to force the President to release the results of the Marikana Massacre commission of inquiry (“Zuma must practise ubuntu and release Marikana report now”).¹⁸² Appeals to recover and embrace the values of ubuntu swung between a yearning for a mythical, precapitalist past when individuals acted in the interests of community, and the enduring need to pacify social relations through ousting any form of violence.

The RLMCP openly challenged this way of conceiving social relations. Not only did the residents’ actions in and of themselves assert the existence of difference, but the residents also expressed diverse demands and priorities (for example, whether to repair existing social housing units or build new ones, how to negotiate access to the list of beneficiaries, etc.). Being “members of one family” that formally recognised diverse cultures and traditions – for example through the “folklorisation” of Heritage Day – was not a guarantee of full citizenship rights. The protests against the museum and service delivery protests more broadly made clear demands for the recognition of difference and diversity, especially when it came to economic inequality and the barriers that the majority of the population faced in overcoming intergenerational deprivation. The protests declared that there could be no ubuntu without redistribution and that the responsibility for sharing should not be shouldered by everyone equally but distributed in accordance with resources.

3. The Politics of Proximity

In Red Location, the “politics of proximity” was not so much an intentional tactic as a result of how closely residents, museum employees, officials and politicians interacted on a daily basis because of the conflict. Proximity makes politics, as frequent and sometimes forced interactions between different groups results in a softening of the borders of belonging.

Attempts to reconcile institutional regulations, roles and individual principles were particularly evident among local officials and politicians, who were torn

¹⁸¹ Bam, cited in ‘Bam encourages South African citizens to embrace spirit of ubuntu’, *SABC news*, 28/11/2015.

¹⁸² Gwala, President of the IFP, cited in A. Wakefield, *News24*, 09/06/2015.

between empathising with the residents and wanting to properly fulfil their job descriptions. Below, I discuss three cases in which the desire to perform a role and find consensus and compromise was countered by an inability to abandon personal convictions and values. All three individuals found themselves faced with the challenge of how to work towards the common good without abandoning the problem of inequality and economic disparity.

Almost all my interviews with officials and politicians took a two-part structure. Initially, interviewees would tend to focus on their role within a hierarchical structure and expressed condemnation of, or at least confusion about, the residents' occupation of public buildings. As the interview progressed, however, they would start to express sympathy and partnership with the protesters and to question some of the policies that they were directed to implement. Lipsky writes that "street-level bureaucrats" are often required to respond to the human aspect of contentious situations and that this sensitivity often manifests itself in discretion and flexibility. He argues that "street-level officials" can exercise discretion as a form of resistance to or non-compliance with policies that they judge unreasonable (Lipsky 1980). It was in the second half of interviews that this sensitivity emerged and criticisms of municipal policies aimed at governing poverty were expressed.

The third case I discuss is slightly different: although the official stereotyped the residents (see Lipsky 1980) and claimed to be totally separate from them (in terms of race, culture and ideology), because of his commitment to professionalism he was actually very receptive to the demands of Red Location inhabitants. Professional ethics and codes of conduct were used as a way of justifying sympathy with the protesters. Another official told me, "the community raises legitimate concerns using municipal assets like leverages. We have the responsibility to protect those municipal assets. So, I try to engage with them" (interview 08/10/2015).

Officials also recognised the centrality of the role played by the residents' committee in gathering and communicating information about various departments that often did not communicate with each other: "if it wasn't for the Red Location Steering Committee, we wouldn't know a lot of things, even if we are not supposed to communicate" (interview 24/11/2015). Although they expressed criticisms and concerns, almost all municipal officials recognised the committee as an organisation to refer to.

In an interview Noero claimed, “[this project] could only come from Eastern Cape, because the ANC is all powerful in the Eastern Cape and, in a sense, decision making is very clear”.¹⁸³ Despite appearances, and as demonstrated by recent crises within the ANC on provincial and municipal levels,¹⁸⁴ that local politicians involved in the project were all members of the ANC did not mean they that held unanimous opinions and tactics. For example, in 2010, it was a local councillor working in collaboration with the local ANC branch who prepared a detailed document to be sent to the ANC Regional Executive Committee and several key contacts in the Municipality demanding political intervention to effectively respond to the issue of social housing repairs. A member of the local ANC branch confided in me during an interview, “local ANC supports the protests but in an informal way. To be honest I have to tell you that I agree with them [the community]. When people start protesting inside ANC they are directly labelled as opposition, but they are not opposition. [...] The community hasn’t got a sense of ownership on the Museum: the ANC local branch has already debated about that; we would like a board that would include community members” (interview 06/03/2015). The leaders and political activists who worked closely with Red Location citizens tended informally to take on the role of mediators and spokespeople and would represent the community’s concerns to higher level politicians. These activities were often not communicated to the media or made explicit in the institutional headquarters in the city centre because people still feared that they would be declared subversive, divisive or guilty of factionalism within the ANC.

F. played a leading role as a city planner in the Municipality. Despite being a middle-class professional, he had an almost emotional bond with the residents and their demands. He told me he felt an affinity with them because he was born and raised in a township, and still returned there regularly to buy groceries despite now living in a suburb on the other side of the city.

¹⁸³ The Architectural Review (2015), *Red Location: Repairing an Urban Fabric*, minute 19:00.

¹⁸⁴ The extent of the fragmentation of the ANC on city and province levels and the related power-struggle in NMB is evidenced by the fact that following the dissolution of ANC Eastern Cape regional committee, Zuma made five visits to NMB in 2015 alone. Between 2012 and 2015 the city saw the succession of four mayors (Faku, Wayile, Fihla, Joordan); all of them were part of the ANC, some of them were dismissed from position. The ANC eventually lost the administrative elections of 2016, conceding one of its primary seats to the Democratic Alliance (DA).

F. stressed the challenges of drafting an urban development plan in a city where not even basic services were guaranteed for all citizens: “there is the strategic plan, but we still need to pick up the rubbish and so we get caught in this service delivery matter and only after we do strategic planning [...] For the moment politics is about killing fires: the protests are called ‘the public telephone’ because they are the only way for people to be assisted” (interview 04/11/2015). Discussing the residents’ protests, he could have perceived as an obstacle to promising development project, F. explained: “For people [it] is difficult to give up their interests in favour of a greater goal because they are just surviving and they lack primary services” (*ibid.*). As he identified with a previously discriminated-against group (he identifies as Coloured), F. felt a greater degree of empathy towards the residents of Red Location and in general towards the communities who he worked with. Even though his visits to Red Location were infrequent, he spoke with awareness of the location’s problems and needs. He explicitly discussed the legacy of apartheid and saw restitution projects above all as a form of symbolic atonement that presented many practical challenges: “the community is disadvantaged because of apartheid legacy, and lots of the projects are made out of white guilt” (*ibid.*).

Q. was a housing officer and so his involvement in the project primarily pertained to the construction of social housing, rather than culture. His position was diametrically opposed to F.’s, but was no less enlightening. At the beginning of his interview, he described his relationship with the residents of Red Location by explaining, “I’m a white man, I will never go to the museum, so I can speak out and I can tell them that they can even burn it, but that’s not my interest, my interest is the [housing] project” (interview 21/04/2015). The first thing he noted was a stark difference between him and Red Location residents, a difference based on the conceptual construction of race that dated back to the years of apartheid (“I will never go to the museum” suggested that the museum’s celebration of anti-apartheid struggle meant it was not a place for white people). Q. declared that his interests were exclusively to do with the problem that he was brought in as a specialist to resolve. Regarding the housing protests, he commented, “the [Red Location] community feels they are very empowered, as they elected the councillor and they voted for the president that promised them houses” (*ibid.*), implying feelings of separation from the ANC government. The officer referred to the leaders of the residents’ committee by

their Christian names (that are not in the Xhosa language), never their isiXhosa names. This practice is also a hangover from apartheid that is especially offensive to amaXhosa people. But despite this, Q. was one of the people who worked in closest contact with the residents and conversed on a daily basis with the protest leaders, with whom he enjoyed an extremely friendly and easy-going relationship. Although he declared little interest in visiting the museum, Q. was one of the most present and probably one of the most enthusiastic public officials working in Red Location. In response to RLSC protests over delays to the repair works and the use of very poor-quality building materials, Q. discharged the responsible construction firm from the job. He was the public face of the Municipality when it came to the repair works and was very well-known to the residents. He acted as a reliable point of contact. In the words of several of my interlocuters in Red Location, he was an “honest guy”, a “good guy”.

4. I, as a person

South African citizens are asked to perform an ambiguous role shaped partially by public discourse aiming for social cohesion and individualised responsibility and partially by the legacies of the social structure of apartheid and the various ways in which this has been reinterpreted and rearticulated on an individual basis. While post-apartheid officially denies and suppresses difference, the categories of apartheid continue to produce material and symbolic divisions and inequalities. Citizens’ identities occupy and appropriate this uncertain space, negotiating the contradictions between the new rules of civil coexistence and the refusal to reduce social justice to a charade of conflict-avoidance. Responses to this structural challenge can on first appearance seem incongruent. However, it is precisely this incongruity that enables us to understand individual efforts to appropriate, re-interpret and adjust the public discourse.

Various authors (for example, Booyesen 2007) have described contemporary South Africa’s “identity crisis” as “a state of consciousness in which most of the social categories by means of which an individual defines himself and his place in society seem to have lost their boundaries and their value” (Andreeva cited in Ivanova 2005: 72). Others, including Dolby (2001) and Durrheim, Mtose and Brown (2011), discuss the resurfacing and endurance of racial categorisations as a terrain of social

identification. In other words, according to this argument, the end of the racist regime lacked alternative identity representations, and so people fell back on, or deliberately revived, previous social categories.

The case of Red Location demonstrates that conflict is not purged from public spaces, but transferred to private spaces. I often heard the qualification “I, as a person” used to introduce opinions that people did not feel able to express in their capacity as officials, politicians or members of a certain social group. The information they would then divulge often took on a confessional tone. The purpose of this phrase was to draw a separation between someone’s public function or role in society and their individual experience. It indicated a shift in the conversation to an individual’s emotions and personal identity. It often felt like a mask had been dropped, that discomfort had been allowed to seep out, revealing a significant discrepancy between public and private appearances. Frustrations, fears, anger and bitterness manifested themselves as feelings of detachment and dissociation.

Since identity is neither static nor neatly delineated (Remotti 1996; Bhabha 2004), definitions of identity crises can be vague. As identities undergo constant change, perpetual slippage may be a more appropriate image than identity crisis. It does not even seem particularly accurate to speak of a re-emergence of the concept of race: a lot of South African discussions on “Blackness” are actually reformulations of ideas developed by Afro-American thinkers that pertain much more to discrimination and the persistence of stereotypes than racial identities. The battlefield of the RLMCP was a space of encounter, rather than polarisation. Forced to interact with and understand each other, the various groups involved ended up questioning predominant representations of identity and belonging. In a context in which there was no language for social structures and relationships that cut across and exceeded categories of class and race, and where terms such as class, oppression, exploitation or disadvantage were so heavily charged that it was impossible to use them neutrally, actions spoke louder than words. People’s actions revealed much more about changes in their identity than what was said about these actions. Identity is continually appropriated and reappropriated; it is constituted by constant inventions, adjustments, superimpositions and developments.

Interactions between radically different groups were enabled precisely by the multidimensionality of identity and the plasticity of belonging, whose mechanisms of

inclusion-exclusion are never static and impermeable, even in the case of conflict. Everyday practices and prescribed behaviours coexist in state of constant renegotiation. For example, as Red Location residents were suggesting alternative activities to the museum, an organisational structure was established and a member of staff was appointed as a point of contact for community activists; conversely, an employee who was judged untrustworthy was continually bypassed. Several residents ended up confiding in another official who then became a spokesperson for community demands that were not represented in the official negotiations.

Du Toit, Swarts and Teuteberg (2016) attribute contemporary protests and South Africa's attempts to contain them to the fact that the 1996 Constitution was designed as a constitutional contract or compromise, a temporary solution that could be renegotiated at any time. They describe the social contract underlying the South African nation as extremely precarious, precisely because it resulted from negotiations that were experienced differently by the opposing sides. The case of the RLMCP, however, suggests that it was precisely the contractual nature of democracy that enabled dialogue between the parties. Du Toit, Swarts and Teuteberg discuss the ongoing necessity of "renegotiating the peace", which is to say the necessity for political powers to debate and agree to an interpretation of the more complex passages of the constitution. And yet, it is precisely the ambiguity that arises from this flexibility of interpretation that keeps social tensions in the sphere of everyday politics, preventing them from escalating into violent conflict. It is through confrontations such as those circulating the RLMCP that the guidelines for democracy are devised and consolidated. Public debate and dialogue over controversial issues allow for shared interpretations to be collectively reached, rather than the responsibility of disentangling the contradictions of the political system falling to individuals.

Part Three. Inhabitation and Defence: Appropriation and citizenship

The RLMCP project came up against the problematics of inhabitation in two ways: part of the project aimed to build new houses, and many of the residents' protests leading up to the occupation of the cultural centre were over housing. The organisers saw inhabitation as a collection of practices that were intimately connected to the formation of society and the exercise of citizenship. They thought it necessary for the residents to take ownership of new ways of living in the township, both through improving their material living conditions and through rethinking the shape of community relations. The RLMCP project understood citizenship primarily as a sense of "civic duty", as appropriating a series of rules and beliefs that were conducive to harmonious relationships between citizens and with the state. Citizenship, however, goes beyond a sense of civic duty. Being a citizen in Red Location was constituted by a wide range of appropriations related to inhabitation and occupation that went beyond basic survival in a place and also included the desire to make that place correspond more appropriately to the inhabitants' understandings of wellbeing. Discussion of ownership and appropriation should not neglect to look beyond the borders of the RLMCP and consider how the citizens of the location would make the space they lived in more appropriate to their everyday needs and worldviews.

The verb "to inhabit" is closely linked to practices of appropriation. The original meaning of "to inhabit", can be traced to the Latin "habere", to hold or to have. Inhabitation in Red Location can be connected to the "politics of presence" (Phillips 1995), to a continued "being there". Anne Phillips makes a distinction between the "politics of presence" and the "politics of ideas". She argues that in the "politics of ideas", accountability is demanded of policies and political programmes and that factors such as gender, race, etc. are considered of secondary importance. In the "politics of presence", on the other hand, political legitimacy derives from the identities of representatives, and so "accountability" rests in characteristics such as gender, ethnicity and belonging to minority groups (Phillips 1995). In "Give a man a fish" (2015), James Ferguson advances the discussion on the politics of presence to conceptualise presence as a form of legitimacy. Starting with an anthropological example of a hunter sharing the meat from his prey, Ferguson discusses a type of

resource distribution which centres around the aggressive demands of those who are understood to be the legitimate recipients of shares. He specifies, “such sharing is [...] based on [... the] ‘presence’ [of...] whoever is there” (Ferguson quoting Widlok 2015: 214). Bayat, however, describes the “art of presence” as oppressed or marginalised individuals’ readiness, responsiveness and resilience (2010). By the “politics of presence”, I do not refer only to physical presence and visibility, but also an extreme form of deliberative democracy in which everyone represents an extremely reduced sphere of interests. Being there, feeling and being involved, being nearby, being on the ground and present at the moment of the decision, being a witness and being in the right place are key conditions for understanding and continuing to assert a right to ownership. Inhabitation, or being a consistent presence in a place, is both the premise and the means of legitimising demands for recognition and redistribution.

Chandra Mohanty offers an eminently political definition of housing and domestic space, articulating the concepts of home, community and identity as centres around which individual experiences, political choices, solidarity, alliances and friendships are formed (Mohanty 2003). In Red Location, it was only those who lived there and were constantly visible who were authorised to participate in decisions that shaped politics, established roles, instigated changes and inspired collective actions. Presence and proximity also implied priority. Being listed as a beneficiary a prerequisite for getting a house and being registered with the ward councillor as unemployed increased the chances of getting a job.

Defence implies the upkeep, protection or custodianship of something considered important. It is also an action with strong territorial connotations. The occupation of the RLMCP demonstrates that the residents of Red Location did more than struggle to protect their property and safety, though this can also undoubtedly be related to defence. Defence encompasses various appropriations of physical and symbolic space; it can be an act of seizing ownership and preventing others’ reappropriations; and it relies on presence and visibility. Thinking through defence is to think simultaneously through preservation, protection and dispossession.

Red Location evidences three sorts of defence: temporal, spatial and moral. The first can be linked to the efforts to preserve, reconstruct and lay claim to the township’s memory. The second can be seen in attempts to reduce crime through repurposing public spaces as social places, transforming space through flexible

processes of combination and substitution. Efforts to regenerate the township's morality can be attributed to the final category: defending value systems through creating and protecting spaces of emancipation and refuge. The prioritisation of change on an individual, moral level over changes on a material level demonstrates the extreme difficulty of transforming the geography of segregation and explains the subsequent recourse to alternative strategies for improving socioeconomic conditions. The effort to make the township inhabitable through strengthening social relations based on the principles of solidarity, mutual aid and interconnection recalls Simone's description of "people as infrastructure". Simone highlights how strengthened collaboration, even if it is temporary and volatile, contributes to the reproduction of a city made from relations and words rather than individuals (Simone 2004).

The many forms of appropriation connected to inhabitation and occupation reveal the limits of policies and urban planning which rely on simplistic ideas about township citizens, whether these be past stereotypes of the townships as exclusively Black and working-class, or present-day assumptions that all inhabitants are disadvantaged and poor. Liberal South Africa has no conceptual room for the multi-faceted citizen who eschews racial and social categorisations, who claims not to need the state and its institutions but rather demands to be recognised as an integral, foundational part of it.¹⁸⁵

Through legal or illegal practices, legitimate or illicit appropriations, the residents destroyed the assumption that a good citizen is someone who follows the state's rules. Instead, they advanced a conceptualisation of citizenship that views the citizen as someone who takes ownership of everyday life, establishes customs and through this, forms the city.

Appropriation practices can also be acts or practices of citizenship. The residents were situated between "being citizens" and "acting as citizens" (D'Amico 2009). That is, they demonstrated the passage from "a model of relations based on *citizenship* (having rights and responsibilities as members of a given community) to a model of relations based on *citizenry* (exercising and actively defending those rights)"

¹⁸⁵ This demand echoes Baldwin's description of being an American citizen during the years of desegregation: "I am not a ward of America. I'm not an object of missionary charity. I'm one of the people who built the country". J. Baldwin, debate with William F. Buckley, 1965, Cambridge University.

(La Bella and Santoro 2011: 20). The task of politics then became that of enabling, facilitating and supporting the appropriation of inhabited places according to three guiding principles: recognition, validation and redistribution.

7. Bread, butter...and roses

“Bread and roses” or “bread and butter”? “Bread and Roses” is the title of a poem written by James Oppenheim in 1911, inspired by American trade unionist Rose Schneiderman’s phrase “the worker must have bread, but she must have roses too”, which then became a famous protest song widely associated with trade unions. The slogan and the song both refer to the idea that workers are entitled to more than basic survival. “Bread and butter”, on the other hand, is used to refer to a staple, something simple, of subsistence. The history of Red Location residents’ protests marks a transition from demands for “bread and butter” material needs, to demands for something closer to “roses”, for the redistribution of resources and equal social status – that is, for recognition as full citizens.

A statement from Abahlali baseMjondolo, a movement of shack dwellers fighting for the right to housing that initially started in Durban and is now widespread throughout South Africa, reads: “We do not only struggle to occupy land. We also struggle to occupy space in the media, in universities and in important debates [...]. We have occupied. We have resisted. Now is the time to develop”.¹⁸⁶ A similar trajectory can be observed in Red Location, albeit in a less prominent and mediated manner. The transition from demands for housing to demands for occupation, justice and the right to contribute to the township’s political agenda has been characterised by repeated attempts at appropriation. Over the course of the protests, the residents developed increasingly broad knowledge and skills, while also trying to grow their power and influence in several specific areas. The residents’ trajectory intersects with that of officials and politicians, who in turn tried to appropriate the protests and steer the location’s development.

The protests in Red Location following the announcement of plans to build the RLMCP centred around repairs to several social housing units built in the early 1990s and demanded greater transparency about the housing allocation processes. The

¹⁸⁶ Abahlali baseMjondolo Press Statement, *Occupy, resist, develop*, 18/12/2015.

transition from these demands to demands for recognition occurred through gradual processes of learning about, utilising and consolidating the types of appropriation that had already gained the residents greater equality with their counterparts. The occupation of the RLMCP was a key action in the transition from basic demands for access to services, to demands for the equal right to influence change in the township.¹⁸⁷ The housing protests, however, did not constitute a united front of residents against local government. The residents did not come to define a collective identity or form a movement, or they simply did not consider this a particularly interesting option. Rather, the conflict proceeded in fits and starts and by trial and error; the exercise of citizenship was above all a form of constant negotiation.

Reaching to an agreement could have led to the leading activists retreating into the private sphere or being politically co-opted. But on the contrary, it was the RLSC's capacity for resistance, rather than the outcome of the protests, that served and will continue to serve as an important precedent, enriching the residents' "repertoire of enunciation", the collection of codes and practices available for drawing upon in political action (Bayart 1985). Bayart highlights how the strategies and tactics used by subordinate groups do not belong to them exclusively, but on the contrary can be appropriated in both directions, upwards and downwards. This was particularly evident in the actions that developed around the RLMCP, in particular in the gradual convergence of different groups with shared codes and *arts de faire* (Bayart 1985).

1. Housing Politics in South Africa and Red Location: from the demand to the need for housing

The entire history of Red Location can be told through the history of housing. Fundamental questions of the creation, transformation, segregation, desegregation and development of the location revolve around housing. When the residents' occupation of RLMCP to demand the restoration of several social housing units was seen as an impulsive, improvised and unexpected collective action but in reality, housing issues and protests over the right to housing have informed political activism in the location at least since the 1990s. In fact, housing issues also propelled protests

¹⁸⁷ This certainly falls under the "right to the city" (Harvey 2008), though it was not informed by long-term goals but propelled by a constant and resolute sense of urgency.

in the 1980s; one of the central disputes of PEBCO was rent hikes. Rent strikes were also one of the principal tactics used by anti-apartheid movements. Actions in the 1980s over the right to adequate housing also led to extended citizenship rights: the work of PEBCO, for example, started from inadequate responses to unmet basic needs, and ultimately developed to focus on socioeconomic inequality and the partial citizenship of the oppressed (Cherry and Gibbs 2007).

The right to adequate housing, to a stable home that could be adapted as desired, is inextricably connected to the right to the city. Makhulu identifies a strong continuity in South Africa between “making home and claiming citizenship” (Makhulu 2015) and discusses the emergence of the “politics of home” as both affective and material. She details how the domestic sphere became a terrain of struggle because of the spatial nature of segregation, migration controls and forced expulsions. Analysing the everyday practices of several informal settlements in Cape Town, Makhulu writes, “these practices not only serve to overcome conditions of material deprivation but at the same time enable actors to claim belonging and recognition or [...] a mode of citizenship” (Makhulu 2015: 11, citing Holston 1999). Fighting for the right to housing also entails developing knowledge of various levels of government and the responsibilities and authorities of various institutions since housing policies in South Africa are dispersed across national, provincial and local levels (and then further fragmented on Municipal and ward levels).

Housing protests in Red Location have a longer history than the conception and construction of the RLMCP. In the 1980s, residents battled against forced transfers to Motherwell and in the 1990s before the formal end of apartheid, housing became the primary source of tensions between residents and institutional representatives. For this reason, the RLMCP should be analysed alongside policies on housing and urban regeneration: it was not just that outcomes in these sectors were co-dependent, but also that interventions in these areas were in dialogue with and strengthened each other. The RLMCP organisers were almost obliged to include a part of the project that focused explicitly on housing – the experimental PELIP housing project. PELIP houses already existed beside the museum but on a very limited scale. Demands for improved living conditions pre-existed the project but experienced a strong resurgence following the announcement of the allocation of public funds to develop the museum. Generally speaking, housing policies were the post-apartheid government’s greatest

promise: after the right to freedom, the right to a home was almost the archetypal measure of human rights. Through promising to build new social housing, the project targeted both the residents and business in a masterfully humanising interpretation of neoliberalism: improvements to the township's aesthetics, security and functionality would have improved the citizens' quality of life and simultaneously attracted investments, eventually fostering business and encouraging innovative economies – first and foremost the knowledge economy. Various residents' committees from the 1990s to the present-day have dismantled this logic, working backwards towards decisions and discussions to scrutinise the relationship between development policies and the outcomes forecast by organisers and politicians. The residents' protests were not part of broader anti-establishment movements but rather aimed at enabling inclusion. The home, which in South Africa symbolises individual dignity and worth as a citizen and a person, was the focal point of this confrontation.

From the 1990s to the present-day, housing policies have transitioned from a reliance on a conception of housing as a 'demand' (implicitly for satisfaction) to a conception of housing as a 'need' (with satisfaction being much less salient), making housing an ambivalent and slippery terrain. It was the South African constitution itself that prompted this transition. The right to housing is perhaps the only socioeconomic right not to be subject to the "transformative constitutionalism" that Klare describes as the long-term project of interpreting, applying and strengthening constitutional laws with the aim of triggering social change through legal processes. Unlike other economic rights qualified in the constitution by expressions such as "progressive realisation", "available resources" and "reasonable legislative measures" (Williams 2014), the right to housing is constitutionally guaranteed.

Article 26 of the 1996 Constitution contains three clauses relating to the right to housing: (1) Everyone has the right to have access to adequate housing; (2) The state must take reasonable legislative and other measures, within its available resources, to achieve the progressive realisation of this right; (3) No one may be evicted from their home, or have their home demolished, without an order of court made after considering all the relevant circumstances. No legislation may permit arbitrary evictions. Several verdicts, such as the Constitutional Court's in *Government of the Republic of South Africa v. Grootboom*, added further qualifications regarding

the application of these clauses – the State was obliged to find housing solutions for citizens with special needs and there was a negative obligation on the State and all other entities to desist from preventing or impairing the right of access to adequate housing. It was later also ruled that the State must mediate between tenants and landlords in cases of contention, a process described as “meaningful engagement”, including respect for the residents’ dignity.

In reality, the right to housing is not absolute, that is, “the Constitution does not oblige the government to put a roof over the head of every citizen” (Wertman 2015: 725). It is, rather, the right to “access” housing. Wertman notes that although the ANC proposed the inclusion of socio-economic rights in the Constitution, the party was rather cautious when it came to the judicial power to enforce these rights, assuming that this would fall to the legislature and the executive. The right to housing is without a doubt central in post-apartheid South Africa, starkly contrasted to the traumas and violations of the apartheid government’s forced evictions that caused the disappearance of entire districts and the dispersal of communities. Forced evictions are seen as the most widespread way in which the police force violated human rights and as a particularly violent form of oppression affecting entire families, causing not only the loss of personal belongings but also undisputable displacement, an incurable wound lasting for generations.

The *South End Museum* in Port Elizabeth, following in the footsteps of the *District Six Museum* in Cape Town, was built to heal the open wound caused by the violent demolition of the South End district in the city centre: the museum houses photographs, documents and a reconstruction of an entire house. To this day, families in New Brighton can quickly point out where their ancestors came from – often districts that are no longer there or that have been rebuilt, whose names are still used in everyday speech. Memory of eviction is inscribed in the urban fabric: the demolition of entire districts in the city centre coincided with the building of new townships in the peripheries, whose inhabitants shared a history of dispossession.

It is therefore necessary to analyse constitutional laws on the right to housing in relation to the open wound that still afflicts South African citizens of all races. The inclusion of these laws in the Constitution represents a guarantee that the past will

not be repeated¹⁸⁸ and promises to protect a right to property acquired through consistent use rather than legal process.

Housing played such a central role in the new South Africa that the South African government prioritised the right to housing over the promulgation of the Constitution itself: the first policy document on housing, the Housing White Paper, dates to 1994. The white paper established various new policies regarding the construction and allocation of social housing and was accompanied by the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP), a programme that brought in a series of socioeconomic development measures. In the RDP, the government set the goal of building 300,000 houses in the five years to follow. In 1997, the Housing Act declared that all levels of government, from the local to the national level, had to encourage construction and development and maintain socially and economically adequate communities with safe and healthy living conditions, eradicating the reality and potential for slums.

In 2009, the White paper on the Policy Context of the National Housing Code added further policies in the housing sector. Indeed, between 2004 and 2009, the government launched the Breaking New Grounds Policy Framework (BNG) with the goal of building “sustainable human settlements”, districts of high-quality houses (which implied the demolition of the informal settlements of *shack dwellers*). The BNG also signalled a change from projects focused entirely on development and that prioritised the number of houses built over the preferences and diversity of beneficiaries to Municipal projects that paid more attention to the beneficiaries. With the beginnings of the global economic crisis in 2007, but also due to the increasing population and unemployment rates, the rate of construction slowed, and the size of the houses built was reduced.¹⁸⁹ The scarcity of public funds together with ever

¹⁸⁸ In reality, *shack dwellers* living in informal settlements are still today subjected to forced displacement and evicted to highly surveilled transit camps with extremely adverse living conditions. See R. Pithouse, *The transit camp is a form of social control*, accessible at www.abahlali.org.

¹⁸⁹ From 1994 to 2000, the annual number of new houses rose from 20,000 in 1994 to 200,000 in 2000. From 2006 to 2009, there was a large decrease from 250,000 new houses in 2006 to 150,000 in 2009. In 2010-2012 the number of new builds fell further to 88,441 in 2012. See Fiscal and Financial Commission, *Exploring alternative finance and policy options for effective and sustainable delivery of housing in South Africa*, 2013. Africacheck, a factchecking website, warns about the accuracy of these statistics: the criteria that the Ministry uses to define a “housing unit” are unclear, see <<https://africacheck.org/reports/minister-sisulu-is-right-sas-housing-delivery-has-almost-halved-since-200607/>>.

growing demand pushed the government to establish contracts with private companies and foundations.

Gradually, however, housing construction went from being prioritised as one of the critical signs of development and an indicator of the effectiveness of public socio-economic policy to become one intervention among many aimed at improving citizens' quality of life. From the early 2000s, the ANC government faced the challenge of reducing the housing backlog, the number of houses that still needed to be built to meet the goal of no South African citizen living in a shack. Despite the constant construction of social houses, however, the rising population rate and steady urbanisation made it extremely difficult to reduce the number of people living in informal or inadequate dwellings. Still today, 13.6% of South Africans live in an informal settlement¹⁹⁰ (in 1996 the number of South Africans living in a shack or similar was 16%).¹⁹¹ In April 2010, the government signed the "Delivery Agreement for Outcome 8: sustainable human settlements and improved quality of household life", an agreement that set a goal of redeveloping 400,000 informal dwellings in a good location, providing access to basic services and establishing the possibility of a property title by 2014.

2. Housing, corruption and protests in Red Location

The protests of Red Location residents touched an extremely sensitive nerve in South African politics. While on the one hand housing was related to rights, welfare and addressing inequality, on the other, the sector suffered from extreme corruption and excessive bureaucracy. It simultaneously symbolised post-apartheid policies and represented one of the worst failures of the public administration.

August-Sauls, a member of the Executive Council for Human Settlement, Safety and Liaison, a cabinet of the provincial government of the Eastern Cape, stated, "corruption in the Housing sector, manifesting in any form that robs people of their homes, is a counter-revolutionary act",¹⁹² accusing anyone who illegally profited off housing policies of betraying national values. And yet, engaging with the everyday

¹⁹⁰ Statistics South Africa (StatSA) defines an "informal settlement" as "an unplanned settlement on land which has not been surveyed or proclaimed as residential, consisting mainly of informal dwellings (shacks)". HDA (2012: 18).

¹⁹¹ StatSA, community census, 2016.

¹⁹² See <https://africacheck.org/factsheets/factsheet-the-housing-situation-in-south-africa/>.

politics of housing meant engaging with one of the least transparent aspects of welfare services.

Housing policies took an extremely long time to be approved and required coordination between multiple different departments and resources. They were thus particularly liable to budgetary trickery: a determined amount of money would be initially allocated to a particular project only to be splintered and rechannelled in various different directions. The involvement of multiple different stakeholders, including small and medium businesses, foundations etc., added a further complication, giving rise to countless types of corruption and embezzlement of public funds. In 2015, for example, the Department of Human Settlements in the Municipality of Port Elizabeth was dissolved and placed under external management because of repeated misconduct and inefficiency. Similarly, the publication of the Kabuso Report in 2011 revealed multiple cases of corruption involving the ex-mayor Faku and the construction of the RLMCP and the surrounding houses in Red Location.¹⁹³

The allocation of social housing also exposed an array of misconducts, ranging from the exchange of favours to the official abuse of power. In Red Location, officials appropriated basic necessities such as milk or mattresses that should have been made available to residents of informal settlements when they were moved into temporary accommodation pending a permanent move. The authors of the report “‘Jumping the Queue’, Waiting lists and Other Myths: Perceptions and Practices around Housing’ (2013),¹⁹⁴ however, indicated that the perception of the waiting list as a form of corruption is also due to fact that there is a sort of “myth” around the waiting list, provoked by administrators referring to attempts to “jump the queue” and the many protests of the residents referring to the order established by the waiting list. In reality, there was no one, infamous list, but several different lists corresponding to different types of allocation. For example, depending on whether someone was registered before or after 1994, or on which of the many programmes they were accessing housing through (the Emergency Housing Program, the Upgrading of Informal Settlements Program, the Social Housing Policy, the Community Residential Unit Program, etc.), their economic status, if there were any family members with special needs or vulnerabilities (such as elderly or disabled people, etc.), the amount

¹⁹³ See ‘Kabuso report, the full story and supporting documents’, *The Herald*, 25/01/2014.

¹⁹⁴ K. Tissington, N. Munshi, G. Mirugi-Mukundi and E. Durojaye (2013).

of time on the waiting list could be longer or shorter. The report, however, lays out how the issue of synchronising the lists was dealt with obscurely and inadequately, meaning citizens had to constantly try to keep up to date to understand the reasons why some people had been on the waiting list for decades.

In Red Location, embezzlement, misunderstanding and the lack of transparency in the housing sector were obvious even before the formal end of apartheid. The recent history of housing policies in Red Location can be dated back to 1990, when a project was launched to address the poor state of many buildings and build 436 new houses (this first phase was called “phase 1”). The provincial government allocated 23 million rand for the reconstruction of Masangwanaville, an area north of what is today the RLMCP. By 1993, however, only half of the phase 1 houses had been built (that is, 218 houses with asbestos roofing, two bedrooms, a kitchen and a bathroom).¹⁹⁵ In the same year, the National Housing Commission allocated 11 million rand for building 396 houses (phase 2) with around 500 more to follow (phase 3).¹⁹⁶

In 1994, following various protests from PEBCO and the recently formed Red Location Area Committee, a committee created with the aim of representing the beneficiaries of Masangwanaville, another 10.4 million rand were allocated to complete phase 1 of the project. A year later, however, the residents protested that the funding had never actually reached the township.¹⁹⁷ In 1996, a group of residents brought together as Community Based Partners (CBP), a platform connected to the ANC, threatened a new sit-in in front of the headquarters of the provincial government, which then led to a series of meetings with provincial and local level representatives. These talks were brought to a halt with the Municipality’s unliteral decision to reduce the funding allocated for Masangwanaville to 6 million rand, a decision that impacted the size of the houses – they would now have two rooms rather than four. The residents of the CBP met this announcement with further protests, until Mayor Faku committed to reopening discussions between representatives of the residents, local and provincial government.¹⁹⁸

¹⁹⁵ Post Reporter, ‘People are Living here’, *The Herald*, 03/01/1993.

¹⁹⁶ M. Mabusela, ‘R 11.7 million upgrading for Red Location’, *The Herald*, 09/02/1993.

¹⁹⁷ J. Matyu, ‘Call to look for missing millions’, *The Herald*, 20/10/1995.

¹⁹⁸ Municipal reporter, ‘Draft on housing policy wanted’, *The Herald*, 06/03/1996.

Following these last agreements, phase 2 became an experimental project in which the community (in reality, the CBP) worked to provide the manual labour for the construction of the houses, while the implementation of the project fell under the responsibility of the Municipality of Port Elizabeth. The local employees hired to build the houses should have received technical training, thanks to fifty internships funded by the Department of Labour. The residents oversaw the list of beneficiaries, prioritising families with a monthly income of less than 800 rand, and signed a contract with all the families involved. The first fifteen houses built should have had a floorspace of 50m². The building plans were approved in the lead up to Mandela's visit to the township.¹⁹⁹

The idea to build the RLMCP therefore took form while the housing project in Masangwanaville dragged on and the inhabitants started to doubt the Municipality's reliability. A year after the national competition for the RLMCP contract, the PELIP housing project was also launched in 1999.²⁰⁰

During the Swedish prime minister Göran Persson's visit to Red Location to inaugurate the PELIP houses, a group of Red Location inhabitants protested against the details of a list of recipients for the new housing projects in the area: "a sixty-year old woman who has lived in Red Location for her whole life said that some newcomers and young people are getting houses before them".²⁰¹ The construction works on the museum also led to the displacement of several families who had built their houses in the area, despite the claims of the architect Rushmere that it was "an empty piece of land".

In 2001, several families who were made to move from the area around the museum's building site and who had therefore been forced into a precarious position on the waiting list for new houses, came together to form the New Brighton Concern Residents' Group (NBCRG). The NBCRG wrote letters to local and provincial government and, receiving no response, protested at the museum building site. One of their principal demands was clarification over the way in which the funding allocated for building social housing was being spent. Following repeated protests in 2003, twenty-six people were arrested for protesting in front of the museum, charged with violation

¹⁹⁹ T. Dlula, 'Red Location get ready for Madiba visit', *The Herald*, 20/03/1997.

²⁰⁰ See Chapter 3.

²⁰¹ S. Mangxamba, 'Swedish leader visits city's oldest township', *The Herald*, 23/11/1999.

of property. The arrests, heavily criticised as an “apartheid-like” measure, was a double-edged sword for the Municipality. After this incident the police never intervened again in the space of the RLMCP.

In the face of intensifying protests and accusations from inhabitants against officials, the Independent Mediation Service of the Eastern Cape (IMSEC) charged the lawyer Luvuyo Bono to mediate between the residents and the Municipality. In the final report, the lawyer recommended the creation of a commission of inquiry to investigate potential transgressions in the allocation of social housing and the list of recipients. Tasked with responding to these transgressions was the Branch Executive Committee (BEC), the local ANC delegation directed by both the ward councillor and the Housing Committee (a group of citizens appointed on an ad hoc basis to implement social housing projects). Although at first the BEC missed the meetings organised by Bono, BEC members were called on several times and the lawyer’s final report warned of serious transgressions, validating the residents’ accusations and suspicions.²⁰² Bono set a date for building works on the houses to restart, September 2003, even though the construction site had not yet reopened. In October, several members of the NBCR marched to the office of ward councillor Jimmy Tutu with a bucket of human waste and emptied it in the office in protest against the perpetual delays.

In November 2003, another project was launched for the construction of 339 houses, but the “historic” residents of Red Location protested because the houses were allocated to newcomers, bypassing families who had lived there for decades and had been forced to move because of the terrible conditions of their houses: “we were born and raised in this place. Our ancestors have lived here for decades and this land was given to us, but now newcomers are being given houses built on our land”.²⁰³ Initially, the residents refused to move to make space for the museum, but gradually

²⁰² The lawyer’s report stated that the Housing Committee had taken on an enormous power to arbitrarily add or remove people from the list of recipients. The document therefore recommended a review of the lists, along with the composition of the Housing Committee, and openly stressed the excessive power of the BEC. It went so far as to advocate for a rethinking of presence of BEC members in all committees overseeing development in the location, given the degree of power and influence that they wielded (IMSEC 2003).

²⁰³ Makina, cited in J. Mawande, ‘Many disenchant former residents claim, “new people”, are being allocated houses which they should get’, *The Herald*, 2006. In the same article, Jimmy Tutu, councillor of ward 15, stated, “people who say that they are the original inhabitants of Red Location, who left the area years ago, are returning to ask for these houses and protesting because we’re giving houses to newcomers”.

agreed rather reluctantly to be placed in Lwandlekazi High School in Wells Estate, an area in the North of the city, rather faraway from Red Location, and in a temporary area next to the location. In 2005, 338 houses were built, costing 11.2 million rand. And yet, new protests from the residents, again emptying buckets of human waste outside the museum, recentred attention on the topic of recipient lists and the fact that the new houses did not meet minimum quality and security standards.

In 2006, the year the museum opened, the NMBM launched another social housing project aimed at Masangwanaville, Malakane, Mhlaba eBoast Crescent and Silvertown, valued at 11.8 million rand. While the residents' protests abated between 2007 and 2008, in 2009 they came back with a vengeance. The reason for this was that 150 families placed in informal accommodation or dilapidated houses had to move, 40 of them to make space for the art gallery and library. The residents, including several elderly individuals, did not want a repeat of 2003, when people who had been forced to move had to live in precarious accommodation for months, and so they refused to move until the new houses had been built.²⁰⁴ The residents were unwilling to dismantle and rebuild their shacks on a plot of land that had been marked out by the Municipality without services, running water and sewerage (the Municipality promised to equip the plot, but only after the residents moved). In a public meeting, Riordan promised to build 210 flats in two-storey houses. The Municipal spokesperson, Baron, claimed, "we don't want to deprive people of their rights, we want to move them to a new and better place".²⁰⁵

In early 2013, a new residents' group formed, the Red Location Steering Committee (RLSC), claiming to be the continuation of the group who had carried forward the 2009 protests.²⁰⁶ The RLSC's primary aim was to force local government to take responsibility for restoring the houses built in phase 2 which were in a critical state, some of them being genuinely uninhabitable. After several meetings with local ANC representatives and a meeting announcing a project to build a football pitch to the north, near the new houses, in October the RLSC forced the closure of the museum and the other already completed buildings and halted building works on the cultural centre, in an attempt to draw attention to the need to prioritise renovating the phase

²⁰⁴ Interview 02/11/2015.

²⁰⁵ Kupido cited in 'Removals hunt museum upgrade', Lee Ann Buffer, *The Herald*, 01/06/2009.

²⁰⁶ Interview 11/05/2015.

2 houses. The residents protested in front of the museum, insisting that the funding for regenerating Singaphi street, the main road leading to the museum, should have been spent on repairing their houses.

In 2014, several Red Location residents, guided by the RLSC, protested yet again in front of the Municipality against Mayor Filha's broken promises. In November 2014, the provincial government had approved 32 million rand to rebuild the phase 2 houses. The building works were to start a month later, but the RLSC spokesperson made it known that the residents opposed the construction of 40m² houses, rather than the promised 47m². A further problem was the type of houses to be renovated: there were 376 houses in need of rebuilding, rather than the 288 that the Municipality suggested. That is, there were 88 houses that had been previously extended by their individual owners that the Municipality had not initially counted.²⁰⁷ There is still to this day controversy over these houses.

In June 2015, the rebuilding of the 288 phase 2 houses had actually started, but a month later, the RLSC asked for one of the building companies contracted on the project to be replaced because they were working very slowly and producing poor-quality houses.²⁰⁸ In August, the building companies closed for several weeks as they had not been paid by the provincial government as previously agreed.

When the works started up again in October and continued until May 2016, the RLSC was persuaded to hand the keys to the museum and the cultural complex back over to the mayor, though not all residents agreed with this decision. For example, those who had had to move to make space for the museum and had not been given a satisfactory response as to the drawing up of lists of recipients disagreed, as did the phase 2 residents who had extended their houses and were still embroiled in negotiations with the Municipality. On the handing over of the keys to the mayor, a RLSC member commented, "we are giving back the keys, but somebody else will close the museum again".²⁰⁹

²⁰⁷ Interview 03/11/2015.

²⁰⁸ Interview 03/11/2015.

²⁰⁹ Telephone conversation, May 2016.

3. Negotiating the right to decent housing

In the townships, the right to decent housing was therefore constantly negotiated, taking a huge amount of time and tireless activism from the citizens, requiring the ability to balance administrative procedures and illegal activities and navigate municipal, provincial and national policies. Events in Red Location, as several municipal officers clarified during interviews, were not the exception but the norm. Being on the waiting list for social housing for ten or fifteen years was not particularly unusual; in fact, one of the interviewees noted that the tensions the project stirred up between the citizens and the Municipality worked in the favour of Red Location citizens, moving them up the policy agenda.²¹⁰

Social housing policies were very competitive. It was not only necessary to make sure that one's own neighbourhood or street was prioritised in the Municipality's development projects, but it was also necessary to try to maintain that priority to avoid delays, suspensions and diversion of funds. Faced with houses that were falling to pieces, it was not enough to wait one's turn; the speed of the project was critical and it was important to be considered first. Further, in order to get the older social houses renovated, it was necessary to be prioritised over those on the waiting list for new houses by emphasising the levels of need and poverty.

There was also competition among the residents of the location themselves, as the length of time lived in the location did not always correspond with being prioritising on the housing list. Further, there were many cases in which the same family managed to register on two separate lists, in two separate areas of the city. It also occurred that recipients of houses would rent them to other people, such as newcomers to the area. Housing policies divided residents into old and new inhabitants, between "people who are from here" and "people who are not from here". The latter group were not only people who had lived elsewhere and then moved, or those who had managed to register on the social housing waiting list while living elsewhere, but also those who weren't often seen or didn't often show themselves: "I've never seen him around" was one of the ways in which distance and otherness were expressed. The common perception of who was entitled to housing was just as complex as the definition of "housing rights" itself: it was proportional to how much

²¹⁰ Interview 04/11/2015.

an individual was understood to belong to a place, embedded in specific social networks, and was also connected to age (elderly people awaiting housing allocations and living in decrepit houses were seen as the most unfortunate in Red Location). This is very similar to the dynamic identified by Elias and Scotson in Wiston Parva (Elias and Scotson 1994), but with the difference that in Red Location “newcomers” did not so easily accept the position of “outsiders”. Tando Msikinya, one of these “newcomers” expressed in no uncertain terms, “[elderly residents] demand that Red Location is theirs, but I believe that a property deed is needed to make such a claim”.²¹¹

Housing rights involved the individual and their belongings, but also their relationships with those who lived nearby and faced the same problems, with public bodies, bureaucracy, the justice system, the local police force, etc. Negotiating the right to housing therefore meant manoeuvring on multiple levels simultaneously and confronting various different codes and political practices. In other words, the right to housing and housing policies triggered various and contradictory appropriation trajectories.

The accounts of multiple residents make it clear how knowledge of housing problems and development projects in the township developed gradually, hand in hand with involvement in the protests, which sometimes happened almost by coincidence. One of the leaders of the RLSC explained how his involvement in the protest started when he was acting as the secretary of a local football team and had gone to a meeting inside the museum about, among other topics, the relocation of the football pitch. As the football club opposed the designers’ proposals, this resident acted as spokesperson for several concerns about the project that later converged in the criticisms advanced by the inhabitants of phase 2. This resident, who was already involved in various social activities (he was also a church minister, as well as the secretary of the football team), explained how he himself was astonished by the role he gradually found himself playing, having never previously been particularly politically active.²¹²

Successful actions would often be repeated, even by different residents’ committees and at a distance of several years. These actions therefore solidified into

²¹¹ Tando Msikinya cited in M. Ndamase, ‘New Brighton RDP houses feud boiling over’, *The Herald*, 07/02/2013.

²¹² Interview 03/11/2015.

collective practices and codes that were legible to all participants in the conflict. Analysis of the evolution of the protests reveals a genuine learning curve. Learning, too, can be a form of appropriation, an assimilation of knowledge and understanding and the skills to apply this knowledge for one's own purposes. The history of the protests is a history of trial and error. While some actions entered into the political vocabulary, others were abandoned or not repeated. In addition to the long experience of protest on a local level, the practices through which the inhabitants of Red Location appropriated the conflict, came to know it, direct it, subdue or provoke it at will, were borrowed by other service delivery protests across South Africa. In Port Elizabeth in 2015, for example, while in Red Location the inhabitants' occupation of the museum was underway, the residents of Helenvale, Booysens Park and Jacksonville, united in the Northern Areas Forum, forced the closure of around twenty schools and blocked highways by burning tyres in the middle of the road in protest against a lack of schoolteachers and a poor quality of education. Police intervention and the residents' response to it gave rise to all-out urban warfare that lasted for several days. In Walmer, the residents protested in a similar manner, with roadblocks and also throwing stones at cars, to draw attention to the gravity of social housing problems. What made Red Location unique, aside from the repetition of protests over the course of twenty years, was that the recourse to violence became increasingly infrequent (albeit not absent) and that protesters instead used various methods that were legal, or at least considered legitimate, in their orchestration of citizenship practices.

4. The Politics of Presence

The residents' accounts suggest how important it was to be physically present, not only for the occupation, but above all for when decisions were made, not necessarily to speak and make your voice heard, but also just to listen. It was not always necessary to be part of a group; you could rely on a trusted person to pass on information. Interviewees, however, stressed the importance of seeing something with one's own eyes, to the information gleaned from facial expressions, to knowing who was with who, to noticing what was happening behind the scenes or on the quiet. Committee members would also be alerted when there was something suspicious going on

around the cultural centre. One of them forcefully stressed that when an RLMCP employee wanted to enter the buildings, for example for security checks, they had to be accompanied by someone from the committee.²¹³

Being present meant being visible. When a committee member came with me to visit the houses that had caused the protests, many inhabitants came out onto the street to greet us, and the RLSC representative approached them to ask if there was anything else wrong or broken. The representative knew almost everyone, especially the elderly residents, and many seemed to know him.

Visibility also guaranteed transparency, as opposed to the occult secrecy dividing communities. Assemblies were held outside the museum. A loudspeaker would announce committee meetings or, for more sensitive matters, messages would be passed from door to door. Attendees sat in a circle, visible to everyone, yet only those more involved would get any closer, out of a sort of paradoxical combination of respect for intimacy and fear that groups, crowds, could be dangerous. The presence of large numbers of people on the street was often accompanied by a strong sense of danger, probably a hangover from the riots of the eighties but also fuelled by contemporary protests. Crowds multiply the politics of presence, when many people came together it would draw attention of the media and politicians.

As presence was so critical, its opposite, absence, took on a negative value. Just as the absence of key family members from private events is only permitted by extreme circumstances, the absence from public events was condemned. As public transport was not always financially or logistically accessible, this didn't apply so much to the residents as to politicians and other officials or building managers. Being absent meant being invisible. Similarly, one of the primary reasons for conflict with the ward councillor or local politicians was when committee members were not informed of or invited to meetings in which the future of the project was being discussed. If inviting someone to these meetings was equivalent to acknowledging them, desiring their absence meant disregarding or belittling their importance. In meetings, particular importance was placed on introducing strangers: strangers were formally introduced by the meeting facilitator, and only after they had been invited to

²¹³ Interview 03/11/2015.

speak could they introduce themselves. This practice is also related to acknowledging the presence of an unknown person, even recognising them as a person.

Reconstructing the actions of local and provincial government with regards to social housing in Red Location and the residents' response to this is a challenging task. Comparing oral sources, documents held by the residents and the Municipality and newspaper articles cannot satisfactorily elucidate the complexity of the various stages. The main problem is that every time the residents protested, this was always followed by a declaration of intent from the authorities, or at least the announcement of further funds to be allocated for building new houses. Declarations and announcements, however, did not mean that expectations were subsequently met. Rather, they were purely discursive actions, mostly engineered to win time and push back the construction deadline to a vague point in the future. These declarations were another form of exercising the politics of presence.

Politicians often visited the site in response to protests and gave speeches in the community hall in New Brighton, rather than in the courtyard in front of the museum. Creating a period of waiting and trying to subdue dissent by claiming it was useless (as institutions were supposedly already working to resolve the problem) was a method of appropriating the issues raised by the residents and putting decision-making power into the hands of officials.

In the history of Red Location's housing, the strategy of making promises was used countless times: in 2009, Richard Baloyi, Minister of Public Service and Administration, accompanied by a parliamentary delegation and by members of the provincial ANC, visited Red Location and promised residents that the phase 2 houses would be rebuilt. In August 2009, Mayor Ben Filha visited Red Location and promised that by October the area earmarked for the new houses (for those who had been made to move to make way for the building works on the library and art gallery) would be equipped with basic services and that then construction works could start. In 2012, during a Christmas meeting with anti-apartheid veterans in New Brighton, the Minister for Housing, Lindile Sisulu also promised to deliver 300 houses to the inhabitants of Red Location by January 2013.

After the occupation of the museum in 2013, however, politicians visited much less frequently, and when they did, rather than these visits being big public events, they happened quietly, almost furtively. In contrast to the propaganda of public

promises, negotiations with the residents, the sign of losing political ground, took place on the quiet. While the buildings of the cultural centre were under occupation by the residents, successive mayors repeatedly made announcements that the museum would reopen and then the houses would be renovated, quoting timelines of two or three months or using periods of time such as school holidays as a reference. None of these timelines were actually adhered to. Members of the RLSC found the declaration of these mythical timelines hilarious, especially during electoral campaigns. They simply commented: “how can they open [the museum] if we are still here?”.²¹⁴

As time went on, however, the residents developed two practical approaches for effectively reappropriating political promises. The first consisted of the use of the promise as a mechanism to demand intervention: through letters, phone calls, visiting offices, speeches in public assemblies, politicians were reminded of and forced to honour the timelines they had promised. The second was more direct, consisting of holding the buildings that had already been built for ransom through occupation. “Ransom” is a fairly regularly used protest tactic in the townships. Usually, however, it refers to people, mostly ward councillors being held for ransom in their own offices or school staff in schools. In some cases, such actions have led to dramatic events or involved police intervention. Forcing buildings to close was also an established technique, but it was usually only a symbolic act lasting no longer than a few days. In Red Location these two protest practices were combined into an explicit strategy: the occupation was proportional to the number of days that the politicians let pass without taking any measures (RLSC members stressed multiple times that they occupied the buildings in exchange for the renovation of their houses and that once the renovation was complete, they would hand the buildings back over to the Municipality); the promises of institutional representatives therefore became an integral feature of the occupation. The occupation of the buildings went even further, providing a precedent for other discontented groups carrying out similar operations and above all taking the city leaders at their word when they promised that the RLMCP was a project for the township and its inhabitants. “The museum is ours”, the residents repeated in an open challenge to policymakers and project organisers. A

²¹⁴ Informal conversation with members of the RLSC, August–September 2015.

public official stated, “the community knows that the museum is its weapon: they are blackmailing the authorities because they know it’s a strategic project. They kidnap the museum, they use it in exchange of different demands because it’s their one!”.²¹⁵ The residents played on the ambiguity of a project that set out to both encourage development in the sectors of culture and tourism and to respond to local needs, but that failed to provide details as to how exactly it would achieve these objectives.

5. Hold it for ransom, don’t burn it down!

Rather than a conflict between two clearly distinct parties, developments around housing in Red Location can be better characterised as a multivocal dialogue between various stakeholders. As already illustrated, to properly understand these events it is necessary to abandon the idea that there was a sort of perpetual hostility between local politicians, public officials and residents. For example, one of the most active members of the RLSC was also the Community Liaison Officer (CLO) for the phase 2 housing project; in 2013 he had been nominated as a mediator for the Municipality, tasked with facilitating communication between the Municipality, the residents and the workers delivering the project on the ground. In Red Location it was possible to be involved in protests while still voting for the ANC, and to be a public official or a member of the museum’s staff and still understand and sympathise with the motivations of the residents. The proximity between different groups and the succession of various housing committees also led to transformations in RLSC tactics, leading to some members splintering off in disagreement. While protests until 2009 made use of a repertoire of tactics that took inspiration from anti-apartheid struggles (the bucket system, *toyi-toyi*,²¹⁶ etc.), the RLSC leadership later chose to renew protest strategies.

The residents did not describe the occupation of the RLMCP buildings as an act of violence, but, on the contrary, they viewed it as proof that they had no intentions of damaging them: “in the old times, we would have burnt everything!” (interview 28/05/2015). The choice to not burn the buildings down, in contrast to a practice that solidified in the 1980s (and is still today widely used in service delivery protests),

²¹⁵ Interview 06/11/2015.

²¹⁶ “*Toyi-toyi*” refers to a form of protest that originates in a tribal dance from Zimbabwe, and consists of singing and chanting slogans while stomping feet on the ground.

when the ANC proposed making the townships ungovernable and ousting every symbol of apartheid from the locations, recognised that the buildings ultimately belonged to the residents, and that the RLMCP project, once corrected, could effectively offer opportunities for growth and profit to the local community. The opinion that the museum could offer opportunities was fairly widespread throughout the course of the project and was not seen to be incompatible with the occupation of the buildings.

In his 2003 report, the lawyer Bono had explained that the residents' misinformation, caused by the failures of the Housing Committee, had caused a lot of frustration and discontent that exacerbated what in his view was a needless conflict:

A clear illustration of a perception problem is when the concerned group came in, guns-blazing on the museum and housing projects not continuing and the said committees stepping down, but after information was shared and some of the perceptions they had on these committees were tested [...] they had no problems with the current projects, in fact they were all for the projects to continue (IMSEC 2003).

Similarly, a member of the group who protested in 2013 declared, “[the museum] is our property; it is the pride of Red Location [...] for 15 years we have been staying in this dire situation. Our roofs are leaking. The houses are full of cracks and you can actually see someone pass in the streets”.²¹⁷ Several of the most prominent protesters seemed to suggest that had it not been for the perennial issue of housing they would not have protested against the museum.

The RLSC's decision to move away from violent tactics was not welcomed by all residents: some activists who had been involved in previous committees decided not to take part in the RLSC. While some maintained that the closure of the museum was counter-productive, others pressed for conflict escalation, advocating even for damage to the buildings if necessary: “I can burn the museum now”, an activist who was in total disagreement with the committee confided in me (interview 28/05/2015). Despite having demonstrated a great deal of autonomy and strong organisation, especially given their limited means, the RLSC had neither the power nor the desire to control the behaviour of all the residents, and although they proposed keeping the buildings intact, the representatives of the RLSC were not able to maintain

²¹⁷ Y. Sobuwa, 'Protests keep museum closed', *The Herald*, 25/10/2013.

total security in the buildings: between 2013 and 2016 there were multiple thefts, a security guard was murdered (under still uncertain circumstances) and some features of the buildings were seriously damaged.

Whether create a degree of distance from anti-apartheid protest tactics or on the contrary to assert their ongoing relevance, whether to justify or denounce repressive measures, in any South African conflict reference to the time of apartheid is one of the most commonly used rhetorical strategies for legitimating one's own actions and their impact. The spectres of apartheid and anti-apartheid struggle were also continually evoked in Red Location. Reparations for the oppression of apartheid was used as a justification for locating the project in Red Location, and housing policies, as previously outlined, were deeply rooted in post-apartheid citizenship reforms. Some of elements of the protests were also connected to apartheid oppression and control, or to the more alarming connotations of anti-apartheid struggle – chaos, the destruction of buildings, and institutional rebuttals. When the police intervened and arrested protesters, the residents accused the Municipality of using the same repressive measures as the apartheid governments had, and on the flip side, when the residents made use of more extreme protest tactics such as disrupting events and especially engaging in acts of violence against councillors (the bucket system, closing the offices, etc.), politicians would insist that apartheid had ended and that these tactics were unacceptable in a democracy. During a protest in 2014, the residents used the words and memory of anti-apartheid struggles: “New Brighton residents have threatened to ‘sabotage the city and make it ungovernable’”.²¹⁸ Gradually, a delicate balance was established between the residents and the Municipality: for their part, the residents, despite protesting and occupying the buildings, stressed how they had reached a sort of settlement with the institutions, since they could have irrevocably damaged the buildings or caused much more serious disruption according to the established forms of protest in the townships. The Municipality, for their part, did not escalate the conflict, but demonstrated their affinity with the community and presented themselves as an institution with a human side.

²¹⁸ Y. Sobuwa, ‘Housing protests grow’, *The Herald*, 03/03/2014.

The expression “to take justice into your own hands” refers to the act of taking individual responsibility for justice and seeking revenge. As time passed, the inhabitants of Red Location effectively appropriated or took ownership of justice in at least two, opposing ways. First, they decided to carry out illegal actions and resort to the use of force; and second, they continued to produce evidence that could prove legally useful, carefully maintaining a paper trail, with the potential need for legal recourse in mind. Sometimes they instigated legal actions, such as in 2003 when the lawyer Bono was tasked with investigating the residents’ accusations of corruption towards the Housing Committee. One woman proudly showed me a copy of a document detailing that she had been a victim of corruption in the housing sector that had been submitted to the Public Protector.²¹⁹ The same woman also kept a copy of the Bono report since her house had been judged safer than others, because the case was less publicly known.²²⁰ The residents repeatedly condemned corruption, demanding that institutions intervened to discharge and punish the perpetrators. To this day, not one of these accusations has been formally pursued.

Relationships with justice were ambivalent: having documents or verdicts to certify legitimacy was considered a fundamental way of holding institutions to account and insisting that they perform their role and resolve internal contradictions. Public bodies were not rejected but called upon to accept responsibility. At the same time, institutions could not be easily trusted: wrongdoings remained unpunished, waiting times were long, promises were broken. Illegal actions meant that the institutions were forced to take notice; they offered a fast track for mediation and intervention. Constituting an emergency was therefore used as a tactic for demanding justice.

²¹⁹ The woman, a previous Red Location resident, had had to move because she lived in one of the earliest houses built in Red Location that had caught fire. She was therefore waiting to be able to return to the social houses built in the place of the houses that had burnt down. No new accommodation was assigned to her, however, while families that had not previously lived in Red Location had got onto the waiting list and had received a house.

²²⁰ Several residents were extremely cautious when it came to keeping sensitive documents, because during apartheid police violation of private homes was a daily occurrence. I cannot say whether such caution is today justified, but it is very important to note how the practice of dispersing documents between various people so that multiple copies are maintained still occurs. Although some of the residents possess or know how to use a computer and some have smartphones, documents are mostly kept in hardcopy.

6. Mastering connections

At least in recent times, the mobile phone has become a crucial tool in the conflict over housing in Red Location: the notice pinned to the door of the museum instructed whoever wanted to enter the building to contact a member of the RLSC on their mobile, and the members of the committee always had their phone in hand. “Having someone’s contact” meant being able to talk with someone as an equal, whether they were the director of the museum or the Department of Human Settlements or delegates from the provincial government. Contacting and being contactable meant being connected, and being connected meant not having to find out about institutions’ decisions at public assemblies but instead being able to arrive already prepared with a decided strategy. Simone highlights how individuals who have to fight for survival in the city’s outskirts, such as kids working on the street, possess a meticulous attention to detail, since under circumstances of constant uncertainty and mistrust of strangers, accumulating even seemingly useless information (the butcher’s opening hours, who’s related to who, the price of bread or drugs) is a form of self-protection and enables increased opportunities for using one’s social network for advantage (Simone 2011). In Red Location and in the context of the protests around the RLMCP detailed knowledge was and continues to be one of the characterising skills of RLSC members.

As one of the members of the group clearly told me, “if you fight for something you need to be in control!” (interview 11/05/2015), that is, in a conflict it is necessary to have a greater familiarity with the terrain and groups involved than anyone else. Statements such as “even the councillor knows less than us! He comes to me for information” (interview 11/05/2015), clearly demonstrate the group’s intention to control the situation and have a stronger and more effective network than institutional processes. When I asked for explanations about how the group had come to have access to the phone numbers of their various interlocuters (knowing from experience that public officials in sensitive departments, such as those for housing or social welfare, often disconnect their office phones and aren’t particularly inclined to receiving citizens), one member replied, “those people... they are humans!”²²¹

²²¹ Informal conversation, May 2015.

referring to a relationship between equals and implying that informal communication channels were much more efficient than institutional processes.

The residents were fully aware of the performative power of a document or phone number. In what Bayart (in Hibou 2013) has described as “faire croire bureaucratique”, they learnt to use bureaucracy to their own advantage by formalising agreements with politicians and public officials or by conserving and archiving documents and statistics so as to be able to cite them against those cited by the project organisers or the Municipality. The history of the protests around the RLMCP is traced by letters (written by the community to politicians and public officials), agreements (between the RLSC acting as representative for the entire community and the Municipality) and memoranda of understanding, declaring the shared intent to honour the established agreements. For the officials, making the residents sign agreements meant that they could later demonstrate that they had approved a certain decision in case there were subsequent issues, for example with housing (a memorandum of sorts was signed when it came to the procedure for allocating housing) or the intended use of a redeveloped area.

The members of various residents’ committees adapted to the use of bureaucratic language and written agreements with various Municipal officials, on the condition that the officials also stayed true to what had been agreed. “We signed a document that the museum could reopen once everything would be in place” (interview 11/05/2015); “we had a petition that we gave to XX saying that we want the people of Red Location to be the preference in term of employment. We also had a memorandum of understanding signed with A. and B. in which they agreed to all our requests but after they selected the staff that had to be employed without informing us” (interview 03/11/2015).

Knowledge of bureaucracy was also a strategy of defence: when the Municipality redrew the borders of wards 15 and 16 and so pushed several RLSC activists out of the ward of the RLMCP (with the result that their status as activists would have been diminished as it rested on proximity with the centre), the activists challenged the decision by identifying procedural errors that would have invalidated the provision. In a similar way, they declared, “we should know what’s going on before anybody else! The IDP says it!” (interview 02/11/2015), referring to the Integrated Development Plan that regulated urban planning and insisted on citizens’

participation in decisions that would affect the future structure of their neighbourhoods.

Mastery of details also meant being able to tell your own story and justify your own motivations. The longevity of the protests entailed a growing competence with media relations: one of the committee members became a sort of spokesperson, giving repeated interviews. Through constant media requests, the history of the protests consolidated into a narrative that coherently articulated connections between events from the 1990s to the present day. It was, however, a selective narrative that prioritised the demands of phase 2 residents to the disadvantage of other struggles (for example those of phase 3 residents). The narration of the protests is an oral history, consisting of omissions, imprecisions and sketchy timelines. Moreover, some of the earliest activists are no longer alive and so it is their children who tell the story of the 1990s. Their accounts are chronologically complex, generally following the same timeline as the project but also adding other key dates, such as local and national politicians' visits to Red Location. Creating a roughly coherent narrative means constructing a shared mythology, using the struggles of the nineties to justify those of the present and highlighting how the appropriation of the museum was the culmination of a much longer chain of events.

7. Refusing cooperation and knowledge of the grey areas

Both RLSC members and those who broke away from the group shared a keen commitment to preventing politicians from appropriating, claiming authorship or assuming leadership of the protests. One of the residents exclaimed, "the ANC came, the EFF came, the DA came, but we chased all of them!" (interview 11/05/2015). A member of the RLSC also narrated how he refused to talk to one of the project organisers who wanted to speak to him during a political meeting: "I said if he wants a report he must come here! I said, 'don't put pressure on me!'. If he cares he would be here by now!" (interview 11/05/2015). Politicians were ubiquitous, occasional allies, but rampant corruption and broken promises made the residents extremely cautious about forming relationships with them.

There was not, however, a complete retreat from politics: disillusion is not the same as disinterest. The residents tended to be very well informed on various

alliances and disagreements within political parties, and above all they were aware that they played a critical role as voters. “It’s our government”, one resident said in reference to the ANC, “we fought for it, that’s why people protest” (interview 02/11/2015). The microcosm of Red Location represents one of the greatest complexities of contemporary South African politics: on the one hand, this ANC stronghold in spite of everything still held the conviction that the ANC represented the people, or at least all oppressed people. There was the idea that each constituent owned a part of the party and its governance, almost in a material sense (“it’s our government”, “they’ve got to do that because we voted for them”). On the other hand, distrust of the political class was common and politicians were condemned for betraying the ideals of anti-apartheid struggle, profiteering and centralising resources at the expense of the population. In Red Location, members of the Ward Committee, an advisory body that controls the township’s resources, were understood as the elite. The Ward Committee has also been nicknamed the Life Committee, because those appointed to sit on it have endured unscathed through all legislatures, sharing grants and contracts between them.

Navigating politics in Red Location also meant developing a rather nuanced knowledge of everyone’s memberships, political backstories, any potential skeletons in the closet, gossip, etc. The best way of appropriating the shady parts of politics was not to remark upon them, but to become familiar with them and to know how to use this knowledge appropriately. While it was impossible to shape political dynamics such as the city branch of the ANC splintering into multiple factions (which obviously impacted on political actions, officials and institutional representatives), it was at least possible to develop an understanding of the underlying currents of alliances and separations, symbolic departures and rapprochements.

The members of the RLSC valued on the words of local politicians, either because of the influence that they exerted on a municipal and provincial level, or because of the movement of the party that they were a part of. In one instance, for example, a resident told me how during an assembly several inhabitants had confronted a local member of the ANC who was trying to quell the citizens’ discontent. They told him that they knew full well that “there was no-one behind him”, that is, that he had been sent because he was closest to Red Location residents, but that this had been something of a withdrawal on the ANC’s part and that he himself belonged

to a minority faction.²²² This attention alone pushed him to check the appointments and contracts for renovating the houses. Usually, the residents were able to trace the specific politics of their interlocuters, including public officials. Similarly, they had detailed knowledge of the political calendar: they waited for politicians' pre-election visits and utilised them to amplify their protests. They tried to understand who among the officials would no longer be in a managerial position after the elections and adapted their tactics accordingly.

8. Appropriation and Recognition

In *Rethinking Recognition*, Fraser discusses a dialectic between recognition and redistribution²²³ in relation to the claims of minorities and discriminated against groups. She proposes an approach that sees recognition as a question of social status.

From this perspective, what requires recognition is not group-specific identity but the status of individual group members as full partners in social interaction. Misrecognition, accordingly, does not mean the depreciation and deformation of group identity, but social subordination—in the sense of being prevented from participating as a peer in social life (Fraser 2000: 7).

Fraser notes how claims for recognition are on the rise while claims for the egalitarian redistribution of wealth are in decline.

The conflict around the RLMCP, which started with specific demands focused on socioeconomic rights set out in the constitution, came to include a series of claims that revolved around the question of recognition, in the sense of the demand for equal participation in social life. This demand for inclusion was formalised gradually, and was not explicitly, universally approved by all the residents. Early conversations and exchanges with Red Location inhabitants reveal how their demands got decidedly broader. This emerges from accounts in which new topics unexpectedly take over the narrative, at first listen seeming to complicate or confuse

²²² Interview 11/05/2015.

²²³ Fraser warns of the risks of seeing recognition as the premise of redistribution, which can lead to a reification of collective identities, displacement and obfuscation of issues relating to redistribution and self-generating and self-affirming collective identities. As an alternative, Fraser opts for a reading of recognition as a question of individual social status.

events. For example, people speaking housing struggles would a minute later allude to the issue of jobs within the museum, and a minute after that to the fact that it was a shame that the library was still closed, instead of becoming a source of employment. Alternatively, they would speak about how they had managed to transform the museum into a social space for group activities. Narratives about the protests seemed disorganised, incoherent, and when questioned on the link between jobs within the cultural centre and housing struggles, the residents were not always able to make clear the connections between the two demands.

Yet, as already discussed, it is beyond a doubt that housing protests have historically been a principal way of contesting the current order, with a series of movements for rent decreases, property rights and more recently the defence of illegal shacks. Housing has also been one of the areas in which the demand for equality and social justice has been particularly explicit. Additionally, the demand for rents to be adjusted to correspond to economic status was one of the ways of resisting racial segregation under apartheid, a battle fought on the grounds of economic need rather than on the slippery terrain of politics.

The protests against the RLMCP never solidified into a wider movement, nor were they used as a template outside of the location. The inherent fragility of the movement lent the protests a flexibility that allowed the mobilisation to adapt and survive through the alternations of various different committees. One of the reasons for this fragility is that the residents of Red Location struggled to form a collective identity, to delineate an “us” and a “them”. Committees were formed to respond to the specific demands of a specific group of residents, even though most of the time no-one expected a problem or a committee to last for so long. One of the leaders of the RLSC repeated multiple times that they had never anticipated a year-long conflict.²²⁴ There was solidarity between the residents with regards to some aspects and claims (such as the solidarity between phase 2 residents and phase 3 residents, who had been more severely affected by the realisation of the cultural centre), but committees or groups of residents remained substantially divided. Close living-quarters meant that inhabitants were aware of others’ struggles, but scarcity of resources meant that everyone had to concentrate their energy on what they

²²⁴ Interview 11/05/2015.

considered a priority. It was not easy, for example, to establish exactly how many people were members of the RLSC. My question was always met with vague responses; while there was a core group of five or six people, and a dozen or so people who regularly attended meetings, the rest of the residents came together when there were protests or public assemblies that, weather permitting, were held outside.

Given the fragmentation and diversity or specificity of different residents' demands, there was not really a collective identity, as theorised by McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly (2007).²²⁵ Members of the RLSC, phase 3 residents, newcomers and older inhabitants all tried to garner support for their own demands, but their diversity ended up creating ever more groups rather than consolidating into a single united front. The occupation of the RLMCP was probably one of the actions that was most widely supported, partly because opposition to the way in which the project was designed and delivered united people under the banner of "residents" or "inhabitants", regardless of the state of their houses. The residents, however, did not demand to be recognised as a distinct group with a specific identity. The fragmentation of the movement meant that the residents tended towards demands that similar to those identified by Fraser, primarily the recognition of individual social status. Certainly, the residents constantly tried ensure that those who lived near the museum were prioritised for jobs, housing, subsidies and information. Although this prioritisation was justified by moral necessity, the residents never defined criteria: each attempt to draw such a definition was poorly received, decried as exclusionary, chauvinist and divisive. Another way to claim priority was to demand it for one's children or for the younger generations (of Red Location, New Brighton or Ibhayi) rather than oneself, a less partial position more sheltered from critiques.

²²⁵ McAdam, Tarrow and Tilly highlight how "the constitution of claim-making actors turns out to be a contingent, dynamic process. Participants frequently shift their collective definitions of who 'we' and 'they' are. They do so especially through two processes. First, they create new connections among individuals, networks, and previously constituted actors in the form of named coalitions, fronts, and organizations. Second, they activate, deactivate, and redraw boundaries separating one actor from other, creating collective stories about the two sides" (McAdam, Tarrow e Tilly, 2007: 5).

The fragmentation of residents into multiple different groups and the lack of a defined collective identity certainly contributed to the fragility of the movement. The Municipality was able to contain the protests by leveraging the protesters' diversity. "They aren't all residents", they often said, or "who are they speaking for?". And yet it was also this diversity that led to a demand for recognition that went beyond demands for the right to decent housing: the township's citizens who lived the geography of segregation on a daily basis demanded full citizenship rights, more than constitutional rhetoric and regardless of their education levels, professions, employment status or income.

8. Preserving Memory, Rebuilding Roots

In Red Location, different actors competed to preserve the township's memories – protecting and safeguarding them, but also controlling them and shielding them from change. They competed to defend history through engaging with the complexities of the politics of time around the RLMCP.

The RLM set out to rebuild strong, community roots through proposing and consolidating a shared narrative of the past and attempting to enlist as many residents and citizens as possible in its particular blend of local and national history, individual and collective memory. The activities of the project organisers and museum staff, however, did not win the approval of all the residents, who negotiated how their past was represented and translated into museum exhibitions. Analysing alternative ways of relating to the past through engagement with the private sphere and periods and people who were not directly related to the anti-apartheid movement invites explorations of the multiple *lieux de mémoire*²²⁶ (Nora 1993) from which the residents reinterpreted their past and positioned themselves in the everyday life of the present.

²²⁶ Nora conceives of *lieux de mémoire* as multifaceted and complex. This chapter draws on a particular aspect of the notion of *lieux de mémoire* as material and concrete, potentially a geographical location, or abstract and intellectually constructed, where the collective memory of a social group forms. "Ces lieux, il fallait les entendre à tous les sens du mot, du plus matériel et concret, comme les monuments aux morts et les Archives nationales, au plus abstrait et intellectuellement construit, comme la notion de lignage, de génération, ou même de région et d'"homme-mémoire". Du haut lieu à sacralité institutionnelle, Reims ou le Panthéon, à l'humble manuel de nos enfances républicaines » (Pierre Nora 1993: 15).

1. Governing through the past and its consequences

It could have been any afternoon in Red Location. Before starting a meeting, several young artists were burning *Imphepho*, a particularly aromatic species of *Helichrysum*, creating a sort of fumigation effect. Still in Red Location, before embarking on a rather lengthy car journey, M. lights a few branches of *Imphepho*, “so the ancestors know where to find me, it’s my satnav”, he explains. *Imphepho* is an extremely common plant; it is rarely sold because it grows almost all over the Eastern Cape. The inhabitants of the location have various uses for it, both as individuals and groups. Its primary function is to invoke and simultaneously honour and placate the ancestors. When it burns, it forms a connection between those burning it and their forebears who still influence their lives. There is no need for a ceremony to use *Imphepho*, though it is a fundamental component of some rituals. While seemingly innocuous, *Imphepho* can induce exciting, slightly hallucinogenic effects. Endowed with particular powers and meanings, *Imphepho* is nonetheless an everyday plant. It represents a direct line to a part of the past that is still alive and continues to act in the present: according to the amaXhosa, ancestors visit the living through dreams, sometimes in groups, to give instructions or reveal truths. Before they become ancestors, a process that takes many generations, the deceased wander the world of the living. The unmistakable scent of *Imphepho* is one of the key characteristics of public and private spaces inhabited by amaXhosa people.

In South Africa, referring to the past is just as frequent and pervasive as the many uses of *Imphepho*. The past is used for justifications, healing, understanding, finding direction, forgetting or remembering. Just as the ancestors are, the past is evoked and honoured but also placated, feared, evaded, and silenced. Regardless of their social status and power, people variously represent the past with a range of different aims. Sometimes the past emerges unexpectedly, with unanticipated meanings and symbols. Other times, it is expressly invoked to draw comparisons and analogies.

This phenomenon is certainly not unique to South Africa. What seems unique, however, is the strong unease that accompanies every evocation or instance of forgetting. Time in South Africa is an object and instrument of social tensions and, above all, a tool of politics and power. Communal nostalgia, memories, expectations

and representations of the past can take on a precise social meaning, transforming into expressions of loyalty to or dissent from the status quo, rebellion against or support for the South African leadership. Any public statement about the past or future has specific associations and comes to be defined against a context that is understood to be its opposite. South African politics is above all the politics of time, particularly of the past. Representations of the past are effectively a tool of governance, since they legitimise interventions, establish hierarchies, assign worth and worthlessness, and most importantly, bestow rights.

The post-apartheid government was strengthened through the representation of a dark past and a present aiming for reparations for injustice through restitution and socioeconomic development. Portinaro, however, notes how the application of restorative justice on a wide scale can lead to “victim proliferation” as increasing numbers of social groups come to identify as victims: cases such as apartheid or colonisation trigger an “explosion” in the number of victims, creating an internal hierarchy between groups claiming reparations. Corresponding to the explosion in the number of victims is the impossibility of accurately attributing responsibility, especially when it comes to issues of social justice or the consequences of past regimes on present socioeconomic inequality. Furthermore, in these cases “compensation and distribution are inextricably intertwined”, that is, “in a market society, when the moral rights of victimhood are inherited, they become rights or demands of a primarily economic nature” (Portinaro 2011: 343).

Many of the social tensions in contemporary South Africa can be interpreted from this perspective: once a past, large-scale injustice has been noted and identified as the cause of present inequality, the victims of this injustice want “a restoration to the situation before rights were violated” (Portinaro 2011: 337), but this is an unattainable goal. In the absence of any possibility of returning to a “baseline”, memory and history take on the role of symbolic compensation. Many tensions between citizens and local and national government are exacerbated by the ambiguous distinction between reparations and symbolic compensation. The only actual recognition of rights seems to come from being included, whether as a protagonist or joint protagonist, in the official history advanced by the TRC and the ANC. And yet, despite claiming to represent the history of the entire South African nation, this type of narrative is extremely selective and marked by hard-to-heal

political wounds. If excluded from the category of activists and combatants, the other option available is that of presenting oneself as a victim – oppressed, previously oppressed, or the inheritors of oppression.

Claims made during the service delivery protests condemned the government for abandonment and disinterest and accused it of perpetuating historic oppression. The residents of the township claimed that the ruling classes had failed to change, since they implemented policies that forced the places they had promised to redeem suffer poverty and dependence. On the other hand, the media and some politicians decried references to the past, to attempts to hold leadership to their promises, as the expression of an unrealistic desire for dependence on public welfare. In this view, those who supported the protests and declined the solution of entrepreneurship were failing to fulfil their own duties as citizens to contribute to national wellbeing. But the inhabitants of the townships, whose citizenship rights were tied to their status as victims and recipients of reparations, would not so easily disregard disparity in the name of social harmony, nor did they trust the market economy that disadvantaged those who had been unable to accumulate wealth.

The museum, the fulcrum of the RLMCP, provides an extremely telling example of the rhetoric and uses of governing through the past. In the case of the museum, the source of development was seen to come from situating the township's history within the nation's history, through purifying conflicts and reintegrating the oppressed into historical narratives as protagonists. Precisely because it was an instrument for governing the past and so relied on simplistic, dichotomising narratives, the museum was riddled with ambiguities and unresolved contradictions.

2. A national museum, a community museum, or a mausoleum?

The home page of the website of Red Location Museum reads: “a world class museum bridging the past towards the future”.²²⁷ The museum is assigned the function of a bridge, “something that makes it easier to make a change from one situation to another”,²²⁸ with the goal of guiding the past towards the future. Bevernage reflects on the description of the Constitution as a “bridge” in reference to the post-script of

²²⁷ See <<http://www.freewebs.com/redlocationmuseum/>>.

²²⁸ See the definition of “bridge” in Cambridge Dictionary.

the interim Constitution of 1993,²²⁹ demonstrating how the concept of a bridge does not only imply something that connects something to something else, but also that implies the two things are separate.

This observation can be applied to the museum of anti-apartheid struggle, the RLMCP building that was designed to represent the past²³⁰ and justify building the other elements of the project. The museum represents a dark past, connected to the present via “the grey areas of memory”, through faint beams of light crossing the main hall. The absence of a guided itinerary through the museum makes space for the subjectivity of memory, but the memory boxes provide a space for commemorating very specific subjects or themes, even though the project organisers had initially envisaged that the boxes would be able to be opened and moved about, and the themes represented within them rotated. The museum celebrates the history of anti-apartheid struggle and ANC martyrs, whose names and portraits are displayed on the internal columns in a way that is reminiscent of the Stations of the Cross. Many of the activists represented both on this “wall of fame” and in photo galleries such as Goldblatt’s or Jon Riodan’s, “Forgotten Faces”, are still alive, but their more recent biographies are omitted or summed up in a few lines. The partial representation of only the part of their lives that conforms to the rosy, official version of history is perhaps the most obvious sign of the museum’s separation between past and future. Similarly, while the residents’ historical resistance to apartheid is celebrated, there are no references to their present lives, or at least these are not narrated with the same richness of detail.

When the present is portrayed in the museum, it seems almost farcical. For example, in response to tourists inappropriately wandering about the RLMCP and trying to take photos of the interiors of private houses, the museum staff decided to reconstruct the interior of a shack in one of the memory boxes. This “semi-authentic” representation mimicked and distorted reality and heavily criticised. The representation of a one-room home with minimal furniture and posters on the walls

²²⁹ The post-script indicates the Constitution itself as a “A historic bridge between the past of a deeply divided society characterized by strife, conflict, untold suffering and injustice, and a future founded on the recognition of human rights, democracy and peaceful co-existence and development opportunities for all South Africans, irrespective of colour, race, class, belief or sex”. *Constitution of The Republic of South Africa*, 1993.

²³⁰ In theory, the library too should have contained the past, since there were plans for a sort of multimedia archive, but this has not yet been built for lack of funds.

was intended as a prototypical urban informal settlement; it blended necessity, tradition and material culture.²³¹ Various musical and dance performances were organised to animate the museum and root it in the surrounding area. These performances drew on Xhosa tradition and a sense of community and can also be interpreted as an attempt to make the past more accessible and inhabitable. The museum was also equipped with a conference hall, implicitly for discussing historical matters. This space provoked fears and conflicting reactions in local politics; reactions never went as far as censorship, but demanded moderation, tact and caution when it came to inviting guests and choosing discussion topics.

Those who could not or would not understand the reasons behind the protests, and even struggled to comprehend mere indifference about the museum, judged that the community did not understand what a museum was or why it was important. It is not impossible that the residents saw the museum as a hostile and exclusionary institution, as the sort of building that they would not have been allowed to access during colonisation or apartheid. In Port Elizabeth, however, there was a lack of real debate about the ways in which a museum, as a collection of artefacts and documents, could effectively portray a past that was still so present, how it could represent a polyphony of sometimes conflicting narratives. In the brief history of the RLM, questions about its purpose cyclically reemerged. The absence of a clear strategy made the role of this sort of building in contemporary South Africa less obvious, also in public opinion.

In general, two interpretations of the museum's function prevailed: the first centred around on the construction of national history, the second on the reconstruction and strengthening of local or community history. Regarding the first interpretation, Leslie Witz stresses how in the years immediately following the end of apartheid, a version of the past was constituted that connected cultural identity, reconciliation and nation-building. This came to be presented broadly as national "heritage" (Witz in Karp 2006). For some people, the function of the RLM should have primarily been to hold national heritage, to be a "museum of the nation" (Rolland and Murauskaya 2009) and conserve exemplary artefacts, values and memories. The phrase "museum of the nation" is more appropriate than "national museum", since it

²³¹ Interviews with museum staff members 12/03/2015 and 16/03/2015. See Roux (2015: 65) for further analysis, also in relation to similar experiences in other museums.

was not a museum that has an official institutional status, such as occurs, for example, with Italian museums, but rather a museum that participates in processes of nation-building. It is, therefore, a *lieu de mémoire* as defined by Pierre Nora – a place tending towards unity and in which collective memory is arranged so as to provide an appropriate framework for the organisation of recollections (Nora 1989).²³² One of the museum staff members declared, “now the government is ours and it has accommodated stuff to make us feel proud of what we are” (interview 20/03/2015). From this perspective, the museum aimed to be of educational value for the entire citizenry, to guide the public through the dark of the past to the light of the present, represented by the other buildings constituting the cultural centre. At the same time, the museum also transmitted an image of South Africa to the external world: in this sense, it functioned as a “theatre of otherness” (Rassool in Karp 2006) and encapsulated the construction of the shared history underlying national identity and differentiating it from others.

Secondly, the museum should have performed the function of a “community museum”. In South Africa, this expression covers a range of different museums, from those primarily for conserving a given community’s artefacts, history or cultural production, to those that are predominantly spaces for social gatherings, meetings, participation and empowerment, spaces in which a sense of community is created or strengthened, or that a given community recognises as their own. Ciraj Rassool warns against thinking of the definition of a “community museum” as neutral or somehow in opposition to a national museum, highlighting that the community museum is in fact often perceived of paternalistically, as a parochial local museum. Community museums are seen as less pretentious and aim to open access to populations that had previously been excluded from such spaces and ways of knowing (Rassool 2006). Witz criticises the interpretation of cultural communities and homogenous identities for risking replicating the segregationist government’s conception of community. From the 1960s, in fact, there was a proliferation of “cultural villages”, reproductions of “authentic” African community life in places that foreign tourists could reach, which further strengthened the equivalence made between ethnicity, identity and culture

²³² Discussing the creation of European museums and *lieux de mémoire*, Marschall further questions whether such places actually omit another mode of remembering, for example that of the amaXhosa and the AmaZulu, based on oral narratives rather than the creation of sites (Marschall 2013).

(Witz 2006). Rassool identifies a further ambiguity: the “community museum” swings between being a local museum with a tight budget and being a museum that can compete with big national museums. The result is an excessive trust that expert consultation will provide a way of achieving desirable outcomes on nevertheless restricted budgets, through marketing and increasing footfall. This tension generates a dynamic in which large portions of museums’ budgets are spent on consultation, while community members mostly participate on a voluntary basis, their role reduced to recording oral histories.

The RLM can be considered a hybrid example. It is a museum that intended to narrate national history through community history and local experiences, but that at the same time utilised several techniques of the “community museum”, such as producing oral narratives and using witness-guides. An additional element is that organisers and politicians never completely relinquished the view of the museum as a sacred space that could contain history like an object to be worshipped or venerated.²³³ In 2005, as the works were nearing completion, Mayor Faku requested that a space within the museum be designated as a mausoleum to house the remains of Raymond Mhlaba and Govan Mbeki. Faku’s wishes, and the announcement of the creation of the mausoleum even before the families had given their consent, were the beginnings of a controversy with the Mbeki family: Moeletsi Mbeki, Govan’s son and the executor of his will, was opposed to exhuming and transferring the body (Mbeki had moreover expressed the desire to be buried with his family in a cemetery in Zwide). The case was closed in 2006 and the Municipality and the ANC received scathing critiques, seeing as the battle over the body was widely considered extremely undignified. A room in the museum remained empty.²³⁴

Being simultaneously a national museum, a community museum and a monument made the Red Location Museum’s activities extremely varied. The task of creating multiple narratives of history – expressed for example in the motto of the

²³³ I have previously discussed how the idea of the sacred was present in the RLMCP in at least two ways: the sanctity of history and suffering (in the Competition Brief) and the aura of sacredness around the building of the museum, that was designed to “create an impression of pilgrimage and sanctuary”. See chapter 2.2 and chapter 4.

²³⁴ Interviews 12/03/2015 and 16/03/2015 with museum staff members. The case was also covered by several newspapers (see for example, E. Van Staden, ‘Govan Mbeki reburial called off’, *News24*, 23/01/2006; B. Jordan, ‘South Africa: Fury Over Plan to Dig Up Mbeki’s Father’, accessed on AllAfrica.org). See Roux (2015) and Smith (2016) for further analysis of the affair.

museum's first year, "seeking to remember the past in many ways" – without an actual strategy to speak of, ultimately resulted in the replication of the trajectories followed by similar museums with national importance.

Janet Cherry, in the evaluation report commissioned by the project organisers in 2012, couldn't help but notice that:

It is a museum of resistance, not a museum of passive suffering. Yet the two most effective exhibits on display at present are those dealing with suffering: the Vuyisile Mini memory box, and the Langa Massacre wall exhibition. [...] There is very little in the content of the exhibits that gives the visitor a critical and nuanced understanding of this creativity and of the multiple and complex strategies of resistance (Cherry 2012, 1).

She also raised an important point about the inclusion of the present within the museum – it could not be limited to individual biographies or dialogues and cultural events, but had to realise the complexity of the area in which the museum was located:

History in such a sensitive social and political context should not be sanitised – there is no reason why the exhibition on the Museum cannot be situated in its social and political context, including the 'ugly bits' – the demonstrations by residents demanding housing instead of museums; the dilemma about what to do with the original old structures inhabited by destitute people living in squalor. Could a 'living museum' have been created in a way which benefitted residents? Were there alternatives that were considered and rejected? (Cherry 2012, 1).

The plea to not sanitise history underlies the reflections of many scholars and activists. Many academics have noted how the certain and static history represented in museums, especially those about local history, clashes with the fluidity of oral accounts, which require revisions, corrections and additions that should have been included in the museum. Several historians also stressed that the history of Red Location, especially its social history, needed more in-depth study.²³⁵

Those who criticised how the Red Location Museum was designed believed that the project had been delivered from the top down, when it should have been designed "from below". Such criticisms echo those made against contemporary South

²³⁵ Interviews 13/02/2015, 17/02/2015 and 04/03/2015.

Africa's development policies and raise a common issue: how to widen participation without compromising on efficiency and competitiveness?

3. Negotiating history and its artefacts

Multiple members of the museum's staff described how convincing the residents to contribute to the museum was more difficult than expected.²³⁶ While the residents could do without the museum, the museum could not do without the artefacts and testimonies of the location's inhabitants. The public glorification, exceptionalising and commodification of Red Location's history caused controversies over the composition and potential uses of this heritage.²³⁷ The inhabitants of Red Location understood that they could negotiate their involvement in various ways. On the one hand, they could establish their own *lieux de mémoire* – arranging objects, dates, people, events in order to structure and give meaning to the location's history. On the other hand, they could decide the material and symbolic value of their artefacts and testimonies. The commodification of their history meant that the residents demanded fair compensation in exchange for their contribution.

The birth of the RLMCP project, however, did not coincide with the emergence of a culture of remembrance in the location. There were already multiple memory-keepers in Red Location and New Brighton. For example, several inhabitants had long been expressing the desire to erect a monument or create a space in memory of George Pemba, a painter who, before dying in 2001, had lived in New Brighton and depicted everyday life in the township. Several residents were known to collect objects relating to the material history and culture of the location – the musician Dudley Tito, for example, kept posters from hundreds of concerts that had taken place in New Brighton. Finally, various elders were identified as the guardians of the location's oral history. In Red Location, and more generally in townships where the little space available was used for multiple purposes, documents and objects pertaining to the history of local groups were collected and looked after by single individuals. Many sports teams and religious groups in Red Location did not really

²³⁶ Interviews 12/03/2015, 16/03/2015 and 20/03/2015.

²³⁷ The process underway in Red Location, on a local scale, reflects a complex series of negotiations over memory and the bolstering of collective memory on a national scale, see Nuttall and Coetzee (1998) and Coombes (2003).

have a headquarters or any other appropriate space for archiving documents. Members of the Red City football team, for example, pointed out to me the person who kept all the material to do with the history of the group at his home; RLSC documents were also kept in the houses of trusted people. The presence of multiple, small, private archives is in and of itself enough to dispel the myth that the residents' protests were motivated by disregard of the importance of conserving memories or by ignorance of places for collecting historic artefacts.

This plurality of sources can lead to difficulties in identifying *lieux de mémoire*. This was one of the aspects discussed in Janet Cherry's evaluation report, which cites one of many voices of disagreement: "One Red Location resident, for example, questioned the absence of a local heroine she knew about: 'Where is Mam'Qati? She stays in Ezinyoka, she was tortured, had her breast shut in a drawer, her fingers cut; she travelled in a pipe underground to Missionvale'" (Cherry 2012: 4). This question recalls many others that residents asked the museum staff about activists or organisations that had been overlooked. There were also people who wanted references to some of the heroes represented in the museum to be removed, as they had subsequently become prominent politicians or controversial figures. The questions "who has decided it?", "who has the right to make decisions about the residents' history, apart from the residents?" were urgently repeated. Of course, not even the residents shared unanimous opinions about history and its heroes.

Repeated disagreements over the artefacts that should have been exhibited to narrate local history point to the negotiable nature of memory. In 2007, the museum staff launched a campaign to collect objects related to anti-apartheid struggles, including books that had been banned, uniforms, t-shirts, documents, photographs, letters and coded messages, tear gas containers, etc. These objects were initially going to be loaned to a museum in Stockholm before being kept in a permanent exhibition in the Red Location Museum. Both museum employees and several academics who had been involved in the campaign described the artefacts collection to me as a failure. The fact that the residents requested payment for donated objects complicated the collection.²³⁸ The same issue arose with the photograph of a family that had been displayed outside the museum, apparently without the permission of the people

²³⁸ Interview 12/03/2015 and 16/03/2015.

portrayed, and also with one of the original houses from the location that was kept outside the art gallery.

In 2014, a homeless man recognised this house as the house in which he had lived with his parents. The man therefore asked for it back: “This is my house and I don’t care what they’ve done [...] I feel sick and tired of being chucked out of people’s houses like a dog while my home is being used in a museum exhibition”.²³⁹ Although his request was taken seriously as the house was uninhabitable, it is interesting to note that through this self-declaration of property, a man who was living in an extremely precarious situation managed to symbolically turn his condition around; he went from destitute to property-owner and ruled that no-one could make use of his property without his consent. He then also used this unexpectedly valuable asset to negotiate and acquire a real house.

The interesting debate is not so much the legitimacy or consistency of specific declarations or claims, but rather the fact that negotiations over history allowed other rights to be asserted and demanded, particularly the right to participate in decisions about the township’s development. Reducing history to a commodity meant making it possessable. For the residents, the history of Red Location primarily belonged to them, as did the objects that represented it. Residing in Red Location or being the descendants of the original inhabitants who had had to move because of the devastating conditions of their houses, in and of itself legitimised ownership of that history, and thus granted the right to decide how it should be narrated and used.

The residents accepted to be identified as the victims of history, but this label did not mean that they passively accepted limits to what reparations they could demand. Rather than the only possible connection between past and future, therefore, the museum was received as but one of many possible bridges, and many inhabitants did not consider it the one that would lead to the best future for the location.

4. Alternative narratives: memories and non-testimonies

If the museum cannot be considered an exhaustive representation of memories of Red Location, what are the township’s other *lieux de mémoire*? How and enabled by what did the residents remember, narrate and transmit the history of the location? What

²³⁹ A. Williams, “Homeless man wants his shack back from museum”, *The Herald*, 10/09/2014.

other versions emerge? When asked to describe the place they lived in, few residents focused on the location's history of anti-apartheid struggles. When discussing the apartheid years, the inhabitants would often concentrate on the 1980s, highlighting elements such as fear, toil and intensifying everyday violence, rather than on negative aspects like lack of freedom and oppression that are central to the official narrative of the segregationist regime. Older inhabitants referred to the years of their youth as an age in which greater poverty was accompanied a stronger sense of community, and for some of them, less severe criminality. Many recollections of "escapes", fleeing between houses, finding unexpected hiding places and receiving support from strangers, are often evoked to narrate the solidarity that is often associated with the time.²⁴⁰

The accounts of people who do not fully identify as activists suggests a clear separation between the discourse about apartheid and private and domestic versions of the past. Accounts about homes, friendships and relationships are much looser and more unpredictable than those about the apartheid regime, which often repeat similar themes and episodes. The residents often remember when or how they became aware of their own exploitation, or the moment in which they understood that others shared their condition of victimhood and social injustice. These are not, however, accounts of militant activism but recollections about discovering the existence of difference and so the possibility of equality. They are stories of books read under the school desk, in the sitting rooms of elders, or disguised between the covers of religious books, or of enlightening conversations during a church lecture on anti-racism or political discussions over a game of chess.²⁴¹

Such moments were often described as a sort of threshold between adolescence and adulthood, related to the development of self-awareness and identity but rarely to membership to a political movement. The poet Mahola remembered having written his first poem about a butterfly coming dangerously closely to the light and getting burnt after having read a banned book by an activist from Namibia that

²⁴⁰ Interviews with residents, 28/05/2015 and 13/05/2015. I encountered similar narratives in various informal conversations. On the relationship between narratives of escape and a sense of solidarity, see Makhulu (2015).

²⁴¹ On the relationship between memory, experience, nostalgia and testimony in South Africa, also see Worby and Ally (2013). In various work, Nuttall has also reflected on the relationship between individual and collective memory and on contemporary artists' re-elaboration of memory (see also, for example, Nuttall 2009).

told the story of his politicisation.²⁴² Another resident described when his brother's friend was arrested in a family setting. Other inhabitants indicated sport, especially the bans on multiracial matches, as a context in which segregation was particularly visible but equally as a critical moment in their course towards emancipation. Several teachers and educators recounted that at the time they used sport to teach about the inexistence of essential biological race and to promote equality between humans, or else to provide an opportunity for pride and relief. Sport was, in fact, an important stage of anti-apartheid struggles.²⁴³

Post-apartheid governments turned sport into an instrument of informal diplomacy and a way of promoting the nation's image; it was utilised as a vector of social cohesion and economic growth, capable of fuelling and legitimising the development of infrastructures and urban regeneration. The organisation of the World Cup in 2010 represents the pinnacle of this tendency.²⁴⁴ Sport eloquently demonstrates how many different versions of memory can develop around the same phenomenon. Normal people's memories of sports teams and amateur competitions during the apartheid years are very frequently recalled. A resident who had taken on the role of location tour-guide led me through various sports fields, past and present, formal and informal. Some people remember the borders of streets through informal football teams (teammates live up to number 10, the opposition starts at number 11, etc.). Some remember open spaces used as sports pitches: the "experimental" part of the New Brighton district behind Avenue A, for example, lent itself particularly well to girls' handball games.²⁴⁵ Explanations also focused on formal sports pitches, the football pitch, the rugby pitch, and particularly prominent figures. Recollections tended to stress how sport was widely followed; there were lots more teams and fans would perch on the roofs of houses to watch their idols play. Many people in Red Location recall the boxing matches at TC White Hall and the local high schools. The

²⁴² Interview 13/05/2015.

²⁴³ This was mentioned several times during interviews and informal conversations. Alegi, in *Sport, Race and Liberation before Apartheid*, emphasized the importance of football in the political development of Luthuli, President of the ANC between 1952 and 1957 (accessible at www.sahistory.org.za). The same author details the relationship between sport, identity and political activism in South Africa (Alegi 2004). Merrett (2009) has analysed the relationship between sport and segregation in Pietermaritzburg.

²⁴⁴ See Baines (2010).

²⁴⁵ This was told to me many times, a common experience for those who were children during the final years of apartheid.

poet Mahola remembers his passion for boxing stemming from how it offered release from a dual discrimination – that resulting from his being a country-boy having moved to the city and that resulting from the colour of his skin.²⁴⁶

Memories of sports participate in a broader category of anecdotes about social life. Recollections of concerts and dancehalls, but also of ping-pong teams, sewing groups, church choirs and scout groups, recall a past in which the township was “alive” with many opportunities for social gatherings and exchanges. This type of recollection was often accompanied by rather discouraging comparisons with the present, by the observation that many of these recreational spaces have disappeared or been replaced by taverns which offer only a form of socialising mediated by alcohol. Memories of the township as a place of culture were undoubtedly effective and, as previously outlined, were used by the RLMCP organisers, mostly as proof of the location’s unfulfilled potential. The residents that I spoke to, however, did not focus so much on the location’s lost artistic splendour as on a nostalgic narrative of a past with which they fully identified, as opposed to an uncertain and sinister present.

This sort of “Ostalgie”²⁴⁷ is encapsulated in various attempts to recall the 1960s and 1970s, especially the period’s fashions or musical genres. The *Khumbula* collective, a group of performers and “trend-setters” from Johannesburg, for example, effectively used nostalgia as a political strategy. While the collective’s main creative activity consists of photographing the members wearing vintage clothes in places that evoke the townships in the 1950s and 1960s, the group’s blog includes an artists’ statement that reads:

We vow to stand by our not so bright history and we pledge to embrace all the four corners of our slams open heartily. no matter how much they spend on their urban renewal projections, our story will forever resonate with the forbidden culture of down town cartels .because for some of us that’s where we were conceived and raised. As for our parents their story remains untold and their dreams remains in the under ground mine dumps, that’s just the way it is and things will never be the same , cause we are the new generation filled with uncapped ambitions.²⁴⁸

²⁴⁶ Interview 13/05/2015.

²⁴⁷ The term “Ostalgie” refers to nostalgia for life in the German Democratic Republic.

²⁴⁸ See <<https://khumbula.wordpress.com/>>.

Khumbula (meaning “remember” in isiZulu) adopted the opposite approach to that of the transition leadership. For this art collective, evoking Black South African urban history through producing realistic images meant setting down roots, affirming their own belonging and most of all distinguishing themselves from the generation that had come before them, a generation that had not managed to redeem their own history.

Another way of situating individual histories within the history of the township was to evoke a timeline punctuated by incidents related to housing: many residents shared the experiences of relocating or moving house, attesting to the precarity and fluidity of housing. Other perceived historical turning points were the mass layoffs and strikes in the 2000s, especially for those who were or had been active in the NUMSA (National Union of Metalworkers of South Africa).

To use the words of Alessandro Portelli, the residents rarely allowed themselves to participate in “survivorism”, the natural tendency to feel like a survivor and protagonist of critical historical events and to place oneself at the centre of the story (Portelli 2005). Rather, their narratives appropriate and re-individualise collective memory. The residents chose to be narrators rather than witnesses; they exempted themselves from the construction of a unanimous truth and instead gave voice to intimate and private histories. Portelli notes how acts of remembrance and narration are “influenced by historical context and the social frameworks of memory, but they are also filtered through individual responsibility” (Portelli 2005: 4). In everyday life in Red Location and New Brighton, there was the prevailing desire to rediscover the individual and subjective sides of apartheid narratives. Biographic accounts concentrated on what would often be narrated as a sort of “non-story”. Accounts of football or rugby games, for example, were unlikely to be included in grand narratives of the apartheid years, and so mistakes, imprecisions and irreverence became permissible. The residents also made a separation between their interpretations of official history (TRC testimonies, biographic works etc.) and individual histories: while official history was considered to be consistently correct, individual history and subjective memories were perceived as changeable and imprecise. And yet, it was precisely these narratives, anecdotes and memories that were entrusted with the task of resolving contradictions, tensions and obscurities. Sharing and comparing individual histories participates in a subjective, social

reworking of the past that cannot but reintegrate the complexities that had come to be purged from official history.

5. Indifference and irreverence

If the RLMCP was a project that shaped the politics of time promoted by local institutions and national government, reacting to it with indifference or irreverence was a refusal of the official version of history, a way of asserting distance from a certain vision of the past and so a certain construction of the South African nation. Above all, it was the younger inhabitants who had an indifferent and irreverent attitude to the museum and the history that it represented.

For some young people in the location, the RLMCP was one of many projects aiming to appropriate public resources; others were uninterested in it from the start. Many were convinced that the project had no real potential to bring about change. South African politics more generally was subject to this apathy and reproach. There was a general feeling among young people in the location that the leaders of anti-apartheid had substantially failed to deliver their mandate of government and had dragged the country into a compromise where nothing had really changed. Disinterest in the RLMCP was a forceful refusal of a reconstruction of the past that was aimed at representing the present as the height of possibility. Those who criticised this view could count on policymakers' ambiguous use of the word "transformation", qualified by adjectives such as "social", "economic" or "ethical" to imply a desire to transform public institutions and services in line with constitutional values, in a gradual move towards greater equality and redistribution. Despite the noble aims implied by the word "transformation", its perpetual re-appearance in political debate suggests a sort of stasis and lack of progress. At a conference about the effectiveness of policies aimed at making the university more inclusive and attentive to inequality, one of the students commented "you cannot have a normal university in an abnormal society",²⁴⁹ highlighting the gap between much-cited "transformation" and actual social policies.

Feelings of irreverence and condemnation were also widespread beyond New Brighton and Red Location. In the performance "Toyi Toyi" (2015), the choreographer

²⁴⁹ Comment made at public talk on university transformation, 12/05/2015.

Kieron Jina expresses his opposition to several aspects of contemporary South African politics. He focuses on the enduring prevalence of the division between different “racial” groups and denounces modern-day corruption. The performance closes with various dancers fighting for a slice of cake that represents the South African nation. In the performance, Mandela symbolises the politics of compromise, as a man who sells out on his ideals in exchange for stability. One of the performers even wears a mask bearing the politician’s face, and another paints his body white. Similar criticisms are also present in the works of Xolisa Ngubelanga, a Port Elizabeth theatre director. In the play “Dinner with Bantu” (2010), Ngubelanga envisages Mandela stuck behind a sumptuously laden table while waiting for Steve Biko. Ngubelanga’s Mandela is firmly stuck in a mythical, idealised past that no longer has anything to do with reality: Mandela no longer leaves the house and Chris Hani has to let him know what’s going on beyond its protective walls.

Both works forcefully critique the establishment and the management of the transition, treating with irreverence its foremost hero and perhaps the only symbol still (at least for now) capable of reuniting South African society. The message of both works is clear: the past is not sacred, and even the undisputed protagonist of anti-apartheid struggle can be derided. “Fat cats”, individuals who made money off their activism and managed to strengthen a position of power during the transition, are also represented with a strong dose of cynicism. An attitude of irreverence towards anti-apartheid led to a desire for other foundational identity myths: rather than subscribing to the values of the struggle, younger generations turned back to amaXhosa history or the ideals of Steve Biko. Both these rediscoveries, that were also often reinventions, were based on the pursuit of greater authenticity in the face of a national construction that was perceived as artificial and false. The term “authenticity” has many connotations and uses. Huggan, for example, distinguishes between a “culture of authenticity” (Taylor 1991), based on an ethically motivated and historically situated pursuit of greater fulfilment and self-knowledge, and a “cult of authenticity”, where the authentic becomes both a sign of loss and a fetishization of redemption (Huggan 2001). In *Red Location*, authenticity was both rediscovered and reinvented. What strikes me as telling, however, is the contrast between perceptions of the official use of history as false or at least as an instrument of power, and the consequent move to an alternative narrative that was closer to self-

representation. The pursuit of greater authenticity was also connected to a desire for alternative temporalities and attempts to forge an identity that exceeded the trauma of apartheid.

6. Experience as legitimisation

If the Red Location Museum was a project to appropriate and narrate the township's history, the residents' criticisms, refusal to collaborate, suggestions of alternative histories and demands for payment can be read as the demand for individual and collective ownership of the location's history. The word "ownership" could here also be replaced by "legitimation": the residents demanded recognition of their rights to narrate, transform and intervene in the township's history. This demand for legitimisation was implicitly also a demand for integration and participation, not an attempt at opposition or separation. Similarly, the refusal and irreverence of their attitudes towards the RLMCP was driven by attempts to re-represent and remake history, not to overturn the status quo more radically.

Legitimation can come about in two ways: it can be prescribed by law, which also proposes conditions to the legitimisation, or it can arise from motivations or causes that are understood to be meaningful or significant. When it comes to the legitimacy to intervene in historical narratives, the sort of legitimisation given by law affects only a small number of people. The laws that recognise defined categories of people as survivors with specific rights can also be read in this way, with survivors being seen as legitimate memory-keepers. While it is unthinkable that individual people could be legally legitimised or entitled to intervene in the narration of history, it is possible that a certain category of people would be recognised as legitimate for particular reasons.

Red Location residents' criticisms and actions fall under of the second category of legitimisation. The residents based their demands for legitimisation on lived experience, or on the knowledge of the history and space of the location that they had acquired through everyday life. The pedagogue Dewey wrote, "on the active hand, experience is trying [...], on the passive, it is undergoing" (1930). Experience is a relationship that implies contact and the possibility of shaping and being shaped. Dewey further stresses that experience is also generated by the "transaction taking

place between the individual and, what at the time, constitutes the environment” (1930).

The criticisms and accounts given by the residents were often preceded by expressions such as “I know because I was there”, “I know because my father or mother told me”, or “I know because I live here”. The logic of explaining through presence is an attempt to connect space and time, storytelling and sensorial experience. The narrator posits themselves as the link between history and spatiality as “the historian’s agenda intertwines with the narrator’s agenda” (Portelli 2010: 1). This connection between inhabitation and experience, and the assumption that experience or proximity are criteria of validity, suggests a conception of citizenship as a relation with space, time, and other people. You can be experienced in something not only by personally having lived through it, but also by virtue of having inherited the memory of it. The sociologist Jedlowski, elaborating on the work of Benjamin, argues that “experience” is not only constituted by merely having lived through something, but that it also requires the subject to recognise or appropriate an event, meeting etc. as an experience (Jedlowski 2007). Dewey, too, notes that “‘to learn from experience’ is to make a backward and forward connection between what we do to things and what we enjoy or suffer from things in consequence” (1930). Experience always implies a dual temporality: it relies upon the past and discourse about the past, but is at the same time consolidated in the present, the time of interpretation. Past and present are continuous and juxtaposed. The museum performed the function of reconstructing and crystallising history but, in doing so only in connection with the past it failed to contribute to the construction of experience in the present. The failures criticised by the residents were often to do with the museum’s relationship with the present and its lack of dialogue with people capable of convincingly connecting present and past, such as elderly curators, elders, artists and even the representatives of the residents’ committee.

According to Jedlowski, experience is appropriated through narration, or steering debates: accounts of everyday life require a moment when one speaker monopolises the discourse (2007). The reactions of Red Location residents, such as their attachment to certain objects or their insistent stories about how they used to live in the original wood and sheet metal houses, can therefore be read as attempts to reconnect narrative and experience, to identify and be recognised as subjects of the

narration. Jedlowski writes: “after an experience of extreme disintegration, narrative reintegrates” (2007: 83), discussing the necessity of giving voice to traumatic events so that they can be rearticulated. In the case of Red Location, the museum replaced the residents themselves: the museum was conceived to reintegrate the location residents into national history, situated as it was in the centre of the location. The contentious relationship between the museum and the residents arose from this original paradox. The residents were deprived of the possibility of telling their own stories and so of reconstructing themselves through narrating and comparing their collective experience.

It was not only diverse individual stories that were suppressed, but also the knowledge systems that these stories conveyed – accounts of solidarity, anecdotes connecting places to specific moments, or details about how certain events played out. I remember, for example, being astonished by an older resident’s detailed account of the public toilets in Red Location during apartheid: he insisted on the fact that there weren’t even walls separating the cubicles (“you could talk while... you know?!”)²⁵⁰ and the various strategies that were used to get a bit of privacy or security. Of all the anecdotes that he could have told me, he chose this one. At first listen, it seemed to me to be of less significance. But in fact, the story described something that was not depicted within the museum and that had left no architectural traces, something that belonged to his experience and symbolised simultaneously the promiscuity and the deprivation of the time, alongside everyday strategies for navigating this.

This move from demands for ownership to demands for legitimisation, justified by lived experience, to intervene in the narration of history is crucial. As regards demands for ownership, institutions can at most grant rights, valorise artefacts or recognise the legitimate owners. With demands for legitimisation, however, experience becomes distinguishing characteristic that can the balance of the relationship between official history and local history, but also between formalised knowledge and practical, tacit knowledge.²⁵¹

²⁵⁰ Interview 03/11/2015.

²⁵¹ By “tacit knowledge”, the philosopher Michel Polanyi refers to a silent element of knowledge, to cognitive skills acquired through experience and that are difficult to verbalise or convey to others. See Polanyi (1966).

9. Defending physical and symbolic spaces

The RLSC's occupation of the museum is only one among many actions in Red Location that can be understood as a form of defence. Physical spaces in the township were defended through maintenance, restoration or repair. Being present in a place discourages the presence of rival groups and at the same time defence can be a form of prevention – neutral or empty places are defended against uses that are considered negative for all society. The inhabitants of Red Location also defended a moral border, a line sketched out between good and bad, justice and injustice. This related to the individual sphere but also divided society into honest citizens and criminals.

Defence is not only an act of conservation; it can also be generative. Defending moral principles, whatever these be, involves the creation of places that are understood to be morally upstanding. Equally, sometimes defence occurs through occupation, through extending one's actions into a new territory or object. Defence also implies a broadening of possibilities (for example, the possibility of feeling at ease, of undertaking specific activities, of cultivating passions). Defence is an activity that prompts cyclical processes: to defend somewhere is to be visibly present, to make a space comfortable and fortified. Such defended places offer a proliferation of possibilities for self-realisation, and this self-realisation can lead to other places or objects being defended. Simone describes the districts of megapolises as being continuously drawn by processes of intersection, that is, "incessant process of acting without a model [...] Instead of consolidating clearly discernible and bounded territories as platforms of action and interaction, there is a process of 'spacing out,' of generating, enfolding, and extending space in which mapping is always behind, struggling to 'catch up' (Simone 2011: 363).

Defence in Red Location related to the creation of space, because spaces that were maintained, safeguarded and appropriated ended up transforming, and because when groups who were considered to be dangerous were ousted from such spaces, this led to further appropriations. This generation of new spaces, however, was not always represented in the township's cartography, as it mostly occurred through forms of a recycling, reusing and sharing. In Red Location and New Brighton, spaces were defended, maintained and reused because this was easier than building new

spaces; or rather, defence was a form of construction that did not necessarily imply changes to a rigid, complex spatial structure.

Defence does not always imply improvement. To defend can also be to impinge on others' liberties or to assert supremacy over a given territory. But regardless, defence always involves asserting ownership and in some way changing the defended place.

In this chapter, I analyse several modes of defence. The analysis is not exhaustive, but offers some starting points from which to reflect on the daily work of repair, construction and the extension of appropriation within the township.

1. Townships: non-insular islands

Red Location and New Brighton offer particularly interesting cases for observing appropriation as a form of defence, precisely because they are places in which change occurs extremely arduously. They are, further, places that were not originally built to be owned or appropriated. The buildings in these places were built as a way of controlling the behaviour of their inhabitants: the townships were designed to be simultaneously generalising and individualising, since they were devoid of meeting or gathering places beyond those for providing basic services, places of worship and schools.

Before discussing how defence was variously expressed in the township, it is important to stress how the word "township" does not designate a clearly defined and delineated structure, nor a completely separate space. Considering practices of "defence" in the township should not entail portraying it as a closed and insular space.

The township can be described as a "non-insular island" in at least two senses. Firstly, the word "township" refers to a wide range of different places grouped together by virtue of more or less similar pasts and more or less comparable complexities in the present. It is therefore a highly mutable definition. Further, the townships are not defined by administrative borders (in this way the word "township" is used in a similar way to "outskirts"). The second reason is that although several townships are in fact remote and inaccessible, it is incorrect to assume that there is not a high degree of mobility between the townships and the city centre, or that living in the townships implies physical or psychological isolation.

Still used today to refer to areas that were conceived, in various points in history, as residential areas for non-white racial groups,²⁵² the words “township”, “location” or “Kasie” (an isiXhosa contraction of the Afrikaans “lokasie”) are more of a legacy from the past than contemporarily accurate terms. The word “township” is in itself extremely vague and is only still used in South Africa to refer to Black or Coloured residential areas. In the United Kingdom and the USA the word “township” today refers to a town in its entirety or a subdivision of a county. In South Africa in the Native Reserve Location Act n.40 (1902) and in subsequent pieces of legislation, the word “location” indicated an African (i.e., Black) residential area outside of town. Other legal terms used at later stages were “native area”²⁵³ or “Bantu urban area”.²⁵⁴ Originally, the word “location” was predominantly used to refer to a specific geographical space with a legal status that varied over time. The word “township” started to be used at the beginning of the 1960s in accordance with the passing of laws such as the Urban Bantu Councils Act (1961) that established semi-autonomous governments in the townships.

Just as spatial segregation in the city did not vanish with the end of apartheid, the language used for segregation did not fall out of use – in fact, the word “township” persists in everyday language even though it does not designate a legally defined area in the post-apartheid era. The word “location” and its equivalent “Kasie” are still used as generic descriptors, even by the inhabitants of ex-locations. Red Location, for example, is in the area of Ibhayi, which is described as a township that is subdivided into smaller units (Kwazakhele, New Brighton 1, New Brighton 2, Zwide, etc.). Defining where New Brighton ends and Kwazakhele begins is not intuitive – the borders of these areas today are difficult to discern, the townships bleed into each other and the development of informal settlements has contributed to the two areas merging. Ibhayi is a placename; the electoral boundaries of wards provide a more meaningful division (wards can also cover two or more locations). The unit of a “township” is partially found in data collected by Statistics South Africa, which aggregates data for “name places”, a term that also encompasses the names of several

²⁵² It is, however, necessary to specify that white people also live in the townships, just as there are a few “slums” that are inhabited mostly by white people. These spaces, however, tend to be defined as “informal settlements”, rather than townships.

²⁵³ For example, the Native Urban Areas Act of 1923.

²⁵⁴ For example, the Bantu Urban Area Amendment Act of 1961.

townships (Ibhayi, Motherwell, etc.). In addition to this terminological confusion, the stratification of various administrative orders and the traces of the evolution of urban geography (Ibhayi is also the isiXhosa name for Port Elizabeth, the bay), these terms have taken on new meanings to do with political dynamics or identity (re)appropriation.

In the introduction to the famous song *The Ghetto* (2012) by *The Muffinz*, “eKasi” is used synonymously with “ghetto” or “favela”,²⁵⁵ a space marked by social injustice, corruption and ambiguous morality, a place that should be avoided. For the official website of South African tourism, however, the townships are places in which it is possible to experience emotional connection, conviviality, a sense of community and South African working-class unity.²⁵⁶

Transformations in the geography of segregation were extremely slow, held back by policies that understood development as the proliferation of spaces for consumption (the only new non-residential buildings near many townships are hypermarkets), by an objective difficulty in regenerating residential areas built in areas at environmental risk or close to industrial zones that are now semi-abandoned, and by the presence of “buffer zones” – huge swathes of deserted land used to separate parts of the city inhabited by different racial groups and that today offer little promise for rehabilitation or regeneration.

Almost a million people in Port Elizabeth alone (67% of the population according to 2005 statistics)²⁵⁷ live and work on a daily basis in diverse locations that share difficulties in urban public transport, the combination of legal and illegal urbanisation, security risks, and a steady stream of workers moving from residential to industrial areas, downtown and the suburbs, because of the lack of jobs close to their own home. This migration is not only for employment purposes: to find a bank

²⁵⁵ “So, this is a story about this place where we come from/In South Africa we call it ekasi/The rest of the world calls it the ghetto/Some places call it the hood/In Brazil they call it *favela* [...]”. The Muffinz (2012).

²⁵⁶ ““While the plusher suburbs have more of a polished veneer, and may serve up more in the way of consumer conveniences, it’s the townships in South Africa where you discover the emotional connection, the conviviality and the sense of camaraderie that underpins South Africa’s working class. The townships in South Africa were designed as fortresses of apartheid control, a malicious and deliberate use of urban planning to alienate communities. Post-apartheid, shacks are being replaced by government subsidised houses, hostels are being carved up into proper family quarters, roads are continuously being tarred, and basic services are slowly being installed”. Source: <http://www.southafrica.net/za/it/articles/entry/article-southafrica.net-townships-in-south-africa>.

²⁵⁷ StatSA 2005. There is however a need to note the inaccuracy of these data, given the difficulties of gathering census data on “shack dwellers” and irregular inhabitants.

or an adequately equipped clinic it is often necessary to travel to other parts of the city. In the 1990s, the transition government prepared to supply the townships by building a series of public buildings such as health centres, libraries and sports complexes. Some of these are still functioning and providing semi-free services, others have been privatised or turned to other uses. The nature of the township as a segregated and disconnected area certainly contributes to the constant movement of its inhabitants. But this daily mobility is also explained by the fact that township inhabitants wanted to access services, recreation and sports activities that corresponded more closely to middle-class aspirations. While the layout of some of the townships gives either an impression of significant immobility (structurally some townships seem relatively unchanged from twenty or thirty years ago), or else on the contrary an impression of breakneck, almost uncontrollable urbanisation (illegal settlements change with a surprising rapidity, sometimes even overnight), an analysis limited to observing buildings would be extremely misleading. The current nature of the locations as areas that are still highly segregated (with an average unemployment rate of 37%²⁵⁸ and an enormous scarcity of services compared to the suburbs), but that at the same time are highly dynamic, make them spaces that need a much wider set of definitions. It would be inappropriate to describe the townships with terms from European and North American literature. The term “peripheries” would exclude the many locations that are close to the city centre; “suburbs” would give the misleading impression of residential, middle-class neighbourhoods, when the locations are characterised by the coexistence of various different categories of urban space; not even “ghetto” would be wholly accurate, considering, for example, Duneier’s study of the United States and the origins of European ghettos.²⁵⁹ Viewed whichever way, the townships *are* the city and replicate the many different ways of producing the city in South Africa (in terms of urban planning, sociality, organisation of public transport, commercial activities, etc.). It is not a question of describing cities as if they were massive “slums” (also because the equivalence between township and

²⁵⁸ Department of Co-operative Governance and Traditional Affairs, Township Transformation Timeline, 2009.

²⁵⁹ Describing Afro-American ghettos, for example, Duneier writes: “The ghetto can no longer be simply defined as a segregated area in which most blacks live. It is better understood as a space for intrusive social control of poor blacks” (Duneier 2016: 12). While the townships were archetypal spaces for intrusive control and the violation of private and domestic space, today the Municipality’s attitude towards the townships swings between abandonment and development from the outside.

slum is often partial and misplaced), but rather of normalising²⁶⁰ rather than exceptionalising the townships.

Speaking about the townships is therefore a fleeting act, and yet the word has the evocative potential to bring various material and symbolic realities together and to encompass representations and stereotypes of inhabitants and incomers alike. Because the term is so vague, it is often reimagined, generating various utopias of what the township should and could become. The idea that the townships have to undergo some sort of transformation is born from an enduring preconception of their uninhabitability, impersonality and inappropriateness. They share the common denominator of having been planned as neutral, ordered, homogenous residential areas that were not necessarily hospitable or appropriate for their inhabitants.

Viewed from this perspective, defensive practices were a response to a pervasive sense of temporariness, precarity and belonging out of habit rather than by birth, by circumstance not by choice. The residents of Red Location and New Brighton made appropriate a place they felt was theirs intermittently and ambivalently, fleeing from the inevitability of a previously imposed structure.

2. No place like home?

In discussing “defensive” actions that took place in the township, I do not mean to imply that everyone involved in repairing and improving the township looked positively on or enjoyed a calm and stable relationship with the place they lived in. The ambiguity of the word “township” reflected on many of the township’s inhabitants, not only because it was somewhat stigmatised, but also because it was not always easy to root one’s everyday life and origins in a place with such ambiguous connotations. The townships were described through the juxtaposition of paradoxes, (just as, essentially, every city should be): hostility and neighbourliness, community and loneliness, vibrant urban life and uneasy abandon. New Brighton, for example, was simultaneously seen as a vibrant and culturally rich township and as one of the most dangerous areas in Port Elizabeth. The townships were universally stigmatised, albeit to different degrees: in Port Elizabeth it was generally better to say you came from New Brighton (the township of art) rather than from Zwide or Walmer

²⁶⁰ To say that poverty or social injustice are the norm is not to say that they are “right”.

(townships with an equal crime rate but without the allure of underground culture), or worse still, from one of the many areas built almost entirely from informal shacks. There was stigma among the inhabitants of the townships themselves, according to different levels of exclusion or dangerousness. In Port Elizabeth, there was also a division between majority Coloured and majority Black townships: individuals who identified as Coloured warned against gangsters from the Black townships, while inhabitants of majority Black townships often described Coloured townships as more dangerous and sordid. This division was fuelled by widespread stereotypes, fuelled by ignorance, of townships that belonged to groups. As already discussed, the legacy of segregation was very strong in Port Elizabeth. Further, with cyclical regularity, various groups of townships would be hailed in the media as “the most dangerous”, with a great degree of emphasis on the rates, scope and severity of crime.

The inhabitants of townships suffered the consequences of inaccurate and contradictory narratives, with attitudes towards them swinging from moralism to paternalism, from fear and suspicion to understanding and piety. At the same time, such narratives proved useful for lobbying the Municipality to intervene, and for presenting themselves as radicals or experts in “harsh reality”. As already discussed, the township and township style also became a brand. Ntombizodumo E. Ngxabi, analysing the accounts of township inhabitants in Crossroads, Cape Town, demonstrates how homes in the city are often referred to in isiXhosa as “indlu” rather than “ikhaya”. The difference is important: the first word refers only to the part of a “kraal” (a typical Xhosa settlement) where the family would not typically gather or bury the umbilical cord of a newly born baby so they could lay down roots. “Ikhaya”, on the other hand, is the house more generally, and carries fundamental symbolic connotations. The questions “where do you live?” and “where are from?” are not always answered in the same way, even by younger people. This is not only because South African cities are characterised by a high degree of mobility. Often, “where are you from?” pertains to one’s clan or family origins, evoking alternative meanings and geographies. The reply “ekasi”, in reference to the township, suggests a system, rather than a place.

Despite the end of apartheid, one can easily hear conversations or read articles in which township inhabitants express a sense of unease arising from the feeling that, at the end of the day, their presence in the city is still seen as unnatural, even

disturbing. A student in the Mdali workshop reporting back from seeing a play in the centre, for example, spoke about how the white students were silent “as they should be”, in contrast to their group of friends who had been unaware of that space’s social rules.²⁶¹ Many accounts of discomfort related to the experience of being a Black student from the township in a majority white school, possibly on the other side of the city. Khanyisa Melwa runs a blog called Kasifixation about issues relating to living in the townships of Port Elizabeth, and published an article written by a student from Cape Town. The student wrote: “I had to fight to be equals with white children. I had to fight while all they had to do is exist, breathe and shit. They were accepted for their whiteness, while I was examined like an alien”.²⁶² Feeling excluded from the world beyond the townships, a world often perceived as “a place for white people”, does not necessarily mean that people withdrew into the townships or idealised their place of origin. Life beyond the symbolic borders of the township seemed difficult, but life within them was no less so.

Many residents of Red Location described their township in similar terms to those used by the RLMCP project organisers – as an empty, monotonous, monofunctional space deprived of its previous vitality. The narratives of those who governed the location and those who lived there were not always opposed. It could be argued, in Gramscian terms, that subaltern citizens conformed to and participated in hegemonic thought. Members of social clubs would even assert with conviction that there were no clubs in the location, or that there was no interest in participating in them, almost negating their own presence and involvement. This paradox came to mind as I listened to members of the Culture Consciousness Society lamenting a lack of liveliness in the place they lived, while their work and existence as a group of young people from the Ibhayi area coming together to organise cultural events suggested the very opposite. Similarly, the equivalence between personal success and getting out of the township (or out of Port Elizabeth, which was considered a minor city) was difficult to unlearn even for those who strongly advocated for social change, rather than individual emancipation, in the township.

²⁶¹ Text produced during Mdali workshop, 2015.

²⁶² Mbali Jozi, *I think I'm Black?*, 2017. Accessed at <www.kasifixation.wordpress.com>.

3. Refuge and 'human regeneration'

Various activities that could be interpreted as “defensive” were attempts to safeguard moral integrity and protect oneself and others from evil, bad decisions or harmful behaviours. The avoidance of decisions, behaviours or places that were perceived as negative or devious also gave rise to the creation of new places, viewed as emancipatory places to withdraw to for shelter.

In *Dinner with Bantu* (2010), director Xolisa Ngubelanga has Chris Hani say: “you should have been there sharing your time with us, somehow those children have managed to incorporate the stones in that dusty pitch into their game plan”. This image of the creative use of hardship as a means of survival and emancipation regularly resurfaces in depictions of township life. One of my interlocutors, after listening to my explanation of why I had come to the location, exclaimed, “ah ok, you are here to measure how thick we are!”²⁶³ and so we started to discuss the meaning of the word “thick”. It literally means “dense” but can also be used to describe something that is difficult to penetrate or made up of multiple layers. My interlocuter and their friend, however, offered the following definition: “Thick as keeping strong, the ability to remain steadfast in your beliefs before or without bowing to the pressures surrounding you. Being able to offer hope in a hopeless environment or being selfless in a selfish place to rise, and be the best you can in an environment that was designed to bring out the worst in you”.²⁶⁴

The idea of transformation in the township was closely linked both to the ability to overcome specific circumstantial challenges and the will to resist a pre-set trajectory and refuse to fall back into a vicious cycle. The township was considered as a disadvantaged starting point, but not an inevitable condemnation. In this sense, “defence” offered the possibility for alternatives to trajectories that were not considered virtuous or emancipatory. Defending morality and places associated with good behaviour started out from a negative proposition: the primary aim was to not be led astray, to steer clear of drugs or alcohol, to avoid gangs, to not become paralysed by unemployment, to not be alone.

²⁶³ Informal conversation.

²⁶⁴ From an email exchange following our conversation.

This perspective permeated both underground culture (for example, it was often repeated by young independent musicians in New Brighton²⁶⁵) and sermons and church meetings in New Brighton and Red Location, in which especially younger members of the congregation were urged to stay alert against negative influences. Even teenage high school students, such as those that I was able to observe during the Mdali creative writing workshop in Cowen High School in New Brighton, identified education, growth and personal success as an escape or break from an inevitable process. Swartz, who conducted studies in the peri-urban township of Langa, near Cape Town, discusses young people's "embedded morality" – "morality is not only about what you do (a morality of action) but also about who you are and who others are to you" (Swartz 2009: 65). At the same time, Swartz writes about the persistence of this perception of inevitability. For the young people she worked with, morality was determined by the fact of living in and coming from the township, making it hard to have total control over your own actions (Swartz 2009).

The young people who Swartz interviewed in Langa identified four moral stances with which young people confronted everyday life: isolating oneself from moral danger; deflecting the township's "Kasi style" and motivating oneself along an alternative path for the sake of one's future; passively absorbing the codes of township life; and abandoning moral codes and tending towards crime, drugs etc. (Swartz 2009).

The young people I interviewed in Red Location identified similar options, with the addition, however, of a fifth – the creation of "safe places". A safe place is not only a place in which to seek refuge from violence, but also a space in which it is possible to feel at ease, in which vulnerabilities are shared and nourished. They are spaces which enabled exchange, provided a bulwark against mistrust and that, being deliberately chosen, are exclusive and exclude. Safe spaces are, effectively, defensive spaces, refuges.

The young organisers of the Unplugged Backyard Hangout (UBH), evenings of open-air music and poetry performances, in a township near to New Brighton, assure potential attendees on Facebook that the UBH is a "safe place", despite there being no organised security beyond the presence of many young people living nearby. "Safe

²⁶⁵ Young musicians and artists between 22 and 35 years old who I interviewed.

places” were also offered by many private garages that would transform for the occasion into creative gathering spaces, despite there being hardly any security infrastructure in the suburbs. Feelings of security came from commonality of purpose, from being among likeminded people, from the mutual desire for sharing. Social life in Red Location and New Brighton still mostly revolved around homes and domestic spaces, precisely because they were perceived as spaces without traps or the danger of moral judgement.²⁶⁶

In response to my questions about her favourite space to socialise, one girl told me, “my favourite space is my lounge” (interview 24/06/2015). Lounges and garages also feature in YouTube videos of casual parties or jam sessions organised in New Brighton in a way that could be described as semi-public: invitees are friends or friends of friends, with invitations shared on social media, but anyone who finds out about the event and comes to have a look also often ends up attending. These events are recorded for two reasons: firstly, to document performances of songs and poetry-slams, often describing life in the location and promoting emancipatory lifestyles, but above all to offer an idealised image of social life in the township for organisers and participants. Behind the performers there appears a flat-screen television and some books, you can see no alcohol or cigarettes, underlining the edifying character of the event.

Several young people from New Brighton, Kwazakhele and Zwide, for example, formed a sort of collective, *CookHouse Poetry*, and their regular meeting place often became a public space. A collage of images and slogans on the walls make the place’s values explicit: “No disrespect”, “Your culture is your immune system”, “A woman’s place is in the struggle”, etc. On the group’s Facebook page, the group description reads: “A place to let down your hair, wash your feet and break bread with eternal beings. Great artists from all spheres”.²⁶⁷

Butler describes “the moment in which a subject—a person, a collective—asserts a right or entitlement to a liveable life when no such prior authorization exists,

²⁶⁶ For the same reason, it is preferable to smoke *dagga*, cannabis, with friends rather than strangers whose reactions can be unpredictable. Explaining the importance of smoking with friends and trusted acquaintances, several people told me similar stories: an acquaintance agreed to smoke with strangers who had violent or paranoid reactions and got into a very dangerous situation. These sorts of accounts, as well as demonstrating being a sort of constant vigilance, highlight the protective, redemptive role of “trusted” people”.

²⁶⁷ From the CookHouse Poetry Facebook page.

when no clearly enabling convention is in place” (Butler 2004: 224). The establishment of conditions that make life liveable, a term with multiple possible interpretations, underlie the development of new activities in the township. These often included sport, art and recreation, sectors in which local government intervention was absent or limited.

Bayat maintains that the genius of “subaltern groups” lies precisely in discovering or generating escapes, spaces and uncontrolled holes, “zones of relative freedom” that lend themselves to being appropriated and filled in. The author creates the category of “social nonmovements” as the collective actions or noncollective actors. Nonmovements “embody shared practices of large numbers of ordinary people whose fragmented but similar activities trigger much social change, even though these practices are rarely guided by an ideology or recognizable leaderships and organizations” (Bayat 2010: 14). These hypothetical or potential collectives are multiplied by an unspoken solidarity in public space (that also involves recognition of common concerns or interests). Nonmovements, however, never become movements, despite being characterised by the involvement of large numbers of people.

The concept of nonmovements is useful to describe the several forms of appropriation that formed the social fabric of Red Location and New Brighton. The various attempts to appropriate and make appropriate the location in the absence of public funding and state interventions shared several commonalities. In addition to the previously discussed assertion of difference from necessarily negative “mainstream” behaviours, these included the creation of groups of shared interests and practices; the formalisation of these groups, even if only through Facebook or a dress-code; declarations of loyalty and commitment to the township; and temporary alliances and solidarity between groups with similar interests.

The central point, however, was that groups – and not only cultural associations but also sports teams or faith groups – shared a desire to elevate and renew the township’s morality and offer a new value system. This desire took various forms: the *Cultural Consciousness Society*, for example, drew from the centrality and emancipatory potential of education promoted by the Black Consciousness Movement

(BCM);²⁶⁸ a martial arts group, on the other hand, spoke of brotherhood, solidarity and keeping violence in check; Red City players stressed the importance of psychophysical wellbeing and the creation of a pedagogical, educational spaces for very young people. Even before launching any projects, *Art Studio*, a collective in its earliest stages, spoke about its aims for unity, engagement and collaboration. Youth groups connected to the Methodist churches focused on altruism and helping the less fortunate.

Behind these declarations of intent was not only the desire to make the township more representative of its inhabitants, or simply more liveable and internally connected, but also the attempt to bypass the political question of recognising or declaring individual or collective identities, and to more directly deal with the way in which these identities could be lived, understood and reinterpreted in a system of relations. There were no grand speeches about the nature of being Black Africans, disadvantaged, poor, or of having fewer opportunities (political topics which were heavily instrumentalised), but rather the focus was on creating spaces and interest groups. Rather than proselytising or insisting on the morality and rectitude of their own intentions, these groups favoured coexistence and merely “be[ing] right here right now”.²⁶⁹ Although the formation and membership of these groups were expressed in terms of private individual choice, they transformed public space through their presence and creation of social spaces, forging a path to other ways of being citizens and township inhabitants. These groups in fact offered a way of witnessing and describing complex and uncertain identity formations. Albeit with limitations, the anti-apartheid struggle had certainly enabled the assertion of equality, the construction of Black pride and Black citizenship, in addition to recognition of the sacrifices made by marginalised people. And yet Butler stresses:

[...] The idea that if you accomplish your identity, you are there; that you've achieved recognition, status, legitimation; and that that's the end of your struggle, as if becoming visible, becoming sayable is the end of politics. That's not the case because what that perspective fails to do is to ask, "What are the conditions of sayability, of speakability, of visibility? Does one want a place within them? Does

²⁶⁸ The BCM interpreted anti-apartheid struggle in terms of material, psychological and spiritual liberation. The movement was born in the mid-1960s when the ANC was operating clandestinely and distanced themselves from several of the Congress's positions. Understanding itself as a movement for Black emancipation, the BCM advocated for anti-apartheid struggle led by Black people and refusing White paternalism.

²⁶⁹ Interview 24/06/2015.

one want to be assimilated to them? Or does one want to ask some more profound questions about how political structures work to delimit what visibility will be and what sayability will be?" (Butler in Olson and Worsam 2000: 744).

Although the Constitution, through non-discrimination, recognised multiple identities that had been repressed and marginalised during apartheid and received international praise for being among the most inclusive and innovative, modern-day practices of appropriation went a step further in their attempt to push at the limits and conditions of existence and experiment with new forms of self-expression, protest and identity.

The lyrical choices and thematic interests of musical groups formed in New Brighton participated in this attempt to delineate multifaceted and intertwining forms of citizenship and belonging: lyrics were composed in isiXhosa and English; the sounds of indie-folk and blues were accompanied by world fusion music alongside intimate songs about concepts that are extremely difficult to translate into English, with lyrics pertaining to village life, poverty or respect for parents and elders and their trials.²⁷⁰ Several of the national government's strategies for advancing social cohesion were also subject to appropriation and resignification: for example, *Heritage Day*, a day on which South African citizens are invited to "celebrate their own diversity" became an opportunity to build, define and assert the township's characteristics and its urban rearticulation of Xhosa culture on the stage of the city centre.

Simone uses the expression "systematic deskilling of [those] bodies" (Simone 2016) to describe the constant reduction of African Americans to unspecialised, unskilled and mono-dimensional labourers. Different modes of "defence" in the township started from the premise of the multidimensionality and plurality of interests and identities, and the implicit refusal of the equivalence between poverty and incompetence, tending instead towards an idealised view of the township as a self-sufficient, integrated and interconnected microcosm. Clearly this view clashes with the high levels of mobility, that were not only necessary but also desired and actively pursued by the inhabitants, but nonetheless it serves to represent the

²⁷⁰ Examples of such groups include Clique-Claque, Ikati Esengxoweni and Umle, an urban indie group based a little further away in Kwamagxaki whose name references the marks of smoke on the rooves of typical amaXhosa homes.

locations as places that possess a certain degree of internal coherence, that build their own cultural heritage and in which human and social capital makes up for material scarcity.

4. Gaining ground, making space

With the exception of the taverns and a few roadside restaurants, it is not easy to find a space in Red Location in the daytime to sit down and casually catch up with friends. The people who I interviewed listed meeting places such as the street, private homes, or more rarely the New Brighton library. There are a few community halls, but they could be very expensive to rent. The churches offered another meeting place but were limited to the congregation's religious activities. The only café was the fast-food restaurant in the local supermarket that, in addition to requiring payment, was not seen as a particularly safe or confidential place.

In New Brighton there are spaces that can be rented for various occasions (ceremonies, assemblies), but there seemed to be a lack of free and accessible meeting spaces. The various attempts to create alternative meeting spaces given the lack of free and accessible space can be connected to another form of "defence" in the township. This unique production and extension of space often consisted of recycling and reusing abandoned spaces, often without official permission, or multiple groups sharing a space by converting places into multipurpose buildings. These places were therefore not officially registered, nor did they appear on any maps, but nonetheless they offered the inhabitants spaces for exchange and connection.

One of the most significant creative urban meeting spaces were "backyards", small rooms built behind houses, usually for housing unmarried adult children, other tenants or children with their nuclear family if they could not find other accommodation or were waiting for the allocation of social housing. The backyards could transform into thriving craft workshops or arts studios – for example one of the young women who I interviewed kept her sewing machine there for making clothes and bags – or they continued to serve as accommodation that occasionally transformed into a rehearsal space for bands or theatre groups. One backyard in New Brighton even functioned as a school for young DJs, becoming an almost public place hosting jam sessions and other events announced regularly on Facebook.

Other multifunctional spaces included social centres that, as was the case with the Njoli Road social centre in Kwazakhele, could host the local ANC office, a dance group for teenage girls, a kung fu gym and ceremonies for religious groups without a building of their own. The chairs and pastor's lectern were set up or put away depending on the day, the kung fu equipment was tucked tidily behind the wings of the stage, ANC signage could be seen in the storage closet. In Red Location, a small church would transform into a gym to hold martial arts sessions. Several young people from New Brighton organised concerts in a hall with a stage owned by one of the Methodist churches. Announcements on social media, but also over the radio and loudspeakers, communicated how a building would be repurposed for an evening or afternoon. The most extreme example of this is perhaps once again provided by the Unplugged Backyard Hangouts, gatherings that had become events attended by an ever-growing number of people and that had initially started simply as a group of friends and young creatives coming together to improvise music and poetry. The desire to expand these events led to the young organisers creating a Facebook page where, until very recently, a hand-drawn map guided attendees to the little park (in reality, a space between the houses and narrow streets of the location) where events were held, as directions could be rather hard to follow for people from elsewhere. The UBH, born in 2015, offered a new space and a new way of socialising: the aim of the group was to hold free or affordable creative events in the name of cohesion and a positive, lively vision of the townships.

Appropriation, making appropriate, corresponds as much to adjusting and improving as to taking for oneself at the expense of others. The township was a site of continual violations of private property – anything with any market value that could be stolen was stolen, abandoned or under-construction buildings, even schools, hospitals and ambulances, were constantly looted. Appropriation is simultaneously an act of addition and subtraction, enrichment and impoverishment. All these actions coexisted in the same spaces, sometimes colliding into each other. Appropriations of spaces for virtuous aims, such as for housing, could occur in a wholly illegal manner, and in the same way, the illicit appropriation of others' spaces and could be totally legal.

To redefine the ways of inhabiting the township is not only to “make space”, to open pockets of shared difference and normalise exceptions that are overlooked by

legislators and policymakers, but it is also to attempt to gain ground, to erode enemy territory little by little and imperceptibly and progressively embark upon a “quiet encroachment on the ordinary” (Bayat 2010: 28). Appropriations in the township were competitive, with abandoned places being easily appropriated by gangs, drug dealers and regular criminality. Where urban planners saw emptiness and abandonment, the residents recognised different ways of appropriating space. Getting there first, or being more organised, meant having the chance to modify these places, acquire usage rights and thus avoid an exclusionary and potentially dangerous form of appropriation. When asked what type of project they would like to see to improve their township, various students aged between 13 and 16 years old who took part in the Mdali workshops at Cowen High School in New Brighton mentioned the conversion of “dump areas” into playgrounds or green areas, or the renovation of uninhabited and crumbling buildings that had become places for drug dealing and gangs.²⁷¹

One boy who participated in the Mdali workshop, imagining the community regeneration of the area, wrote: “After we have done with cleaning, each person will go around collecting wood and wires so that we could fence around the place that we have cleaned so that nothing or no one will get inside while we are still working with the place”.²⁷² Negotiating for, obtaining and maintaining space are key for any activity.

Gaining ground requires the ability to rely on profitable relationships and a range of contacts to handle logistical matters. For example, knowing someone trustworthy who owns a minibus is helpful for organising transport within the township, an essential component of an event’s success; knowing pastors or influential members of a church’s congregations means being able to ask to borrow the halls or car parks adjacent to the place of worship.

While I was speaking with a group of people of varying ages about their interests and pastimes, a young man burst out laughing and told me, “We can do everything in the townships, township is like walking on a free haven” (interview 11/06/2015). The absence or intermittence of law enforcement, abandonment, the accessibility of illegal networks and the ease of controlling territories made the townships rife with various sorts of criminal activity, but at the same time enabled the

²⁷¹ From the writings of participants in Mdali workshop, 2015.

²⁷² From a text produced during the Mdali workshop in the second half of 2015.

rejection of rules and the permanence of liminal conditions, or the creation of spaces and practices that did not always find equivalents in the suburbs, allowing not only for survival, but also for a better quality of life in the township.

The Red City football team, for example, used part of the cultural centre as a football pitch, organising multiple training sessions for players of various ages. This informal solution allowed the team to play in several tournaments, as they would rent a field only when necessary.²⁷³ Another, less formalised team trained on an abandoned piece of land that was not owned by any of the members and that without the knowledge or permission of the landowner, was slowly becoming their regular pitch.²⁷⁴ Without permissions, the women who managed the hostel next to the RLM added a container at the rear in order to hold an after school-club for the children of nearby schools.²⁷⁵ Residents' requests to use the RLMCP buildings for not exclusively cultural activities should be read in the same way: access to a space or building, unless explicitly prohibited or simply in the absence of enforcement, made it open to any use. For this same reason, lands purchased as building plots were often fenced off to prevent the erection of shacks.

Effectively, you could do anything in the townships: learn to play music, sing, sew, cook, act, gather for discussing or doing politics. This was also possible because many inhabitants worked either in the townships or in other areas of the city as teachers, university students, sportspeople and artists. The social spaces and activities that occurred in the townships, therefore, resulted both from the inhabitants' skills in defence and their continual efforts for expansion, but also from the mobility and connections created between the township and other areas in the city. Makhulu notes: "citiness itself is very often generated from the margins [...] we can [therefore] move some theoretical distance from the tendency to parochialize the poor, to imagine that their struggles are somehow banal, delimited by the local" (2015: 14).

²⁷³ Interview 10/06/2015.

²⁷⁴ Interview 19/11/2015.

²⁷⁵ Interview 16/06/2015.

5. Cleanliness and Policing

In New Brighton, cleanliness (attention to healthiness, hygiene and decorum), and policing (practices related to security and countering criminality) are extremely important. They constitute two other ways of “being present” in the location, as opposed to absence, abandon and neglect. Both cleanliness and security recall how apartheid government at least officially prized hygiene and decorum and punished disorder and degradation. Both cleanliness and security remain central during post-apartheid, but they have come to be rearticulated by the residents as forms of defence. The residents, that is, supported initiatives relating to policing and cleanliness, whether in collaboration with institutions or by supplanting and replacing the Municipality’s interventions.

When I asked one of the ward councillors to tell me about the problems that New Brighton and Red Location faced, I was expecting him to highlight unemployment and housing shortages. The councillor did in fact mention these problems, but only after describing the environmental risks of the area, especially in terms of the inhabitants’ health. Insalubrity was caused by the transformation of many areas into illegal dumping grounds, the neighbourhood’s proximity to the industrial zone, and the fact that the south of New Brighton is crossed by a highway that allows heavy vehicles to reach the factories. The plumbing systems for drinking water were also old and worn out, unsuitable for the contemporary population density and unsafe from a public health perspective, in addition to needing constant maintenance. Further, the structure of the township, with roads so narrow as to make it difficult for cars to travel down them, made it difficult to install pavements or public green spaces.²⁷⁶

Concerns about the problems of pollution and the environment were common. This is not to say that New Brighton residents were all environmentalists; rather, the councillor complained that citizens had a “sense of entitlement”, that they took the Municipality’s interventions for granted. He told me, “Now people see themselves as if they are entitled so they just dump stuff ’cause they say it creates jobs as the Municipality must come and pick it up” (interview 24/06/2015). However, the residents shared certain ideas about decorum and cleanliness, stemming from the

²⁷⁶ Interview 24/11/2015.

combination of the impact of apartheid and the more or less articulated awareness of the importance of living in a healthy environment. The young participants of the Mdali workshop, for example, also spoke about cleanliness (of public spaces, school toilets, ditches on the side of the road), associating cleanliness and hygiene with moral rectitude and dirtiness with corruption and degeneration.

Townships were often built in dangerous and unsanitary places, close to rivers or stagnant water, meaning that they were subject to annual flooding and that inhabitants had to use polluted, unpotable water. New Brighton was built close to industrial plants and suffers all the health risks that come with this. The residents saw the problem of hygiene and cleanliness as an everyday problem of primary importance. For example, several residents destined for Phase 3 houses questioned the material with which the houses would be built, raising concerns not only about its durability but also its health risks. However, the Municipality struggled to implement effective solutions, such as decontamination or microbiological analysis, which would have entailed large expenses. As with other policies related to poverty reduction, attention was focused on how to promote good behaviour, rather than on addressing the issues of the places people lived in. The councillor underlined, “when people build roads in our communities they do it just to allow the traffic flows” (interview 24/06/2015), demonstrating how interventions carried out in the townships were not focused so much on the needs of the inhabitants as on the city’s urban development plan.

In New Brighton, groups of volunteers in receipt of a daily symbolic amount of compensation from the ward councillor’s office were charged with cleaning the streets and maintaining public green spaces. The courtyards of public buildings, especially the churches, were kept obsessively tidy. Places that looked clean and healthy were made to stand in contrast with dilapidated areas and dumping grounds, creating a juxtaposition between the positivity of presence and defence and the negativity of neglected spaces (that were also spaces, such as roadsides, that should have been the Municipality’s responsibility).

If ensuring “cleanliness” was associated with presence and the reappropriation of space, the same can be said for acts of “policing”, that is, security

and crime prevention. Laars Buur, studying vigilantism²⁷⁷ in New Brighton, has demonstrated how this practice in the township is not new, but can be dated back to the “location committees” established in the 1920s and the self-organised “street committees” of the 1980s, and was given new life by the creation of the Amadlozi in the early 2000s (Buur 2006). These vigilante groups have been analysed as resulting from the absence of the state and the passing of the responsibility for security to private citizens, but more recent studies demonstrate how they can also be considered as part of the process of state formation (Fourchard 2011), or at least as organisations that straddle public and private space and perform a similar function to the state when it comes to security (Buur 2006, drawing on Lund 2001). They therefore effectuate in a type of “defence” that should not be understood as necessarily opposed to but rather in constant negotiation with the local government. For Buur, furthermore, vigilantism corresponds to the need to establish the external limits of society, represented by what comes to be defined as the criminal (Buur 2006). Indeed, vigilante groups also tend to condemn activities such as witchcraft that they deem harmful for the wider community (Jensen and Buur 2010). Although vigilantism is a complex issue in which citizens’ agency sometimes results in extreme violence, these groups clearly demonstrate the themes of relationships with space (vigilantes only have legitimacy to act within a defined community), defence and control, and the desire to establish a moral order that is more appropriate for the residents – one that results from a dialogue between human rights as enshrined in the Constitution and behaviours shaped by culture and custom (Jensen and Buur 2010).

6. The Construction of Wellbeing

The last few years in South Africa have seen a renewed interest in the thought of Stephen Biko, the leader of the Black Consciousness Movement (BCM), not only among academics but also more broadly among university student movements.²⁷⁸ There has

²⁷⁷ The term “vigilantism” refers to the enforcement of public order by private police forces. In the literature on vigilantism in South Africa this term is used in this way or in reference to the constitution of self-organised groups of citizens working to counter criminality in the township they live in. There are contrasting views about the “enforcement of public order”.

²⁷⁸ Biko’s name was frequently and forcefully referenced in the statements and declarations of the #RhodesMustFall and #FeesMustFall student movements, which respectively called for the decolonisation of university campuses and protested against the increase of tuition fees. See, for example, N. Mathibela and S. Dlakavu, ‘Biko lives in Fallism’, *News24*, 11/09/2016 and R. Pather,

been an emphasis on escaping the conditions of oppression and subalternity, with a view to rectifying inequality and reconstructing subjectivity.

One possible explanation for this recent rediscovery of Biko's thought is probably his insistence on fighting against privilege. For Biko, white privilege resulting from the exploitation of Africans and "separate development" were the first structures that needed to be abolished in order to construct a society of free men that would have provided the preconditions for every citizen being able to "rise and attain the envisioned self".²⁷⁹ Abolishing privilege meant refusing offers of integration into a system that promised to treat Black people as equals but failed to change the status quo. Secondly, he maintained that there was a need to abandon the idea of the inevitability of Black people's oppression. The perception of the inevitability of exploitation had to be corrected through universal emancipation, or in other words, through developing the knowledge and critical sensibility to rearticulate Black subjectivity and so envision possible alternatives (Biko in Stubbs 1987).

At the end of apartheid, the ANC government's neoliberal swerve came to interpret freedom in terms of freedom of choice, especially consumer choice, and the possibility to express one's entrepreneurial skills and sell one's skills on the market (Hart 2002). While for Biko, freedom was the condition of escape from the system, for the ANC freedom became an objective that could be achieved through economic integration and a set of policies to encourage South Africa's economic growth and market competitiveness. Discourse on equality came to be replaced by discourse on the freedom of choice and skills development, with no suggestion of transforming privilege.

The rediscovery of Biko's thought stems from the fact that living in the township today means having to confront public discourse that construes wellbeing as a question of individual responsibility and personal efforts towards integration

'Rhodes Must Fall: The university must be decolonized', *The Daily Vox*, 01/04/2015. Even Julius Malema, EFF leader, commented on the protests: "Biko and Hani would salute students today" (from S. Madia, 'Biko and Hani would salute students today', *News24*, 14/10/2016). The American activist Angela Davis, at the Steve Biko Foundation, traced a parallel between Biko's ideas and the student movement (11 Sept. 2016. 17th Annual Steve Biko Memorial Lecture). Naomi Roux (2015) has extensively analysed graffiti portraying Biko in Port Elizabeth, interpreting them both as a form of reinscribing alternative memories into urban space (in Port Elizabeth, the image of Biko is much less visible than that of Mandela, even though Biko's history is more closely connected to the city) and as one of the various ways that Biko's heritage has been mobilised and appropriated by the city's youth.

²⁷⁹ Biko in Stubbs (1987: 49).

while inequality is a blatant aspect of everyday reality. In the townships, inequality was not only a question of the distribution of wealth, but also a question of disproportionate and unbalanced service provision.

In 1966, Athol Fugard together with his theatre company The Serpents Players, staged his plays in New Brighton. In *The Coat*, he has Aniko, a woman waiting for her husband to return from an apartheid prison, say:

Life isn't just eating samp and beans, with meat once a week, or washing the white man's underpants and sleeping in council houses. We are a nation with men, and one of them wore this coat. Can I not struggle a little for him? When he comes back can I not say: Yes, it was hard for us as well. But we waited. We had faith. Here is your coat, my husband. We kept it for you. (Fugard 1993: 43).

Fugard's uses Aniko's efforts to keep her husband's coat, her refusal to exchange it for the basic means of survival, as a metaphor for the ideals of emancipation. For Fugard, being human in the township means having faith in freedom and refusing to renounce things you hold dear.

In 2010, on the other hand, Ngubelanga represented Mandela as having to offer a definition of what it is that makes a man based on an obsession over who gets to decide the criteria for redistribution:

Define what makes you a man. How much food you can put on the table, does that make you the man? Is it the stature of those that sit with you or is it the way you eat your food on your table, hands, fork and knife or spoon? Is being a man to have authority to decide who has what share of the food you provide, who has the bigger portion who gets none? (Ngubelanga 2010).

In Ngubelanga's play, Biko decides not to return to a South Africa in which everything seems deliberately unchanged, to the advantage of a privileged few: "Do you really think I want to return to a house I left 33 years ago to find it looking the exact way? No change of address, the hedge denied of its impulse to grow, cut and trimmed to fit the mould and standard I last saw it in?" (Ngubelanga 2010). The leadership failed to revitalise a rhetoric of emancipation that had been stripped of meaning; the township inhabitants distanced themselves from a perspective in which it was only the privileged few who could enjoy anything beyond basic survival: "Those children will

not be satisfied by oomuncumuncu²⁸⁰ for long; soon they will come to the realization that they deserve more. They will grow and their hearts will become more heavier and bolder. Will it be wrong for them to demand a more human stand point, when that time arrives?" (Ngubelanga 2010).

The rediscovery of Biko occurred in two not always concordant manners: firstly, frustrations at the persistence and exacerbation of inequality forcefully recentred attention on privilege; and secondly, discourse on freedom and emancipation assumed new meaning. In both cases, however, it was not a question of proposing alternatives but of humanising the current system.

The rearticulation of discourse about privilege led to demands for redistribution and social justice. These demands were made predominantly by formal political movements and involved calls for policies to address socioeconomic inequality and the availability of resources in the name of a defined collective identity. With varying intensity, these demands insisted on the abolition of privilege, which some groups such as the Economic Freedom Fighters (EFF) still articulated exclusively along racial lines, while others, such as the United Front (UF) read more in terms of class difference.

Discourse about freedom in terms of reformulating subjectivity occurred a lot less in formal politics and emerges more forcefully through analysis of everyday practices. Appropriating and defending physical and symbolic spaces in the township can be read as a way of reformulating subjectivity in two ways: as an attempt to increase one's skills to the greatest extent possible in order to take a quicker route to integration, and as the creation of emancipatory spaces "on the margins of the system. In the first case, the prevailing idea is of a "connected world" (Boltanski 2008) in which it is essential to incessantly develop one's skillset and network in order to "become employable" (Bono in Hibou 2013). In the second case, the emphasis is on the desire to not sacrifice oneself to the market. Young people would often declare that they didn't want to "become like their mothers", or live to "serve whites". Their disdain was not for the domestic work of their mothers, but rather compliance with systemic exploitation. Their solution was therefore to create places to shelter from real life, where they could cultivate their own emancipation and take refuge from the

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A nutritious dish of corn and beans mostly fed to children

exclusionary logics of meritocracy or personal success. Biko wrote, “*material* want is *bad* enough, *but* coupled with *spiritual poverty*, it *kills*” (Biko in Stubbs 1987: 28).

Everyday appropriation in the township – in terms of making it appropriate for the life of its residents – was fuelled by a constant tension between calls for the state to intervene to redistribute resources and improve services, and individual and collective actions aimed at personal fulfilment and greater mental and physical health. With the re-emergence of radical thought and the incorporation of neoliberal policies during post-apartheid, expectations of democracy did not focus so much on freedom as on vague understandings of universal wellbeing.

Conclusion. Against the state?

In this thesis, I analysed the practices of appropriation observable from the RLMCP project within a twenty-year period from 1996 to 2016. My starting point was to refuse to reduce appropriation to mere adherence to the aims of the project or to the management of the project as *stakeholders*, or to the mere occupation or claiming of ownership of a project by those living nearby. Rather, starting from the etymological meaning of appropriation as the act of "making one's own" and "making fit", I proposed a definition of the phenomenon that would allow for the consideration of both appropriation practices that operate on the material level and those that operate on the symbolic level, and that interact with both the dimension of time and the dimension of space. I also gave great importance to the relational dimension of appropriation, understood as the unfolding of power relations, but also as a way of defining identity. I therefore analysed appropriation practices in relation to three aspects, which I called scores, i.e. interweaving phenomena involving different actors: change, belonging and citizenship.

By analysing the way in which a series of public problems - such as marginality, unemployment, decay - for which the RLMCP is presented as the solution have been put on the agenda at Red Location, and by tracing the transformation of the location into an extraordinary place and the construction of the development agenda at Red Location, I have shown how different practices of appropriation accompany the projects from their conception, and how the projects themselves are forms of appropriation of a place, and of its representation of the past and future. I also analysed how the representations produced by the project are then further re-appropriated by the residents.

Understanding the RLMCP as a device for governing social interactions, I reconstructed the prescriptions of conduct inherent in the project. I have shown that the disciplining implicit in the RLMCP is functional to the construction of social cohesion and the appeal to individual freedom, two neo-liberal oriented elements at the foundation of the new South African nation, and highlighted how the project draws on the oppressor-oppressor dialectic, i.e. the formula through which the South African political transition took shape. I then analysed the conflict around the RLMCP, pointing out how the residents' protests and their occupation of the buildings cannot

be interpreted as mere hostility to the project, but as an implicit response to the simplifications generated by the promoters' intentions to discipline. I considered the residents' criticisms and claims from the perspective of the multiple affiliations to which the residents of the location ascribe and from the asymmetric and stratified citizenship of which the townships are an expression. Analysing the multiplicity of memberships led me to understand how they are further reformulated in the course of the conflict and allowed me to reflect on the relationship between national and ordinary citizenship.

Finally, I have considered the conflict over dwelling that takes place in Red Location as a useful level of analysis for understanding how, through the appropriation of protest practices, information, contacts, and transversal knowledge, township residents express a demand for recognition and come to expand the boundaries of substantive citizenship. I have also analysed how residents' relationship to history and memory takes the form of a series of appropriation practices that challenge the representation of history crystallised in the Red Location Museum and express a demand for experience-based legitimisation. Extending my observation to the appropriation practices of everyday life, I have shown how the various groups that structure themselves within the township aim to bring about a moral regeneration, which is realised through the preservation and creation of spaces made comfortable, shared, hospitable, healthy and decent, as well as through the securing of public places. The practices of appropriation consist of the effort to transform the township from a space originally designed to turn residents into obedient citizens to a space that allows itself to be designed and transformed to suit its inhabitants. I have also highlighted how practices of appropriation are ascribed to the confrontation, competition and cooperation that characterise the everydayness of democracy both in South Africa and elsewhere.

Observing ownership practices ultimately led me to question the way in which inhabitants perceive citizenship and act as citizens, and thus the relationship between rulers and ruled, elected and voters, but also the relationship between citizens and the city, and citizens and the state. Reflecting on ownership highlights some useful elements in understanding how processes of governance are constructed, how the state experience is lived on a daily basis, and what is the role of conflict in South African democracy.

Ownership and governance processes

Gillian P. Hart argues that the 'developmental local state' has become the seat of the contradictions of the post-apartheid government, and the site of expression of the most vulnerable side of neo-liberal capitalism (2002: 12). Indeed, in South Africa, it is at the local level that the greatest friction between institutions and citizens seems to occur. Protests in townships are subject to two recurrent interpretations: on the one hand they are seen as the deliberate rejection of neo-liberal policies and their effects (Bond 2004; McDonald 2002; Oldfield and Greyling 2015), and on the other they are portrayed as spontaneous and uncontrolled reactions to adverse living conditions. The latter reading is the most frequent in the media and political debate.

In the first case, the movements that develop in the township are accused of being 'ultra-left²⁸¹', that is, of being the last anachronistic legacy of the anti-apartheid movements, in a context where what is needed is no longer revolution, but reconstruction. In the second case, protests are mostly referred to as a law and order problem in a state where the memory of violence constantly reiterates the non-peaceful expression of dissent.

In many cases, protests are interpreted as open acts of opposition by residents and as the consequence of the state choosing to minimise itself, delegating the performance of its most critical functions to non-governmental organisations, private individuals or development agencies. Above all, the state seems to be withdrawing from the protection of secondary rights, that is, the socio-economic rights articulated in the South African Constitution. The attention of scholars concerned about the gradual disappearance of the state from townships ends up focusing on the self-organisation, resilience, resistance and autonomy of citizens vis-à-vis the state (Zuern 2011; Chance 2015; Makhulu 2015; Teppo and Houssay-Holzschuch 2013; McDonald 2012). Observing the practices of appropriation at Red Location, however, highlights how the RLMCP project itself is a sign of the presence of the state 'by other means', i.e. through delegation and intermediation, and represents the desire to affirm the

²⁸¹ The term 'ultra-left' refers to an expression coined by President Thabo Mbeki to refer to the socialist factions within the tripartite alliance, namely ANC, Congress of South African Trade Unions (COSATU) and the South African Communist Party (SACP). Mbeki saw the ultra-left as a destabilising force for the alliance.

centrality of the public sector in development policies, at least as the engine leading to private investments and with a role of guaranteeing and hedging investment risks.

With regard to the RLMCP, the *business plan* states that once the complex is fully operational, it could be managed by a private company. The case of the RLMCP suggests that in townships 'the state does matter' (Bayat, 2009). This is why the citizens of Red Location seek to relate with local administrators and navigate party dynamics, appealing to institutions before individual personalities. Residents' claims and protests are both an indication of the presence of the state and an expression of the inhabitants' desire to increase and diversify this presence. Conflict, therefore, is a privileged level of analysis through which to read the presence and shortcomings of the state, as well as the ways in which citizens contribute to making the state.

The conflict around the RLMCP is certainly fostered by miscommunication, or lack of foresight, however it cannot simply be seen as the failure of local government, but rather as a moment of confrontation between government and citizens in which groups of residents are able to assert their claims. The conflict itself can be read as an expression of different ways of interpreting the South African constitution and social contract from dissimilar worldviews. The hostage-taking of the cultural complex is a reminder of the accountability and political responsibility of the administrators, and is in fact an exchange linked to the fulfilment of promises (once the houses are renovated and rebuilt, the residents hand over the keys). The occupation of the RLMCP is itself a piece - anomalous but not unrelated to the history of protest practices in South Africa - of the construction of the process of governance.

More generally, in Red Location it is possible to identify three modes of governance that develop from different appropriation efforts: negotiation, the creation of connections between individuals and social partners, and poaching or erosion. Regarding negotiation, residents, officials, political representatives, and artists participate in the governance of the location by trying to acquire adequate power and negotiating credibility on issues of their interest. Appropriation in this case concerns the obtaining of something that can be further exchanged (e.g. the occupation of museum buildings), but also the occupation or garrisoning of something symbolic (including a certain identity representation or narrative of history), or something that has acquired strategic importance, or something that has been previously constructed and conquered and whose permanence is to be ensured. Bayat

points out that usually 'the actors' confrontation with the authorities does not take place with regard to the conquest of an advantage, but mainly with regard to the defence and expansion of already conquered advantages' (Bayat 2000: 550). Actors seek to gain control over something that is believed to be important for the future, as is the case in Red Location and New Brighton for spaces that might otherwise be occupied by criminal groups or used for activities that are perceived to be harmful to the community. Control or possession, whether legitimate or illegitimate, involves increasing the ability to influence decisions about the intended use or future of a space or object.

It is also governed through the creation of connections and networks. To take ownership of a common problem (e.g. development), to adapt a solution in a way that is as consensual as possible (e.g. housing renovation), to take ownership of knowledge and reuse it (as is the case with residents' knowledge of bureaucracy and municipal regulations), to belong to a given community, to a group (the exploited, the oppressed, but also residents, officials, decent people), to understand the reasons of others: these are all activities that make it possible to overcome certain divisions and even, if necessary, to cross barricades, without considering oneself or being considered a traitor. At Red Location, one connects to ask for help and support, but also to influence, convince, broaden consensus. Creating connections also means identifying numerous and diverse borders of inclusion-exclusion, with often blurred and overlapping boundaries. In the case of Red Location, the clear identification of friends and foes, allies and competitors is an arduous task: each is a little of one and a little of the other depending on the objects and claims considered, and the period of time. Even in the field of identity representation, appropriation establishes symbolic connections of various kinds, allowing individuals to break out of isolation, free themselves from assigned identities, bind themselves to worlds and places far removed from each other (identifying themselves as cosmopolitan, African, member of the Methodist church, etc.) and express alternative social representations to those based on racial categorisations or class.

The practices of appropriation also account for the processes of governance that occur through actions of erosion and 'poaching'. De Certeau states that "everyday life invents itself through endless poaching on the property of others" (De Certeau 1984: 12), referring to the personal trajectories of culture users or consumers, which

imply other uses of cultural or consumer objects than those considered by their creators. The scholar argues that 'the presence and circulation of a representation (imparted by preachers, educators and popularisers, as the key to socio-economic advancement) tells us nothing about what it is to its users. We must first analyse the manipulation of the users who are not its creators' (1984: 13). The RLMCP field shows how representations are reappropriated and thus also despoiled and reformulated by the various actors. Through his conception of the extended state, Gramsci emphasises the dialectical relations between civil society and the state, that is, their thinkability in terms of unity and difference. If civil society is the space of consensus, public opinion is connected "with political hegemony, it is the point of contact between civil society and political society, between consensus and force²⁸²". Actors, therefore, in dialogue, share the same political, economic and social system and, through confrontation, arrive at small erosions of the hegemonic framework. To erode does not exactly mean to modify, and at the same time what is eroded changes form. At Red Location the questioning of the institutional framework or the construction of citizenship is not an explicit or intended end, but on certain issues and in certain ways, it does happen. Starting with a discussion on the future of the RLMCP, we end up talking about economic and social rights, equality, social justice.

The conflict around the RLMCP itself can contribute to governance: on the one hand, the conflict is what allows residents to increase their influence over the governance of the township, broadening the ways in which they can participate in decisions about the future of the location, i.e. going beyond the range of possibilities established by law; on the other hand, it is through conflict management, mediation operations, the organisation of public confrontation sessions, promises and concessions that the local government governs the day-to-day life of the location.

This type of conflict, urban and on issues of access to services and public interest, develops around precise canons that have been consolidated over time. The Red Location protests are not the spontaneous expression of discontent: they are part of a long history of protest and resistance practices that has composed a language and an alphabet. Today's residents also write by appropriating and making use of these signs: sometimes they copy, sometimes they invent new words. The same goes for the

²⁸² A. Gramsci, Q 7, 83: 914. See gramsciproject.org, entry: 'consensus'.

municipality. Sometimes it resorts to the language of previous administrations, even those ostracised by the present, other times it draws on contemporary and international practices. In the history of the location, conflict, declined in various forms, has been constituted as the moment of the unveiling and articulation of different ways of thinking about the relationship between the governors and the governed, between the elected and the electorate.

Conflict is also a way of bringing political leadership and citizens closer together, it is a call by citizens for proximity and for a closer relationship with the local, and it expresses the need for a change of perspective: it invites the leadership to think about the city from a specific space. In an extremely fragmented city like Port Elizabeth, the conflict has consolidated itself as a demand for decentralisation of the places of political decision-making, so much so that, in the last business plan of the project, drawn up before the occupation of the buildings, the promoters of the RLMCP envisage moving part of the Municipality's offices inside the cultural complex.

Analysing the contemporary conflict in Red Location through the practices of appropriation that run through it allows us to relate it to past conflicts, abandoning a periodization that draws a clear line between apartheid and post-apartheid and re-reading apartheid in terms of a government of the everyday, unquestionably oppressive and violent, but still constituted by the proximity between administrators, officials and citizens and their interactions. Relating past and present conflicts and practices of appropriation is not a way to normalise or minimise apartheid, but, on the contrary, to think of residents as actors and agents, now as then, and also in a limiting and segregating context. The interest is also to restore complexity to a historical narrative that sees the political transition as a kind of *cordon sanitaire* designed to ensure that the present is not contaminated by the past. As is evident from the biographical accounts and reflections of the residents, the apartheid and post-apartheid times are much closer than they are portrayed. In memories they sometimes interpenetrate and blur. Transition is the time of the laborious coexistence of past and present. Azola Dayile, a 20-year-old poet from Kwazakhele, the township bordering New Brighton, in a poem dedicated to the place he lives in writes: 'There is none else/But to mourn/Both equally your death/And perilous being²⁸³ '.

²⁸³ Dayile, *Requiem for Kwazakhele* accessible at www.badilishapoetry.com.

Citizenship, between space and memory

The analysis of appropriation practices is also functional in understanding the state experience and the relationship with the space and memory of the city of the residents of Red Location. The demands for recognition that derive from the appropriation practices identifiable in Red Location are the result of an obligatory exercise of self-determination. Rokkan described citizenship as the right to have roots ('right to roots') and at the same time the right to have options ('right to options'): that is, the citizen has the right to have a territory or a community as a reference, and at the same time to choose the place where he or she can have as many opportunities as possible, i.e. also to move to another reference system, another territory, etc. (Rokkan 1970).

Appropriation concerns a series of practices linked to both the sphere of roots and the sphere of options, dealing with both attachment and affection, and with change and the creation of new opportunities. Substantial citizenship is rooted in the local dimension and insists on social rights, it is a "site of individual and collective identity production" (La Bella and Santoro 2011: 25) and creates the conditions for "recognition and [of] self-recognition; that is, where citizens have the opportunity to discover who they are, and not only what they have" (La Bella and Santoro 2011: 25).

The protests around the RLMCP, at Red Location, emphasise this dimension of rethinking the self, not least because, more than others, they are struggles rooted in the present, but strongly linked to the past. Appropriation practices establish an inseparable link between citizenship, space and memory. In Red Location, the citizen is first and foremost an inhabitant and a resident, and indeed, if he/she cannot inhabit it worthily, his/her citizenship is diluted and diminished. In addition, the relationship with space and with others is consolidated through time and experience: the ability to be able to read change and to preserve one's own memories, or to translate those of others into one's own, are fundamental aspects of citizenship. Citizenship is made up of multiple and interconnected belongings, which are expressed simultaneously with national belonging, which, however, on its own, is an empty descriptor and does not suffice to explain the citizen, nor to make him/her such.

The analysis of appropriation practices around the RLMCP also allowed me to observe the construction of public spaces. In South Africa itself, there is a tendency to

justify the disputes that occur in or about public spaces as being due to the fact that South African citizens are not accustomed to this kind of notion, as in the townships gathering spaces were reduced to a minimum, and today the neo-liberal city tends to build fortified neighbourhoods within cities, creating new separations. Certainly the topographical structure, the legacy of apartheid and the feeling of insecurity make the construction of public spaces very difficult, especially if they are understood in an idealised and idealised way, i.e. as spaces to which all citizens have equal access and in which all share the same idea of collectivity, community, decorum or respect. Yet the RLMCP field is a public space, at least from the point of view of the conflict that has taken root there, which in fact involves a large number of institutional and non-institutional actors, who also argue over a definition of collective good. The residents of Red Location have identified the RLMCP as a space through which concerns and claims can be brought out and pooled, and, moreover, they have leveraged the deepest and most ambiguous meaning of that very space: public space is for everyone, and therefore it is also theirs. And it is especially theirs, since they live nearby, and so it is surely here that the municipality has provided for them to come and socialise, learn, spend time.

Analysing the residents' relationship with the RLMCP makes one realise how public space is a space that needs multiple individual and collective appropriations to be considered as such; that is, public space is always someone's space, and, first and foremost, it is the municipality's space. The residents seem to set an *aut aut*: either it is considered first and foremost as belonging to the location, or it is considered as belonging first and foremost to the city. But in the latter case, residents end up reading it as an enclave, and not as a truly appropriatable space. As one official effectively summed it up: 'to maintain a house properly, you have to own it!²⁸⁴'.

Subalternity and citizenship

Starting from appropriation has allowed me to use other categories to read social relations, diluting, but not ignoring or rejecting, the dominant-dominated dialectic: after all, the first to read social relations as relations of power are precisely the

²⁸⁴ "To keep a house in a proper way you must be the owner!". Interview conducted on 04/11/2015.

residents, who, strengthened by this awareness, act accordingly. Exploring appropriation as a relation has led me to read subalternity relations rather than a repertoire of subalterns. Rather than talking about *urban subaltern* (Roy 2011; Bayat 2009; Ismail 2013; Denis and Zerah 2017) I found it more appropriate to talk about 'subalternity relations'. Valentina Pazé writes: "There is no 'look from nowhere' from which to make impartial judgements. The point of view of those who, from the outside, judge the behaviour of others in terms of subalternity has nothing objective about it. It is, trivially, the subjective viewpoint of a person other than the alleged subaltern. Not necessarily more rational, wise or coherent than him' (Pazé 2014: 95). Drawing from Guido Liguori, Pazé identifies at least three ways in which Gramsci formulates the characteristics of subalternity, which can be ascribed to a group's incapacity for autonomous initiative and organisation, to a condition of a group expressed in a collective consciousness and the consequent struggle for the conquest of hegemony, and to the psychological disposition of those who allow themselves to be influenced or dragged along because they are incapable of analysis (Liguori 2011).

None of these three formulations can be said to be the defining characteristic of Red Location residents. Instead, it is possible to state that there are power relations in the location that can be traced back to one or the other aspect of subalternity. Living in the township does not automatically entitle one to the label of subaltern, but rather means being subject to relations of subalternity. While it is inaccurate to speak of subalterns in Red Location, it is much more straightforward to speak of citizens. The awareness that they are citizens, and South African citizens, is evident and is the starting and ending point of the protests. This does not give the inhabitants the strength to self-organise permanently, nor does it give them unlimited *agency* or blind faith in the common future, nor does it prevent despair and the difficulties of everyday life from extinguishing interest in collective life. Quite simply, there is an awareness of being entitled to rights, even where these rights are not guaranteed, respected or exercised.

Analysing the practices of appropriation, the practices even before their results, regardless of their effectiveness, has led me away both from a narrative of the residents' journey that emphasises the emancipation aspect, and from labelling the institutions as the devil. Red Location is not a den of rebels, any more than the

departments of the municipality are made up of a collection of narrow-minded and conservative officials.

Appropriation practices are acts that consider different kinds of horizons: sometimes they are actions of urgency, sometimes they are actions projected into a more distant future, sometimes they are the fruit of a utopia. To establish what, among all these actions, entails a rebellion or a resistance, and which, among them, is more interesting or more profound than another, would be to carry out an absolutely subjective operation, and, in many cases, an a posteriori reconstruction of non-existent intentions; or perhaps existing, but contradictory, not always clear and in any case unsuitable for the drafting of a mythology. Nor is the promoters' strategy decided from the outset. Their appropriation practices also follow a path at different speeds, proceeding by trial and error. Appropriation outlines a series of attempts, a few tactics, and very few certainties.

In "From Dangerous Classes to Quiet Rebels", Bayat traces the theories and ways in which subalterns have been studied in urban space, starting with Marx and ending with contemporary theories. The article reviews the various perspectives (from *empowerment* to *spatial solidarity* to the *resistance paradigm*) to end with the author's "quiet encroachment". Its aim is to highlight how from a representation of the urban subaltern as a passive subject one arrives at the reading of his every gesture as an act of resistance (e.g. through Scott's studies in the 1980s), and then returns to an analysis in which the idea of intentionality is substantially more mitigated and the potential for opposition and political organisation is considered from the specificities of contexts.

The question of intentionality accompanied my research from the very beginning. To what extent did the residents of Red Location feel they wanted to become 'quite rebels' (Bayat 2000)? Is it rebellion to occupy buildings? And building a *safe place*? What can be the revolutionary scope of demanding the renovation of the social housing in which one lives? And that of striving for moral regeneration? In the specific case of the protests around the RLMCP, neither the category of rebellion nor that of resistance seemed to me to be useful in analysing very different actions, carried out by individuals who chose to come together in committees, but who never started a movement, let alone tried to broaden support. The support desired by residents is the support of institutions, conceived in their most visible form, i.e. as a set of public

officials and administrators with whom it is possible to communicate, and whom it is necessary to call to account. The call for the institutions' intervention is not an act of submission, but is interpreted as a right of citizenship and as the first step towards correcting systemic inequality.

At Red Location, it was clear from the outset that the intentionality of acts is not always proportional to effectiveness. The strength of what actors do results also by the way in which the action is received. When the residents took possession of the buildings, they did not think that this act of appropriation would weigh so heavily and last so long. At that moment there was no idea of opening a long-term conflict, nor the thought of being able to occupy for years. The resistance of the actors, understood as the intensity and durability of their occupation, was in turn dependent on the institutions, which never opted for forced eviction.

Drawing a direct link between everyday life and survival, and between survival and resistance, or even survival and opposition, does not seem to me the most appropriate way to represent a very diverse multitude of people sharing similar living conditions. Not everyone feels the need to understand their survival as a form of resistance, and not everyone has the means or the possibility to do so. In many cases, the desire for integration is stronger than the desire to oppose the system.

The protests of the citizens of Red Location and their efforts to appropriate and reinvent the township spaces account for an attempt to achieve prosperity and self-realisation. In themselves, the protests do not constitute an open or coherent contestation to neoliberal thinking and its translation into public policy, but they do criticise its effects, advocating for rehumanisation and rebalancing. To account for the inconsistencies between criticism of the system and the desire for integration, and the conflicting tensions between a sense of inevitability or a commitment to change, is not only necessary, but also indispensable to recognise that the location is embedded in a global contemporaneity. The finding of the presence of similar dynamics, north and south of the planet, can only lead to rethinking theoretical boundaries, which are no less limiting than geographical ones. In the case of the RLMCP, the significance of the observed practices can be explained and analysed regardless of its immersion in the theoretical paradigm of the Global South. The creation of the RLMCP and its contestation are, after all, an expression of the same neo-liberal politics, the same questions about contradictions and the same demands for change that we can observe

in European, Asian or North American cities. The discursive formulations and social practices that are created at the intersection of these tensions cannot be reduced to the response of the peripheries to the imposition of the policies of an identifiable centre, but rather must be read from the perspective of a continuous circulation and interaction between actors.

My main aim has been to analyse the practices of ownership by combining being and having, material and symbolic planes, action and projection of the self, and trying to speak of life rather than survival, that is, of an everyday life not reduced to the bone, but strongly imbued with codes and moral orders. Telling the normality of the township is much more difficult than telling its alleged exception, not least because one cannot draw on the sometimes exoticist vocabulary with which one tends to trace the margins and then tell about the marginalised of the township.

Describing living, and “continuing to have” in all its declinations, allowed me to speak of dignity, suffering or hope without therefore mythologising or stigmatising the everyday life of the residents. I understood Red Location as a place where the search for and construction of a substantial citizenship are customary, with all the difficulties and achievements it entails, and this is enough to make its ordinariness extremely meaningful.

The analysis of this paper stops at 2016 and the handing back of the keys to the mayor, with a view to the reopening of the museum and the continuation of work on the completion of the cultural complex, at a date to come. Certainly there will still much to be written on the redemption of Red Location, and how to produce it, imagine it, appropriate or counter it.

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Attachments

Annex 1: Cartography

Fig.1. The metropolitan city of Nelson Mandela Bay and Red Location. (1) Port Elizabeth; (2) Uitenhage; (3) Despatch. Source: elaboration on OpenstreetMap map base.

Fig. 2. Red Location, New Brighton, Ibhayi. Black rectangle: RLMCP area, larger rectangle: ward 15 boundaries. Dashed red line: approximation of the boundaries of New Brighton according to residents. Source: Elaboration on OpenStreetMap map base.

Fig. 3. The development of New Brighton township from 1902/3 to 1952/4. Phases of development: (1) Red Location 1902-3; (2) White Location 1925-8; (3) McNamee Village 1938-43; (4) Kwaford 1948-51; (5) Boastville 1948-9; (6) Elundini 1951-4. Source: Data compiled from Baines (2002) and Robison (1996) on GoogleMaps map base.

Fig. 4. *RLMCP and surroundings* (2015). Source: Elaboration on GoogleMaps map base.

Annex 2: Mapping the struggle

The following is a description of the sites and related events that are most frequently mentioned in the descriptions of the history of Red Location and New Brighton. The descriptions to which I refer are contained in: the location history compendia produced by the promoters of the RLMCP and attached to the various master plans or project presentations; the location history accessible through the official RLM website, the insert of the local newspaper *The Herald* entirely dedicated to New Brighton and its history¹.

- (1). Migrant Workers' Hostel The hostel, together with the original dwellings, is seen as the symbol of the living conditions of unaccompanied migrant workers. Now disused, it is located on Singhapi road, the access road to the cultural complex.
- (2-3). The railway station and the Rio cinema, now converted into a church, contain all the symbolic significance of the 1950s, and in particular of the *Defiance Campaign* and *Paint Riot*. In 1952, the *Defiance Campaign* started at the railway

¹ See the museum website: <www.freewebs.com/redlocationmuseum>; the insert *New Brighton celebrating 110 years*, 'The Herald', 13/07/2013; the *Draft proposal for the upliftment of Singaphi street, New Brighton, as a tourist attraction*, Red Location Museum Staff, 2013; the *Urgent appeal for the long overdue rectification of RDP houses*, Office of cllr Jv Tutu, Ward 15, 2010;

station. Begun with a large rally and prayer meeting, the Campaign, launched by the ANC-SAIC, South African Indian Council, consisted of breaking the rule that blacks were not allowed to enter whites-only spaces: firstly thirty volunteers, led by Raymond Mhlaba, and, after about fifteen days, another eighty-five, had crossed the whites-only entrance to the New Brighton railway station. The Campaign continued with a series of strikes involving some eight hundred and fifty people. During this period the number of NCA members increased dramatically. The *Defiance Campaign*, which had spread nationally, is seen as a decisive event in the choice of the Congress' strategy of struggle. In late 1952 *Paint Riot* erupted: two policemen attempted to stop two men at New Brighton station, suspected of stealing a can of paint from another station. The men resisted and were helped by other passengers. During the scuffle, an officer killed one of the men. A spontaneous riot against the police broken out. The policemen fired into the crowd. One white man was killed. The victims had been seven black and four whites persons, as well as many injured. The white residents of New Brighton fled the township. The Rio cinema, New Brighton's only movie theatre, was burnt down as a result of the riots and the owner and two staff members lost their lives. The riots represented a very strong break from the protest actions that had preceded them and heralded a new season of strong repression, culminating in the banning of the ANC IN 1960. Today there is a church in place of the Rio cinema, which has retained the building's original structure.

(4-5). The late 1950s - early 1960s is evoked by the basement spaces and hiding places in the wooden and tin houses dating back to the establishment of the township (4) and the *Emlotheni Memorial* (5). The rows of houses that housed the workers and their families recall to the creation of the Umkhonto WeSizwe (MK). The MK, created in 1961, marked the transition of the ANC to armed struggle, and saw the organisation of one of the first cells at Red Location². The MK acted through sabotage actions, which also led to the death of some civilians.

² The motivations for the creation of the MK are listed in a document entitled 'Outline of a Syllabus for a brief course on the Training of Organisers' in which the objective of the MK is identified as the acceleration of the ANC's programme, in the face of the fact that the peaceful resistance campaigns had not had the desired effect and in the meantime the apartheid government's repression had intensified. 'Port Elizabeth became the centre of sabotage training (...) of all the actions cited in the subsequent Rivonia trial, 35 per cent emanated from the Eastern Cape' (SADET 2005:120).

Its members were trained in other African states and often remained in exile. Sabotage targets in Port Elizabeth included the New Brighton Labour Bureau, a power station also in New Brighton and the offices of the *Bantu administration board* and the *Bantu Education Department*. Vuysile Mini and the other five activists belonged to what was probably the first commando of the MK. The accounts of the location history always include the launching of the M-Plan, carried out by Mandela, who was present in person at the location, following the ban of the ANC. The plan called for the construction of a complex network for each township, made up of small cells corresponding to about ten dwellings capable of providing political education and recruiting new members. The cells were then coordinated by a *chief steward*³. Red Location is in fact one of the few places where this plan has actually been implemented. The presence of Mandela, who came to coordinate the operations, is seen as a kind of proof of the centrality of the location in the anti-apartheid struggle.

(6-7). The site of the TC White hall in Red Location (6) and the Centenary Great Hall in New Brighton (7) recall the Young Lions revolt. Red Location, New Brighton, Kwazakhele, Zwide, remained prominent locations in the anti-apartheid struggle in the 1970s and 1980s. The *struggle* was mainly led by civil society organisations (*civic organisations*), as the NCA was banned and its members were forced into hiding. In July 1976, following the tragic outcome of the student riots in Soweto⁴, an uprising also broke out in Port Elizabeth in connection with the protests against Bantu Education, an educational system whose aim was to centralise the education of the black population in the hands of the state, in order to control and keep down the level of schooling of the *African working class*. At the Centenary Great Hall, a large hall in Ntshekisa road, New Brighton, a boxing tournament was in progress; the agents, trying to prevent the crowd

³ Mhlaba and Mufamadi (2001: 95).

⁴ On 16 June 1976 in Soweto, Johannesburg, the police killed at least 23 people - this is the official number, but to this day it is not clear how many people were actually victims of the police repression, some sources speak of two hundred, including many minors - who had gathered at a march from Phefeni high school to Orlando Stadium, to protest against Bantu Education and in particular against a measure that consisted in the introduction of Afrikaans in basic education and the recognition of this language with a status that placed it on a par with English. The violent repression of this peaceful demonstration led to the spread of protests nationwide. The events in Soweto also had strong repercussions internationally, with expressions of strong dissent directed at the apartheid government. In particular, the riots sealed the entry of students and youth organisations into the anti-apartheid struggle.

from entering, shot and wounded four people: it was the spark that preceded a long series of clashes. The student movement (the young activists were then nicknamed Young Lions) was organised from the *high school* in Kwazakhele, where in 1977 thirty-one students were accused of terrorism and arrested. The uprising in Kwazakhele, New Brighton and Zwide became so large that in November 1976 all primary and secondary school students in Port Elizabeth went on strike. In New Brighton the police arrested 474 boys⁵. In 1977, the death of Stephen Biko, the leader of the South African Student Organisation (SASO) from which the Black Consciousness Movement (BCM) started, due to his arrest and detention in maximum security in Port Elizabeth, contributed to the escalation of violence. The mysterious death of Siphiso Maxwell 'Congress' Mthimkhulu, a student from Kwazakhele, member of the South African Student Movement (SASM), and later leader of the Congress of South African Students (COSAS), who was first poisoned with thallium while detained at the PE police station and later abducted and barbarically murdered along with his friend Topsy Madaka in Cradock is to this day evoked by Port Elizabeth activists as a symbol of the heinousness of the Nationalist Party regime.

(8-9). In the ANC's vision, schools and *bottle* shops (i.e. state-owned alcohol outlets) represented different expressions of the same oppression: if schools kept blacks subservient through *Bantu education*, local government control over the production and sale of beer in the townships was seen as a way of making the locals weak by incentivising and pandering to heavy drinking. In reality, the apartheid government had an ambivalent relationship with *beer halls* and taverns (*shabeens*), oscillating between total repression, widespread control and in later years more *laissez-faire*. In 1984, a new organisation joined the young students in the townships: the Amabutho, volunteers organised as veritable militias. Some of them were members of the Port Elizabeth Youth Congress (PEYCO), a PRO-ANC youth organisation that in the 1990s would coalesce into the ANC Youth League. At Red Location the Amabutho burnt down the *bottle store* that has now been converted into a hostel (9). Another bottle store was

⁵ SADET (2005: 587).

located on Mendi road (8). The redevelopment of this building has been ongoing for many years.

Annex 3: Images

1. RLMCP: FROM PROJECT TO UTOPIA

Fig. 1. RLMCP members return the keys to Executive Major Danny Jordan (26/05/2016). Source: SABC news.

Fig. 2. Red Location structure plan (1996). The first plan for a cultural complex at Red Location designed by architects Rushmere and Thompson. The original plan also included a housing part, not for residents of the location, but for guests at conferences, festivals etc. Source: Rory Riordan personal archive.

Fig. 3. *Projection of the RLMCP upon completion (2012)*. Legend: 1. 1000-seat theatre (*planned in phase 3*); 2. Museum and restaurant (completed), 3. Library (completed, but not equipped), 4. Art gallery (completed), 5. 400-seat theatre (*planned in phase 3*), 6. Music school (*planned in phase 3*). 2012. Source: Rory Riordan personal archive. Other elements were also proposed, but were not all included in the business plan, or were included at first and then excluded. For example, a memorial statue of the Rivonia Trial, which is still in the business plan, a recording room for a local television station, a meeting room for the City Council.

Fig. 4. J. Noero, A. Factor and D. Long, *The Transformation of Red Location (2012)*, 19.4 x 3, 5 m, ink on paper, presented at the *Venice Biennale*. In this large plan, Noero imagines the completed RLMCP, the realised housing projects, the construction of car parks, the creation of urban gardens. It is a portrait of a smart neighbourhood and a connected community. Source: noeroarchitects.com.

Fig. 5. Above: *Section of the social houses planned for Red Location* (not yet realised). Below: *Section of the PELIP houses, already realised (1999)*. Source: noeroarchitects.com. In explanation of the project, Noero reports: "The construction of the project buildings will require the displacement of 150 families living in the *shacks* to a space immediately adjacent to the project space. From the drawings it is possible to understand the kind of neighbourhood, and community, that the project aims to build: there is public greenery, people walk in the street, children play football, shops are nearby.

Fig. 6. *Promotional poster of the museum, designed by A. Du Plessis (2010)*. The last image on the bottom right, the hand with the red ribbon, is one of the museum's logos. The expressions 'Shaap' and 'Hola7' are colloquial and youthful expressions of the Xhosa majority townships. "Shaap" means "OK, perfect" and "Hola7" is one of the ways of asking "how are you?".

Fig. 7. Book and magazine covers depicting the RLMCP. Top left: *Architect*, 1999. The image reproduces a detail of Noero's design and depicts the memory boxes and the light effect referring to the twilight memory concept; bottom left: *Sustainable Community Planning Guide*. The first image at the top of the magazine shows the PELIP Houses. The middle image is from the *Digest of South African Architecture*, 2012. The image depicts the art gallery and the wood and sheet metal house that has been preserved on the outside. On the bottom right is the cover of *Contemporary South African Architecture in a Landscape of Transition*, 2006. The image depicts the entrance to the museum and the courtyard in front.

2. The RLMCP: A PLACE

Fig. 8. *Red Location's original sheet metal houses (2008)*. The photo was taken in the space that now stands in front of the art gallery. These houses were destroyed. Some pieces were salvaged for the construction of *shacks*. Source: A. du Plessis.

Fig. 9. The *entrance to the RLMCP from Singhapi road* (2015). The larger panel shows all the components of the cultural complex. In the distance, one notices the library building (right), the outdoor projection screen in the amphitheatre (left) and the museum building (left). Source: Art Station.

Fig. 10. Exterior of the *museum* (2015). In the afternoon, the museum's outdoor space is transformed into a playground. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 11. *RLM entrance and PELIP houses* (2015). Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 12. *Space outside the library* (2015). The benches running along the outside walls of the library are one of the haunts of teenagers and young people in the neighbourhood. On the ground: rubble, dried leaves and litter. Source: Art Station.

Fig. 13. *Red Location Lodge* (2015). Hostel adjacent to the museum. The red container at the bottom is the *Red Location Café*, which was always closed during my stay. Source: Art Station.

Fig. 14. *Signs hanging at the entrances to the buildings of the cultural complex* (2015). The one on the left, hanging in front of the Art Gallery, and drawn up by the RLSC, reads: 'This complex has [been] closed by the community. No one is allowed to [stay] in the vicinity without the presence of the RLSC. We are not responsible for what might happen to those who enter. By order of the president'. The one on the right, hanging at the museum entrance, written by the museum staff, reads: 'The museum is temporarily closed. We apologise for any inconvenience: The RLM is closed due to community protests. For more information please contact the Museum's Assistant Director, Christopher du Preez (contact details follow)'. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 15. Vuyo Nyambayo, left, and Mxolisi Nduvane, right, members of the RLSC, talk outside the museum (2015). Source: M. Montanini.

Fig 16. Residents' protests in front of the RLM (2009). Source: The Herald

Fig. 17. Poster for the exhibition 'Truth be told. A visual story about the reasons why the RLM WAS closed by the Red Location community' (2016). The exhibition, also sponsored by the Municipality, was organised by artists Banele Njadayi, Bamanye Lethu Ngxale and Zinziswa Mavuso, at the Opera House.

Fig. 18. *Original dwelling preserved outside the art gallery (2015). One wall is painted in the colours of the ANC. Behind it, some panels can be glimpsed above which the history of the houses in the location is told. The panels are badly damaged.*

Fig. 19. *Art Station member Thabo balancing on the iron fence around the old Red Location house (2015). Source: Art Station.*

3. A LOOK AROUND THE RLMCP

Fig. 20. *Neighbourhood shop* (2015). Shop on Avenue A, the parallel street to Singaphi road, access road to the RLMCP. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 21. *Mechanic* (2015). Near Singaphi road. In the background *middle-class* houses. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 22. *Phone card shop, mobile phone repair and greengrocer* (2015). Photo taken near the RLMCP. Source: Art Station

Fig. 23. *Methodist Church* (2015). Source: Art Station

Fig. 24. *Methodist Church* (2015) near the RLMCP. Source: Art Station.

Fig. 25. *Social Houses* (2015). South West side of the RLMCP. Source: Art Station

Fig. 26. *Shacks*, informal habitation (2015). South side of the RLMCP. Source: Art Station

4. "APPROPRIATED" SPACES

Fig. 27. *Dudley Tito's studio (1)* (2015). Dudley Tito was a long-time Red Location jazz musician who passed away in 2016 at the age of 75. The studio, on Avenue A, was housed in a room built in the backyard, a courtyard behind the house. Tito had several contacts with the RLM: an interview with him was used as a source for an exhibition on the music of New Brighton and he also played on several occasions at events organised by the museum before it closed. In an interview, however, he urged the City Council to address the housing and unemployment problems of Red Location before thinking about the museum. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 28. *Dudley Tito's studio (2)* (2015). Tito collected posters of New Brighton music performances, from the 1980s to the present day, collected all around the backyard walls. The

photo shows one of Tito's most treasured posters: it is a poster announcing a concert in New Brighton's Rio Cinema that Tito had organised for the same day as Mandela's release. The musicians, past the starting time of the concert, astonished that no spectators had turned up, went out to ask for an explanation: only then, they learnt that Mandela had been freed. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 29. *Youth training of the Red City Players (RCP) (2015)*. The RCP are one of the Red Location's football teams and have obtained a kind of informal permission from the museum staff to train in the space adjacent to the amphitheatre (in the distance, the museum's industrial outline is visible, and on the right the screen for outdoor cinema). Source: M. Montanini.

Fig: 30. *Dj Academy. School for DJs (2015)*. The studio is located in Red Location, in the backyard of a private house. Source: M. Montanini.

Fig. 31. *Art Station (2015)*, backyard of a private house in Red Location. Various photographs of the neighbourhood hang on the walls. Source: Art Station.

Fig. 32. A poster promoting an event organised by the Culture Consciousness Society in Kwazakhele (2016). One of the members of the society is wearing a cloth with a portrait of Biko. On the left it is announced that it is possible to travel there by taxi at much lower prices than the norm. Source: Ccs, Facebook page.

Fig. 33. Left: *Collage, part of the decoration of the new venue of The Coohouse Poetry, in Kwazakhele (2016).* It is a room in a courtyard of a private house, recently refurbished to host jam sessions and performances. Events are announced on the group's Facebook page. Right: *Directions to the venue of the Underground Backyard Hungout (2015).* The UBH is an open-air event, held in the evenings, on a monthly basis, and is a mixture of music and *slam-poetry*. These were the first indications posted on the facebook page of the group that organises the UBH. In 2016, given the turnout and success of the events, the map was replaced with a GoogleMaps geolocation. Source: The CookHouse Poetry and UBH Facebook pages.

Fig. 34. *Jazz concert* (2015). Concert in a tavern (neighbourhood bar) in Red Location. Source: Art Station.

Fig. 35. *Afternoon musical improvisation at a tshisanyama* (2015), Red Location.

Annex 4. Quoted interviews and map of research locations

1. LIST OF CITED INTERVIEWS

13/02/2015	Academic who collaborated with the RLMCP
16/02/2015	Academic who collaborated with the RLMCP
17/02/2015	Academic who collaborated with the RLMCP
19/02/2015	Member of the museum staff
04/03/2015	Academic who collaborated with the RLMCP
06/03/2015	Member ANC local branch
12/03/2015	Member of the museum staff
13/03/2015	Rory Riordan
16/03/2015	Member of the museum staff
20/03/2015	Member of the museum staff
21/03/2015	NMBM Officer, Strategic Projects
21/04/2015	NMBM officials, Human Settlements, Housing delivery
21/04/2015	Ward councillor, ANC
11/05/2015	Member of the RLSC
12/05/2015	Architect who helped organise the competition for design and construction RLMCP
13/05/2015	Former Red Location resident, poet
18/05/2015	Councillor, ANC
28/05/2015	Former RLSC member
28/05/2015	Resident, Red Location-New Brighton
10/06/2015	Red City players, Red Location
11/06/2015	Members of the New Brighton-KwaZakhele martial arts group
16/06/2015	Members of the cooperative that manages the Red Location Lodge
23/06/2015	NMBM Officer, Human Settlements, Development and Support
24/06/2015	Artist, Port Elizabeth
29/07/2015	Official, Mandela Bay Development Agency (MBDA)
01/08/2015	NMBM official, Human settlements, Housing delivery
04/08/2015	Academic who collaborated with the RLMCP
06/08/2015	Teachers, Jarvis Gqamlana, Red Location
20/08/2015	Artist, Red Location
08/10/2015	RLMCP staff member
02/11/2015	Member of the RLSC
03/11/2015	Member of the RLSC
04/11/2015	NMBM Officer, Human Settlements, Development and Support
04/11/2015	RLMCP staff member
14/11/2015	Member of the RLSC
15/11/2015	Member of the museum staff
16/11/2015	Ward councillor ANC
19/11/2015	Artist, Red Location
20/11/2015	Official, Sport, Recreation, Arts and Culture
24/11/2015	Ward councillor ANC
12/12/2015	Artist, New Brighton
17/12/2015	Rory Riordan

2. MAP OF RESEARCH LOCATIONS

Fig. 1. *Research locations.* (1) RLMCP, outdoor space; (2) Red Location-New Brighton (Coven High School/Jarvis Gqamalana Primary School/Hoza hall, councillor office Red Location/backyards and private houses/St. Stephen Church and other churches/former Rio Cinema/Centenary Hall-Nangoza Jebe hall/public library/tavern); (3) Kwazakhele (Private houses/Kenako Mall/taverns and backyards/kung fu gymnasium and community centre) (4) Zwide (Public Library/Tchisanyama/taverns); (5) Missionvale (Missionvale, NMMU campus); (6) Summerstrand (South Campus Nmmu/Office Center of Advancement of Non Racialism and Democracy, CANRAD); (7) Humewood (South End Museum); (8) Central (The Herald Archives/Directorate of Human Settlement/ Offices of Municipal Councillors/ National Union of Metalworkers Office, NUMSA/BIRD Street, NMMU Faculty of ART/OPERA House/Atheneum/Dojon services); (9) Park Drive (Directorate of Sport, Recreation Art and Culture); (10) Richmond Hill (Heroldt Architects/ private homes/ bars and concert halls); (11) Uitenhage, Mandela Village (UF meeting). Source: Elaborated on OpenStreetMaps map base.

